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Foreword from the National Chair, 2023-2024

Lydia Wiernik, University of Edinburgh

The ULAB proceedings showcase some of the incredible, innovative work presented at our annual conference. We are honoured to share here ten writeups and squibs from ULAB XIV.

This year's conference was the first hosted by the University of Sussex and the third to adopt a hybrid model, increasing accessibility and enabling worldwide attendance. We held workshops, plenaries, and talks on topics ranging from British Sign Language and cognition to sociophonetic variation, and had lively panel discussions with current and past committee members on what it's like being involved with ULAB. Sussex's conference saw many familiar UK and global affiliations but also welcomed two new ones: Ibn Tofail University in Morocco and University of Michigan in the United States. The conference, and the present proceedings, are the outward reflection of yearlong internal efforts by ULAB's National and Local Committees. A *massive* thanks must go to Local Chair Milly Sandy and the rest of the Local Committee, whose hard work made ULAB 2024 possible; to Ro Dhasmana, with whom I had the pleasure of sharing National Chair responsibilities; and to Archivist James Berriman and JoULAB's copyediting team for so masterfully compiling these proceedings.

The incredible efforts of both Committees not only facilitated this year's activities but ensured the longevity of ULAB as an organisation. Over the past year ULAB continued the outreach and community building which lie at the heart of its mission; JoULAB completed its 2nd workshop series and launched a podcast, both aimed at making academic publishing more accessible, and the National Committee wrote an open letter to universities cutting linguistics programmes in solidarity with our field and its future. Though many longtime committee members graduated this year, drawing their ULAB terms to a close, the conference marked a successful reinvigoration of the organisation, with many new faces elected to the 2025-26 National Committee. The continued existence of and interest in ULAB underscores the necessity of such an organisation and how deeply those involved care for it.

The 2024 conference also marked my last term on the ULAB Committee. I have had an amazing four years as part of this organisation and grown in countless ways as a linguist and a person. But if I could pass on just one thing, it would be this: *have fun*. It is in your best interest to enjoy the work you do, whether it be your dissertation, or a course assignment, or just the notes you take during lectures. I believe linguistics and academia and ULAB are, at their core, about the same thing: joy for what you love, and an excitement for figuring out the unknown. I encourage you to get involved, put yourself out there, and express how you feel about the topics that excite you. I can entirely guarantee that you will not be alone in this at ULAB, no matter how niche your syntactic theory(!).

I'm incredibly grateful for everyone I've had the honour of being on a committee with, and I'm so excited to see what the future holds for committees to come.

Once more, a huge thank you to the Archivist and copyeditors for compiling this work, to the Local and National Committees for facilitating the conference, and to all those who shared their phenomenal research during the conference and within these pages.

Please enjoy the 2024 ULAB conference proceedings.

Foreword from the Local Chair, 2023-2024

Milly Sandy, University of Sussex

I had the privilege of hosting the ULAB 2024 conference at my home institution, the University of Sussex, and what an amazing experience it was! We were delighted to welcome linguistics students from all over the UK, as well as (virtually) from further afield, including: Porto, Toronto, and Michigan. Over the busy three days, attendees enjoyed a programme covering a wide range of linguistic topics. The 33 student talks addressed a wide range of individual and well-thought-out topics, while the three inspiring guest speaker plenaries covered syntax, sociophonetics, and lexis-oriented sociolinguistics. Attendees were also able to attend a panel and/or workshop each day, which provided more interactive learning experiences on fascinating topics such as cross-linguistic patterns, post-graduate study, and British Sign Language (BSL). However, ULAB 2024 was not just about academics; it was also about bringing linguistics students together in a setting that allowed us to form bonds and take in Brighton's vibrant city! On the night of each of the three days, social activities, such as a games night and a social dinner in Brighton, were held to encourage participants to come together and take advantage of the opportunity to connect with other linguists that ULAB provides.

I am particularly proud of the Local Committee's work; despite having just four committee members, we successfully organised and hosted a highly enjoyable conference. So, a massive thank you goes to Becky (Secretary), Mae (Vice-Chair), and Bronny (Social Sec) for your incredible efforts and hard work. Additional thanks to the National Committee for their invaluable advice and support in making ULAB 2024 at Sussex possible. Finally, a shoutout to the Department of English Language and Linguistics and the School of Media, Arts, and Humanities at the University of Sussex for their generous funding and assistance throughout the entire organisational process. I am greatly looking forward to ULAB 2025 at UCL!

Introduction to the Proceedings

James Berriman, University of Portsmouth

It is an honour and a delight to present the Proceedings of the 2024 ULAB conference. The papers comprising these proceedings show some of the finest Linguistics research from the United Kingdom and further afield, all written by undergraduate students.

ULAB 2024 was held at the University of Sussex, with the conference venturing south of London for the first time since 2012. As has become the norm, guests and presenters had the choice of attending in-person or online via Zoom, maximising the number of people able to engage with the student presentations, plenaries, and workshops taking place over the course of the three days. With every passing year, organisers are more equipped to deal with any technical difficulties and the local committee dealt admirably with the challenges that this hybrid model posed, as well as the logistical issues of a marathon and travel disruption occurring in the city during the conference.

It is a huge honour to be elected as archivist this year. As someone who engaged later in their undergraduate career, I felt as if I had unfinished business with ULAB, so I am pleased to have the opportunity to contribute in my own way and follow in the footsteps of the many great people who have held this role previously. My journey as archivist began with finalising the publication of 2023's Proceedings, a process which has put me in good stead for compiling this year's edition, as we continue the great tradition of giving conference presenters the option to have their research published.

This publication now joins the wealth of resources in ULAB's archives, accompanying previous Proceedings editions, our magazine U-Lingua, our journal JoULAB, presentation slides, conference programmes, and many other relics of ULAB history.

These Proceedings are comprised of ten articles written by undergraduate students who presented the research of these very papers at ULAB XIV in April 2024. They are organised into two parts. Firstly, in Section A, full length papers that were assessed and graded as part of a university course, achieving a Class I or II.1, or international equivalent, can be found. Section B is made up of shorter squibs and write-ups. These papers are shorter assessed pieces and works conducted independently of university courses and were therefore ungraded. This method assures students access to publication regardless of length of paper or stage of study. All are of outstanding quality and span the many fields of study within Linguistics.

Compiling these Proceedings has been a long process, and I am grateful to many for their contributions over the course of this journey. Firstly, thanks to the team of copyeditors Kasia Koston, Rachel Oliver, Leo Wong, and Nicky Yang for their mammoth effort editing and proofreading these papers with outstanding diligence. Thank you to Cameron Benson-Davis for designing the tremendous cover page. The dolphins are included as a reference to the University of Sussex's crest. I am also hugely grateful to previous ULAB archivist Lydia Wiernik for their mentorship and responding to my endless barrage of questions and queries with clarity and patience. Finally, the effort of the national and local committees cannot be underestimated, and I am sure that all will echo that sentiment. A huge thanks is owed to them for their role in organising such a successful conference.

Please enjoy the 2024 Proceedings of ULAB.

SECTION A

ASSESSED CONTRIBUTIONS

The following contributions have been assessed by academic institutions and have been awarded a Class I, Class II.1, or international equivalent.

‘Kermit Sueyslide’: Scraping Orthographic Innovations Bypassing Twitter’s *Kill* Censorship

Cameron Benson-Davis

University of Warwick

Abstract. This research aimed to document linguistic innovations strategically bypassing content moderation censorship based on a typology by Kim et al. (2021). It focused on the word *kill* and common synonyms by generating a small corpus that identified the frequency of items across selected regions, as well as the conversational context yielding them. Orthographic optical strategies were the most common across the entire corpus, appearing even in scrapes of items predominantly falling under other categories. An issue, however, is that it may prove difficult to study an environment akin to X (now formerly Twitter) because the site has since made their REST API inaccessible. This paper ideates a myriad of ideas to take this project further in response to the change.

Keywords: self-censorship; censorship evasion; social media; substitution; altering; Twitter; scraping; orthography

1 Introduction

On 23rd December 2022, screenwriter and anti-transgender activist Graham Linehan’s Twitter account was reinstated almost thirty months after suspension. Many pro-transgender and anti-racist activists were dismayed, particularly those whose activism shared to Twitter had been removed or algorithmically downplayed (Haimson et al., 2021). This disproportionate content moderation has led to an uncertainty among activist and non-activist Twitter users about the exact criteria that determines censorship. While some have resorted to developing external circumvention programs to bypass social media censorship (Di Florio et al., 2014), others have been observed to alter the orthography or wholly substitute potentially sensitive words or phrases that have historically triggered tweet, tweet-equivalent, or entire account takedowns in both English (Burrell et al., 2019, p. 11) and other languages (Hiruncharoenvate et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2021; Sanei, 2022, p. 461). The present study aims to exemplify a typology of linguistic innovations strategically bypassing censorship of *kill* and common synonyms by generating a small corpus identifying frequency across selected regions and the conversational context yielding them.

2 Literature Review

Dialectological work on social media is undertaken not only to identify the translation of users’ spoken dialect features into facets of their digital footprint (Gonçalves & Sánchez, 2014; Jones, 2015; Strelluf, 2019, 2020, 2022; Willis, 2020), but to additionally predict changes and observe social developments in the translating phenomena (Eisenstein, 2018). However, online subcommunities have often developed exclusive words, phrases or multimodal memes as markers of social identity (Barasa, 2013; Penney, 2020). A bulk of scholarship has therefore oriented itself around such communal online norms forming variation that is ‘geographically anchored’ to the internet (Eisenstein, 2018, p. 370). Sometimes, the two fields have intertwined, such as the widespread appropriation of African American Vernacular English (Heine, 2022). Despite the massive influence that African American culture at large

has had on the Western digital culture that Twitter helps mediate — the diaspora often being the origins of viral dances, songs, slang, food recipes, and more — Black cultural intermediaries have reported censorship of their content critiquing systems perpetuating xenophobia, including Twitter, while xenophobic rhetoric from conservative-leaning accounts remain (Haimson et al., 2021).

Twitter has two processes to maintain its content: curation and moderation (Burrell et al., 2019). The former collects users' behaviour and uses it as a base for recommending new content, while the latter uses a separate set of criteria to prevent certain content from being recommended. Content moderation typically involves identifying frequencies of key words attached to a certain topic. The first example that Twitter (2022) gives in their current policy of hateful conduct is *I will kill you* to demonstrate violent threats. However, they do not detail how their algorithms discriminate between the varying contexts in which *kill* may be used. This results in earnest commentary on murder and the systemic issues that perpetuate it to get flagged and moderated alongside genuine threats. *Kill*, *murder*, and *suicide* used in jest to intensify embarrassment or self-deprecation, as opposed to describing sensitive topics, also do not flout Twitter's policy but have similarly been taken down. *Kill myself* and *commit suicide* are now linguistically bleached phrases expressing embarrassment or other negative emotion (Smith & Linker, 2021). In tweet *l*, for example, which censors 'killing' with vowel substitution, the author is probably not seriously considering suicide because they are angry with a videogame.

Kim et al. (2021) outlined a typology of strategies bypassing content moderation algorithms. Users employ a range of morphological, phonological, semantic and optical alterations to a transmission — the content created within a single tweet, upload, comment, message, etc. — to make them undetectable by content moderation yet understandable for their intended audience. For example, they may substitute letters for other resemblant characters such as *k!ll* or *|<177*. More covert methods involve orthographically and semantically dissimilar but phonologically similar alternatives. Tweet *a* (see Appendix) arguably implicates a threat and is an example of a phonology-based evasion strategy in English. Meanwhile, Kim et al. have observed a culturally-bound metaphor emerging among Korean users tacitly agreeing that *notepad.exe* refers to the speaker holding criticism without explicitly divulging it in the transmission.

3 Methodology

An initial pilot scrape was conducted a month before data collection began to test the technology and usage of variable *unalive*. A survey then requested undergraduates to reformulate sentences containing *kill*, *murder*, and *commit suicide* in contexts of varying severity and irony under the assumption that such words would flag their imaginary social media accounts to content moderators and be taken down. It was noted in the prompt that the words were only flaggable when spelled exactly as the prompt presented them. Figure 1 shows answers utilising strategies described by Kim et al. (2021), and were selected as independent variables for scrape, and returned useful or nonsensitive data.

The scrape itself involved using Twitter's REST API with RStudio via OAuth (Katamaneni et al., 2018). The twitterR API has a benefit over popular alternatives such as Tweepy with Python as twitterR can collect tweets published within a timeframe that is larger than seven days. While R often requires more lines of code than Python, RStudio alleviates this. The written content, author username and ID, bio, user they were replying to (if applicable), number of likes, retweets, and user-reported location (according to bio) of tweets were collected. Additional English-only and in-content-only parameters were added to prevent incidental usernames not tweeting an independent variable, non-English leetspeak, or unintended leetspeak-presenting items from appearing. Data was formatted into .csv files and manually scoured for anomalies, such as tweets mentioning usernames containing an independent

variable. The pilot *unalive* corpus was added afterward with minor omissions of metadata to fit in with the rest of the findings.

Figure 1: Distribution of independent variables in corpus.

Social media corpora transgress traditional methodologies’ requirement of subjects’ informed consent; due to their generally massive scale it would be unsustainable to anticipate any response, let alone explicit consent to be studied, from every individual subject. Fiesler and Proferes (2018) investigate these ethical complexities from subjects’ point of view: owners of public Twitter accounts are generally unaware that their tweets may be used by researchers, and over half of users do not mind if a single tweet of theirs was used in context. However, depending on the intent and content of the study, many would prefer a request for consent before extracting them, or to be anonymised. Nevertheless, Twitter requires any reproduction of a tweet — at minimum, the transmission and the username behind it — to be verbatim. Not every study has followed this, though (Burrell et al., 2019). In any case, accepting Twitter’s terms of services involves users recognising the susceptibility of the public identity and subsequent tweets they create to being accessed for research, journalism, and entertainment. Rossi et al. (2022) suggest implementing the same ethical safeguards one would when disclosing sensitive in-person data, which is especially relevant when studying candid admissions, anxieties or ignorance about emotionally and politically sensitive topics. As such, anything deemed too graphic, such as legitimate or deeply described violence and suicidal ideation have not been considered for analysis or representation, but examples have not been pseudonymised due the study’s minute initially-intended audience and scope.

4 Results

Eight responses to the survey fell under the typology of strategies described by Kim et al. (2021). None involved morphologically altering the flaggable stimulus, though two — *murda* and *sewerside*— fell under the morpho-phonological category. *Murda* ends with an unrhoticised variation of standard ‘er’ schwa /ə/ that leans toward (but does not absolutely assume) /æ/; meanwhile *sewerside* leans on the phonological similarity of established word *sewer* and dialectal pronunciations of original *suicide*. Common innovations of *kill* came under what Kim et al. (2021, p.12) refer to as ‘optical tricks’, like

su!c!de, *k!ll* and *ki77*, or under ‘semantic tricks’. This includes substituting *kill* for *unalive* or the 🗡 emoji [U+1F52A]. While Kim et al. (2021, p.11) note of glottalised or voiced consonants as a common innovation, e.g. ‘diZZZgustting (disgusting)’, this is usually among Korean users. However, omitting the final position vowel and velarising the voiced alveolar plosive /d/ for /k/ to produce *merk* — originating from AAVE, though likely more originally — was suggested. *Body*, another relevant substitution from the same dialect, was another answer, but only standard uses of the word were scraped. *Commit* was also trialled in the survey, but the only collected alternative was *kermit*, which in turn was only observed in contexts alongside innovations of *suicide*.

Taking into account manually omitted entries using the CTRL+F search tool, a total of 2,619 tweets were scraped and reformatted. An average of 291 tweets per independent variable was collected. However, *k!ll* garnered double due to a scrape of its past-participle form as well, since none were collected in the initial search, even though plenty of gerund items (e.g. *k!lling*) were found.

5 Discussion

There were a variety of morpho-phonological innovations. *Murda* was commonly observed in contexts displaying other orthographic innovations of AAVE, for example intensifier *ong* (‘on god’), contraction of *ain’t* and auxiliary *be*, plus acronym *OTY*, often in relation to digital media (*GOTY* ‘game of the year’, *AOTY* ‘album of the year’), each of which are exemplified in tweets *c*, *b* and *d*, respectively. This is supported by trends in geolocation across users of *murda*, such as Detroit, MI whose Black communities have historically heavily utilised AAVE (Knapp, 2015), among various diasporas across the United States, which is just as Jones (2015) studied. More examples from the corpus include Philadelphia, Florida, and Houston. In this sense *murda* is likely less an alternative to *murder* by the means of censorship-evasion, and more a conscious marker of Black identity. *Murk* usage behaved in the same way, though *murda* differs in that it often appears in relation to hip-hop, a tenet of African American culture, notably in the examples *b* and *d* (see Appendix). *Coty* in the latter abbreviates ‘cypher of the year’, an appraisal of the act in which rappers take it in turns to perform. Further evidence that *murda* is a cultural marker of identity rather than an evasion strategy is the tweet *e*, whose author chooses not to censor ‘committing’ despite placing it next to a potentially flaggable word. However, if *murda* were an evasion strategy, it is likely it would have been.

Similarly, though much rarer, was a formulation with *sewerside*. Interestingly, it is the only word censored in jade’s tweets (*h*, *i*), despite also using *commit* and *murder*. The signification of sewers in a context where sewers are not relevant conveys an absurdism or surrealism so prevalent in online meme culture (Wiggins, 2019), but the sincerity of the tweets refrains the author from leaning further into the style. Compare this to tweet *a*, which phonologically innovates *commit suicide* more exaggeratedly than other examples, inserting <l> to result *slide*, and opting for *kermit*, too. The literal referent, Jim Henson’s Muppet character Kermit the Frog, has been a popular subject in meme culture as much as it has popular culture (Palmer, 2017). It is almost as if *kermit* may only arise in an ironic or post-ironic context. Tweet *a*’s *kermit sueyslide* conveys a literal demand, an undercurrent of the absurdism of meme culture, and the kinship between users over that. Certain strategies also appear to have an illocutionary element of sarcasm, irony, or post-irony to alleviate the severity of the claim. Emerging *unalive* also captures this, largely from the absurdity of negating *alive*, an adjective, which already has a negation with *dead*, and using it as a verb in place of canonical *kill* (tweet *r*). *Sewerside* and *unalive*, therefore, are innovating multidimensionally: not only morpho-phonologically by representing other words, but simultaneously engaging with contemporary meme aesthetics whilst indicating shared awareness of shifting language norms of Twitter as an environment.

There were uses of *sewerside* in wholly sincere contexts devoid of memetics, such as the common ‘trigger warning’ format in example *j*, but the vast majority heavily evoke some semblance of humour, which Kim et al. (2021, p. 12) class under semantic strategies. In most sincere contexts, though, other evasion strategies that notably don’t have memetic associations were preferred (tweet *k*). The same goes for *kill*-alternatives via optical tricks. Orthographic optical strategies were the most common across the entire corpus, appearing even in scrapes of items falling under other categories (see tweet *k*). *Su!c!de* did not evoke the same pragmatic information as *sewerside*, evident in the higher number of serious contexts in which it was used. Due to the severity of the content of some tweets they will not be included in this paper. A sample of the corpus containing the use of *su!c!de* was available for the reviewing parties, should they wish to see them at their discretion. Similarly, *k!!!* was used with sincerity in almost every instance; items exhibiting the exaggerative illocutionary force only took up approximately 7.65% of the *k!!!* scrape. Meanwhile, leetspeak *ki77* data revealed nearly the opposite, where 12.6% of contexts were in specific reference to murder. Exaggerative, linguistically weakened *ki77* was often used in reference to parasocial relationships, normally discussing celebrities or objects to whom they were constantly exposed, for example tweets *p* and *q*.

This was the case for the knife emoji is modified via processes such as flooding (Hilte et al., 2020; tweet *u*).

6 Conclusion

This study corroborates the typology put forward by Kim et al. (2021), and with it, we can put the presence and purposes of *unalive* and similar variables on formal record. It exemplifies several contexts of content moderation evasion in the dialect of the English-speaking online subcommunity, and points out words which are not such strategies. Users apply additional pragmatic value to morpho- and phonological alterations, but not to orthographical ones. Overall, this is a useful way to discern the differences between items that should and should not be susceptible to censorship. The rest of the conclusions will primarily identify the rich foundation for future work laid out by this introductory study.

Several methodological implications and notions arising from the data could not be addressed due to the study’s small scope. Unlike most entries into these proceedings, this was not a dissertation project, and the following implications should be considered for a project with a similar detail. On top of the potential for in substitution for a whole lexical item was recorded, this study did not record any instances of emoji only partially in place of text as depicted in Figure 2, and so necessitates documentation.

The TikTok from which Figure 2 originates uses the text, emoji, video, and audio modes to talk about suicide without malice. In it, there are two censorship evasion strategies immediately evident: the close-captions use the gerund *unaliving*, and the headline graphic substitutes the vowels <ui> for

confounded face 😬 [U+1F616]. This is an intriguing instance of text-emoji multimodality. A semantic trick in the words of Kim et al. (2021), the emoji of choice pragmatically prioritises to connote an air of discomfort and sadness over phonological, morphological, or optical familiarity to the substituted characters. Interestingly, though, this kind of multimodality is not always as harmonious or motivated by censorship-evasion either. Similar to the screenshotted caption of the cropped video uploaded by @mrcrim3 in Figure 2, some video content on sites like TikTok and YouTube have been observed to use censorship-evasion tactics in their close-captioning, but *kill* or *commit suicide* is still spoken. It may be useful to study the role of multimodal evasion-strategies in social media where multimodality is natural and more prevalent than on Twitter, like TikTok, YouTube, and Instagram.

Figure 2: *Cropped screenshot of a video by TikTok user and teacher @mrcrim3.*

Furthermore, new work should consider alternative, more rigorous approaches such as sentiment analysis; how to dodge or moderate the constraint of bot accounts in scrape data; and, most importantly, the future of Twitter-scraping. The feedback from the original version of this assignment emphasised the methodological value of this study. However, about a week after assessment, access to Twitter's APIs was closed from the public, which means linguistic study via Twitter-scraping, including an update to the methodology and data of the present project, has become indubitably difficult, if not impossible. As valid as sites like Mastodon and Bluesky Social seem as alternatives for study, they're nowhere near as large and in-depth as Twitter, simply because they are younger. Therefore, results may not be as thorough. There have been recent, thorough attempts to document social interactions and user-generated content on Twitter recently, though (Failla & Rossetti, 2024). Scholars must also be conscious that data from these websites may also be skewed, as they attract a demographic that is a minority under the grander Twitter user base, characterised by specifically being opposed to Twitter. Lastly, Bluesky (2024) is now letting users customise how their own feeds are moderated, which will eliminate the need to think of evasion strategies. It would be interesting to see if and how any evasion strategies like *unalive* persist despite their lack of necessity. Nevertheless, the Bluesky user base is dwarfed by the phlegmatic majority who will continue to candidly use Twitter until they or the website itself are *unalive*. This should be at the forefront of the scholar's mind when designing a scrape or scrape-like approach.

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8 Appendix

8.1 Appendix: Selected Posts from Twitter

- (a) **Thorne™** If I was ratioed this many times on Twitter and was already promoting eating disorders I'd probably kermit sueyslide FR
- (b) **Uncle Iroh** Jada Kingdom ain't have to murda that beat like that
- (c) **gibby** ong we needa legalize murda
- (d) **Mike McCombs** Coty, I think you about to witness a murda...
- (e) **AlmightyKelon** Starting conversations is like committing murda sometimes
- (f) **MVP Tatum** [...] Dude will murk you and go drink a 5th of vodka like nothing happened
- (g) it's taking everything in me not to murk this ho
- (h) **jade** i'd literally commit murder for a mcdonalds rn
- (i) **jade** someone find me a new rules dublin ticket before i commit sewerside
- (j) **Comet** TW // Sewerside mention [...]
- (k) **AKIO ♦ MONOTONEDUO!** // suicide mention [BREAK] its so easy to apologize abt ur sewerside jokes [...] funny how you still have a platform /aimed
- (l) **Karp** KAYLING MYSELF IN FRONT OF NETEASE HQ AND MAKING MY SEWERSIDE LETTER ABOUT HOW IDV'S GACHA SYSTEM IS DOGWATER AND THEY NEED TO GIVE ME FREDERICK S TIER NOW!
- (m) **mistress of horror.** seeing you hurt breaks my heart in such a different way, i don't know. i'd k!ll for you angy. please text me anytime, my phone is right in my hand
- (n) **tylersherro** this show drags out so long. i just need to know who k!lled wes
- (o) **_t.a.w.e** if su!c!de ever crosses your mind just know i'd rather sit down with u for days listening to your story than tell it. [BREAK] i love you.
- (p) **fk** dear 2021, pls ki77 trump
- (q) I'm so down atrocious I'm ready to ki77 for that Xiao perfume
- (r) **AliciaMarie** Id be using every chemical in my cabinets to unalive that critter

- (s) **indyonce** 🗨️ i only say unalive because ppl will be petty and report your tweets for the other words
- (t) **professor jomayton** i will 🗨️ covid
- (u) **minjeongie** I will 🗨️ 🗨️ 🗨️ 🗨️ 🗨️ 🗨️ 🗨️ him

Due to the severity of the content of some tweets they will not be included in this assignment. A sample of the corpus containing the use of *su!c!de* was available for the reviewing parties, should they wish to seem them at their discretion.

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‘I’m on the Way Back from the Game’: A Corpus-Assisted Discourse Study Comparing Pronoun Use in the Football Phone-In ‘606’

James Berriman

University of Portsmouth

Abstract. In this corpus-assisted discourse study, the linguistic environments of pronouns are analysed and compared in calls to the BBC Radio 5 Live football phone-in ‘606’. Phone-ins are ripe for research, as they allow laypeople to debate with professionals to a large audience. This paper examines a 75,000-word corpus of British English football phone-in data to compare pronoun use between callers whose teams won and lost and establishes the themes they construct. Collocation and concordance corpus tools are utilised, allowing for a comparative analysis of 112 transcribed calls, not only comparing usage between pronouns themselves, but also how they are used differently by supporters whose teams won or lost. Collocation results show that the pronouns ‘I’, ‘we’, ‘you’, and ‘they’ are used in constructions that fit into six linguistic and thematic categories. The additional context provided by the concordance analysis shows that these can be simplified into just two purposes: constructing stance and building credibility. There is little difference in how credibility is invoked between the callers whose teams won or lost, but as expected, the losers employ a more negative stance towards their situation. The stance constructions incorporate a variety of pronouns, whilst credibility is primarily built through first person pronouns. I argue that stance is a principal element of calls in programmes where views on a subject are given. Credibility is also paramount, because the callers’ stances can only be taken seriously when they state their credentials to prove they can comment on the topic as an expert.

Keywords: corpus linguistics; football phone-in; collocation; concordance; corpus-assisted discourse studies

1 Introduction

Football phone-ins have been integral to the sport’s media landscape for many years, with the first being broadcast in 1986 (BBC South Yorkshire, 2008), offering callers the chance to air their views to a radio audience in a programme called ‘Praise or Grumble’. Many British stations have since adopted the format, such as the national BBC Radio 5 Live, with 606, the programme featured in this study. It attracts a national audience of callers and listeners, allowing for a representation of a diverse group of people and teams. It is reputable due to the BBC’s status as a broadcaster and its regular schedule means that shows are spread out evenly across the season, giving a profile of fans’ views at different points in time. All phone-ins require a host to interact with the callers, with 606 being presented by former footballers Robbie Savage and Chris Sutton in the 2022/23 season. This period was chosen as the most recently completed season, meaning that data is up to date and an accurate profiling of current trends.

In linguistic research, many studies have explored radio phone-ins, but less attention has been paid to the football subgenre. Previous research helped to shape the research questions of this paper, with those being ‘how does pronoun use differ between supporters whose teams have won and lost?’ and ‘what themes do callers construct?’. To answer these questions, 112 calls from twelve programmes are transcribed, before being separated into two corpora, where callers whose teams lost or won are kept apart. A corpus-assisted discourse analysis framework is used, and collocation and concordance tools highlight language patterns. Collocation statistics are utilised first, raising interesting similarities and differences that are then explored in more detail with the additional context provided by concordance

lines. The analysis focuses on the themes of stance and credibility, through the lens of six collocation categories.

Stance is a central element to the discussion. DuBois (2007, p. 163) defines it as ‘a public act by a social actor, achieved dialogically through overt communicative means, of simultaneously evaluating objects, positioning subjects (self and others), and aligning with other subjects, with respect to any salient dimensions of the sociocultural field’ (as cited in Myers & Lampropoulou, 2012, p. 1208). For a phone-in, these are the views which callers share. Myers and Lampropoulou later write that ‘a crucial aspect of speaker identity is entitlement to answer the specific question one has been asked’ (p. 1216), which forms the definition for credibility, another important theme of this paper. This is concerned with how callers prove that they have the knowledge to speak on a topic, as an expert.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Language and Radio Phone-Ins

Radio phone-ins have frequently been a topic of interest for research. Thornborrow (2001) rationalises this, as they form scenarios where professionals and experts are given the opportunity to interact. Discussion focuses on a given topic, with the role of the host including the assurance that calls provide insight into that topic. Common phone-in themes that have been researched include politics (Hutchby, 1999; Thornborrow, 2001; Fitzgerald & Housely, 2002; Thornborrow & Fitzgerald, 2002; Ellison, 2014; Chichon, 2020), general aspects of life (McCarthy & O’Keeffe, 2003; O’Sullivan, 2005; Kilby & Horowitz, 2013; Roy, 2013; Versteeg & te Molder, 2018), and sport (Xiang, 2003; Ponton, 2011), with Ponton’s research being the only that investigates football programmes. Their intrigue arises from their unique characteristics, such as the gulf in power between host and caller and the public mass audience (Bednarek, 2014, p. 5), hence needing to satisfy what is regarded as a ‘good call’ (O’Sullivan, 2005, p. 732). Interactions are high stakes as a result, with callers being cognisant of the impression they give off and the consequences of how they are perceived (O’Sullivan, 2005, p. 720).

Conversation analysis has often been the methodology used for radio phone-ins (Fitzgerald & Housely, 2002), yet tend to analyse small data sets, unlike the large-scale methodology of corpus analysis. There have been few attempts to collect radio phone-in texts and apply a corpus linguistics framework, despite the many tools offered by the software. McCarthy and O’Keeffe (2003) first built one of these corpora, studying vocatives in a 55,000-word corpus of Irish English. It is clearly distinguished from the present paper, which contains British English and a substantially larger corpus of 75,000 words. The vocatives were deemed to manage turn-taking, topic, and face concerns, which links to pronouns as they both can act as forms of address. Bednarek (2014) then used the 200,000-word Australian corpus of radio talk for a larger research project, where the concept of involvement was studied with the N-Grams tool. She went on to recommend that ‘it might be interesting to look more closely at pronouns’ (p. 14), supporting Roy’s (2013, p. 17) earlier endorsement of pronouns referring to collectivities of people in research, helping to narrow the scope of the present study. More recently, Beeferman et al. (2019) reported on the ambitious project to build a 2.8-billion-word corpus of American radio talk but has been neglected in actual linguistic research since its creation.

Before Bednarek’s recommendation, pronouns have rarely been dealt with explicitly, except Xiang (2003), who found pronouns to collocate with opinion markers to express personal views on American sports radio. Since then, they have received some more focus. In the context of political news radio, Ellison (2014) found a crude binary between the use of pronouns, proposing a contrast between the ‘protagonist we’ and ‘antagonist they’ (p. 98), highlighting an obvious distinction between ingroups and outgroups. This distinction can be attributed less precisely to second person pronouns, with Jautz

(2014) identifying that the pronouns ‘you’ and ‘your’ can involve different people at different junctures of conversation (p. 24). Since this slew of studies, pronouns have again ceased to receive warranted research attention, whilst identity has been a preferred theme.

Outside of the corpus studies, researchers have sought to organise calls, studying the introductory sections where callers are greeted and brought on to speak (Hutchby, 1999; Thornborrow, 2001). These are known as ‘openings’ (Hutchby, 1999) and allow the host to ‘bring the caller into the participatory frame’ (Thornborrow, 2001, p. 122). In these organisation attempts, researchers have noticed that the ‘institutionality’ and power imbalance results in the linguistic tools a caller can use being limited (Hutchby, 1999, p. 57; Thornborrow, 2001, p. 119). Necessary features of the openings are ‘call-relevant identities’ (Fitzgerald & Housely, 2002, p. 586): the information used to describe the caller as they are brought into the conversation. Location is the usual standard, but for football phone-ins the supported team is given instead. Kilby and Horowitz (2013) also stress the importance of this seemingly minor feature. They postulate that listeners already make judgements about the caller at this point, and it is the callers’ goal to provide their ‘expert credentials’ to prove their points are valid. Credibility and identity are heavily interwoven in this genre of communication and described as ‘crucial’ to the whole process by Chichon (2020, p. 5). Being a football fan is deemed a significant identity by society (Gee, 2014, p. 25), so it is therefore interesting to analyse how this identity is managed by radio callers, especially considering that it is a self-ascribed identity.

2.2 Corpus Linguistics

Corpus linguistics (CL) is the large-scale study of language aided by computer technologies (Partington et al., 2013). The modern corpus tools allow for a fast and reliable analysis of large bodies of texts, with this collection of texts being known as corpora (McEnery & Hardie, 2012, p. 2). In some form, corpus linguistics has existed long before computers revolutionised the process, but the neo-Firthian school and its main proponent John Sinclair helped to establish the methodology in use today. The concepts of collocation and discourse are central to this (McEnery & Hardie, 2012, p. 122). The studies that have been since been conducted examine an incredible range of topics, which shows how the methodology can be applicable to almost any research question. The emergence of the internet has allowed for corpora and corpus tools to be shared, helping to create this productive research community (Crosthwaite et al., 2023, p. 365). McEnery and Hardie distinguish between the established ideas of ‘corpus-based’ and ‘corpus-driven’ studies, with corpus-driven following the neo-Firthian methodology of a ‘bottom up’ study, whilst corpus-based is defined as ‘top down’. Put simply, the researcher has no preconceived notions about what they might find in corpus-driven research, on the contrary, they may be aiming for a more targeted analysis if it is corpus-based (2012, pp. 241-242). Partington builds on the traditional ideas by offering ‘corpus-assisted discourse studies’ (CADS), which is defined as a CL subset that uses computerised corpora to study language ‘as communicative discourse’ (2013, p. 10). Crosthwaite et al. (2023) map out the trends in CL research over the past 20 years, finding CADS research to rank highly alongside work studying social media, politics, and news discourse. The bibliometric data reveals the long-lasting impact of the influential researchers and the cumulative effect they have had on emerging researchers who cite their early works (p. 366).

Concordance analysis is widely regarded as a key component of CL research (Gillings & Mautner, 2023, p. 1). A concordance tool can provide a ‘display of every instance of a specified word or other search term in a corpus’ (McEnery & Hardie, 2012, p. 241), also giving the context on either side of the search term. These can be investigated to find any thematic co-selections and how they create meaning (Cheng, 2011, p. 8) and these patterns can be syntactic, semantic, or a combination of both (Gillings & Mautner, 2023, p. 1). To ensure that these conclusions are reliable, researchers must decide

whether to alter their texts, as interpreting the contextual information of concordances can prove challenging. Gillings and Mautner recommend that the researcher flags these decisions to the reader (2023, p. 7).

Collocation tools can also prove to be beneficial in CL research, which is defined as a ‘co-occurrence relationship between two words’ (McEnery & Hardie, 2012, p. 240). The tools can provide data for how frequently words appear near each other and when they are found, they are a result of a single choice, rather than two (Cheng, 2011, p. 77). This suggests that speakers can be predisposed to use certain words in a particular linguistic context, and this can prove interesting to compare across corpora exactly how context-specific it can be.

2.3 Language and Community

A key focus for this research is the idea of language and community. Football fandom is itself a form of community, which exists on multiple levels. How callers manage their identity with regards to their communities is a point of interest, which will be explored linguistically through the lens of pronouns.

Mercer (2007) describes how, amongst other offerings, communities give their members a discourse and a collective identity (p. 108). He adds to Lave and Wenger’s theory of ‘communities of practice’, which are defined as ‘groups which are united by common purposes and who engage in joint activity’ (p. 116), so football fandom is certainly applicable to this idea. Viggiano (2021) applies this model within a corpus analysis, noting that the concept has been adapted to include virtual communities (pp. 59-60). The activities members partake in, and the shared knowledge gained over time, help to contextualise what brings the community together. Mercer posits that there are relations within groups, as new members are ‘trained’ by ‘experts’ (p. 116) and exposure to the narratives of experts helps the new members to ‘speak the discourse’ (p. 117). On the other hand, he reinforces how it is difficult for members to share thoughts which could be deemed unconventional in the discourse (p. 115). Therefore, callers need to manage this carefully if they intend to do so, so they could employ techniques such as vagueness, where the message is implied but able to be defended against if questioned.

Older work also highlights the relevance of language as a means of constructing identity and community. Fairclough (1989) makes a similar identification by mentioning the role of ‘discourse as a social practice’, where ‘the language activity which goes on in social contexts... is *part* of those processes and practices’ (p. 23). This is especially true for a radio phone-in, as language is virtually the only tool for callers to use when communicating through this medium. An interesting theory presented by Fairclough is that of ‘member resources (MR)’ (p. 11), which are socially determined prototypes for typical narrative structures and expected sequences of events. Mercer (2007) identifies another facet of a community being a ‘history’ (p. 108), so the evolution of discourse over time contributes to the typical language that might be used, helping to shape MR. Knowledge of these MR help to give credibility to speakers and position themselves as experts. Fairclough refers to how underlying conventions determine the organisation of discourse (p. 28). Speakers who break these conventions distinguish themselves from the rest of their community and are at risk of being dismissed or ridiculed. The conventions also determine how power is constrained (p. 47) and create power imbalances between established experts and new members.

Plenty of research has analysed the use of pronouns as a means of constructing community. Recently, Hadikin (2020) conducted a corpus analysis of the string ‘we are’ in an online community forum and found writers were ‘primed to use certain strings’ (p. 75). Pavlidou (2014) describes how self-attribution to different groups can be invoked by the pronoun ‘we’, and its use determines those people as a group (p. 7). These can extend over ‘different domains’ (p. 5), so the contextual information is needed to deduce who qualifies and who does not (p. 8).

Other pronouns have proved to be matters of interest, such as in Myers and Lampropoulou’s paper concerning the impersonal ‘you’ (2012). They argue that it is a marker of stance, as well as categorising speakers into groups (p. 1211), similarly to the ‘we’ function. It invokes an idea of shared perception (p. 1212), because the implication is that someone without the experiences of the speaker could expect to see something similar. A useful conclusion is that entitlement to answer a question is key to a speaker’s identity (p. 1216), so this provides another usage where the ultimate function is to build credibility. This could be prevalent in radio phone-ins, as callers need to prove this entitlement by showing how they are qualified to contribute to the programme.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data Selection

Many radio calls were needed to address the research questions and form a sizable corpus of authentic spoken texts. Several radio phone-ins exist in the UK, but the BBC Radio 5 Live programme ‘606’ was chosen due to its reputable status and regular schedule of two programmes on Saturday and Sunday each weekend of the season. As the most recently completed season, the 2022/23 English Premier League (EPL) was chosen to ensure analysis of current language trends on the show. Initially, it was intended to use BBC Sounds as the source of past programmes, but these were deleted at the beginning of the new season in August 2023. Box of Broadcasts (Learning on Screen, 2023) was used instead to reliably collect data.

Based on a small sample to test the forthcoming transcription process, I calculated that I would be able to transcribe calls from 12 programmes in the allocated timeframe. I split these into six Saturday and six Sunday programmes, to ensure as many teams as possible were represented in the corpus. A random number generator was used to generate numbers between six and 38 that aligned with the corresponding rounds in the season. The first five rounds were discounted due to the calls being more prospective, whereas I wanted to focus on callers’ reactions to matches. Three programmes were randomly chosen, but discarded as they did not maximise the number of potential calls in the corpus. For two of these, cup matches dominated the programmes, which were discarded due to the different factors at play in these competitions. Table 1.1 shows the programmes that were chosen and their inclusion.

Table 1.1: Programme inclusion

Round	Sat. Date	Sun. Date	Inclusion in Final Corpus	Reason If Discarded
11	15 th October 2022	16 th October 2022	Yes	
13	22 nd October 2022	23 rd October 2022	Yes	
16	12 th November 2022	13 th November 2022	Yes	
20	14 th January 2023	15 th January 2023	Yes	
25	25 th February 2023	26 th February 2023	No	Cup matches taking place
26	4 th March 2023	5 th March 2023	Yes	
28	18 th March 2023	19 th March 2023	No	Cup matches taking place
31	15 th April 2023	16 th April 2023	Yes	
32	22 nd April 2023	23 rd April 2023	No	One programme this weekend

Once these were identified, I began the transcription process.

3.1.1 First Transcription Stage

After the programmes were requested and available for listening, I noted the caller’s team, result, time stamp, and first name for identification, as well as any potential variable that could mean that call would need to be discarded. Once completed, the criteria for inclusion were decided. The calls were transcribed with several alterations for a thorough corpus analysis, hence they stray from Hammersley’s (2010) idea of ‘strict transcriptions’ (p. 559), so the rationale for each decision will be discussed in turn.

There was an uneven number of callers in the winner’s calls (WC) and loser’s calls (LC), with 70 winner calls compared to 55 loser calls. Three teams were overrepresented, so each was capped at seven calls, therefore the conclusions are representative of all teams, rather than the most popular ones. After balancing, 13 calls were discarded, resulting in a final WC of 57 calls. The study focuses on the EPL only, so fifteen Scottish and lower league English calls were discarded, because they featured too infrequently to judge if fans of these competitions differed in their language use when calling. The largest reason for discarding calls was due to the result being a draw. They are perceived as an in-between outcome, with elements of victory and defeat. Supporters rarely call up afterwards, with them accounting for just over 10% of the total calls, so they were not afforded their own category. The following table shows a breakdown of the reasons some calls were not included.

Table 1.2: Breakdown of discarded calls

Reason	No.	% of Discarded Calls	% of All Calls (166)
Draw	17	31.48%	10.24%
Team Outside of EPL	15	27.78%	9.04%
Corpus Balancing	13	24.07%	7.83%
Team Did Not Play	3	5.56%	1.81%
Debate with Previous Caller	2	3.70%	1.20%
Talking About Different Team	2	3.70%	1.20%
Ethical Concerns	1	1.85%	0.60%
Unfinished Game	1	1.85%	0.60%
Total	54		32.53%

3.1.2 Second Transcription Stage

This stage comprises the automatic transcription of the calls. The duration is determined from the presenters' introductory greeting until they thank the caller for participating. If they are instead cut off without a farewell, the transcription ends with the caller’s final utterance. Interruptions for the news, interviews, or live sport updates are removed, and the transcription continues when the caller is reintroduced. The audio quality of the programme was poor, resulting in difficulty picking up the sound with ordinary speakers. To mitigate this, the calls were played through a Bluetooth speaker and transcribed automatically, using the Otter.ai software (2018).

3.1.3 Third Transcription Stage

The software is not always accurate, so the aim of this stage was to ensure that the transcriptions are an exact replication of what is said by the callers and presenters. I played the audio and paused to make corrections, then listened once more to ensure complete accuracy.

3.1.4 Fourth Transcription Stage

The final stage involved making the final edits before inputting them into a concordancer. This process was intended to make the corpus a better imitation of written language, so the concordance and collocation patterns could be more comparable and consistent between the corpora, so stuttering, repairs, and self-corrections were removed to create more coherent language. Non-standard verb forms were also changed to ensure comparability in the collocation analysis. Repetition for effect, however, was left unchanged. Albeit in a non-academic source, Williams (2018) notes that this is a feature of the English football lexicon, using the example ‘top, top player’ (p. 88). Fillers are a common feature across the transcriptions and, again, as to not disturb the concordance patterns, they are removed when disrupting the flow of speech, but are kept when occurring between clauses to give an idea of a speaker’s potential hesitancy. The final alteration was to retrospectively add subject pronouns that were deleted. As this study analyses pronouns, they are easier to investigate using corpus methods when they are physically present in the texts, instead of being implied.

The texts were converted to individual plain text files to be compatible with the concordance software ‘AntConc’ (Anthony, 2014). The texts were initially separated into two folders, with the winners’ and losers’ calls kept apart for similarities and differences to be found. From this, another two folders were created, but with the presenters’ dialogue removed. As the focus is concerned with supporter discourse, these two corpora will be primarily used, with the full corpora only being used to provide context where it is otherwise not clear. The caller utterances are tagged with a ‘C:’ before they speak.

Table 1.3: *Subcorpora word counts*

Corpus	Word Count
Winners Corpus (WC)	37236
Losers Corpus (LC)	36887
Winners Corpus Callers Only (WCCO)	23584
Losers Corpus Callers Only (LCCO)	24674

Ethics were a great consideration during this process and any identifiable information given by the callers was deleted from the corpus. Any information deemed overly specific was removed, whilst making minimal disruption to the texts. My institution’s ethical procedures were followed, and an ethics form was submitted and signed without issue.

The following table shows a small section of a larger breakdown of the callers in the corpus. The entire table in Appendix 1 shows the information of each caller that determined inclusion.

Table 1.4: *Sample of participants breakdown*

Caller Name	Supported Team	Team Result	Date of Programme	Corpus Inclusion	Discard Reason
Nick	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Tom	Everton	Lost	15 th October	Yes	
Joe	Wolves	Won	15 th October	Yes	

Glyn	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Ollie	Bournemouth	Drew	15 th October	No	Draw
Gareth	Everton	Lost	15 th October	Yes	
Luke	Plymouth	Won	15 th October	No	League One team
Derek	Celtic	Won	15 th October	No	Scottish team
Jo	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Matthew	Wolves	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Tom	Plymouth	Won	15 th October	No	League One team
Bart	Manchester City	Did not play	15 th October	No	Did not play

Including a diverse range of teams allows for a comprehensive profile of football supporters throughout England. Due to the fanbase sizes, some teams will form a larger part of the corpus. An advantage of the large corpus is that virtually all the teams in the league were represented at least once, but due to their results appeared more in one compared to the other. The only team that did not appear was Southampton. This was not remedied to avoid cherry picking data and it would not have been time effective to find a Southampton caller in another programme.

Table 1.5: *Representation of teams in subcorpora*

Team	No. of calls in WC Before Balancing	No. of Calls in WC	No. of Calls in LC
Arsenal	12	7	0
Aston Villa	4	4	2
Bournemouth	1	1	0
Brentford	1	1	0
Brighton	2	2	3
Chelsea	6	6	5
Crystal Palace	1	1	3
Everton	2	2	7
Fulham	0	0	1
Leeds	0	0	2
Leicester	1	1	4
Liverpool	13	7	4
Manchester City	6	6	4
Manchester United	9	7	2
Newcastle	3	3	2
Nottingham Forest	2	2	2
Southampton	0	0	0
Tottenham	5	5	8
West Ham	0	0	4
Wolves	2	2	2
Total	70	57	55

3.2 Analytical Approach

Corpus analysis is the primary analytical tool that will be utilised in this analysis. More specifically, a CADS framework is applied to investigate the discourse of football phone-ins. The analysis forms a hybrid between quantitative and qualitative methods, with the preconception of a focus on pronouns allowing for a more refined study, but what is found in the corpus itself will be used in whatever form it takes to answer the research questions. What is considered an interesting finding is subjective to the researcher, so themes of credibility and stance will be prioritised as they link directly to the outlined research questions.

3.2.1 *Concordance*

The ability to analyse ‘key words in context’ is a feature of AntConc that will be used. A certain word or phrase can be searched in the concordancer and a given number of words context on both sides, providing an ordered presentation for the linguistic environment the search term can be found in. In this analysis, pronouns will be the input to find concordance patterns on both sides. This allows for patterns to be found by making connections between the words appearing around the search term.

3.2.2 *Collocation*

The collocation tool enables more focused analysis, as it provides the most frequent words that appear directly alongside others. For this analysis, pronouns will again form the input into this tool, with collocation patterns on either side. More specifically, the right side will likely provide more interesting patterns. Due to the *Subject-Verb-Object* sentence structure in English, subject pronouns will often begin sentences, so the preceding word will be separate and unrelated. By this definition, verbs will be expected to occur alongside subject pronouns, so they will be analysed to see what they achieve in interaction. This is a useful starting point for research, as it gives an idea of the kinds of terms that are worth analysing using the more precise tools.

4 Analysis

The collocation results were able to be separated into six categories, based on their word class and thematic meaning. These are shown in tables throughout this analysis, with the numbers corresponding to their ranking according to AntConc’s likelihood measure. The totals are not consistent for each pronoun, so Table 2 shows the total number of collocates for each. The numbers were capped at 30, as to not overwhelm the reader with data.

Table 2: *Collocation totals*

Corpus	I	We	You	They
WCCO	30	23	17	11
LCCO	30	23	10	15

4.1 Constructing Stance

4.1.1 *Opinion Markers*

Table 3.1: *Winners Corpus opinion markers*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
-----------	---	----	-----	------

agree	15			
feel	18			
knew	26			
know	20		1	
look			3	
love	10			
mean	3			
need		20		
needed		23		
reckon	28			
think	1		13	
thought	7			
wanted	12			

Table 3.2: *Losers Corpus opinion markers*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
agree	16			
believe	12			
expected	29			
feel	20			
hate	22			
hope	26			
know	15		1	
look			8	
love	25			
mean	3			
need		4		
seemed				11
suppose	18			
think	1			
thought	7			

The primary manner of realising stance is through opinion markers. The tables show slight variation in the markers used, with those in bold indicating they collocate in both corpora. Many of the corpus-specific collocates are different word forms or synonyms for more common terms. The most interesting to note are the LC rankings of the very negative ‘hate’ and the slightly sceptical ‘suppose’. These collocates show a preference for callers talking about their thoughts and emotions to the hosts and listeners. This phenomenon tends to be realised in the ‘I’ environment, which is understandable as the caller cannot speak on behalf of those who agree or disagree; they cannot say what is going on in *their* heads, so instead bring others into the conversation in other collocation categories. The verb ‘know’ ranks highest out of all second person ‘you’ collocations, with ‘look’ also featuring in the list. A vast number of callers will frequently use ‘you know’ as a filler between clauses, with the goal of enticing support from the hosts. If the hosts respond with agreement, this greatly benefits the callers, who could be seen as putting their point across successfully. The verb ‘need’ only collocates with the first-person

plural pronoun ‘we’, the only feature for both terms. Furthermore, ‘they’ only collocates with ‘seemed’ in the LC.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 CarHASTWon51C.txt	mention today, I heard the Tottenham fan going on about his owner and whatever and	I think it	s time that people celebrated the Villa owners, and also Chris Purslow,
2 JohnnyMCIWon55C.txt	time last year. They had top four in their hands and then they bottled it.	I think it	s the same thing. I think it's all well and good
3 JohnnyMCIWon55C.txt	in their hands and then they bottled it. I think it's the same thing.	I think it	s all well and good to have a blip but at this
4 MichaelLWWon45C.txt	in every competition last year until the last minute. There was a World Cup and	I think it	s a wee bit of burnout. I think they were meant to
5 MichaelLWWon45C.txt	I think they were meant to have a few players playing in the World Cup.	I think it	s a wee bit of burnout, but the right man's there.
6 MoCHEWon42C.txt	You know, what he did for the club in that year was just amazing, but	I think it	s pointless sacking Potter now when I think it's more of
7 MoCHEWon42C.txt	that year was just amazing, but I think it's pointless sacking Potter now when	I think it	s more of a backwards step. I think if we can get
8 MoCHEWon42C.txt	I think with the new signings as well and the interviews that he's had	I think it	s fair to say that he should be sacked. I don't
9 PatrickARSWon37C.txt	come back from injury. So we're vulnerable. We're ahead, but we're vulnerable,	I think it	s okay to say that, yeah.
10 PhilARSWon35C.txt	again. And United for me, they're third or fourth or whatever they are, but	I think it	s between us and United.
11 ShazARSWon34C.txt	Hi, Robbie. Hi, Chris. Yeah,	I think it	s a great performance. Every week I think maybe we're not
12 ShazARSWon34C.txt	but then after about four or five weeks into the season, I start believing and	I think it	s about time all the Arsenal fans start believing now and I
13 YayaARSWon44C.txt	twenty six games. So it's an amazing time to be an Arsenal fan. And	I think it	s incredible to see the progress within the last three years since
14 YayaARSWon44C.txt	s incredible to see the progress within the last three years since Arteta came and	I think it	s a lesson for all the clubs to really believe in the
15 MichaelLWWon45C.txt	the league cup. Good luck to him. We beat United seven nil today. Chris, yeah,	I think it	has been burnout. I mean, we played every game last year right
16 DamonASTWon26C.txt	have worked something out, personally. I was never one to get on his back and	I think it	is that sort of balance between "is it the manager, is it
17 MarkBREWon22C.txt	Brentford side is gonna turn up, that's the trouble, but I tell you what	I think it	is. Last season we lost one nil at home and two nil
18 MatthewWOLWon5C.txt	you ask what's Wolves' identity now, I'm not sure I could answer that.	I think it	just looks a bit messy at times and I think Nuno would
19 NickTOTWon1C.txt	m just saying I saw it and I don't think it was a penalty.	I think it	was a bit of a coming together. I think the VAR shouldn't
20 MatthewWOLWon5C.txt	old son and we've been bickering about it all week, gents, to be honest.	I think it	would be a good move to get him back. I think people
21 DaveASTWon17C.txt	can be quite fickle, as you know. Yeah it's a massive call, especially considering	I think it	s his first actual Premier League game in charge of a club.
22 JohnnyMCIWon55C.txt	difference there. I don't think after the loss, well it's a draw but	I think it	s a loss, I think he shouldn't have said it straight
23 ThomasEVEWon16C.txt	today, great performance by Everton today. Calvert-Lewin especially coming back made a big difference,	I think it	was a fantastic goal. We sit in the paddock, which is near

Figure 1.1: *Winners corpus 'I think it' concordance.*

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 AlexASTLost9C.txt	everything he's got and I'm afraid it was awful. It was absolutely diabolical.	I think it	s the lack of coaching and that's why the manager has
2 BenLEELost13C.txt	Gnonto now feel, you know, he's not played, a full Italian international. Helpful? Do	I think it	s helpful? I don't think it's hurtful. I don't
3 BrianLEELost43C.txt	Southampton didn't have to play until the following night. Yeah, not because of football,	I think it	s just because of the rules now. That stupid thing, I mean,
4 DuncanCRYLost10C.txt	now after, last week, we just scraped by Wolves. I just want Vieira gone now.	I think it	s just an absolute shambles. Vieira gone. Absolutely. Absolutely, I think the
5 JamesEVELost28C.txt	comes out today of all days when the fans are having a sit in protest,	I think it	s convenient that all of a sudden, all this comes out, and
6 JamieCHELost19C.txt	he is now and I think he needs the time he needs at Chelsea and	I think it	s a rebuild for us and if we give him the time
7 JamieMUNLost44C.txt	on the linesman, that's really disappointing and I think I agree with you, Chris.	I think it	s a really bad day. I think United will be fine and,
8 KevinWOLLost15C.txt	was being told what players he's got to bring in or what have you.	I think it	s still the same now, the signings they've made. No, I
9 LouisTOTLost35C.txt	pains me to say, but I think this is partly down to Conte, but equally	I think it	s a much bigger issue at Tottenham than that. I think this
10 SimonLIVLost8C.txt	like to think that I'm not, like children, get influenced by bad role models.	I think it	s completely correct. I agree with you. I tell the boys in
11 TazTOTLost34C.txt	know, pressure is on. Lloris, it's time to go, sorry. You retired from France,	I think it	s time to go from Spurs as well. Thank you very much.
12 LeeCHELost51C.txt	percentages. A percentagician. I don't want to say it again. Maybe forty nine percent.	I think it	could be. What did you say? Yeah, a percentagician. No, that's
13 NickTOTLost50C.txt	can change the formation, you can try changing something, but he just never did. And	I think it	got to the stage where he had so much going on in
14 DeanMCILost53C.txt	weren't as direct as we were, sort of slowing it down quite a lot.	I think it	is the fear of in behind because we do have the high
15 MichaelEVELost47C.txt	Evening, guys. I think I've been at a historic game today in that	I think it	will be the last ever three o'clock kickoff on a Saturday
16 LeeCHELost51C.txt	at me. Right, look at the table. We're closer to relegation than the top.	I think it	s nine points now. If they win their game in hand, And
17 PatrickCRYLost37C.txt	you know, there needs to be a change at the Palace. Yeah, I think so.	I think it	s time. Well, what's he done? What's he done this
18 PennyNEWLost46C.txt	Brentford are and I would love to see someone like Brentford really, really do well.	I think it	s the latter of those, Robbie. I really do. I think Manchester

Figure 1.2: *Losers Corpus 'I think it' concordance.*

The principal, most common stance construction is shown by concordance lines for ‘I think’. Due to its vast frequency in the corpus, the search term is more refined to pinpoint a more specific pattern, which can be gleaned from the concordance for ‘I think it’. As mentioned, this is an integral construction that callers can employ to convey their opinion and would often provide a brief synopsis of the reason they called into the programme. Thornborrow (2001, p. 134) observed that hosts can judge whether a caller has supplied a sufficient answer, so their role is to prevent a caller from going on irrelevant ramblings. To clarify their point, callers deploy an ‘I think’ structure that grants them the ability to summarise the

argument they wanted to make. It is a mutual benefit, because a direct and to-the-point call will be easier to interpret and support, but also helps the hosts, who are not needed to intervene in the organisation of the call and can manoeuvre between callers more easily. The actual construction itself tends to show a polarising attitude and as could be expected, the winners tend to be more positive, exemplified by lines 11, 13, and 23, and the losers are very negative in 4, 7, and 9. The winners themselves are a little more measured, whereas the emotion of defeat can result in an extreme call. When assessing the actual context of when this construction is used, it becomes clear that it mostly expresses the opinion on the recent match or the state of the team’s season. The caller can impart information that the listener might not know or have realised, helping, amongst a fandom, to share thoughts between the group. In a method of callers negotiating the power imbalance between themselves and the expert hosts, they make judgements on what is acceptable to say. They position themselves equally as experts by being able to critically form an opinion on the discussion at hand. It could also be a way of carefully managing a more controversial opinion, such as WC 8 and 9. Versteeg and te Molder (2018, p. 719) acknowledge that radio phone-ins deviate from face-to-face conversation, as hosts actively engage in confrontation, so callers need to manage alternative opinions to defend against this disputation.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	and then obviously we did spend in the January that he was there, but then	you look	at the back five. We've got our back five there, only four
2 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	back five there. We bought obviously Bruno Guimaraes in, as well, and Chris Wood. Then	you look	at the injuries, also, that Newcastle have suffered. No Saint-Maximin, Guimaraes has
3 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	ve conceded the least goals. So, let me put this across to you then. If	you look	at the Newcastle squad, and you look at Arsenal, Liverpool, Manchester City and
4 JaydenNEWWon20C.txt	I liked him a lot, but he tends to go on the right side and	you look	at the ones alongside him, Stones right side, Kyle Walker right side. I
5 JohnTOTWon23C.txt	to be patient, you want to, but then there's another side of it where	you look	at the evidence with your eyes and what you see and you're
6 MatthewCHEWon40C.txt	just heartbreaking to see the way they are, the way they're playing. And when	you look	at the likes of Mason Mount, we're probably going to lose Mason
7 ThomasEVEWon16C.txt	ten, I wouldn't say any higher than that for this season. I think if	you look	at the top six, it's going to be very difficult for anyone
8 MoCHEWon42C.txt	and I don't think he deserves to be sacked after just a tough season.	You look	at the injuries that we've had this season. I mean, some of
9 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	manage those big personalities when you've got big players in the teams, but when	you look	at when Eddie Howe came in obviously took over Steve Bruce, Newcastle at
10 JaydenNEWWon20C.txt	opinions on this. When they talk about a left sided centre back. Exactly, I mean,	you look	at when Southgate took over England, he said 'I'll consider players playing
11 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	me put this across to you then. If you look at the Newcastle squad, and	you look	at Arsenal, Liverpool, Manchester City and even Tottenham we'll include, and Liverpool
12 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	the Premier League, which I would never have said at the start of season. When	you look	at it really, obviously we've played a game more, so net, probably
13 PeterMUNWon33C.txt	because by the rules of the law, he wasn't interfering with play and if	you look	at ref's guide, the ref's guide said there's actually a
14 ShaunLIVWon10C.txt	score the goals, he's putting them on a plate for players all the time.	You look	at Salah, his assists and his goals are always near the top. Now
15 JaydenNEWWon20C.txt	blessed with left sided defenders, Robbie and Chris, they're not. So, I mean, when	you look	at that squad now, Conor Coady, I liked him a lot, but he
16 BeniLIVWon47C.txt	ve got Gakpo, we've got Nunez, we've got young lads. But then if	you look	at those who are going to be leaving, Bobby Firmino, that's a
17 MatthewWOLWon5C.txt	think the whole world, including him, in his head was all over the shop. If	you look	back before that, we were super organised, right, we had it, we had
18 AaronMUNWon25C.txt	I'm very well, Chris, how are you doing? Robbie, how are	you? Look,	I know Chris said a seven, me personally I would give him a

Figure 1.3: *Winners Corpus 'you look' concordance.*

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 BrianLEILost43C.txt	They are rubbish. Well, I mean, in the Premiership we have, they're shocking. If	you look	at it, Ileanacho should have had four. No, they didn't play us.
2 DuncanCRYLOst10C.txt	the best teams in South London, aren't we? I think so. I mean, when	you look	at it, we've been in the League for long enough now. I
3 BernardWHULost32C.txt	that immensely. I don't think he's used Paqueta in his best position. Really,	you look	at the way he played for Brazil in the World Cup and I
4 LindonEVELost31C.txt	saying is, right, there's players out there, that will come to Everton, because if	you look	at the top teams, right, that are in the top half of the
5 JimTOTLost33C.txt	But my point for today, ringing up, Chris, was, I believe, truthfully, that you know,	you look	at Arteta at Arsenal. He's got Arsenal blood flowing through his veins.
6 TonyMCILost18C.txt	last five. I take your point, I know what you're saying, Phil Foden, if	you look	at him, he's constantly looking to pass the ball to Erling Haaland.
7 ChristianTOTLost48C.txt	top of League One now, looking like they might get into the Championship and then	you look	at Levy building Mario Kart courses underneath the stadium and all the rest

Figure 1.4: *Losers corpus 'you look' concordance.*

Diverting focus to second person pronouns, the frequent collocation of a ‘you look’ structure is worth attention. It becomes immediately apparent that the referent is vague, a function researched extensively by Myers and Lampropoulou (2012). They note that the person or people being addressed in interaction are the usual referent when ‘you’ is used, but another use they define as ‘a kind of impersonal reference that does not pick out any particular person, but is the equivalent of someone, anyone, or one’ (p. 1206). In the present corpora, this construction conveys an opinion that the caller deems to be obvious and

assumes that the hosts and listeners would agree, such as WC 7, 13, and 17. The meaning of the verb ‘look’ is not meant literally; the caller does not want the listener to see something but is instead concerned with noticing a certain pattern. By deploying an imperative or conditional structure, as in the above cases with ‘if’ featuring immediately before the search term, the caller outlines a method that anyone would be able to follow and come to the same conclusion. This phenomenon is mirrored in Myers and Lampropoulou (2012, p. 1210), who suggest that the speakers recategorise themselves into a more general set of people to give the impression that many other people would relay the same message if they were in the same scenario. Alternatively, someone without these experiences could experience it for the first time and expect to see what the interlocutor has described. The caller positions themselves as an expert by being able to comment on an experience as shared, which itself bolsters the argument by invoking the stance of other people. They are presenting themselves as able to accurately interpret the matters at hand and transfer that information to others. It tends to be more common in the WC, with both corpora employing positive and negative stances. As before, the LC is a little more polarising, with humour used to mock players and owners. This is not present in the WC, so shows how the losers call the programme as a way of dealing with the negative emotions associated with a poor result.

4.1.2 Auxiliary Verbs

Table 4.1: *Winners Corpus auxiliary verbs*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
am/are	11	17		6
did		14		
didn't	25	13		10
do	22			
don't	4		11	
had		4		
'm/'re	2	1	2	1
've	5	2	5	2
was/were	8	3	17	3
wasn't/weren't				5

Table 4.2: *Losers Corpus auxiliary verbs*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
am/are	10			4
did				
didn't		15		13
don't	4	18	9	
had		9		
have		20		
haven't		7		12
'm/'re	2	2	2	1
've	6	1	3	2
was/were	13	3		3

wasn't/weren't				7
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The grammatical function of auxiliary verbs means that there is little variation between the corpora. It is natural for them to provide common collocations due to their high frequency and necessity in some tense constructions. This collocation category has a hybrid function, invoking both stance *and* credibility. The credibility element will be explored in Section 4.2. The different word forms are paired, because they have the exact same meanings, and the difference is only grammatical. The only significant difference is shown by the increased chance of ‘haven’t’ collocating in the LC, ranking highly in the ‘we’ environment. It might have been expected to see a comparative increase in negated auxiliary verbs in the LC, but this example is the only one that shows an indication of this being the case. When comparing between pronouns, the ‘I’ environment shows a higher quantity of collocations in the WC, but a lower quantity of ‘we’ collocations. Overall, contracted forms are preferred, hinting at a potentially informality in the genre. This opposes the patterns identified by Hadikin (2020), who found a high level of formality to show expertise and education. This is also a desired intention of radio callers but is realised in different ways.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 JohnnyMCIWon55C.txt	one of our famous runs that we've done in the last few years. And	we're going	to win the Premier League and then in the FA Cup Manchester
2 ShazARSWon41C.txt	for you as well. Do you think where Arsenal were last season and considering when	we're going	to win, I'm not going to say if because I think
3 YayaARSWon44C.txt	of atmosphere, I think is making a difference to Arsenal. I'm not gonna say	we're going	to win the league. We obviously should, from where we are now.
4 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	your league cup win. So what, you won a league cup. My point is that	we're going	nowhere. I'm a Liverpool fan, I've been a Liverpool fan
5 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	done over the last few years, Bobby's been in the middle of it all.	We're going	nowhere. We're here forever, Robbie, We're never going to stop.
6 DamonASTWon26C.txt	been awful at the start of the season. But for the last couple of weeks,	we're going	into the break happy, so up the Villa. Do I think we'
7 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	re going nowhere. I'm a Liverpool fan, I've been a Liverpool fan from 1973.	We're going	nowhere and, okay, we beat United seven nil today but I expected
8 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	He should be happy. But they got beat seven nil today, by the mighty reds,	we're going	nowhere, right, and I was saying to a guy the other day.
9 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	We're going nowhere. We're here forever, Robbie, We're never going to stop.	We're going	nowhere. Of course. You think a manager that's won a few
10 JohnnyMCIWon55C.txt	easy because Arsenal are bottling it, they're bottling it right now. And I think	we're going	on a run, one of our famous runs that we've done
11 YayaARSWon44C.txt	it really is when you have a clear vision, when you have a clear synergy	we're gonna	achieve so it's incredible. I'm really over the moon. No.
12 BenLIVWon47C.txt	sat on the edge of our seats thinking "oh they're gonna lose the ball,	we're gonna	do this", you know, I think Konate, going back into that back
13 EmmaNFWon32C.txt	He got us promoted last year, he took us to Wembley. I don't think	we're gonna	forget that. What, jealousy that we have stayed up? How many years
14 JoshARSWon39C.txt	game. At two nil down, yeah, of course you would because you were thinking "right	we're gonna	lose this, our lead is only going to be two points". But
15 AaronMUNWon25C.txt	week saved, we can maybe go and get the likes of Ivan Toney and now	we're gonna	pay more than we would have at the start of the season.
16 JoeWOLWon2C.txt	nineteen, twenty year old injury prone player from Colombia, so I don't know who	we're gonna	play. I don't want to play boring, round the back, defensive
17 ShazARSWon41C.txt	confirms what I knew a couple of months ago that this season is ours and	we're gonna	win the title and more and more people are starting to believe.

Figure 2.1: *Winners Corpus 'we're go*' concordance.*

	File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	DannyFULLost24.txt	re overachieving. There's going to be a point for the season, coming up, where	we're going	to drop points, hundred percent. It's going to come up. At
2	EmmaCHELost54C.txt	I've seen us win the league and I've got to be happy that	we're going	to be a mid table team. I'm going on Tuesday against
3	GarethEVElost2C.txt	and Pickford knew that. Kane's done nothing wrong. I mean I'm Welsh, so	we're going	to be playing Harry Kane in the World Cup and I'd
4	JamesEVElost28C.txt	come out in midweek and back him one hundred percent, then that says to me,	we're going	to stick with him. Now the fans have also got to stick
5	JamieCHELost19C.txt	every faith in Graham Potter. I think he just needs that time and I think	we're going	to do well. I think we can do well.
6	NickTOTLost50C.txt	I ain't going anywhere near that, Jesus Christ'. So I don't know who	we're going	to end up with. I guarantee we'll end up with either
7	PennyNEWLost46C.txt	degree are pretty much a well established team and we all pretty much know what	we're going	to get. With those others it's a surprise, isn't it?
8	SimonWHULost41C.txt	of us had to stay up there because we couldn't get a train back.	We're going	to Cyprus next week. I didn't go today because I'm
9	MarkLEILost30C.txt	give him a lot of money. But if they don't give him that money,	we're going	down or, we're like James the Everton fan was saying, we'
10	ChrisLIVLost26C.txt	can pull them back up. He hasn't done it in five months, has he?	We're going	down. We're eighth. You know, teams like Villa, who lost to
11	JamieMUNLost44C.txt	Liverpool are playing for nothing. I know they've had their cup final today, but	we're going	in different directions, I think. Liverpool, fair play to them, but we
12	ChrisLIVLost26C.txt	Got Wolves next week, replay, then we've got Chelsea. I can't really see	we're gonna	get anything out of that. So we've had five months, this
13	PatLIVLost29C.txt	team driving forward. And it was almost like "come on lads, do your best but	we're gonna	get nothing out of this game today". Teams don't train to
14	PatLIVLost29C.txt	top four is a bitter pill, really. Fourth, yes, I mean, I don't think	we're gonna	get any higher than fourth and we'd be lucky to do
15	MichaelCRYLost39C.txt	I mean, come on. Palace is always gonna be a mid table team. You know,	we're gonna	be there. If we can stay up, for me, that's a
16	MichaelCRYLost39C.txt	there. If we can stay up, for me, that's a bonus and anyone thinks	we're gonna	go into Europe or do anything better, I mean, they need to
17	GordonNEWLost49C.txt	game at St. James' on Sunday. It's not far from Izmir. That's where	we're going.	I think so, yes. I'll catch you when I come back,

Figure 2.2: Losers Corpus 'we're go*' concordance.

The environment of 'we're going' and the contracted 'we're gonna' show some of the clearest contrasts between winning and losing. By employing this structure, they are referring to something that the caller predicts will happen in the near future. The callers' goals are to remind people that their team is at their peak and will be staying there for the foreseeable future. In the WC, this construction is usually concerned with a prediction of success, where the team wins an individual game or a piece of silverware, such as in 1, 3, and 11. By using the first-person plural pronoun, the supporters identify their own role in propelling their team to success. They see it as a reward for their loyal support and will position themselves alongside the team to celebrate their achievements. This helps to galvanise the fanbase because they feel part of the community. In the LC, a sense of pessimism prevails in 1, 9, 10, and 14, with the callers expecting a worst-case scenario, even mentioning relegation in some calls. The recency bias of these callers seeing their team lose results in a difficulty to compartmentalise, as it is not so simple to stay positive after defeat.

	File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	BenCRYWon50C.txt	at the moment. Why wouldn't you be? The Gallagher hole was huge. You know,	you don't	know how big a hole is until there isn't someone standing
2	MichaelIIVWon45C.txt	than him. I had you on last night and the Arsenal fan, he was blind.	You don't	know what that wee lad is sitting there, talking to you. I
3	DaveMCIWon49C.txt	to do and occasionally that's not going to work. When you go out and	you don't	do what your manager wants and you don't play as a
4	DaveMCIWon49C.txt	and occasionally you have a bad day and you draw one one with Forest, but	you don't	have a bad day and lose seven nil. So do you seriously
5	DanieNEWWon18C.txt	of those Newcastle players would go into any of those squads? Absolutely, you're right.	You don't	know, but I would say from the argument it's always gonna
6	DamonASTWon26C.txt	saying in the dressing room or in training was actually causing negativity among the players,	you don't	know. All I can say is that I'm absolutely buzzing. It'
7	DaveMCIWon49C.txt	work. When you go out and you don't do what your manager wants and	you don't	play as a team, which is what he's done today. It'
8	BenLIVWon47C.txt	it's a different ballgame wherever you play, but you've got to believe. If	you don't,	then there's no point watching the match. Yeah, I mean like
9	CarlASTWon51C.txt	clubs. Look what's happening to Everton. You don't get Everton, occasionally you will,	you don't	get the Villa fans phoning in, these heritage clubs, phoning in. And
10	CarlASTWon51C.txt	suffered and you know, there's lots of clubs. Look what's happening to Everton.	You don't	get Everton, occasionally you will, you don't get the Villa fans
11	MichaelIIVWon45C.txt	is number one to gurn, he's the champion and he pushed the lines, man.	You don't	do that, I don't think Robbie even did that. You don'
12	MichaelIIVWon45C.txt	lines, man. You don't do that, I don't think Robbie even did that.	You don't	push the lines, man. No, I don't think he should be
13	PeterNEWWon38C.txt	No, don't go "mhm", they're a good team, but that's another thing.	You don't	want to talk about Mr Cleeve on the radio right now. I

Figure 2.3: Winners Corpus 'you don't' concordance.

	File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	TomMCILost27C.txt	thinking "oh, we've got to give it to him again" or whatever, you know,	you don't	know what's going on. So I wasn't looking forward to
2	TomMCILost27C.txt	possibly, the point you said about Haaland, is that playing on the player's mind?	You don't	know if they're thinking "oh, we've got to give it
3	MarkLEILost30C.txt	be any in between. Well, if you don't want to give him money, because	you don't	trust him because I've got to be quite honest, some of
4	MarkLEILost30C.txt	in a lot of trouble like they are. So get a new man in if	you don't	trust him. Yeah, that's the thing. The only name and I
5	ChristianTOTLost48C.txt	know, I mean, what do you expect if you get rid of a manager and	you don't	have another one lined up and you're prepared to let the
6	BrianLEILost43C.txt	offside trap completely and you'll have far more entertaining football. But you would, because	you don't	need these silly linesmen because they can't even get a corner
7	AndyBRILost7C.txt	striker did that to their defender that goal would have been ruled out straight away.	You don't	push a player just to get past them. He flattened him to
8	AndyBRILost7C.txt	their defenders that goal would have been disallowed. It is a push on a player.	You don't	push, you can't, because you're not allowed to. Any tackle
9	AndyBRILost7C.txt	t push a player just to get past them. He flattened him to the ground.	You don't	think it was a foul? That's fair if that's your
10	MarkLEILost30C.txt	to back him. I don't think there can be any in between. Well, if	you don't	want to give him money, because you don't trust him because
11	MichaelLIVLost6C.txt	a Scottish kiss on someone and I bet you regretted doing that, didn't you?	You don't	think you did? Well, you must've done something you regretted. Yeah.

Figure 2.4: Losers Corpus 'you don't' concordance.

Once again, the use of the second person 'you' shows an impersonal function when collocating with 'don't', but more often targets a specific entity as an attribution of blame. The impersonal function usually occurs when the caller wants to express doubt, collocating in a longer string of 'you don't know' in the top concordances. The implication of this use is that it is impossible for a layperson to come to conclusions in the scenario. It is, of course, not the intention of the caller to represent themselves as a layperson and is instead to outline a negative stance, referring to the unintelligible chaos at the club, where even expert fans have no better understanding than a less knowledgeable supporter. As for the attribution of blame, it is a goal of phone-in callers to assess who was worthy of blame or praise. The assessed entities encompass the players, managers, owners, and officiators, shown by 2, 6, and 10 in the LC. A handful of collocations add to the discourse about refereeing decisions, using a 'you don't' construction as a way of making the rules seem clearer, including 6, 7, 8, and 9 in the LC. The negative stances suggest that certain players were cheating, which deflects from the poor result suffered by the callers' teams. The hosts are referred to sparingly, showing an unwillingness to challenge the power imbalance. In the LC, interrogatives are also deployed in the use of this structure in 9 and 11, which is less face-threatening for the hosts, because they can easily disagree when they answer the question. Alternatively, if the point was put across via a declarative, it would be more difficult for the addressee to interrupt and refute the claim.

4.1.3 Experience Markers

Table 5.1: Winners Corpus experience markers

Collocate	I	We	You	They
beat		16		
lose		19		
played		5		8
saw	14			
tried				7
win		9		

Table 5.2: Losers Corpus experience markers

Collocate	I	We	You	They
backed		17		
chose				9
finished		23		

gambled				10
lost		8		
played		22		
turned	27			
won		9		

Experience markers are perhaps the most inclusive of the collocation categories. I propose this term as a description of the types of verbs that are tangible and able to be proved or disproved. They relate to physical experiences that are not mental. As with auxiliary verbs, their function is hybrid and pertains to both stance and credibility. The distinction between these functions is simple, with stance being invoked through the collocations of verbs relating to the actual sport. On the other hand, credibility is instead concerned with verbs that are more general and have nothing inherently to do with football, which are analysed in Section 4.2. As a result of the high number of potential verbs that this category could include, there is little overlap between corpora. The frequency of the collocations is not particularly high, but they tend to occur in the ‘we’ and ‘they’ environments.

The only comparable collocation is the ‘we played’ structure. It occurs infrequently in the LC, but interestingly is not indicative of a negative stance in 1 and 3. Despite appearing rarely, these callers attempt to find a positive when the result was poor, describing how the team played well or a tactical change that had an impact. This is also infrequent in the WC, but there is again a noticeable lack of negative stances being taken. Most of the collocations occur when a different team is the object of the verb phrase, where the recent game is compared to a historical one.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 CarIASTWon51C.txt	There were probably fifty thousand people in there, it was just cramped, people walking, when	we played	Barcelona in 1977, I think or '78. And we were two nil down with ten
2 CarIASTWon51C.txt	never walked out, I was with my dad, I was about seven years old when	we played	Barcelona. There were probably fifty thousand people in there, it was just cramped,
3 MichaelLIVWon48C.txt	expecting today, the performance I saw. It was completely a million miles away from when	we played	Brentford. We didn't turn up. When we played Brighton, we didn't
4 MichaelLIVWon48C.txt	a million miles away from when we played Brentford. We didn't turn up. When	we played	Brighton, we didn't turn up. When I was at Wolves, we just
5 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	beat United seven nil today. Chris, yeah, I think it has been burnout. I mean,	we played	every game last year right to the last minute. We were in every
6 MatthewWOLWon5C.txt	we had some great results. And I just think watching the game today, yes, but	we played	okay in the first half but we lack organisation in the second half
7 DaveMCIWon49C.txt	this point onwards they will fall to pieces. No, they played really good football. No,	we played	really well. We made loads of chances and what happens in football is
8 MatthewWOLWon5C.txt	were super organised, right, we had it, we had an identity, we had an organisation,	we played	some really good yes, okay, it was counter attacking, but when we went
9 PhilARSWon35C.txt	because Tottenham are so hit and miss. I knew we would get a result today.	We played	them off the park and we were just our brilliant self again. And
10 StuartNFOWon21C.txt	we got, you know, the arm was outstretched, to save him from going offside, but	we played	well, Chris, and the enthusiasm in the team. I mean, I sit in

Figure 3.1: Winners Corpus ‘we played’ concordance

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 JedMCILOst38C.txt	seem to press well. We're better without a forward, that was proved last season.	We played	better without a forward. It's gonna be close. Yes.
2 TonyMCILOst18C.txt	two seasons. Once Sergio Aguero went, we've got nobody else and that's how	we played	it, the false number nine. So yeah, we've just taken a little
3 MichaelCRVLOst39C.txt	the team of the eighties. I mean, it's a long time ago. I thought	we played	really well today, we lost, fair play, but I actually thought we showed
4 JimTOTLOst33C.txt	got man of the match. It was like we didn't play that badly, but	we played	the second half and the issue I've got is it was a
5 DerekLEELOst33C.txt	have gone out and got a striker because all they did, Rodrigo, if you remember,	we played	Tuesday night or Wednesday night and then Rodrigo got injured, then they were

Figure 3.2: Losers Corpus ‘we played’ concordance.

4.1.4 Modal Verbs

Table 6.1: Winners Corpus modal verbs

Collocate	I	We	You	They
can	16	8	4	
could		21	8	

'd	17	15		
'll	9	7		
might		22		
should		6		
will				11
would	6	18		

Table 6.2: Losers Corpus modal verbs

Collocate	I	We	You	They
can	14	5	4	
could		12		8
couldn't		21		
'd	5	16		
'll	17	6		5
should		14		6
will		10		
would	11			

Wiggins (2017, p. 173) defines modal verbs as verbs that implicate the speaker’s degree of ability, obligation, intention, or permission to be able to perform an activity. As with auxiliary verbs, there is a limited repertoire of verbs available to the speaker, so there is little difference between the corpora for these verbs themselves. The majority fall in the ‘we’ environment, with little variety in the frequencies of the collocations. A more striking difference, however, is the variation between the verbs that collocate with the third person ‘they’ pronoun, with ‘should’ and ‘could’ appearing in the LC but not WC. A limitation of AntConc is how it splits negated contractions into two words, meaning some verbs cannot be identified in a collocation list, such as the distinction between ‘can’ and ‘can’t’.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	gonna happen is, you see the teams around us, they know we've done it,	we can	do it and we've done it before and I won't say
2 BenLIVWon47C.txt	we've got to change from doubters to believers, you know, and I totally think	we can	do that. No, I think ninety five percent is a bit of a
3 MoCHEWon42C.txt	Potter now when I think it's more of a backwards step. I think if	we can	get Europa League football this season, I'm hoping, that will be a
4 JohnnyMCIWon55C.txt	Champions League this year purely because of Erling Haaland, I think, is Real Madrid. If	we can	get past Real Madrid, I think we win it. And I know that'
5 JoshARSWon39C.txt	re gonna lose this, our lead is only going to be two points". But if	we can	grab a point it'll be three at least but to turn that
6 AaronMUNWon25C.txt	needs to go in January. That's what four, five hundred k a week saved,	we can	maybe go and get the likes of Ivan Toney and now we're
7 ThomasEVEWon16C.txt	I have to say that he's been brilliant this season. I would say that	we can	push towards the top ten, I wouldn't say any higher than that
8 PaulLEIWon24C.txt	stuff like that and he's found his feet a bit now and then hopefully	we can	recruit in January again.
9 MoCHEWon42C.txt	he'd had the summer transfer window, and early next season, I think, is when	we can	start saying is Potter the right man for Chelsea. I think this season,
10 PatrickARSWon37C.txt	I do, but I know that it's not a shoo in. Now, of course	we can	win it but I would say the game against Manchester United coming up
11 GlynTOTWon3C.txt	you very much, Chris, we didn't rate you very highly; No, to be fair,	we can'	t even push, because Arsenal are gonna fade away. They always do. Even
12 DaveMCIWon49C.txt	I just want you to tell me who is the best manager in Manchester. And	we can'	t talk about ten Hag in the Champions League because he never got
13 BenCRYWon50C.txt	percent, and Brighton. Mate, I'm a Palace fan who lives in Brighton, of course	we can.	My house is probably in trouble. I don't know.

Figure 4.1: Winners Corpus ‘we can’ concordance.

	File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	JamesEVELost28C.txt	Lampard, did you say? It's not all on him. I generally don't think	we can	afford to sack him. I think he would have gone after Brighton and
2	JamesEVELost28C.txt	him, I think he'd have been gone by now. I just don't think	we can	afford to sack him. For Moshiri to come out in midweek and back
3	AlexASTLost9C.txt	clearly out of reach. I don't think the club is in a position where	we can	aim that high, frankly, I think we would need to see some form
4	JimTOTLost33C.txt	is Arsenal. The problem we've got at Spurs is Levy seems to think that	we can	buy trophies. He tried it with Mourinho, it didn't work, he's
5	JamieCHELost19C.txt	just needs that time and I think we're going to do well. I think	we can	do well.
6	LeoMUNLost45C.txt	as long as we do respond, alright, I think we'll be fine. I think	we can	finish in the top four and I think we can go for one
7	EmmaCHELost54C.txt	numerous times. But that's probably one of the biggest wins Chelsea women have. If	we can	get past Barcelona because they're more in form. Yeah, I have more
8	LeoMUNLost45C.txt	ll be fine. I think we can finish in the top four and I think	we can	go for one of the cups, hopefully, but top four and already a
9	VernonCHELost22C.txt	do, we've got this sort of recall that goes back so many decades, that	we can	recall every player, every debut. This is what football fans are. This is
10	MichaelCRYLost39C.txt	always gonna be a mid table team. You know, we're gonna be there. If	we can	stay up, for me, that's a bonus and anyone thinks we're
11	PatLIVLost29C.txt	but at times you just think, "well, where are they?" We don't look like	we can	win games ugly anymore, which we did last season. Well, you took the
12	JimEVELost17C.txt	gonna play him every week. But we've had patience, we've had enough patience,	we can'	t afford to have patience with managers. We need somebody who's gonna
13	JamieCHELost19C.txt	what would happen to us, who knows, but it's all about moving forward and	we can'	t be looking back. Maybe. Obviously we're used to winning trophies, but
14	MichaelLIVLost6C.txt	brilliant manager and I don't want anyone to have a go at him. But	we can'	t compete with the wages, that's the problem. It's down to
15	LeeCHELost51C.txt	dead. That's finished. There's no chance. That game's over. It's finished.	We can'	t defend, we can't score, it's finished. Look at Roy Hodgson.
16	BrianWOLLost12C.txt	t seem to be cutting it at Premier League level. I do believe now that	we can'	t exist until New Year with an interim coach. The situation is so
17	AlexASTLost9C.txt	promoted and earn his career there, I think I'd rather see Villa go, if	we can'	t get the top quality in we'd all love, Sean Dyche short
18	LeeCHELost51C.txt	There's no chance. That game's over. It's finished. We can't defend,	we can'	t score, it's finished. Look at Roy Hodgson. Look at when he'
19	JamesEVELost28C.txt	s off the table now Watkins is injured, so who are we going to get?	We can'	t afford anyone. Today, we backed that team. At half past one we
20	KevinWOLLost15C.txt	bring back, well I'll bring him in, I would approach for Sean Dyche. If	we can'	t get Nuno I'd go for Sean Dyche. I know they're

Figure 4.2: Losers Corpus 'we can' concordance.

The concordance lines for 'we can' show that it is negated frequently in the LC, in examples between 12 and 20. When this is not the case, the verb phrase is qualified in the left context with the verb 'don't', as well as conditional clauses. The level of ability implied by using the verb 'can' is low, compared to the negated 'can't', which is much more certain. This phrase is concerned with the team's ability to succeed, but there is also a prevalent semantic field of money. The caller takes a stance where they lament the funds available in 1, 2, 12, and 19, another sign of pessimism as they bring into question the efficiency with which their club is run. The collocation appears less in the WC, but the negativity about money is not present. The theme is more hopeful, with the callers employing the lower level of modality as a method of hedging to highlight what is possible, but perhaps not likely, as in 1, 2, and 10.

	File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	RickMUNWon56C.txt	the years, de Gea has made the saves and kept United in games in matches	they should	have lost and I would say that, for several seasons, United really only
2	RickMUNWon56C.txt	in the Premier League, de Gea was making the saves and keeping United in games	they should	have lost, so United need to keep him, he needs to sign his

Figure 4.3: Winners Corpus 'they should' concordance.

	File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1	ChristianTOTLost48C.txt	fifth and in the Europa League to be fair, and it's just a shambles.	They should	be doing better, but then there's no one at the helm. You
2	SimonLIVLost8C.txt	it all goes wrong and sometimes they overstep the mark and it's quite right	they should	be punished for it. But let's not, you know, take this out
3	PennyNEWLost46C.txt	be encouraging a lot of the Manchester supporters to call up but I mean, honestly,	they should	be surprised at how quiet they are. So when you talk about who
4	ChristianTOTLost48C.txt	could turn the team around a bit because obviously their confidence on the floor and	they should	be trying harder. You're right Chris, but just give that a go
5	DerekLEELost3C.txt	the best strikers in the country and this time, I mean, the load of tosh,	they should	have gone out and got a striker because all they did, Rodrigo, if
6	JimEVELost17C.txt	me today, I convinced them to go over. They have season tickets and they say	they should'	ve gone to see Celtic, but anyway, the thing that I would like

Figure 4.4: Losers Corpus 'they should' concordance.

As for the 'they should' concordance, this shows a more extreme emotional reaction as a stronger level of modality is used. It occasionally shows a shift in pronoun use where the club or players that would usually be referred to as 'we', have changed to show their discontent after losing. Ellison (2014) concluded that, in political radio programmes, pronoun use can be simply reduced to 'we' referring to the perceived protagonist and 'they' referring to the antagonists. These attributions of blame illustrate

the disdain towards entities that were previously perceived as ‘protagonists’, where their effort is brought into question; something very basic. The goal of these callers is to vent these emotions and take the stance that something needs to change. The fifth example is directed at the club's decision makers, with the implication being that the fans do not back them and use pronouns to distance themselves from these poor decisions.

4.1.5 Communication Markers

Table 7.1: Winners Corpus communication markers

Collocate	I	We	You	They
heard	21			
said	13			
told	19			

Table 7.2: Losers Corpus communication markers

Collocate	I	We	You	They
laughed			6	
listened	21			
said	8			
say	24			
talked	28			

The final collocation category that invokes stance is communication markers. This category includes all dialogue and conversation where there is an implied speaker and listener, resulting in a preference for past tense as the communication has usually been completed. Most of these appear in the environment of the pronoun ‘I’. This is one of the rarer categories, with the simple past tense verb ‘said’ being the only marker that features in both corpora with any regularity.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	I love him, he's like Bill Shankly all over again. I love him. Like	I said	to you Robbie a long time ago, I love Bobby Firmino and I'
2 MohammedMCIWon57C.txt	listen to me. Do you remember when they beat Brighton away? Do you Remember? And	I said	to you we're coming for this league, Robbie, I told you, this
3 NigelMUNWon28C.txt	like, you know, but I asked him about the young lad Garnacho, you know, and	I said	to him, "is he playing today?" He smiled, he said he's in
4 JIICHEWon43C.txt	playing as a team. I think they're playing as individuals and that's why	I said	to your producer I think Chelsea needs Emma Hayes and I mean the
5 JIICHEWon43C.txt	without him. I'll give him a bit of credit. I feel sorry for him.	I said	that to your producer. I feel sorry for him. I think he's
6 TomASTWon19C.txt	has just been obliterated. The last time that I phoned your show, a year ago,	I said	that we should go and get Steven Gerrard and I remember you two
7 AaronMUNWon25C.txt	to cheer about the last couple of seasons, so we need to be realistic. So	I said	at the start of the season if we finish fifth and won a
8 EdMUNWon36C.txt	they? They've got us, they've got Fulham and they've got Brentford. Brentford,	I said	Brighton to your producer on the phone, but Brentford, that's not a
9 MichaelLIVWon48C.txt	object. I went in full tilt and gave Robertson a really good dressing down because	I said	his performances to date, up until a couple of weeks ago, have been
10 RichardMUNWon27C.txt	as I say, still have the League Cup, so your treble's on. I know	I said	last year when we beat Leeds that the quad was on, but this
11 DanielNEWWon18C.txt	a fantastic job and the manager who I would like to equate him to, and	I said	this to my dad the other day when we were watching the Everton
12 MichaelLIVWon45C.txt	me "we need to do this, we need to do that, buy this, buy that",	I said	yes, but we've got the right man in charge. I love him,
13 NigelMUNWon28C.txt	the squad for the day. He said to me, "what do you think of him?"	I said "	I've been following him" I said, you know, from youth level, following
14 NigelMUNWon28C.txt	you know, from youth level, following him in the last few years, you know, and	I said "	what do you think as the manager and the coaching staff? What do
15 DavidCHEWon11C.txt	He's probably a big fan of yours. We're devastated for him, but as	I said,	Thiago Silva, is absolutely fantastic. A lot of people say we wish we
16 NigelMUNWon28C.txt	to me, "what do you think of him?" I said "I've been following him"	I said,	you know, from youth level, following him in the last few years, you

Figure 5.1: Winners Corpus ‘I said’ concordance.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 SimonWHULost41C.txt	us. It doesn't seem like it to us. When he goes out to,	I said	before, the big clubs and he sets up not to lose and clearly
2 TomMCLost27C.txt	thought there was only gonna be one winner here and I wasn't surprised. As	I said	before, you can't complain as a City fan. Thanks, have a good
3 JimTOTLost33C.txt	Mourinho, it didn't work, he's trying it with Conte, it's not working.	I said	before, you'll remember me, I said get Klinsmann and Sheringham in or
4 TomMCLost27C.txt	that "come on let's get a second, come on let's get a third."	I said	last night, you know, you obviously have the best conversations in the pub
5 LeeCHELost51C.txt	you laughed at me. I have to say you're not laughing now, are you?	I said	last time there's more chance of Chelsea getting relegated than winning the
6 LeeCHELost51C.txt	asked me for a percentage. You said what's the percentage of Chelsea getting relegated.	I said	last time, I said fifty one percent relegation, forty nine percent Champions League.
7 DavidLELost42C.txt	when we had lost five two at Brighton and called for Brendan Rodgers to go.	I said	to Chris, we've gotta give him more time. I then came on
8 MichaelCHELost16C.txt	so disappointed, they really do, I don't think he knows his best formation. As	I said	to the guy who took the phone call, he said "it's a
9 DannyFULLost24.txt	and dropped seven points. In the league, we would be fifth. No. Fantastic job. Like	I said	to you, I think we're overachieving. There's going to be a
10 TomMCLost27C.txt	said last night, you know, you obviously have the best conversations in the pub and	I said	I don't feel confident. I said I feel United are on a
11 TomMCLost27C.txt	have the best conversations in the pub and I said I don't feel confident.	I said	I feel United are on a slow but very steady upward trajectory under
12 TomLELost52C.txt	was no plan b to get us out of the mess we were in. And	I said	after we got rid of Rodgers, I hope they've got someone in
13 LeeCHELost51C.txt	haven't. There's no upturn at all. We're terrible. No, this is what	I said	before. I didn't want Frank back. We need De Zerbi. We need
14 LeeCHELost51C.txt	percentage. You said what's the percentage of Chelsea getting relegated. I said last time,	I said	fifty one percent relegation, forty nine percent Champions League. Now I'm saying
15 JimTOTLost33C.txt	trying it with Conte, it's not working. I said before, you'll remember me,	I said	get Klinsmann and Sheringham in or at the very least get Pochettino back
16 MohammedWHULost21C.txt	Chris? Do you remember what happened last time, when I talked to you last week?	I said	that we have to beat Palace. Yeah, but look, we lost to Palace
17 MichaelLNLost6C.txt	you must've done something you regretted. Yeah. Well I just think it was, as	I said	a massive game for us to beat Manchester City. Today Notts Forest were
18 BenLELost13C.txt	going to play him why is Gelhardt not playing off him, for instance, or as	I said	Gnanto who seems to have arrived in Leeds and gone missing? We've
19 AndrewTOTLost40C.txt	beaten Man City, we've beaten Chelsea. Yeah. So what I was saying, so as	I said	last time I was on the show I was very effusive about the
20 BrianLELost43C.txt	not good enough. They've never kicked a football in their lives, that's what	I said	people like yourself and Robbie, professional footballers should come back as referees. Just
21 JedMCLost38C.txt	all that injury time. Fifteen, twenty minutes, he must've been. Well, I mean, like	I said	the thing is we don't press as well with Haaland in the
22 AlexASTLost9C.txt	comes in and works. So I'd rather have someone with Premiership experience. So, as	I said	this is as bad as 2015/2016 as far as I'm concerned, the way

Figure 5.2: Losers Corpus 'I said' concordance.

The goal of this collocation is to invoke and repeat a stance that was taken previously in another conversation that is worth repeating to a larger audience. These types of conversations can act as the breeding ground for football phone-in discussions, as they raise questions or interesting points for adjudication. The callers do not show a change in opinion since the original stance was taken. When a previous conversation is revisited, there is, of course, an implied listener. The identity of this participant can be beneficial for creating an interesting discussion, but this is a more individual phenomenon where patterns are harder to ascertain. A pattern that is evident, however, is the repetition of the callers' point to the producers, such as 8 in the LC and 4 and 5 in the WC. The producers ultimately choose the callers allowed to put their views on air, so by invoking them as a participant, this implies that the producers considered the stances to be interesting and worth airing.

4.2 Building Credibility

As we have already seen, the primary use of pronouns is in constructions that outline stance. It is the prerogative of the hosts to undermine the callers, as good debate facilitates a good call. The constructions of stances need some basis, and the callers need to state their credentials and *why* they are qualified to talk on the topic. As recognised by Fitzgerald and Housely (2002, p. 597), callers provide authentication to their opinions. The listeners will know nothing about them other than the information from the opening sequence, so callers need to bring this into the conversation when advantageous.

4.2.1 Auxiliary Verbs

Table 8.1: Winners Corpus auxiliary verbs

Collocate	I	We	You	They
am/are	11	17		6
did		14		
didn't	25	13		10
do	22			

don't	4		11	
had		4		
'm/'re	2	1	2	1
've	5	2	5	2
was/were	8	3	17	3
wasn't/weren't				5

Table 8.2: Losers Corpus auxiliary verbs

Collocate	I	We	You	They
am/are	10			4
did				
didn't		15		13
don't	4	16	8	
had		9		
have		20		
haven't		7		12
'm/'re	2	2	2	1
've	6	1	3	2
was/were	14	3		3
wasn't/weren't				7

As discussed previously, auxiliary verbs functioned in collocations for both stance and credibility constructions. This distinction only becomes clear upon examination of the concordance lines. The above collocation table is a replica of the one fully analysed in the earlier chapter.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 JillCHEWon43C.txt	How are you? I'm great, thanks. Did you get it right? Well,	I'm a	season ticket holder. I didn't go today because I'm so
2 PeterMUNWon33C.txt	I am Robbie, yeah. Well, I'm not just a fan,	I'm a	season ticket holder. Absolutely. It was a fantastic day and it's
3 PaulBOUWon54C.txt	Oh, great, couldn't be better. I know, it's amazing.	I'm a	bit concerned though, because you said that we might stay up now.
4 ShazARSWon41C.txt	s decision not going our way and it's a human error. But, I mean,	I'm a	blind person, but to get VAR decisions wrong in the last three
5 JohnTOTWon23C.txt	got nothing to complain about" but when you watch the quality of that football, honestly,	I'm a	Church of England vicar, right, and that was like the Easter weekend
6 MichaelIIVWon45C.txt	So what, you won a league cup. My point is that we're going nowhere.	I'm a	Liverpool fan, I've been a Liverpool fan from 1973. We're going
7 BenCRYWon50C.txt	of the National League. He's got football problems. A hundred percent, and Brighton. Mate,	I'm a	Palace fan who lives in Brighton, of course we can. My house

Figure 6.1: Winners Corpus 'I'm a' concordance

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 TomMCILost27C.txt	and as a squad they seemed to have more desire. I think they did, seriously.	I'm a	City fan. No, they seemed to want it more and we seemed
2 TonyMCILost18C.txt	I'm being smug, I'm not. I have full faith in Pep Guardiola, but	I'm a	City fan from thirty years ago, so I love the guy, I
3 SimonLIVLost8C.txt	people have got no patience and are just too quick to shoot people down. Sorry,	I'm a	grassroots manager. I manage my son in an under eighteen team. I'
4 PatLIVLost29C.txt	quick to look at, well, "oh we're on a bad run, sack the manager".	I'm a	great believer, you know, form is temporary, class is permanent and Jurgen
5 MichaelLIVLost6C.txt	they knocked us out in the Champions League. They beat us over two legs. So	I'm a	Liverpool fan. Yeah, I love Liverpool. When I saw them play I
6 DannyTOTLost36C.txt	Spurs fan. Believe you me, I've gone and watched Spurs lose for enough years.	I'm a	proper Spurs fan. I actually think the problems start at the top
7 BernardWHULost32C.txt	has been dropping off a cliff in the league and I go to home games,	I'm a	season ticket holder. The last quarter of last season, you could already
8 BrianLEILost43C.txt	was six inches away. He was protecting his face. It's just ludicrous. No, because	I'm a	twenty five year season ticket holder. That's it. I've finished

Figure 6.2: Losers Corpus 'I'm a' concordance.

These concordance patterns show the context for the construction ‘I’m a’, which is the principal way of invoking identity. There are different categories of identities, each going to various lengths to provide expert credentials that allow them to be judged as such (Kilby & Horowitz, 2013). The first of these is invoking a ‘season ticket holder’ identity in 1 and 2 in the WC and 7 and 8 in the LC, which shows a certain level of devotion regardless of their team’s fortunes. The act of attending games every week is perceived favourably and is a key tool for enhancing credibility, qualifying the caller’s stance as they refer to the evidence of their own eyes. There is a hierarchy within the fandoms themselves, suggesting that these identities ensure the callers to position themselves at the top. Foster and Kilby (2023, p. 556) refer to these as ‘mundane discursive manoeuvres’ that ‘elevate a narrow version of this identity’. This narrowed identity, in a football context, is the sense of entitlement these match-going supporters have; there is nothing that inherently means that more casual fans cannot form the same opinions as season ticket holders. There is another category of identities, characterised by having little reference to football, including 4 and 5 in the WC. Fitzgerald and Housely (2002, p. 586) corroborate that ‘there is a layer of identity membership that is not topic orientated’. They are not obsolete, helping to create an authentic and memorable call, invoking a more specific identity that few callers can stake a claim to. Despite appearing minor, the deployment of these identities is key in helping to ground the call in reality. When an element of anonymity is at play, credibility is built when the participant situates themselves ‘as a ‘real’ person’ (Vasquez, 2014, cited in Jacknick & Avni, 2017, p. 62). It is theoretically possible for anyone to call up and say anything, regardless of whether it is what they believe. These seemingly unrelated identities add an element of accountability to the caller that makes it seem as if what they say is a more irrefutable opinion. With all these identities, the listeners sympathise with one who shares an identity with themselves (Jautz, 2014, p. 22), so there is always potential for credibility to be built when these constructions are deployed.

A conspicuous pattern is that shown by the concordance for ‘I’m just’. As for the denotative meaning of the adverb ‘just’, there is an element of politeness and an unwillingness not to overrepresent, especially if that experience is not universal. Meanwhile, the first three winning concordances can be attributed to the callers positioning themselves as match-going, by referring to them travelling home from the stadium. For many fans, and especially away fans, this is part of the experience; they will drive home and think about what they have seen, so sometimes they might want to share their thoughts with a larger audience and decide to phone the programme. An element of the adverb is time-bound, as they were only *just* there. This links to fan hierarchy, because a fan’s status is undermined when they leave matches early, therefore it is beneficial for callers to suggest that they stayed until the end of the match. The advantages of callers positioning themselves as match-going have already been discussed and this is another construction that allows them to be perceived as experts, but the frequency with which it appears implies that they also want to appear as experts of the phone-in genre. Foster and Kilby (2023) posit that speakers who construct their identity in accordance with norms trump the arguments offered by other speakers, so it is beneficial for callers to hint that they frequently listen to the programme and hear other callers use this construction. The lack of left concordance context shows that it often occurs at the beginning of the calls. Hutchby (1999) explains this as he notices that openings allow the callers to align themselves with the identities they want to perform. The match-going fans deem that identity to be integral in building their credibility, so they offer these identities as a prelude to the stance they take in the call and means that they are immediately protected from having that aspect brought into question.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 DamonASTWon26C.txt	Yeah absolutely amazing, buzzing.	I'm just	on the way back now, in the car, but yeah, a really,
2 DavidCHEWon11C.txt	Hello mate,	I'm just	on the way back from Villa Park. All I've rung up
3 MichaelEVEWon15C.txt		I'm just	on my way home from Goodison. I mean, I really rang in
4 NickTOTWon1C.txt	won, don't get me wrong, and I'm glad that they gave it but	I'm just	saying I saw it and I don't think it was a
5 RickMUNWon56C.txt	Good evening. First time caller to the show.	I'm just	saying that David de Gea deserves to be Man United's top
6 ShazAR5Won41C.txt	a row. I think this will be a bigger achievement than that. Would you agree?	I'm just	saying in terms of achievement. Yes, one Premier League in isolation, but
7 MatthewCHEWon40C.txt	But he's just proved to me that, I mean, I'm not being funny.	I'm just	a fan, humbly, and I'm thirty nine years old and I
8 SimonBRIWon52C.txt	job? Absolutely not. Well, maybe, who knows? And the appointment of Frank Lampard, who knows,	I'm just	going with what I've heard. I mean, so yeah, all I
9 DeanLIVWon46C.txt	How are you doing, Robbie? How are you doing, Chris? Yeah, absolutely and	I'm just	leaving Anfield now, actually. My question, really, was to you, Chris, because
10 JohnTOTWon23C.txt	in a nutshell. Crucifixion on Friday, resurrection on Sunday. It was painful at times and	I'm just	trying to believe what people tell me, trying to believe that we

Figure 6.3: *Winners Corpus 'I'm just' concordance.*

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 SimonLIVLost8C.txt	I'm very well, thank you. How are you? I think	I'm just	a bit fed up with the whole culture of all of us
2 VernonCHELost22C.txt	to anybody. It was just one of those things that sometimes happens, you know. Well,	I'm just	saying that this is the sort of passion that fans have for
3 BillBRILost25C.txt	shocked. Yes, Solly March. I just want to say great show, I love the show.	I'm just	shocked today. I'm still in shock now because that's not

Figure 6.4: *Losers Corpus 'I'm just' concordance.*

4.2.2 Experience Markers

Table 9.1: *Winners Corpus experience markers*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
bottled				4
broke	29			
got		11		
lived	27			
remember			10	
went	24	10		

Table 9.2: *Losers Corpus experience markers*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
gave		19		
regretted			7	
remember	19			

The collocation for experience markers is easier to separate between stance and credibility, with the credibility being constructed by verbs that appear to not be related to football. The potential verbs that could fit into this category are vast, so there are few parallels between the corpora. Many are part of individual anecdotes offered by callers to build credibility by invoking certain identities, hence they rank lowly.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 MohammedMCiWon57C.txt	bottled the FA Cup with Giggs going through everyone, do you remember, Robbie? And now,	they bottled	the Europa League, Robbie. Europa League, I'm not even there, Robbie. Robbie,
2 MohammedMCiWon57C.txt	United, when Hasselbaink scored and they gave United the treble. Do you remember that? And	they bottled	the FA Cup with Giggs going through everyone, do you remember, Robbie? And
3 MohammedMCiWon57C.txt	bottle job mentality. We know that, Robbie, you remember them. Alex Ferguson, all those times	they bottled	the league, with two games to go against Leeds United, when Hasselbaink scored
4 JohnnyMCiWon55C.txt	last year, this time last year. They had top four in their hands and then	they bottled	it. I think it's the same thing. I think it's all

Figure 7: *Winners Corpus 'they bottled' concordance.*

Despite the low frequency of these collocations, the concordance of ‘they bottled’ still raises an interesting phenomenon that is present in modern football discourse. In the literature concerning discourse as a social practice, Fairclough (1989, p. 11) introduces ‘members’ resources’, which are prototypes for typical narratives. These are ‘socially determined’, so can be affected by factors most relevant to the communities. Mercer (2007, p. 108) notes that communities offer their members ‘a history’, which is certainly a predominant factor in determining football discourse. One of these available factors is rivalry; it is not enough to support one team, but fans also need to actively engage in the dislike and mockery of rival teams to bolster their expert credentials. Teams gain certain reputations due to their typical performances over the course of this history and one of the most negative reputations is that of ‘bottlers’, when they routinely relinquish good positions in individual games and across seasons. This is demonstrated by the above concordance, a construction only used in the WC, suggesting that it is only deployed when the callers are holders of linguistic power. Had their team lost, they would not have the grounds to mock their rivals this way. It is evident that the football community is significant in determining attitudes and beliefs towards issues, as supported by Chichon (2020, p. 7). The callers themselves would not have been the ones to choose a rivalry to pursue, but engaging in the discourse determines how credible they appear.

4.2.3 Politeness and Address

Table 10.1: *Winners Corpus politeness and address*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
alright			9	
doing			12	
guys			7	

Table 10.2: *Losers Corpus politeness and address*

Collocate	I	We	You	They
alright			5	

The final collocation category is that of politeness and address markers. The dichotomy of the phone call results in phatic communication between host and caller. This type of communication is indicated by second person pronouns, as found by Bednarek (2014) in a radio phone-in corpus and, in this case, is limited to collocating with only ‘you’.

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 EdMUNWon36.txt	s a Manchester United fan. How are you Ed? C: How are you doing fellas?	You alright?	Alright thanks, can you win it, Ed? C: What's that fellas? Can
2 GlynTODWon3.txt	Right then, Glyn is a Spurs fan, how are you, Glyn? C: Hello mate,	you alright?	Glyn, you must have had potato bravas in a tapas. C: Pardon? Never
3 MikeLIVWon8.txt	Mike, you're a Liverpool fan. C: Hello lads,	you alright?	Hi Mike. C: I've been at the game today, thanks for having
4 CarlASTWon51.txt	Carl, you're a Villa fan. C: Hello chaps, how are you doing,	you alright?	Alright Carl. C: Mate, can you tell by the tone of my voice
5 JoshARSWon39.txt	Josh, Arsenal fan. C: Hey boys,	you alright?	Josh, Josh. C: Come on, let's have it. Were you there today,
6 MoCHEWon42.txt	How are you? C: How are you, gents? Alright, Mo? C: Very well, how are	you, alright?	Well, you must be a bit upbeat Mo, after today? C: Yeah, it'
7 ThomasEVEWon16.txt	Thomas, how are you? Everton fan. C: Hi,	You alright,	gents? How is it going? Alright Thomas? C: Yeah, I've been to

Figure 8.1: *Winners Corpus 'you alright' concordance.*

File	Left Context	Hit	Right Context
1 MohammedWHULost21.txt	Mohammed, a West Ham fan. C: You alright guys? How are you, mate? C: Yeah,	you alright,	Chris? Yeah, very good thanks. That's nice to hear. C: Do you
2 LouisTOTLost35.txt		You alright,	gents? How are you? Okay, Louis, thank you. C: Good. Yeah, look, fair
3 JamesEVELost28.txt	James, you're an Everton fan. C: Hi, good evening,	you alright?	How are you, James? C: Oh well, I suppose there's only one
4 LeoMUNLost45.txt	Leo, a Manchester United fan. How are you, Leo? C: Hi, evening Robbie, evening Chris.	You alright?	Leo, quick question before we start, is Erik ten Hag the best manager
5 MohammedWHULost21.txt	Let's go to Mohammed, a West Ham fan. C:	You alright	guys? How are you, mate? C: Yeah, you alright, Chris? Yeah, very good
6 DeanMCILost5.txt	who is a Man City fan, how are you Dean? C: I'm alright, are	you alright?	Yeah alright, we've got you, Dean. C: I thought I would crawl

Figure 8.2: Losers Corpus 'you alright' concordance.

This concordance can be primarily explained by the conventionality of politeness. It is the norm for phone calls to begin with a greeting; hence, they can be found in the openings. It could be jarring for the caller to be overly eager and start with their point instead of establishing common ground through phatic communication. Due to its frequency in various forms, such as in the concordance above, the hosts will be expecting this sort of greeting, before then shifting into the main section of the call. Callers are 'required to have a tacit understanding of the "rules" of debate and discussion' (O'Sullivan, 2005, p. 732), so the callers should expect that they need to begin with a segment of this kind. Despite it being unlikely that host and caller would have ever interacted before, familiarity is present in the terms of reference used to refer to the hosts, which is because 'callers "know" hosts from listening to their shows' (Jautz, 2014, p. 20). The hosts might elicit the callers' general views or might ask for an opinion on a specific topic of that programme. Sometimes this is football-related, but can also be light-hearted and humorous. This leads into credibility, as the levels to which the callers engage with the hosts' prompts can give them support. According to Chichon (2020), the hosts could be viewed as experts and their support, or lack thereof, could be seen as significant. Their views on the stances taken by the callers can therefore influence the way those callers are perceived. Any callers who do not demonstrate forms of politeness during the openings already leave themselves vulnerable to a lack of host support, with any resulting criticism harming their credibility.

5 Conclusion

To return to the research questions outlined in the introduction, there are few differences in the pronoun use between callers whose teams won or lost. The collocation data can be categorised into six groups, and further classified into the themes of stance-taking and credibility. Phone-in callers will have a point they want to say on radio, which will express views on a variety of entities, such as the performance of their own team, their owners, or referees. Constructions that impart stances use a wide range of pronouns, to demonstrate the group of people that take that view. It might be limited to that speaker themselves, or they might want to show that it is commonly held and potentially obvious. The main difference, as could be expected, is that losers take more negative stances. A striking difference is the preference of losers to deploy third person pronouns with modal verbs. One might predict that unhappy supporters shift from 'we' to 'they' to describe their team, which is a feature found in the corpus, but is not common amongst all callers in similar scenarios. Over the course of the paper, it has emerged how important credibility is to what the callers say. The link between stance and credibility arises because, while callers can take any stance they wish, they might not be taken seriously. In that case, they use pronouns in credibility constructions to invoke identities that prove they have expert status, as both an expert of their team and an expert of the format of the programme. The result of the caller's team has no effect on their deployment of credibility structures. They tend to be realised through the pronoun 'I', as callers are only concerned with managing their own credibility.

As for the limitations of the study, the collocation only focuses on the token directly to the right of the pronoun, resulting in potential patterns in different positions of the pronoun's environment not being found. The rationale for not including draws in the corpus was mentioned earlier, but it could still be interesting to compare with the other corpora and whether those callers aligned themselves with

positive or negative stances. As with all corpus research, personal biases can affect the interpretations of the data identified by the analytical tools. I have my own personal experiences of the season, after following it closely myself. For example, stances that I might deem controversial or extreme might not be perceived as such by the caller and their fanbase. It is impossible to accurately comment on a speaker's intentions when using a certain utterance, but corpus methods show patterns that allow them to be interpreted more precisely.

Overall, this study has broken new ground by applying a CADS framework to analyse a football phone-in, a previously untested combination. The quantity of interesting findings suggest that this genre is worthy of further research to investigate its other aspects. The six collocation categories are versatile in their application and can be used to study and compare collocation across any topic a researcher wishes. The themes of stance and credibility will continue to be of interest and researchers will continue to study them to add to the comprehensive literature on their respective functions in discourse.

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7 Appendix

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7.1 Appendix One: Participants Breakdown

Table A1: Full breakdown of participants’ information that determined corpus inclusion

Caller Name	Supported Team	Team Result	Date	Corpus Inclusion	Discard Reason
Nick	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Tom	Everton	Lost	15 th October	Yes	
Joe	Wolves	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Glyn	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Ollie	Bournemouth	Drew	15 th October	No	Draw
Gareth	Everton	Lost	15 th October	Yes	
Luke	Plymouth	Won	15 th October	No	League One team
Derek	Celtic	Won	15 th October	No	Scottish team
Jo	Tottenham	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Matthew	Wolves	Won	15 th October	Yes	
Tom	Plymouth	Won	15 th October	No	League One team
Bart	Manchester City	Did not play	15 th October	No	Did not play
Ryan	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	Yes	

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Steve	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	No	Corpus balancing
Steve	Arsenal	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Derek	Leeds	Lost	16 th October	Yes	
Greg	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	No	Corpus balancing
Anthony	Arsenal	Won	16 th October	No	Corpus balancing
Andy	Aston Villa	Lost	16 th October	Yes	
Mike	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Stampy	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	No	Corpus balancing
Chris	Chelsea	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Amit	Manchester United	Drew	16 th October	No	Draw
Shaun	Liverpool	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Paul	Newcastle	Drew	16 th October	No	Draw
Logan	Birmingham	Won	16 th October	No	Championship team
Dean	Manchester City	Lost	16 th October	Yes	
David	Chelsea	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Adam	West Ham	Drew	16 th October	No	Draw
Gordon	Arsenal	Won	16 th October	No	Corpus balancing
Steve	Chelsea	Won	16 th October	Yes	
Michael	Liverpool	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	
Matthew	Manchester City	Won	22 nd October	Yes	
Steve	Manchester City	Won	22 nd October	Yes	
Sam	Chelsea	Drew	22 nd October	No	Draw
Andy	Manchester United	Drew	22 nd October	No	Draw
Michael	Everton	Won	22 nd October	Yes	
Andy	Brighton	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	
Simon	Liverpool	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	
Jay	Manchester United	Drew	22 nd October	No	Draw
Thomas	Everton	Won	22 nd October	Yes	
Derek	Celtic	Won	22 nd October	No	Scottish team
Alex	Aston Villa	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	

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Adi	QPR	Won	22 nd October	No	Championship team
Duncan	Crystal Palace	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	
Carl	QPR	Won	22 nd October	No	Championship team
James	West Ham	Lost	22 nd October	Yes	
Brian	Wolves	Lost	23 rd October	Yes	
Dave	Aston Villa	Won	23 rd October	Yes	
Ben	Leeds	Lost	23 rd October	Yes	
Daniel	Newcastle	Won	23 rd October	Yes	
Connor	Southampton	Drew	23 rd October	No	Draw
Damian	Tottenham	Lost	23 rd October	Yes	
Tom	Aston Villa	Won	23 rd October	Yes	
Kevin	Wolves	Lost	23 rd October	Yes	
Ben	Watford	Won	23 rd October	No	Championship team
Josh	Leeds	Lost	23 rd October	No	Ethical concerns
Gavin	Leeds	Lost	23 rd October	No	Debates with previous caller
Michael	Chelsea	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Jayden	Newcastle	Won	12 th November	Yes	
Jim	Everton	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Stuart	Nottingham Forest	Won	12 th November	Yes	
Mark	Brentford	Won	12 th November	Yes	
Tony	Manchester City	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Jamie	Chelsea	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Terry	Everton	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Mohammed	West Ham	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
John	Tottenham	Won	12 th November	Yes	
Dave	Tottenham	Won	12 th November	No	Debates with previous caller
Vernon	Chelsea	Lost	12 th November	Yes	
Brian	Celtic	Won	12 th November	No	Scottish team
Jay	Manchester United	Did not play	12 th November	No	Did not play
Ollie	Wolves	Unfinished game	12 th November	No	Unfinished game

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Paul	Leicester	Won	12 th November	Yes	
Aaron	Manchester United	Won	13 th November	Yes	
Damon	Aston Villa	Won	13 th November	Yes	
Richard	Manchester United	Won	13 th November	Yes	
Andrew	Brighton	Lost	13 th November	Yes	
Aaron	Manchester United	Won	13 th November	No	Corpus balancing
Jake	Arsenal	Drew	13 th November	No	Draw
Danny	Fulham	Lost	13 th November	Yes	
Lee	Burnley	Won	13 th November	No	Championship team
Paul			13 th November	No	Not talking about own team
Nigel	Manchester United	Won	13 th November	Yes	
Bill	Brighton	Lost	13 th November	Yes	
Tracey	Tottenham	Won	13 th November	Yes	
John	Arsenal	Drew	13 th November	No	Draw
Chris	Liverpool	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Abdullah	Manchester United	Won	14 th January	Yes	
Reg	Manchester United	Won	14 th January	No	Corpus balancing
Andrew	Brighton	Won	14 th January	Yes	
Tom	Manchester City	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
James	Everton	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Pat	Liverpool	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Mark	Leicester	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Emma	Nottingham Forest	Won	14 th January	Yes	
Lindon	Everton	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Peter	Manchester United	Won	14 th January	Yes	
Bernard	West Ham	Lost	14 th January	Yes	
Shaz	Arsenal	Won	15 th January	Yes	
Jim	Tottenham	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Taz	Tottenham	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Phil	Arsenal	Won	15 th January	Yes	

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Louis	Spurs	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Alan	Arsenal	Won	15 th January	No	Corpus balancing
Ed	Manchester United	Won	15 th January	Yes	
Danny	Tottenham	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Patrick	Arsenal	Won	15 th January	Yes	
Patrick	Crystal Palace	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Ben	Middlesbrough	Won	15 th January	No	Championship team
Jed	Manchester City	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Shaun	Arsenal	Won	15 th January	No	Corpus balancing
Peter	Newcastle	Won	15 th January	Yes	
Michael	Crystal Palace	Lost	15 th January	Yes	
Josh	Arsenal	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Andrew	Tottenham	Lost	4 th March	Yes	
Simon	West Ham	Lost	4 th March	Yes	
David	Leicester	Lost	4 th March	Yes	
Jake	Arsenal	Won	4 th March	No	Corpus balancing
Matthew	Chelsea	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Brian	Leicester	Lost	4 th March	Yes	
Shaz	Arsenal	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Mo	Chelsea	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Jill	Chelsea	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Dan	QPR	Lost	4 th March	No	Championship team
Yaya	Arsenal	Won	4 th March	Yes	
Neil	Blackburn	Won	4 th March	No	Championship team
Ryan	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	No	Corpus balancing
Michael	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	Yes	
Jamie	Manchester United	Lost	5 th March	Yes	
Dean	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	Yes	
Ben	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	Yes	

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Leo	Manchester United	Lost	5 th March	Yes	
Penny	Newcastle	Lost	5 th March	Yes	
Michael	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	Yes	
Dave	Manchester City	Won	5 th March	Yes	
Elaine	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	No	Corpus balancing
Sanj	Arsenal	Won	5 th March	No	Not talking about own team
Rizwan	Liverpool	Won	5 th March	No	Corpus balancing
Michael	Everton	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Christian	Tottenham	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Gordon	Newcastle	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Nick	Tottenham	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Hitesh	Leeds	Did not play	15 th April	No	Did not play
Ben	Crystal Palace	Won	15 th April	Yes	
Carl	Aston Villa	Won	15 th April	Yes	
Simon	Brighton	Won	15 th April	Yes	
Lee	Chelsea	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Josh	Manchester City	Won	15 th April	Yes	
Tom	Leicester	Lost	15 th April	Yes	
Paul	Bournemouth	Won	15 th April	Yes	
Ben	Ipswich	Won	15 th April	No	League One Team
Johnny	Manchester City	Won	16 th April	Yes	
Aggie	Arsenal	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
Adam	West Ham	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
Ivan	Arsenal	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
Rhys	Nottingham Forest	Lost	16 th April	Yes	
Alex	Arsenal	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
James	West Ham	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
Rick	Manchester United	Won	16 th April	Yes	
Emma	Chelsea	Lost	16 th April	Yes	
John	West Ham	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw

Neil	Norwich	Lost	16 th April	No	Championship team
Sanj	Arsenal	Drew	16 th April	No	Draw
Mohammed	Manchester City	Won	16 th April	Yes	
Michael	Nottingham Forest	Lost	16 th April	Yes	

7.2 Appendix Two: Collocation Tables

Table A2: Winners Corpus 'I' collocates

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
think	1	171	44	861.940	4.200
'm	2	117	45	754.430	4.659
mean	3	72	31	462.529	4.663
don't	4	74	36	347.728	4.098
've	5	49	26	128.075	2.923
would	6	32	19	100.314	3.274
thought	7	16	15	70.280	3.983
was	8	42	20	63.757	2.104
'll	9	15	11	59.963	3.783
love	10	11	7	49.938	4.055
am	11	7	5	45.497	4.683
wanted	12	10	9	38.087	3.683
said	13	16	11	36.933	2.729
saw	14	7	6	36.120	4.321
agree	15	9	8	35.636	3.766
can	16	17	15	34.918	2.542
'd	17	9	8	35.636	3.531
feel	18	7	5	31.392	4.031
told	19	5	2	24.270	4.198
know	20	25	19	23.320	1.586
heard	21	5	3	20.438	3.835
do	22	16	14	20.019	1.889
just	23	18	14	16.402	1.568
went	24	6	5	15.048	2.876
didn't	25	7	7	13.052	2.403
knew	26	4	3	13.000	3.361
lived	27	2	2	12.989	4.683
reckon	28	2	2	12.989	4.683
broke	29	2	1	12.989	4.683

fully	30	2	1	12.989	4.683
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Table A3: *Winners Corpus 'we' collocates*

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
're	1	66	32	337.872	4.602
've	2	66	28	315.286	4.407
were	3	50	26	247.102	4.523
had	4	17	10	61.793	3.759
played	5	10	7	45.710	4.359
should	6	9	5	38.856	4.207
'll	7	9	7	37.307	4.100
can	8	13	12	36.892	3.209
win	9	11	4	33.545	3.364
went	10	7	6	29.576	4.153
got	11	15	13	27.770	2.445
i	12	1	1	27.668	-4.106
didn't	13	8	7	27.641	3.650
did	14	8	6	25.348	3.452
'd	15	6	6	23.893	4.001
beat	16	5	4	21.913	4.252
are	17	10	10	17.740	2.387
would	18	9	4	17.160	2.498
lose	19	4	3	16.141	4.037
need	20	4	3	14.867	3.831
could	21	5	5	13.407	3.105
might	22	3	2	12.650	4.153
needed	23	2	1	12.136	5.153

Table A4: *Winners Corpus 'you' collocates*

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
know	1	137	36	819.442	4.916
're	2	40	22	144.860	3.702
look	3	18	11	79.921	4.238
can	4	19	12	64.575	3.579
've	5	21	15	42.649	2.577
the	6	1	1	35.311	-4.397
guys	7	7	7	34.936	4.560
could	8	9	8	33.102	3.775
alright	9	7	7	32.499	4.367
remember	10	6	2	29.934	4.560
don't	11	13	8	24.458	2.466

doing	12	8	7	22.320	3.167
think	13	18	11	20.845	1.829
and	14	1	1	16.894	-3.546
you	15	1	1	14.857	-3.406
to	16	1	1	14.540	-3.383
were	17	10	7	13.603	2.024

Table A5: *Winners Corpus 'they' collocates*

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
're	1	39	21	213.616	5.002
've	2	22	13	85.140	3.981
were	3	15	13	56.799	3.945
bottled	4	4	2	33.334	6.574
weren't	5	4	2	27.297	5.896
are	6	8	7	22.246	3.224
tried	7	2	2	19.140	6.896
played	8	4	3	16.360	4.196
just	9	8	7	16.099	2.611
didn't	10	4	4	14.187	3.809
will	11	3	2	11.516	4.022

Table A6: *Losers Corpus 'I' collocates*

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
think	1	167	44	854.955	4.277
'm	2	113	41	764.501	4.788
mean	3	77	31	507.079	4.770
don't	4	73	37	324.270	4.012
'd	5	33	17	153.319	4.132
've	6	52	28	120.670	2.727
thought	7	17	11	87.189	4.352
said	8	22	15	81.085	3.633
just	9	29	20	58.124	2.507
am	10	6	5	39.866	4.788
would	11	15	12	37.702	2.888
believe	12	8	6	36.214	4.088
was	13	26	15	31.688	1.859
can	14	17	15	30.202	2.336
know	15	25	19	30.118	1.847
agree	16	7	5	27.622	3.788
'll	17	10	8	21.803	2.651
suppose	18	4	3	21.638	4.466

remember	19	6	4	21.331	3.566
feel	20	5	5	21.144	3.940
listened	21	3	3	19.923	4.788
hate	22	3	2	19.923	4.788
generally	23	3	2	19.923	4.788
say	24	10	9	18.997	2.438
love	25	5	5	16.480	3.410
hope	26	3	3	13.340	4.051
turned	27	3	1	13.340	4.051
talked	28	2	2	13.280	4.788
expected	29	2	2	13.280	4.788
personally	30	2	2	13.280	4.788

Table A7: *Losers Corpus 'we' collocates*

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
've	1	100	33	493.368	4.429
're	2	74	36	400.760	4.711
were	3	33	21	150.294	4.287
need	4	19	12	96.250	4.585
can	5	20	14	60.745	3.329
'll	6	14	11	54.231	3.894
haven't	7	10	7	52.684	4.698
lost	8	9	6	40.136	4.257
had	9	13	11	32.410	2.943
will	10	10	5	32.329	3.476
I	11	1	1	31.342	-4.256
could	12	9	9	30.554	3.587
won	13	7	5	29.417	4.106
should	14	9	8	27.557	3.359
didn't	15	9	7	26.256	3.257
'd	16	9	8	23.265	3.016
backed	17	3	1	23.083	5.546
don't	18	13	10	21.563	2.281
gave	19	3	3	18.628	5.131
have	20	14	12	18.010	1.953
couldn't	21	3	3	13.695	4.324
played	22	5	5	13.559	3.113
finished	23	3	2	12.680	4.131

Table A8: *Losers Corpus 'you' collocates*

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
know	1	120	39	768.926	5.230
're	2	28	16	98.077	3.671
've	3	27	17	65.869	2.901
can	4	13	8	34.233	3.069
alright	5	6	5	25.255	4.171
laughed	6	3	1	24.591	5.908
regretted	7	3	1	24.591	5.908
look	8	7	7	20.429	3.289
don't	9	11	6	19.646	2.401
to	10	1	1	12.214	-3.198

Table A9: *Losers Corpus 'they' collocates*

Collocate	Rank	Frequency	Range	Likelihood	Effect
're	1	30	20	154.498	4.831
've	2	22	14	75.457	3.667
were	3	14	11	63.421	4.472
are	4	9	7	31.095	3.729
'll	5	7	5	29.889	4.317
should	6	6	5	24.554	4.196
weren't	7	4	3	22.817	5.268
could	8	5	4	20.191	4.161
chose	9	2	1	19.341	6.969
gambled	10	2	1	19.341	6.969
seemed	11	2	1	13.828	5.969
haven't	12	3	3	13.044	4.384
didn't	13	4	4	12.544	3.509
had	14	5	3	12.311	2.987
don't	15	6	5	11.855	2.588

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Dissecting the Frog: Understanding ChatGPT's Sense of Humour

Matt Hayden
Newcastle University

Abstract. As the popularity surrounding large language models like OpenAI's GPT series grows, it is crucial to explore areas where they still underperform, particularly in understanding humour. While models such as ChatGPT have demonstrated state-of-the-art results on benchmark tests (Brown et al., 2020), studies like Borji (2023) highlight their consistent failures in explaining jokes. This research investigates why such failures occur by analysing ChatGPT's ability to interpret humour using the General Theory of Verbal Humour (GTVH) (Attardo & Raskin, 1991). GTVH suggests that jokes arise from the interplay of two semantically overlapping but fundamentally opposed scripts. This study hypothesises that ChatGPT's architecture would be able to identify these opposed scripts. To test this, ChatGPT was asked to analyse 14 variants of two novel jokes, each crafted according to GTVH's seven differences. Each version was presented five times, and the responses were qualitatively analysed for patterns in success and failure. The findings showed that ChatGPT consistently failed to identify the relevant scripts and often misallocated importance, frequently overemphasising noun phrases or relying on familiar patterns from its training data. These errors mirror those seen in tasks requiring complex semantic reasoning, such as the Adversarial NLI dataset (Nie et al., 2020). There were further difficulties in spatial and physical reasoning, consistent with Borji (2023). Thus, the hypothesis was falsified. However, the study successfully identified specific shortcomings of ChatGPT, which may inform future work on the model.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; humour analysis; semantics

1 Introduction

In recent months surprise, fear and amazement have been expressed, both on social media and through various news outlets, regarding artificial intelligence's ability to replicate human-produced natural language. Results from Brown et al (2020), the paper which was released alongside OpenAI's GPT-3 language model, show state-of-the-art or near state-of-the-art results on a number of benchmark tests. Casual use of ChatGPT (OpenAI 2022), a language model based on GPT-3.5 and fine-tuned to produce human-like conversation, can seem to support these findings. However, digging deeper into answers given by the model can begin to reveal some cracks. An area of difficulty for ChatGPT is humour, particularly when it is asked to explain why something is funny. An example of this is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Example of ChatGPT explaining humour (Miller, 2023).

It is a commonly held belief that humour is an inherently human behaviour, integral to who we are as a species and unlearnable for AI. Unfortunately, humour is indeed so integral to human communication that any form of AI which wishes to mimic human conversation must display at least a basic understanding of it. The goal of this paper is therefore to understand how and why ChatGPT misunderstands humour. This is done through testing the model's ability to identify two pieces of information important to understanding a joke. As explained in Section 1, according to the Semantic Script Theory of Humour (SSTH) (Raskin, 1985), the key to understanding any joke is to identify its two overlapping, opposed scripts. Following this theory, this paper tests ChatGPT's ability to identify scripts with the idea that, through analysis of its answers, we may learn more about the process it follows and therefore the mistakes it makes.

In total, ChatGPT is asked to identify scripts in 14 jokes, giving five answers for each. These jokes were designed to be maximally informative, following principles in the General Theory of Verbal Humour (GTVH) (Attardo & Raskin, 1991). Answers are scored on the extent to which the relevant scripts are identified. From this data some clear trends appear. Most importantly it seems ChatGPT is incorrectly assigning importance to words in the joke, leading to the misidentification of scripts. This may explain why it struggles to explain jokes. Section 1 gives background information on SSTH and ChatGPT. Section 2 describes how the jokes used in testing were designed. Section 3 then explains the testing method employed. Sections 4 and 5 give the results of this test followed by a discussion of their significance. Finally, in Section 6 this method is evaluated, and proposals are made for future testing.

2 Background Information – ChatGPT, SSTH and ANLI

2.1 The Semantic Script Theory of Humour

The test given to ChatGPT in this paper is based on the idea that, in order to explain a joke, a language model, or a person, must simply identify the two scripts within it which share two set relationships. This in turn is based on the Semantic Script Theory of Humour (SSTH) (Raskin, 1985). In SSTH, humour arises in a text from the presence of two overlapping but opposed scripts. A script here refers to a package of semantic information directly evoked by a word (Raskin, 1985, p. 81). It is the current hypothesis a person holds for a concept, such as an object or an event, which contains prototypical lexical and encyclopaedic knowledge about said concept (Raskin, 1985, pp. 82-83; Attardo, 2020, pp. 30-31). For two scripts to overlap means that the text is compatible, at least partially, with both scripts (Raskin, 1985, p. 99). The two scripts being opposed means that the situations created by each script cannot co-occur, one presents a real situation and the other an unreal one. For example, in the joke:

‘A man went to a hardware store and asked for some nails.
“How long do you want them?” asked the sales assistant.
“Oh,” said the customer. “I was rather hoping to keep them.”’
(Tibballs 2006, p. 326)

The two scripts are ‘physical length’ and ‘length of time’. Both are evoked by the text and yet both readings cannot be true at once. According to SSTH, the humour in all jokes arises from these two scripts. The relationships are unchanging and thus, to explain any joke we, or ChatGPT, must simply identify the two relevant scripts. This is what is tested in this paper.

2.1.1 ChatGPT: Training Data and Architecture

To understand and predict how ChatGPT may perform at script identification, it is necessary to know more about its underlying architecture. Throughout this paper, various models of Open AI’s GPT technology will be referenced. ChatGPT is the model tested, specifically the version which employs GPT-3.5. A version of ChatGPT which uses GPT-4 is now available, however this was not the case at the time of testing. GPT-3.5 uses the same training data and underlying architecture as GPT-3 but has the benefit of extra, more recent training data from up to September 2021 (OpenAI, 2023).

ChatGPT’s task is to generate human-like speech. To do this, when given a prompt, it predicts which word should follow the last, repeating this process to form an appropriate response. These predictions are informed by both the prompt and behaviour learned during training. GPT-3 uses training data taken from five corpuses, each containing text scraped from books and web pages online (Brown et al, 2020, pp. 8-9). The words in these corpuses are broken down into smaller clusters of letters and punctuation to ease memory use and processing costs. These are called bite-pair-encoded (BPE) tokens. The five corpuses contain 489 billion BPE tokens in total. On top of this pre-training data, ChatGPT received finetuning to better adapt it to conversation (OpenAI, 2022). This included reinforcement learning, where answers given by the model were ranked by human judges with higher ranking answers being rewarded. This data allows ChatGPT to build a model of how frequently tokens appear and should appear together. This information is encoded through embeddings. Embeddings are strings of numbers, assigned to tokens, which capture various pieces of information about them. They act as coordinates on a multidimensional graph on which embeddings considered to be related are drawn together. This captures semantic relatedness. When one embedding is evoked, this can spread to closely related embeddings, partially evoking them too (Pilehvar and Camacho-Collados, 2020, p. 5). This mirrors the views presented in Raskin (1985, p. 81) regarding scripts and their relationships. Scripts are viewed as nodes linked together on a semantic graph. The length of these links reflects the relatedness of the scripts. This allows us to understand overlap and opposedness. The two scripts will have short links to

some of the same scripts. However, they will also both be linked to scripts which cannot coincide. ChatGPT employing a similar system may therefore allow it to capture the same relationships.

Furthermore, ChatGPT may be helped by its use of transformer architecture. In older language models, input sentences were compressed into a single embedding, making it difficult to capture the totality of the information in the input (Pilehvar & Camacho-Collados, 2020, pp. 81-82). The use of a transformer mitigates this issue as ChatGPT is able to access individual embeddings assigned to every token in the prompt and answer up to that point (Pilehvar & Camacho-Collados, 2020, pp. 71-82). This allows the model to deal with all tokens in the same way as opposed to favouring those produced or seen more recently. Furthermore, the transformer employs an attention mechanism. This assigns importance to each previous token related to its usefulness in determining the current token (Pilehvar & Camacho-Collados, 2020, pp. 72-74). This should allow ChatGPT to identify scripts evoked partially by various words across a joke, while ignoring irrelevant scripts.

2.1.2 ANLI Dataset Scores

Although it does not seem that ChatGPT has been tested on script identification before, Brown et al (2020) does give the results GPT-3 achieved on many standard language model tests, including Adversarial Natural Language Inference (ANLI). ANLI (Nie et al, 2020) is a dataset which asks a language model to determine the relationship between two texts: entailment, contradiction or neutral. It is designed to be challenging, with GPT-3 failing to achieve convincingly above random chance, 33%, in all but one condition, in which it achieved 40.2% (Brown et al, 2020, p. 63). It seems though that ChatGPT does at least have some ability to understand complex semantic relationships, however it does generally struggle. This paper seeks to learn more about why this difficulty occurs.

3 Joke Design

To gain the greatest insight into ChatGPT's process when identifying scripts, it was important that the jokes used in testing were designed to be maximally informative. The first step towards this goal was to avoid using jokes which had appeared previously in ChatGPT's training data. Jokes were created from scratch in an attempt to prevent this being an issue. A further advantage of this creative approach was that it allowed jokes to be tailored to test specific aspects of ChatGPT's process. This tailoring was informed by a follow-up theory based upon SSTH, the General Theory of Verbal Humour (GTVH) (Attardo & Raskin, 1991). GTVH builds upon SSTH, splitting jokes into six Knowledge Resources (KRs): Language (LA), Narrative Strategy (NS), Target (TA), Situation (SI), Logical Mechanism (LM), and Script Opposition (SO). These KRs reflect choices in the construction of a joke. The description of each KR is based upon those of Attardo and Raskin (1991, pp. 297-309). Note that, at times, a change in one KR necessitates a change in another, particularly LA. The jokes, their relevant scripts, and the choices of KRs are given and explained below.

Joke 1 Original (OR) - Politicians are like fortune tellers, pay them and they'll say exactly what you want to hear.

Script A – Knowledge, ability, honesty, making accurate predictions

Script B – Corruption

Joke 2 Original (OR) - How many reality TV stars does it take to change a lightbulb?

Three. One to hold the bulb and two to spin him round.

Script A – Simple, everyday task

Script B – Stupidity, lack of real-world knowledge or practical skills

Table 1: *Language choices*

	OR	LA
KR Description	The choice of words and syntactic constructions which make up the joke.	
Joke 1 Choices	Plain, simple	More verbose, less common
Joke 1(LA)	Politicians behave in a manner akin to clairvoyants, give them your money and they will say precisely what you wish to hear.	
Joke 2 Choices	Seeks numerical answer	Seeks reason in answer
Joke 2(LA)	Why does it take three reality TV stars to change a lightbulb? They think they need one to hold the bulb and two to spin him round.	

1(OR) represents how such a joke may be told in day-to-day life. By contrast 1(LA) uses more verbose language less common in natural conversation. This may make the scripts harder to access as 1(LA) is less likely to resemble text seen in ChatGPT’s training data. In Joke 2, both variants use plain language but 2(LA) changes the nature of the riddle. Instead of asking for a numerical answer, it asks for a reason. This change of ordering should not affect ChatGPT’s performance, thanks to the transformer’s access to the embeddings of the entire joke.

Table 2: *Narrative strategy*

	OR	NS
KR Description	The genre of the joke, for example it may be presented as a story or expository text, a series of questions and answers or a personal ad.	
Joke 1 Choices	Expository text	Question-and-answer/Riddle
Joke 1(NS)	Why are politicians like fortune tellers? Pay them and they’ll say exactly what you want to hear.	
Joke 2 Choices	Question-and-answer/Riddle	Question-and-answer sequence
Joke 2(NS)	‘Do you think one reality TV star can change a lightbulb?’ ‘No.’ ‘Two?’ ‘No. It takes three. One to hold the bulb and two to spin him round.’	

1(OR) takes the form of an expository text. Hempelmann and Ruch (2005, p. 376) found this was the most common NS across three joke databases. The format of 1(NS) is less common and splits the data relevant to identifying the two scripts in a different way. This should not cause issues given that the

transformer can still access all embeddings across the joke. 2(OR) is a riddle which uses the lightbulb trope seen in many jokes. This was chosen in part due to the LM used in many lightbulb jokes and in part so that a common trope and NS may be compared to a rarer one. 2(NS) uses a question-and-answer format taken from Attardo and Raskin (1991, p. 300). Poor performance on this variant may indicate that ChatGPT is over reliant on a template for lightbulb jokes seen frequently in its training data.

Table 3: Target

	OR	TA
KR Description	Who or what the joke takes aim at.	
Choices Joke 1	Politicians	Florida Senators
Joke 1(TA)	Florida senators are like fortune tellers, pay them and they'll say exactly what you want to hear.	
Choices Joke 2	Reality TV stars	Idiots
Joke 2(TA)	How many idiots does it take to change a lightbulb? Three. One to hold the bulb and two to spin him round.	

Politicians are a common target for humour, in fact Raskin (1985, pp. 222-237) dedicates an entire chapter to political humour. 1(TA) uses a similar but more specific target to test whether target specificity makes Scripts A/B less accessible. It may be that as opposed to Script A/B being directly evoked by 'Florida senators', the joke evokes Florida senators which in turn evokes the script of politicians which evokes Scripts A/B. This second route, if followed, may give more chances for ChatGPT to be led astray. Reality TV stars were chosen as the target for 2(OR) to try and minimise the offensiveness of the joke while still maintaining an association between Script B and the target. The use of 'idiots' in 2(TA) is intended to evoke Script B more directly than 'reality TV stars' in 2(OR). If ChatGPT scores much higher on this variant than any other, then it may be that it has difficulty with the script of 'reality TV stars' or simply with fuzzier, less direct evocations in general.

Table 4: Situation

	OR	SI
KR Description	SI refers to the props and setting of the joke, the scene in which the joke occurs.	
Choices Joke 1	Fortune tellers, paying someone	Antiques, buying something, auctions
Joke 1(SI)	Politicians are like prized antiques, they can be auctioned off to the highest bidder.	
Choices Joke 2	Changing a lightbulb	Drawing a picture
Joke 2(SI)	How many reality TV stars does it take to draw a picture? Three. One to hold the pen and two to move the paper.	

Here 1(OR) makes a human-to-human analogy, comparing politicians to fortune tellers whereas 1(SI) makes a human-to-object analogy, comparing politicians to antiques. It may be that the lack of human connection makes Script A less accessible as human qualities are not as easily evoked by non-human items. In contrast to 2(OR), 2(SI) involves a situation, drawing a picture, which, while common in life, likely appears in jokes much less frequently than changing a lightbulb. Lower scores on this variant in comparison to 2(OR) would suggest that ChatGPT is reliant on the situation of a joke appearing frequently in its training data to identify its relevant scripts.

Table 5: Logical mechanism

	OR	LM
KR Description	All jokes to some extent use some form of faulty logic which requires a certain suspension of disbelief. LM reflects the type of faulty logic employed by a joke.	
Choices Joke 1	False Analogy	Reasoning from false premises
Joke 1(LM)	A fortune teller goes to speak to his friend. 'I've got to be honest with you, I can't do this job anymore,' says the fortune teller, 'all that happens is people pay me money and I tell them exactly what they want to hear.' 'Well, that sucks,' replies the friend, 'but at least it sounds like you could have a great career as a politician!'	
Choices Joke 2	Figure-ground reversal	Faulty Reasoning
Joke 2(LM)	How many reality TV stars does it take to change a lightbulb? Three. One to hold the bulb and two to look for a tool box.	

Hempelmann and Ruch (2005, p. 371) found false analogy to be the most common LM. It is an example of faulty logic; two entities are presented as alike in some way when in fact this is not really true (Attardo et al, 2002, p. 13). In comparison, reasoning from false premises uses correct logic (Attardo et al, 2002, p. 10). If we share the apparent assumption of the friend, that politicians just say what they are paid to say, then there is no faulty logic in the exchange, and it makes perfect sense. All variants of *Joke 2* bar *2(LM)* employ the figure-ground reversal LM. The normally static item, the person changing the bulb, and the item which normally moves, the bulb, switch roles (Attardo & Raskin, 1991, p. 303). Understanding how and why this represents faulty logic, that would nevertheless lead to completion of the task, requires both world knowledge about how a lightbulb is changed and physical/spatial reasoning. Borji (2023, pp. 3-4) demonstrates that ChatGPT often struggles with tasks that require physical/spatial reasoning. *2(LM)* only requires world knowledge about how the script of 'changing a lightbulb' is normally carried out to understand the faulty reasoning employed. Success on *2(LM)* but difficulty with the other variants may point to issues with ChatGPT's physical/spatial reasoning. Difficulties with all variants, bar *2(SI)*, may be due to a lack of world knowledge about how a lightbulb is changed.

Table 6: Script opposition

	OR	SO
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KR Description	The exact nature of the opposed scripts in the joke. Oppositions fall under three categories: ab/normal, non/actual (which present a real and not real situation) and im/possible.	
Choices Joke 1	Non/Actual – ability or honesty/corruption	Ab/normal - smart or ability/dumb or lacking ability
Joke 1(SO)	Politicians are like fortune tellers, they claim to see the future but really know nothing at all.	
Choices Joke 2	Ab/normal – smart/dumb or practical skills/no practical skills	Ab/normal – simple, practical task/conflict or drama
Joke 2(SO)	How many reality TV stars does it take to change a lightbulb? Three. One to change the bulb and two to have a screaming match about who broke the old one.	

Hempelmann and Ruch (2005, p. 371) found non/actual SOs to be the most common. *1(SO)* by contrast uses an ab/normal SO. While stupidity is not necessarily a script commonly associated with politicians, it is an example of a direct negation SO (Attardo & Raskin, 1991, p. 108). It may be that ChatGPT finds this type of opposition easier to identify than the more nuanced and indirect honesty or ability/corruption SO. The smart/dumb opposition in *2(OR)* is common across many jokes. By contrast, the simple task/conflict opposition is unlikely to appear as frequently in ChatGPT’s training data. However, the frequency of the smart/dumb opposition may lead to it being much more weakly associated with ‘reality TV stars’ when compared to the SO in *2(SO)*. Higher scores on *2(SO)* may point to issues with common scripts not being evoked strongly enough by weakly associated words.

Given these choices and the discussion in previous sections, I propose two hypotheses regarding ChatGPT’s performance. First that *2(TA)* will be the highest scoring variant. This joke uses a direct negation LM, uses plain language in the form of an expository text, contains a common joke situation and uses a target which should directly evoke *Script B*. Despite this I also propose that ChatGPT will score higher on *Joke 1* than *Joke 2* overall. This is due to *Joke 2* employing the figure-ground reversal LM and ChatGPT’s difficulties with physical/spatial reasoning.

4 Method

As previously stated, the aim of this paper was to gather qualitative data from which insights may be drawn into ChatGPT’s process when identifying scripts. Whether or not an answer correctly identifies the relevant scripts is to a certain extent subjective. Changes to this experiment which may produce more objective, but less quality-rich data are given in Section 6. There is however still value in quantitative data as it makes spotting trends in the answers easier. Answers given by ChatGPT were therefore judged against 4 criteria labelled A, B, E and O.

A and B were considered fulfilled if *Scripts A* and *B* respectively were correctly identified. These scripts are somewhat fuzzy and thus they were considered to be correctly identified if the answer referenced one of the concepts given in Tables 2 and 3. Some variants required different scripts and these are also given:

Table 7: Alternative answers to Joke 1

Joke 1	
<i>Script A</i>	<i>Script B</i>
Knowledge, honesty, doing a job honestly, making accurate predictions, ability	Corruption, being bought

<i>I(SI)</i> – Being valuable, being venerated or respected	<i>I(SO)</i> – Stupidity, lack of knowledge, inability to make accurate predictions.

Table 8: *Alternative answers to Joke 2*

Joke 2	
<i>Script A</i>	<i>Script B</i>
Simplicity, ease, practical skills, reality TV stars as normal people	Stupidity, lack of practical skills, lack of real world knowledge, uselessness
	<i>2(SO)</i> – Over dramaticism, behaving in an over-the-top manner, conflict, emotion

E was considered fulfilled if the answer contained no incorrect extraneous information. O reflects whether or not the nature of the script opposition was correctly identified. This was not originally intended as a measure and is not explicitly asked for in the prompt, however the majority of answers, 91%, referred to the nature of the script opposition in some way. An answer which did not reference this was still given a point but is marked as ‘ / ’ in Tables 9 and 10. Data is therefore presented with two different totals, one excluding the O scores and one including them.

Each joke was presented to ChatGPT in the following format:

‘According to the Semantic Script Theory of Humour, a joke is compatible fully or in part with two different scripts. These scripts are also opposed in some way. Please identify these two compatible, opposed scripts in the following joke:

[Joke]’

The prompt was intended to be concise but sufficiently informative. There were no answers where ChatGPT completely misunderstood the task and therefore it seems the prompt succeeded in this goal. Each variant was presented to ChatGPT and then the answer was regenerated to give five answers for each variant, 70 answers in total. When given the task, the option for ChatGPT to learn from the prompt was turned off to avoid later answers being affected by the results of earlier ones.

5 Results

Tables 9 and 10 contain the scores of every answer given by ChatGPT. An *x* represents that the answer fulfilled the criteria while a – represents that it did not.

Table 9: Results of ChatGPT's attempts at identifying the scripts

		Joke 1 Scores																																									
Categories	Original					Language					Narrative Strategy					Target					Situation					Logical Mechanism					Script Opposition					Total							
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5		
A	x	-	-	-	1	x	x	x	x	-	4	x	x	x	-	x	4	x	x	x	x	x	5	x	x	x	-	-	3	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	-	-	x	3	20		
B	x	-	-	-	1	x	x	x	x	-	3	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	x	-	x	2	x	x	x	-	x	4	-	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	-	-	x	3	13		
E	x	-	-	-	1	-	-	x	-	-	1	-	x	x	-	-	2	x	-	x	-	-	2	x	x	x	x	-	4	-	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	-	-	x	3	13	
O	x	-	-	-	1	-	-	/	x	x	2	-	x	x	-	-	2	x	-	x	-	x	3	x	/	/	x	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	-	-	x	3	13	
Total	3	0	0	0	0	3	2	2	3	1	0	8	1	2	2	0	1	6	2	1	3	1	2	9	3	3	3	1	1	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	0	0	3	9	46
Total + O	4	0	0	0	0	4	2	2	3	2	1	10	1	3	3	0	1	8	3	1	4	1	3	12	4	3	3	2	1	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	4	0	0	4	12	59

		Joke 2 Scores																																									
Categories	Original					Language					Narrative Strategy					Target					Situation					Logical Mechanism					Script Opposition					Total							
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5		1	2	3	4	5		
A	x	x	x	x	x	5	x	x	x	x	x	5	x	x	x	x	x	5	x	x	x	x	x	5	-	x	x	-	-	2	-	x	x	x	x	4	x	x	x	x	-	4	30
B	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	x	-	-	3	x	x	x	-	-	3	x	x	-	-	x	3	x	x	x	x	-	4	x	x	x	x	x	5	18	
E	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	x	-	-	3	-	-	x	-	-	1	-	-	x	-	-	1	x	x	x	x	-	4	9	
O	-	-	-	-	0	-	-	-	-	-	0	x	x	/	-	-	2	x	x	/	-	-	2	-	-	x	-	/	1	-	x	x	x	-	3	x	x	x	x	x	5	13	
Total	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	5	2	2	2	1	1	8	3	3	3	1	1	11	1	2	2	0	1	6	1	2	3	2	1	9	3	3	3	3	1	13	57
Total + O	1	1	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1	1	5	3	3	2	1	1	10	4	4	3	1	1	13	1	2	3	0	1	7	1	3	4	3	1	12	4	4	4	4	2	18	70

Graph 1: Total scores of joke 1 and joke 2.

Graph 1 presents the combined scores for *Joke 1* and *Joke 2*. ChatGPT performed better on *Joke 2* both including and excluding scores for **O**, thus falsifying the hypothesis that ChatGPT will perform better on *Joke 1* than *Joke 2*. This result is surprising given ChatGPT's previous struggles with physical/spatial reasoning.

Graph 2: Joke 1 and 2 by score category.

Joke 1 and Joke 2 by Score Category

Graph 2 shows ChatGPT’s performance on *Joke 1* and *Joke 2* broken down by score category. Highest performance was achieved in identifying *Script A* in both jokes, scoring 57% (20/35) and 86% (30/35) respectively. In comparison, *Script B* was correctly identified in 37% (13/35) and 51% (18/35) of answers. The strong scores of *Joke 2* in identifying *Script A* are likely due to the popularity of lightbulb jokes and discussions of them in ChatGPT’s training data.

Graph 3: Total scores of joke 1 and 2 without O.

Joke 1 Vs Joke 2: Total without O

Graph 4: Total scores of joke 1 and 2 with O.

Graphs 3 and 4 give the scores of *Joke 1* and *Joke 2*, broken down by KR. $2(TA)$ was not the highest scoring KR, as predicted in Section 2, therefore falsifying that hypothesis. Instead, ChatGPT performed best on $2(SO)$, $2(TA)$ was, however, the second highest scoring KR along with $1(SI)$. Finally, ChatGPT failed to score at all on $1(LM)$. While the complete lack of scoring is a surprise, $1(LM)$ was designed to employ a rarer, more conversational LM. It seems this was difficult for ChatGPT to parse.

6 Discussion

6.1 General Trends

As shown in Graph 2, ChatGPT had much greater success in identifying Script A than Script B. ChatGPT's much stronger performance in identifying Script A in Joke 2 compared to Joke 1 is largely the reason that the hypothesis regarding relative performance on Jokes 1 and 2 was falsified. A reason for this success with Script A may be how and where each script was evoked within the jokes. Script A in both jokes is likely to be the first, or one of the first, scripts evoked by a single key NP in the joke. In Joke 1, it is likely evoked by 'politicians' and to a certain extent 'fortune tellers', whilst in Joke 2, Script A is probably evoked by 'to change a lightbulb'. In contrast, Script B is evoked by the sum of many scripts. In Joke 1, the combination of 'politicians', 'fortune tellers', 'exactly what you want to hear' and 'pay' may be required to evoke Script B. 'Pay' is in many ways the key word, many answers failed to correctly identify Script B as they didn't mention payment in any way, as shown in answers $1(LA4)$ and $1(TA4)$. This likely also explains ChatGPT's success at identifying Script B in $1(SI)$, as shown in $1(SI1)$ and $1(SI3)$. This variant contains multiple words which may evoke money/being bought, 'auctioned', 'bidder', 'antique' and 'prized', which in turn links to the script of 'corruption'. These successes and failures point to an issue with ChatGPT's attention mechanism, as it does not give enough importance to 'pay' for identifying Script B in Joke 1.

< 4 / 4 > According to the Semantic Script Theory of Humor, the two scripts involved in the joke are:

1. The script of "Politicians as Clairvoyants": This script suggests that politicians have the ability to know what people want and need, just like clairvoyants who can predict the future or see things that others can't. This script is compatible with the joke because politicians are being compared to clairvoyants in their ability to tell people what they want to hear.
2. The script of "Politicians as Liars": This script suggests that politicians often make false promises or say things they don't really believe in, just to gain support from voters. This script is opposed to the previous script because it portrays politicians as dishonest and manipulative, rather than insightful or intuitive.

The humor in this joke arises from the incongruity between these two scripts, which are both partially compatible with the joke but also inherently contradictory.

Figure 2: *I(LA4)* (OpenAI, 2022).

 In the joke you provided, the two compatible, opposed scripts can be identified as follows:

1. Politicians as prized antiques: This script portrays politicians as valuable and sought-after individuals, similar to prized antiques. It implies that politicians have a certain worth or value that can be recognized and appreciated.
2. Politicians being auctioned off to the highest bidder: This script suggests a negative perception of politicians, highlighting the perception that they can be influenced or bought by the highest bidder. It alludes to corruption, where politicians may prioritize the interests of those who provide the most financial support or favors.

These two scripts are compatible as they both involve politicians, but they are opposed in their portrayal. The first script presents politicians in a positive light, emphasizing their value, while the second script takes a more cynical perspective, suggesting they can be influenced or controlled by money.

Figure 3: *I(LA4)* (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 4: *1(TA4) (OpenAI, 2022).*

Figure 5: *1(S13) (OpenAI, 2022).*

This links to a trend in Joke 2. Script B, ‘stupidity’ or ‘lack of practical skills’, was often missed in favour of the script of ‘over dramaticism’ or ‘frivolity’. It seems that these are the scripts most strongly evoked by ‘reality TV stars’ for ChatGPT. Therefore, instead of reconsidering this association, given the rest of the prompt, ChatGPT’s answer is tailored to fit this script of ‘over dramaticism’. This leads to answers such as 2(LA1), where it is suggested that the ‘spinning’ referenced in the joke is done in order to attract attention to the reality TV stars as opposed to being due to their supposed stupidity. This suggests that ChatGPT is placing too much importance on connections learned in its training data and not appropriately considering information given in the prompt. This may also be caused in part by issues with the figure-ground reversal LM and physical/spatial reasoning, as discussed further in Section 5.6.

Figure 6: 2(LA1) (OpenAI, 2022).

Finally, many answers contain incorrect/contradictory extraneous information. 2(NS1) provides an example of this behaviour. Only answer 1(LA3) contains no extraneous information at all. Often, this information comes in the form of an incorrectly identified opposition between scripts. This trend of overly verbose answers is acknowledged by OpenAI (2022) in their blog post introducing ChatGPT. They suggest it occurs because human trainers show a preference for complex, verbose answers which supposedly demonstrate more in-depth knowledge. This leads to ChatGPT being rewarded for such answers and therefore preferring them in the future.

Figure 7: 2(NS1) (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 8: *1(LA3) (OpenAI, 2022).*

6.2 OR and LA

ChatGPT performed poorly in 1(OR), 2(OR) and 2(LA), while achieving average scores in 1(LA). The exception to this is 1(OR1) which is a near perfect answer. In 1(OR) there is too much focus on negative scripts associated with ‘politicians’. 1(OR2) provides an interesting example of this. This seems to stem from an assumption that the two NPs, ‘politicians’ and ‘fortune tellers’, are the root of Scripts A and B. ‘Fortune tellers’ as a script and its associations are given too much importance, again pointing to issues with the attention mechanism. ChatGPT performs much better on 1(LA). Scripts A and B are both identified more frequently. It is not clear why this occurred, but it seems in part to be caused by ‘clairvoyants’ evoking ‘predicting the future’ more strongly than ‘fortune tellers’. Furthermore, the phrase ‘give them your money’ is given more importance than ‘pay’ is given in 1(OR), leading to the monetary aspect of Script B being evoked.

In both 2(OR) and 2(LA), Script A is identified in every answer. This result is not surprising given that changing a lightbulb is a common joke setup which ChatGPT is likely to have seen in its training data alongside explanations of such jokes. ChatGPT however has no success in identifying Script B. ‘Reality TV stars’ most strongly evokes the script of ‘over dramaticism’ and the rest of the prompt is not enough to change that. The lack of change between 2(LA) and 2(OR) suggests that changing the nature of the answer, from giving a number to giving a reason, had no effect.

Figure 9: *1(OR) (OpenAI, 2022).*

Figure 10: *1(OR2)* (OpenAI, 2022).

6.3 NS

Script A is more accessible in variant 1(NS), than in 1(OR). The reason for this is again unclear. The question-and-answer split leads to the positive aspects of politicians being more strongly evoked. However, this does not aid in identifying Script B. It seems ‘pay’ being at the start of a separate sentence did not assign it greater importance as there was still a failure to recognise the payment aspect of Script B, see 1(NS5). The uncommon NS of 2(NS) did not present an issue for ChatGPT. In fact, the further breaking down of the answer appears to have made Script B easier to identify, perhaps because it emphasises that ‘one’ is the expected answer to the original question.

Figure 11: *1(NS5)* (OpenAI, 2022).

6.4 TA

In Section 2 it was suggested that the greater specificity of ‘Florida senators’ may make Script A harder to identify. This was not the case. ChatGPT had no issues with ‘Florida senators’ evoking the scripts of ‘political duties’ and ‘honesty’. It seems that ‘Florida Senators’ was not an isolated script which would have to evoke ‘politicians’ before any other script for the joke to make sense. In fact, the greater specificity appears to have made Script A easier to identify. Variant 2(TA) was predicted to be the highest scoring. Although ChatGPT did have success with this variant, this hypothesis was ultimately falsified due to issues identifying Script B and the nature of the resultant opposition. These issues are

shown in 2(TA4). One script was deemed to be related to ‘physical comedy’. This seems to stem from an issue with physical/spatial reasoning, the figure-ground reversal LM and a misunderstanding of how the act of ‘spinning’ fits into this.

Figure 12: 2(TA4) (OpenAI, 2022).

6.5 SI

ChatGPT identifies Script B more successfully in 1(SI) than in 1(OR) and gives less incorrect extraneous information. The human-to-object connection does not seem to have had an effect, contrary to the suggestion in Section 2. As described previously, this success may be to do with greater signposting of the monetary aspect of Script B throughout the joke. In 2(SI), ChatGPT has difficulties identifying Script A. Where in previous variants the model seemed to have some world knowledge about how the script of ‘changing a lightbulb’ is normally carried out, this is not the case for drawing a picture. This leads to answers such as 2(SI1) and follows the reasoning given in Section 2. The combination of this lack of world knowledge with difficulties in physical/spatial reasoning also causes issues in identifying Script B.

Figure 13: 2(SI1) (OpenAI, 2022).

6.6 LM

1(LM) was the only variant in which ChatGPT scored 0%. As opposed to being caused by the correct reasoning employed in the LM, as suggested in Section 2, the issue again seems to stem from a failure to appropriately assign importance. The key word for evoking both scripts is ‘politicians’ however this comes at the end of the joke after a long section mainly focused on ‘fortune tellers’. ‘Fortune tellers’ and related scripts are then given too much attention leading to answers such as 1(LM1). This result is particularly striking given that 1(LM) reflects a style of humour very common in natural conversation. 2(LM) is the only variant of Joke 2 which does not require physical/spatial reasoning. This may have led to ChatGPT having greater success identifying Script B as its identification was instead largely reliant on world knowledge of how the script of ‘changing a lightbulb’ is normally carried out. It may also be helped by ‘tool box’ strongly evoking the script of ‘practical skills’.

Figure 14: *1(LM1) (OpenAI, 2022).*

6.7 SO

ChatGPT performs well on 1(SO). 1(SO1) and 1(SO2) are good answers which each score 100%. It seems that the script of ‘dumbness’ is either strongly evoked by ‘politicians’ or the commonness of ‘dumbness’ as a script in jokes prevented lack of association from being an issue. It may also be that the phrase ‘know nothing at all’ strongly evokes ‘dumbness’. ChatGPT seemed to place a lot of importance in ‘what you want to hear’, the final phrase of other variants which led it to miss out on the monetary aspect of Script B. 1(SO3) and 1(SO4) do still highlight ChatGPT’s tendency at times to simply list the scripts most strongly evoked by NPs in the joke, a behaviour also seen in Joke 2. 2(SO) is the highest scoring variant. This is likely because Script B is aligned with the script ‘reality TV stars’, which most strongly evokes ‘over dramaticism’ for ChatGPT. This further highlights ChatGPT’s difficulties in going beyond its first assumptions when identifying scripts. If the script to be identified matches these assumptions, then ChatGPT is likely to succeed.

Figure 15: *I(SO1)* (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 16: *I(SO2)* (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 17: *I(SO3)* (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 18: *1(SO4)* (OpenAI, 2022).

In summary, the two hypotheses proposed in Section 2 were falsified. ChatGPT performed better on Joke 2 than Joke 1 and variant 2(SO) was the highest scoring not 2(TA). One trend became apparent, ChatGPT appears to have issues assigning importance appropriately to words in the prompt. This led in some cases to key nuances of scripts being missed, e.g., the money aspect of Joke 1 Script B, and in others to irrelevant scripts being given too much weight, such as the script of ‘over-dramaticism’ in Joke 2. ChatGPT also at times relied too much on patterns seen in its training data, ignoring key information given in the prompt.

7 Evaluation of Method and Future Tests

This paper’s main goal was to learn about ChatGPT’s ability to identify overlapping but opposed scripts in jokes. This followed from an overarching goal of gaining a better understanding of how and why ChatGPT fails to explain jokes. I believe the method used to gain this information was ultimately successful. From the elicited answers, some key issues became apparent, primarily that importance or attention was being improperly assigned to different words in the prompt. This may help to explain answers such as Figure 1, where ‘afraid’ is assumed to be more important than necessary to the understanding of the joke, leading to a nonsensical answer. As a whole, ChatGPT seemed to grasp what was being asked of it. I therefore suggest that the testing method had merit. However, it was not without issue. This links to a secondary goal of this paper, the proposal of a method to test script identification objectively across model and experiments. The format used in this paper admittedly involves subjective judgement by one individual and would therefore be inappropriate for this task. One change could be to employ more than one person to judge answers. However, a better method may be to reduce the options for answers to a true/false binary. Examples of this are given in Figures 19 and 20. This method would allow for greater standardisation and objectivity as models could be marked against a pre-determined answer sheet. A format similar to the one in the ANLI dataset (Nie et al, 2020) would be appropriate, using joke-script pairs which a language model had previously failed to correctly identify.

Figure 19: Example of current method (OpenAI, 2022).

Figure 20: Example of true/false binary method (OpenAI, 2022).

8 Conclusion

This paper set out to gain a better understanding of why ChatGPT at times fails to explain jokes. SSTH (Raskin, 1985) proposes that, in jokes, humour arises from a text containing two overlapping, opposed scripts. This led to testing ChatGPT's ability to identify these scripts and then analysing the elicited answers in order to learn more about its process. ChatGPT was asked to identify scripts in fourteen joke variants, designed using GTVH (Attardo & Raskin, 1991). Two hypotheses were proposed and falsified. Firstly, ChatGPT did not perform better on variant 2(TA) than any other. Secondly, it scored higher on Joke 2 than Joke 1, contrary to the proposed hypothesis. Analysis of ChatGPT's answers revealed some key issues, largely with how attention or importance was assigned. In particular, too much importance was given to NPs in the jokes, often leading to other key words being ignored as thus scripts being misidentified. Similarly, too much weight was given to patterns found in ChatGPT's training data, leading to nuances in the prompts being missed. Issues with physical/spatial reasoning, highlighted in Borji (2023) were present and often answers contained incorrect or contradictory extraneous data, an issue noted by OpenAI (2022).

Finally, modifications to the method employed in this paper were suggested. Further research could seek to build on this method. The first step in this would be to create a database of joke-script pairs, possibly consisting of pairs which ChatGPT failed to identify. This would create a purposefully difficult benchmark test, similar to the ANLI dataset. Once created, this database could be used to test whether the method as a whole is useful for understanding how ChatGPT identifies scripts and therefore how it explains humour.

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10 Appendix One: ChatGPT Answers

The appendix of the individually published article (available on Zenodo) contains the full list of every answer given by ChatGPT (OpenAI 2022). They are omitted from the Proceedings for reasons of length.

Perspective-Taking in Adult Monolinguals and Multilinguals

Minhee (Ines) Lee

University of Edinburgh

Abstract. Humans excel in cooperative communication, showcasing a remarkable ability to efficiently navigate misunderstandings through pragmatic competence, which involves understanding the context and the knowledge states of their interlocutors. Seminal research by Keysar et al. (2000) and Epley et al. (2004) has highlighted the indispensable role of perspective-taking in effective communication, enabling individuals to adjust their initial self-centred interpretations to better align with the context. This has sparked an inquiry into whether multilingual individuals possess superior perspective-taking abilities compared to monolinguals. This dissertation explores the faculty of spatial perspective-taking among adult monolinguals and multilinguals. The study adopts and modifies the director's task, as originally conceived by Keysar et al. (2000), for its experimental framework. Participants are engaged with a task involving a 4x4 grid filled with objects and a corresponding picture of the target grid arrangement. Their challenge is to guide a counterpart, who views the grid from an inverted left/right perspective, to rearrange the objects to match the target grid. This setup critically tests the participants' executive control, necessitating the suppression of egocentric biases and the accommodation of the counterpart's perspective. Findings from this investigation reveal that multilinguals demonstrate superior accuracy compared to monolinguals across both reproduction and verbal guidance tasks. The study also delves into potential limitations that might obscure the multilingual advantage in perspective-taking, such as the effects of training and external variables.

Keywords: experimental pragmatics; perspective-taking; Theory of Mind; bilingualism

1 Introduction

1.1 What is Theory of Mind?

Theory of Mind (ToM), alternatively known as mind reading or perspective-taking, represents the cognitive capacity to infer the thoughts, beliefs, and emotions of others, thereby anticipating their actions (Baron-Cohen et al., 1985). This faculty is pivotal for social interaction as it facilitates an understanding of others' mental states, even when they diverge from one's own perspective. The false-belief task, a widely recognised method of evaluating ToM, assesses an individual's comprehension that people may hold beliefs about the world that differ from reality. Research has consistently shown that children typically begin to successfully complete false-belief tasks by the age of four (Baillargeon et al., 2010), marking a significant milestone in cognitive and social development.

1.2 The Relationship Between Theory of Mind and Language

A quintessential application of Theory of Mind (ToM) in human interaction is evident in the realm of communication. Grice (1969) dedicated his research to the pragmatic aspects of verbal communication, positing that its core features include the expression and recognition of intentions. Expression refers to the speaker's utterances, serving as input for the listener, while recognition entails the listener's processing of these utterances to grasp the intended message. Grice likened this pragmatic interpretation to a form of decoding, wherein the listener extracts the speaker's intended meaning from the provided

verbal cues. This process is complicated by instances where the linguistic meaning of the utterance diverges from the speaker's actual intent.

Consider the issue of referential ambiguity illustrated by the example:

- (1) I was at the party with Susie and Leah. Everything was alright until she spilt juice on my white shirt.

The ambiguity arises from the pronoun 'she' in the second sentence, leaving the referent's identity unclear. This could imply Susie, Leah, or another person at the party. To clarify this ambiguity, the listener must rely on prior utterances, the context, or subsequent information provided by the speaker. It also underscores the listener's responsibility to maintain an awareness of the knowledge shared with the speaker throughout their conversation.

Irony introduces a further layer of complexity. Consider a scenario where it is heavily raining outside, and a friend remarks.

- (2) What a perfect day for a picnic.

A literal interpretation would erroneously imply that a day with heavy rain is ideal for a picnic. However, a cooperative listener, by taking into account the context and the speaker's tone, would discern that the speaker is employing sarcasm. The remark about the rainy day being perfect for a picnic is recognised as irony, underscoring the speaker's actual intent to highlight the incongruity of the situation.

These examples underscore the critical role of pragmatic competence in facilitating cooperative dialogue. Effective communication demands that listeners not only track the conversational context and shared knowledge but also consider the speaker's mental state, including intentions and attitudes. For example, recognising the irony in statement (2) involves inferring the speaker's sarcastic intent. Thus, ToM — the capacity to understand and attribute beliefs, desires, and intentions to oneself and others — is foundational to pragmatic competence. Several decades after Grice's hypothesis, Sperber and Wilson (2002) speculated the existence of a specialised ToM sub-module dedicated to pragmatic comprehension, rather than a general ToM module. Nonetheless, they concurred with Grice's perspective that pragmatic interpretation fundamentally exercises ToM abilities.

2 Research Background

2.1 The Relationship Between Theory of Mind and Bilingualism

2.1.1 Initial Investigation into the Impact of Bilingualism on ToM Development

Previous research has predominantly concentrated on populations exhibiting delayed development in Theory of Mind (ToM), such as individuals diagnosed with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). This observation led linguists and psychologists to speculate on the existence of a demographic potentially experiencing accelerated ToM development, juxtaposed against those with delayed development. Bilingual children, who are exposed to and regularly use two or more languages from an early age, were identified as potential subjects for this hypothesis. The pioneering study by Goetz (2003) marked the initial investigation into the impact of bilingualism on ToM development. The study comprised 104 participants, segmented into 32 monolingual Mandarin speakers, 32 monolingual English speakers, and 40 bilingual Mandarin-English speakers. Given that the developmental shift in ToM typically occurs between the ages of 3 and 4 (Hogrefe et al., 1986), the participants were evenly divided between these

two age groups. To control for socioeconomic status, the groups were matched based on parental education levels, requiring at least one parent to have completed college-level education. For the bilingual participants, Mandarin served as the primary home language, with English exposure beginning around the age of 2, primarily through daycare and supplemented by English inputs at home from parental conversations or media, including television.

The study utilised four distinct ToM tasks: the appearance-reality task, a level-two perspective-taking task, and two false-belief tasks, including one designed by Hogrefe et al. (1986), known as the false-belief content task. The procedure involved presenting a box of M&M chocolates to the children, prompting them to guess its contents. Upon their response, the experimenter revealed an unexpected item, such as a toy car, inside the box. The box was then closed, and the children were asked what a friend, who had not seen inside the box, would guess its contents to be. Bilingual children underwent testing in one language initially, followed by a second test in the other language a week later. Monolingual children were also tested twice, with a week's interval, in their native language. To ensure novelty, the ToM tasks were available in two versions (A/B), altering only specific details like the M&M box contents while keeping the general procedure consistent. The findings highlighted a significant age effect, with 4-year-old participants outperforming 3-year-old participants. Notably, bilingual participants outperformed monolingual ones in ToM tasks, particularly during the first test. However, this bilingual advantage was less pronounced in subsequent testing, as monolingual showed significant improvement in three ToM tasks. Goetz (2003) clarified that the absence of improvement in bilingual participants' ToM abilities did not signify a decline, but rather indicated that, having achieved optimal performance on the first test, these participants encountered a ceiling effect with limited scope for further improvements in the second test. This phenomenon sets up the point that bilingual advantage in ToM will be relatively hard to demonstrate in adults, perhaps due to ceiling effects.

2.1.2 Mechanisms behind the Bilingual Advantage in ToM

Goetz (2003) successfully identified a bilingual advantage in Theory of Mind (ToM) development but did not delineate the mechanisms through which bilingualism could enhance ToM capabilities. Goetz (2003) suggested three potential explanations — executive functions, metalinguistic awareness, and sociolinguistic awareness — as likely contributing factors to this enhanced ToM development among bilingual individuals, yet empirical support for these hypotheses remained elusive. Subsequent research endeavoured to determine the most credible explanation for the bilingual advantage observed in ToM.

2.1.3 Executive Function

The executive function hypothesis posits that improved executive control abilities in bilinguals contribute to their superior ToM development. Executive functions refer to the suite of cognitive processes responsible for regulating attention and controlling goal-directed behaviour. This includes skills such as working memory, inhibitory control, and cognitive flexibility (Diamond, 2013). Of these, inhibitory control and working memory are speculated to be pivotal in facilitating the enhanced ToM observed in bilingual individuals. Inhibitory control is defined as the capacity to focus on pertinent information while suppressing irrelevant stimuli. Working memory involves the temporary storage and manipulation of information.

Bilingual individuals frequently engage in language inhibition, selectively suppressing one language while using another. For instance, an Italian-English bilingual student residing in England may predominantly use English at the university, concurrently inhibiting her native Italian while communicating with her peers. This cognitive mechanism parallels the processes involved in ToM,

wherein one must suppress their personal mental state to contemplate the mental state of others. An illustrative example is the Sally-Anne task (Baron-Cohen et al., 1985), where the participant is aware that an object has been relocated yet must respond based on Sally's believed mental state, not their own knowledge. Thus, the participant would indicate that Sally will search for the object in its original location, despite knowing its actual whereabouts, showcasing the interplay between inhibitory control and ToM capabilities in bilinguals.

Kovács (2009) proposed two theories to elucidate how proficiency in managing multiple languages might bolster executive control abilities, thereby facilitating ToM development. The first, termed the competence change account, posits that bilingual individuals frequently encounter situations where their mental representations diverge from reality more so than monolinguals. Such recurrent exposure to scenarios requiring the inhibition of these representations purportedly cultivates superior ToM skills in bilinguals. Conversely, the performance factor account contends that while all children possess innate ToM abilities, additional capabilities like inhibition are essential for resolving tasks involving false beliefs. Kovács (2009) referenced Leslie et al. (2005)'s dual-component model of ToM reasoning to further delineate the performance factor account, which suggests that ToM mechanisms are employed to understand beliefs or desires of oneself or others. However, tasks involving false beliefs necessitate the suppression of the assumption that these beliefs are accurate, thereby requiring an additional, gradually developing mechanism, such as a selection processor, to meet these inhibitory demands.

The study engaged 64 participants, divided evenly between Romanian-Hungarian bilinguals and Romanian monolinguals, with an average age of 3 years and 3 months. It incorporated two distinct ToM tasks: a conventional false-belief task and a language-switch variant of this task. The standard task replicated Wimmer and Perner (1983)'s false-belief location task, while the modified version introduced a language-switch scenario involving two puppets — a monolingual and a bilingual — deciding where to purchase ice cream. Upon the puppets' arrival at the ice-cream store, the seller, speaking a language unknown to the monolingual puppet, announces that ice-cream is sold out, but sandwiches are available. Participants were then asked to predict the monolingual puppet's next action. Kovács (2009) posited that the two theoretical accounts would generate distinct predictions: the competence change account anticipated no difference in bilinguals' performance on the standard task compared to monolinguals due to the specific training effects of language switching. In contrast, the performance factor account predicted a general advantage in inhibitory processing among bilinguals, suggesting their superior performance on both ToM tasks. The results indicate that bilingual participants significantly surpassed monolingual ones in both tasks, supporting the performance factor account, which attributes enhanced ToM abilities in bilinguals to advanced inhibitory control.

Ngyuen and Astington (2014) expanded the discourse on the cognitive mechanisms underlying false-belief task performance by incorporating working memory alongside inhibitory control. They conceptualised working memory not merely as a system for maintaining information but also as one that manipulates it. In executing false-belief tasks, participants must first retain and recall the narrative's key details, such as the object's initial and ultimate locations, effectively juggling dual representations of reality in their minds. Subsequently, they must identify and choose the representation that deviates from actuality to successfully navigate the false-belief task. This approach marked a departure from Kovács (2009), who focused on comparing the false-belief and inhibitory control abilities of monolingual and bilingual participants, by also evaluating working memory capabilities.

The study involved 72 participants, divided into three groups: 24 English monolinguals, 24 French monolinguals, and 24 bilinguals, fluent in both English and French. Participants' ages spanned from 3 to 5 years. To evaluate ToM, the research incorporated two established false-belief tasks: the change-in-location task (Wimmer & Perner, 1983) and the unexpected-contents task (Gopnik & Astington, 1988). In addition, a Stroop task, also known as the Day-night task (Gerstadt et al., 1994),

was administered to assess conflict inhibition capabilities, wherein participants were instructed to state ‘sun’ upon viewing a moon image and vice versa. This task consisted of 16 trials, evenly split between sun and moon cards, presented randomly. To assess working memory, a backward word span task, akin to the backward digit span task from the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children-III (Wechsler, 1991), was employed. Participants were asked to reverse and recall sequences of words, starting with two words and increasing in number with each successful trial until failure to accurately recall the sequence prompted task termination. The findings indicated that bilingual participants excelled over their monolingual counterparts in false-belief tasks, corroborating results from previous research. Further analysis sought to identify correlations between performance on false-belief tasks, the Day-night task, and the backward word span task. No correlation was found between the Day-night task and the false-belief tasks, indicating no discernible mono-bilingual difference in Day-night task performance. However, a significant correlation emerged between the backward word span task and false-belief tasks, bolstering the argument that working memory serves as a foundational component in the comprehension of false beliefs.

Nguyen and Astington (2014)’s research offers an alternate explanation to Kovács (2009) by attributing bilinguals’ enhanced ToM development to superior working memory rather than inhibitory control. They argue that bilinguals, who maintain dual mental lexicons and routinely select the appropriate language based on context, engage in continuous working memory practice. This ongoing engagement with working memory tasks, necessitated by bilingual communication, purportedly facilitates the development of ToM abilities beyond that of monolingual counterparts, who lack such regular working memory exercise in communication contexts.

2.1.4 *Metalinguistic Awareness*

Metalinguistic awareness refers to the capacity to consciously reflect on and analyse the formal aspects of language as an object of thought. This awareness enables bilingual individuals to recognise from an early age that speakers of different languages have distinct lexical representations for the same concepts. For instance, what is known as a ‘school’ in English is referred to as ‘schule’ in German, despite both terms denoting the same institution where children are educated daily. Similarly, ToM is predicted on the understanding that mental states can diverge from actual circumstances. Metalinguistic awareness can be evaluated through tasks such as the synonym judgement task (Doherty & Perner, 1998). In this task, experimenters introduce various objects to participants, assigning two different names to each. For example, a toy boat may be identified as either a ‘ship’ or ‘boat’. Once participants are acquainted with the objects and their labels, they are asked to name an object. Subsequently, a puppet is introduced, which uses the alternate label for the object. Participants are then tasked with determining whether the puppet’s label is an appropriate synonym. If the puppet refers to the toy boat as a ‘boat’, the participant should affirm the correctness of the puppet’s choice. Conversely, if the puppet incorrectly identifies the toy boat as a ‘car’, the participant is expected to reject the puppet’s designation.

Diaz and Farrar (2018) embarked on a longitudinal study to examine the predictors of false-belief understanding in later developmental stages among preschoolers, assessing the impact of language proficiency, metalinguistic awareness, and executive functions. Initially, the study involved 38 English monolinguals and 40 Spanish-English bilinguals. After a year, 25 of the monolinguals and 22 of the bilinguals, who had not moved away, were reassessed using the same tasks. The comprehensive battery of tests included evaluations for false-belief understanding, inhibitory control, working memory, metalinguistic awareness, and language proficiency. Initially, the participants undertook three language tasks aimed at measuring their vocabulary breadth. Subsequently, they were engaged in three false-belief tasks mirroring the design by Wimmer and Perner (1983) to examine change-in-location understanding. Inhibitory control was evaluated through three variations of the Stroop task, including

the Day-night task, whereas working memory assessment was conducted via a digit memory task requiring the recall and reproduction of numbers. Metalinguistic awareness was gauged through four tasks, one of which was the synonym judgement task. Another notable task was the symbol substitution task, wherein participants had to acknowledge that symbols (words) could be interchanged, such as referring to a bird as a 'banana' and inferring its ability to 'fly'.

The findings revealed that, for monolinguals, scores in executive function and language tasks were significant predictors of false belief understanding a year later. Contrastingly, for bilingual participants, it was the metalinguistic awareness scores that significantly forecasted their performance on false-belief tasks after a year, challenging previous research that highlighted executive function as the sole enhancer of ToM abilities in bilinguals. Thus, Diaz and Farrar (2018)'s research proposes that metalinguistic awareness might offer a more accurate explanation for the bilingual advantage in ToM development.

2.1.4 Sociolinguistic Awareness

The final aspect under consideration is sociolinguistic awareness, which pertains to bilingual individuals' capacity to adapt their language use to suit the communicative needs of their interlocutors. This awareness stems from the observation that different communities prefer different languages, contingent upon their social and environmental contexts. For instance, Japanese individuals typically communicate in Japanese, the nation's official language. The sociolinguistic awareness hypothesis posits that such recognition contributes to a deeper understanding that mental states can vary among individuals. *Petito and Kovelman (2003)* discovered evidence of sociolinguistic awareness in bilingual children as young as two years old. These children demonstrated the ability to select the appropriate language based on their conversational partner's linguistic background. In situations where there was a mismatch between the languages spoken by the child and the interlocutor, the children were observed to switch language deliberately to facilitate effective communication.

Relative to the extensive body of research on executive control, studies examining the connection between sociolinguistic awareness and ToM are markedly scarce (*Yu et al., 2021*). One notable investigation into this relationship was conducted by *Tare and Gelman (2010)*, involving 28 English-Marathi bilingual children divided into a younger cohort (mean age of three years and two months) and an older cohort (mean age of four years and six months). This study encompassed three distinct tasks: the object naming task, the free play task, and ToM tasks, all undertaken in both languages. Initially, the object naming task required participants to identify objects presented by the experimenter in the language of instruction. For instance, if questions were posed in English, responses were expected in English, and similarly for Marathi. Failure to respond in the correct language prompted the experimenter to seek clarification. The free play task involved unstructured interaction with toys or puzzles, during which children were anticipated to converse in the experimenter's language. ToM understanding was assessed through tasks modelled after *Wellman and Liu (2004)*, focusing on false-belief comprehension.

The object naming task results revealed that 25 participants accurately named objects in English on their first attempt. However, a significant proportion struggled with Marathi labels, with 75.6% of the younger group and 58.1% of the older group failing to respond correctly even after three prompts, likely due to the lesser proficiency in Marathi. During the free play task, participants' linguistic choices were categorised into complete English/Marathi usage, code-switching, or other expressions like exclamations, particularly noting language use during Marathi interactions. A substantial portion of younger participants (70%) used Marathi, contrasted with 25% English and 5% code-switched responses. Among older children, 80% used Marathi, 10% English, and 10% included English insertions. Analysis of the relationship between performance in sociolinguistic awareness tasks and ToM tasks indicated that children who adeptly adjusted their language in the object naming task

demonstrated higher ToM task scores. This finding lends support to the hypothesis that bilingual advantages stem from engaging in pragmatic adaptations, such as language switching to meet conversational partners' linguistic preferences.

2.2 The Director's Task and its Previous Studies

2.2.1 *Director's Task*

Traditionally, research investigating perspective-taking capabilities has utilised false-belief tasks, which assess the ability to consider another's mental state as a criterion for task completion. Diverging from this norm, Keysar et al. (2000) proposed a new experimental approach — a type of referential communication game. This method aims to explore how individuals navigate communicative ambiguities by employing perspective-taking strategies.

This new experimental method introduced by Keysar et al. (2000) is known as the director's task. This task positions a participant and a confederate on opposite sides of a vertical array filled with various objects. The confederate assumes the role of the director, who, guided by a picture depicting objects in specific locations, must instruct the participant — the addressee — to rearrange the objects to mirror the arrangement shown in the picture. To delve deeper into the significance of perspective-taking within the comprehension process, Keysar et al. (2000) incorporated a unique condition. This involved altering the visibility of certain slots from the director's perspective, thereby creating a divergence in perspective between the director and the addressee. For instance, as illustrated in Figure 1, the director can see only two candles, whereas the addressee can see three. This discrepancy sets the stage for a critical trial designed to test the hypothesis regarding how addressee utilises heuristics to resolve communicative ambiguities. For example, should the director instruct, "Put the small candle below the bottle," a perspective-taking addressee, aware that the director can only see two candles, would comprehend that 'small candle' refers to what is actually the medium-sized candle from their own viewpoint. Conversely, an addressee who fails to engage in perspective-taking and relies instead on an egocentric heuristic might mistakenly move the actually small candle that is occluded from the director's view.

Keysar et al. (2000) implemented the director's task in an experiment with 20 native English-speaking participants, each assuming the role of the addressee while the experimenter served as the confederate director. The study comprised a total of 12 trials — half within an experimental condition necessitating perspective-taking to acknowledge the director's limited view of certain objects, and the other half serving as control trials. Eye movements of participants were meticulously tracked using Applied Science Laboratories eye-tracker technology, premised on the understanding that eye fixation on a referent object often precedes physical action towards it. This eye-fixation data provided insights into the addressees' referent identification process. The findings from this experiment can be distilled into three key observations.

Figure 1: *Director's task setup from Keysar et al. (2000)*

Initially, analysis of fixations on occluded objects indicated that addressees engaged more with these objects — both in frequency and duration — under experimental conditions where they were contextually relevant, as opposed to control conditions. This behaviour underscores the addressees' consideration of occluded objects in interpreting directives. Secondly, while initial eye movement towards an occluded object was swift, subsequent shifts in focus to the mutually visible object were slower in the experimental conditions. This suggests that reconciling the intended referent with its initial occluded consideration prolongs the process when the object is not visible from the director's perspective. Finally, the movement of the last fixation before action highlighted a significant delay in the experimental condition, reflecting the final decision-making phase of the addressees. This delay, alongside an extended duration to finalise a decision under experimental conditions, implies that integrating the director's perspective and excluding occluded objects from consideration complicates and slows decision-making. Remarkably, 17% of participants physically interacted with occluded objects, demonstrating the strong pull of egocentric bias despite awareness of the director's obstructed view. These outcomes elucidate that while addressees do recognise and attempt to adjust for the director's differing perspective, this adjustment process can be neither swift nor infallible, occasionally leading to selection errors.

2.2.2 *Director's Task with Adult and Child Participants*

Several years after their initial work, Keysar collaborated with other psychologists to explore the dynamics of perspective-taking across different age groups. Epley et al. (2004) posited that the capability for accurate perspective-taking is not innate but rather developed over the course of one's life. As a result, while adults may exhibit fewer egocentric errors than children, this does not necessarily imply that they have entirely moved beyond the modes of thought characteristic of childhood. Egocentrism, according to the authors, persists throughout life rather than being a transient stage of early development. They proposed two theories to explain why adults display fewer egocentric biases compared to children.

The first theory, termed the theory-driven account, suggests that adults are less prone to projecting their own perspectives onto others during interpretative processes. This indicates that adults engage in fundamentally different cognitive mechanisms for perspective-taking than children, informed by cumulative life experiences that enhance their understanding of how other minds operate. Such experiences reinforce the recognition that their perceptions might diverge significantly from those of

others, forming a basis for the mature theory of mind that facilitates the suppression of egocentric interpretation and promotes the consideration of others' mental states.

The second theory, known as the egocentric-correction account, proposes that both adults and children initially approach perspective-taking with an automatic egocentric bias. The difference lies in adults' improved ability to consciously correct these biases as needed. This suggests that while the initial interpretation may be egocentric in nature, adults possess a more refined capacity for subsequent correction, distinguishing their perspective-taking process from that of children.

Employing the director's task previously utilised by Keysar et al. (2000), Epley et al. (2004) involved 33 native English-speaking children and their parents. Each participant played the role of the addressee, with the experimenter acting as the confederate director. The experimental design included a total of 4 trials, each comprising four distinct instructions, one of which was designated as the critical trial. Similar to Keysar et al. (2000), participants' eye movements were meticulously recorded. The findings indicated more pronounced egocentric behaviour among children compared to adults during object manipulation tasks. Specifically, adults exhibited a lower tendency to reach for occluded objects than did children. Analysis of eye movement data across all trials revealed that adults identified objects more rapidly than children, with all participants showing a quicker initial fixation on occluded objects as opposed to those visible to both parties. Notably, there was no discernible difference in the speed at which adults and children fixated on occluded objects. However, a significant difference was observed in the rapidity with which they directed their gaze towards objects observable by both the director and the addressee. This suggests that while adults were equally likely as children to initially consider an egocentric object as the intended referent, they were significantly more adept at adjusting this initial bias and refrained from acting upon the occluded objects. Such eye movement patterns align with the egocentric-correction account, highlighting a process where information is first interpreted through an egocentric lens before being corrected or adapted to acknowledge the perspective of another. The study concludes that the automatic processing of personal perspective does not significantly differ between adults and children, yet the two groups diverge in their ability to execute controlled adjustments necessary for aligning with another's perspective.

2.2.3 Director's Task with Bilingual Participants

Navarro and Conway (2021) recently broadened the study applying the director's task to include adult bilingual participants. Building on prior research, as detailed in the preceding section, it has been consistently found that bilingual individuals surpass monolinguals in tasks assessing ToM capabilities, such as those evaluating false-belief understanding. Navarro and Conway (2021) concur with the notion that certain facets of the bilingual experience might enhance the ability to comprehend differing perspectives. They propose that the interaction between bilingualism and ToM could be elucidated through two theoretical frameworks. The first, termed the performance view of ToM, posits that bilinguals' superior ToM abilities stem from heightened executive control, a result of continual language switching and the inhibition of non-target languages. The second framework, the competence of ToM, suggests that bilinguals' early and ongoing development of metalinguistic awareness plays a critical role. This perspective argues that bilinguals consistently refine their initial, egocentric theories about others' thoughts, acknowledging that individuals possess distinct mental states which may not always align with reality. Despite these insights, it remains to be determined whether one or both of these perspectives adequately account for the observed bilingual advantage in ToM tasks.

The study modified the director's task, initially developed by Keysar et al. (2000), to assess the perspective-taking aspect of ToM in both monolingual and bilingual adults. The researchers hypothesised a modest yet significant difference, anticipating that bilingual adults would excel over monolinguals in tasks requiring ToM, particularly in conditions demanding an understanding of

another's perspective, but not in tasks devoid of this requirement. The participant pool comprised 37 self-identified bilinguals and 41 monolinguals, all recruited from a college in California, USA. Each participant assumed the role of the addressee, with the experimenter serving as the confederate director. The study's structure involved 8 control trials (termed the no-director condition) and 8 experimental trials. The control trials did not necessitate perspective-taking but instead focused on the participants' ability to suppress dominant responses in favour of adhering to a set of task-specific rules, thereby assessing general executive control functions. The experimental trials, on the other hand, required participants to engage in level one perspective-taking to deduce the director's viewpoint, constantly mindful of the distinction between their perspective and that of the director. Furthermore, upon completing the 16 trials of the director's task, participants were prompted to detail their cultural experiences, including identification with various cultures on a 0-10 scale. This additional inquiry was inspired by Wu and Keysar (2007), which posited that cultural background might influence ToM abilities.

The findings revealed that participants generally exhibited lower accuracy under the director condition than the no-director condition. Specifically, in the director condition, bilinguals demonstrated superior performance over monolinguals, yet no significant difference was observed in the no-director condition. A notable interaction between cultural exposure and trial type was identified, highlighting the influence of engagement with multiple cultures on ToM abilities. Participants who reported exposure to more than two cultures throughout their lives showed enhanced performance in the director condition compared to those with monocultural backgrounds. Navarro and Conway (2021) posited that several factors contribute to ToM, enabling bilinguals to surpass monolinguals in tasks requiring perspective-taking. However, they hypothesised that enhanced executive control is not the sole contributing mechanism; metalinguistic awareness also plays a crucial role. They suggested that metalinguistic awareness could potentially reduce the executive control demands of competing ToM tasks. Furthermore, the positive correlation between multicultural exposure and ToM performance indicated that even monolingual individuals with extensive multicultural experiences could outperform monolinguals with limited cultural exposure. This suggests that engaging with multiple cultures, akin to the linguistic navigation experienced by bilinguals, involves a form of perspective-taking that is beneficial to ToM development.

2.3 Suggestion: Applying Director's Task to Measure Spatial Perspective Taking

Keysar et al. (2000) introduced the director's task, an experimental approach demanding refined inhibitory control beyond what is required for false-belief tasks, rapidly gaining popularity as a method for assessing perspective-taking capabilities. To successfully complete the director's task, participants must consistently remind themselves that the director cannot see certain objects. The findings of Epley et al. (2004) highlighted that adults commit fewer egocentric errors than children, with adult participants less frequently misidentifying or moving objects obscured from the director's view compared to their younger counterparts. Nonetheless, initial eye fixation data revealed that adults still possess a pronounced inclination to initially consider occluded objects as the intended referent. Crucially, the final eye fixation data indicated that adults are able to rectify their initial egocentric bias more swiftly and accurately than children, suggesting that perspective-taking is a deliberate and fallible process, even among mature individuals.

This dissertation proposes a new experimental approach to assess perspective-taking abilities, drawing inspiration from Keysar et al. (2000)'s director's task. Unlike the original task, which established a perspective disparity by occluding slots from the director's view, this novel method

engenders perspective differences by inverting the left and right perspectives between the participant and a confederate. Crucially, it maintains a consistent top/down orientation to introduce a dimension that is consistently shared between the director and matcher, enhancing their ability to synchronise perspectives. The experimental setup mirrors that of the director's task, featuring the participant and a small puppet named Barry situated across from each other, each with a 4x4 grid. This arrangement is designed to foster a collaborative atmosphere. The procedure echoes the original task: objects are placed on the participant's grid, and it is explained that Barry possesses an identical set, albeit with an altered left/right perspective. After ensuring the participant's comprehension, a photograph depicting the target grid configuration is provided, illustrating a repositioned arrangement of objects. The participant's challenge is to conceptualise this target grid from Barry's viewpoint and verbally guide Barry to reorganise her grid accordingly.

This methodology demands considerable inhibitory control, necessitating that participants not only visualise the initial and target grids from Barry's perspective but also articulate instructions for aligning Barry's grid with the target layout, all while disregarding their left/right dimension of it. This task, akin yet distinct to Keysar et al. (2000)'s director's task, is designed to evaluate perspective-taking through inhibitory control. The complexity of this task is not only anticipated to test the limits of inhibitory control among adults, but also designed to probe the persistence of the bilingual advantage in adulthood. Specifically, it seeks to ascertain whether this advantage diminishes over time or remains robust, enabling both bilingual and monolingual individuals to achieve a sufficiently high level of performance to navigate most pragmatic settings without significant difficulty.

3 Methods

3.1 Participants

This study involved 36 students from The University of Edinburgh, comparing 13 monolinguals and 23 multilinguals. Participants were categorised based on their life-long regular use of two languages versus those who had not engaged in such linguistic practice. This classification was grounded in the criteria used by Rubio-Fernández and Glucksberg (2012) in their comparative study of ToM abilities between adult monolinguals and multilinguals, utilising false-belief tasks. The primary criteria for participant classification included the duration of second language (L2) knowledge and the frequency of daily L2 use. These details were gathered through a pre-experiment questionnaire.

Multilingual participants were defined as those who had acquired a second language before the age of 9 and had been actively using it for at least 10 years. The average age of L2 acquisition among participants was 4 years, with an average of 17 years of L2 usage. The L2s represented in the sample included Japanese (n=1), English (n=14), Mandarin (n=4), German (n=2), and French (n=2). Given that all participants were students at The University of Edinburgh, selected based on stringent academic standards, no significant differences in IQ or verbal abilities were anticipated. The average age of monolingual participants was 20.8 years, and for multilingual participants, it was 21.7 years. Among the monolingual group, there were 5 female and 1 non-binary individual, while the multilingual group included 17 females and 2 non-binary individuals. At the time of participation, English served as the dominant language for all participants, regardless of their linguistic background.

3.2 Tasks and Materials

3.2.1 Pre-Experiment Questionnaire

Prior to initiating the experimental tasks, participants were required to complete a pre-experiment questionnaire designed to gather essential demographic information and language usage profiles. The questionnaire employed a short-answer format, commencing with queries about the participant's age and gender. Subsequent questions focused on identifying the participant's first language (L1) and inquired about proficiency in any additional languages (L2). Participants indicating multilingual abilities were further prompted to specify the age at which they commenced learning each second language (L2). Additionally, the questionnaire sought information on the frequency of daily usage for these additional languages, requesting participants to quantify their usage in terms of a percentage of their day (e.g., 50% or 70% of the day).

3.2.2 Reproduction Task

The initial task, termed the reproduction task, involved participants replicating a 4x4 grid arrangement either from their own perspective or from that of the confederate, Barry. During control trials, participants were furnished with an empty 4x4 grid alongside a set of miniature objects. The experimenter then presented a photograph depicting a 4x4 grid with objects arranged from the participant's viewpoint. Participants were instructed to recreate the displayed grid arrangement on their blank 4x4 grid utilising the miniature objects. In these control trials, the task was expected to be straightforward for participants, as it merely involved placing the miniatures in alignment with the visual reference provided.

Conversely, in the critical trials, the setup mirrored that of the control trials, with participants receiving an empty grid and an identical assortment of miniature objects. The distinction lay in the photography shown by the experimenter, which now depicted the 4x4 grid from Barry's perspective. The challenge for participants in these critical trials was to accurately reproduce the grid as it would appear from Barry's standpoint on their own empty grid, necessitating the use of perspective-taking skills to reverse the arrangement of objects according to the left/right orientation. This task aimed to evaluate the participant's ability to adapt their spatial understanding to accommodate a viewpoint distinct from their own.

3.2.3 Verbal Guidance Task

The second task, termed the verbal guidance task, builds on the complexity of the reproduction task, requiring heightened levels of inhibitory control. In control trials, the experimenter organises objects on a 4x4 grid, indicating to participants that these objects mirror the arrangement on their grid. The experimenter then presents a photograph depicting a 4x4 grid where the positions of the objects have been altered, asking participants to describe the modifications from their initial arrangement based on the perspective shown in the photograph. In these trials, participants are anticipated to successfully complete the task by simply recognising the differences between the actual grid setup and the depicted target grid, as no perspective-taking is involved.

In contrast, during critical trials, the experimenter arranges objects on a 4x4 grid, informing the participant of the presence of identical objects on their grid, with the caveat that Barry's grid reflects a reversed left/right orientation. Following this setup, the experimenter shows a photograph of a 4x4 grid with altered object positions, instructing the participant: "This target grid is depicted from your perspective. Imagine how this grid would appear from Barry's perspective and describe the necessary adjustments from Barry's original grid to achieve this configuration." Participants in critical trials must acknowledge the discrepancy between the target grid and Barry's perspective. Critical trials oblige participants to not only conceptualise both the initial and target grids from Barry's viewpoint but also

to communicate directions to rearranging Barry's grid to match the target, all the while neglecting their direct visual input.

3.3 Procedure

Participants commenced the study by reviewing the experiment's information sheet and signing an informed consent form. Following this, they were prompted to complete a pre-experiment questionnaire. During this time, the experimenter prepared the recording equipment and launched the presentation software to display the target grid images used in the experiment. Upon completion of the questionnaire, the experimental phase began, with all participants initially engaging in the reproduction task before proceeding to the verbal guidance task.

For each task, the experimenter provided a detailed explanation of the procedures and expectations. To ensure comprehension, participants underwent two practice trials, receiving feedback on their performance to clarify any misunderstandings. The reproduction task consisted of three control trials and five critical trials, with the complexity of the task escalating by increasing the number of objects on the grid – from two, to three, to five, and finally to seven objects. Control trials encompassed arrangements of two, three, and five objects, while critical trials included these configurations and additionally tested the seven-object setup twice. This design aimed to explore the participants' performance under more challenging conditions, particularly with a higher number of objects, by repeating the seven-object configuration.

The sequence of control and critical trials was pseudo-randomised to prevent participants from discerning any patterns that might lead to automatic responses. Upon completing the eight trials of the first task, the procedure for the verbal guidance task mirrored that of the reproduction task. Participants received a brief overview, followed by two practice trials for task familiarisation. Subsequently, they undertook three control and five critical trials, with the number of objects on the grid increasing in a similar manner to the first task. This incremental approach was designed to gradually increase task difficulty and assess the participants' adaptability and perspective-taking abilities in varied scenarios.

3.4 Scoring and Quality Check

In the reproduction task, the experimenter assessed the accuracy with which participants positioned the objects, considering only their initial attempt as their official response. A scoring sheet was used to record the accuracy of each object's placement on a trial-by-trial basis, marking each as either correct or incorrect. Similarly, for the verbal guidance task, the experimenter gauged the precision of the verbal instructions provided by participants, again taking into account solely the first attempt for scoring purposes. A corresponding score sheet was employed to document the correctness of instructions for each object during each trial. Subsequent to the completion of the experiment, the experimenter meticulously reviewed the recordings to verify the accuracy of the evaluations.

3.5 Ethics Approval

This research received full ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the School of Philosophy, Psychology, and Language Sciences (PPLS) at The University of Edinburgh.

4 Results and Analysis

Figure 2: Overall accuracy of participants in Reproduction Task.

The complexity of the experimental tasks was incrementally elevated by varying the number of objects on the grid – from two to three, five, and ultimately seven. This design assumes that an increase in the number of objects will introduce confusion among participants, leading to a decline in accuracy. Responses for each object placed were coded as ‘correct’ or ‘incorrect’. Across the critical trials of the reproduction task, this approach allowed for compiling average accuracy rates, enabling direct comparisons between monolingual and multilingual participants. Specifically, monolingual participants demonstrated an 87.8% accuracy rate. Meanwhile, the multilingual participants achieved a higher accuracy rate of 95.3% for the critical trials.

Figure 3: Accuracy per number of objects in Reproduction Task.

The subsequent analysis, delineated across four graphs, presents the overall accuracy of participants in critical trials, categorised by the number of objects. Overall, across all object quantities, the multilingual group consistently demonstrated higher accuracy rates compared to the monolingual group, albeit the differences in accuracy rates were modest.

Figure 4: Overall Accuracy of Participants in Verbal Guidance Task.

Echoing the methodology of the reproduction task, the experimenter assessed the overall accuracy of each participant in the verbal guidance task by judging the accuracy of the verbal instructions provided for each object, categorising them as either correct or incorrect. This information was aggregated to calculate the mean percentage of correct responses for each group, enabling a direct comparison between monolingual and multilingual participants. Specifically, this analysis honed in on the critical trials of the verbal guidance task, offering a focused examination of accuracy rates within these more demanding scenarios. The findings revealed that monolingual participants attained an average accuracy rate of 72.2%, showcasing their general capacity to accurately convey the required arrangements. In contrast, multilingual participants demonstrated a higher average accuracy rate of 87.7%, outperforming their monolingual counterparts.

As anticipated, both groups exhibited a decline in accuracy relative to the reproduction task, potentially a result of the verbal guidance task's increased complexity and the additional inhibitory control it necessitates. The difference in accuracy rates between the groups showed a numerically larger difference of 15.5% in favour of multilingual participants, exceeding the gap observed in the reproduction task. This numerical increase in disparity highlights the superior performance of the multilingual group in tasks requiring greater cognitive control, pending further analysis based on underlying assumptions.

Figure 5: Accuracy per number of objects in Verbal Guidance Task.

Mirroring the approach of the reproduction task, the complexity of the verbal guidance task was systematically increased by varying the number of objects displayed on the grid – from two, to three, five, and finally seven. This design assumes that an increase in the number of objects will introduce confusion among participants, leading to a decline in accuracy. An analysis, visually represented across four graphs, illustrates the overall accuracy of participants during critical trials, segmented by the number of objects involved.

Figure 6: Predicted probabilities of accuracy in Reproduction Task.

Table 1: Summary of the fixed effects of the model (Reproduction Task)

Variable	Estimate	Std. Error	Z value	Pr (> z)
(Intercept)	3.29	0.70	4.70	<0.00001
mono_multimul ti	1.66	1.25	1.33	0.184
num_obj3	0.14	0.82	0.17	0.869
num_obj5	-0.76	0.69	-1.10	0.272
num_obj7	-0.91	0.67	-1.36	0.174
mono_multimul ti: num_obj3	-2.36	1.34	-1.76	0.078 ***
mono_multimul ti: num_obj5	-0.89	1.26	-0.70	0.483
mono_multimul ti: num_obj7	-0.68	1.24	-0.55	0.583

Utilising R (R Core Team, 2023) and the lme4 package (Bates et al., 2015), the data were analysed using a Generalised Linear Mixed-Effects Model to examine the impact of various factors on a binary outcome, while also accounting for random effects resulting from data clustering. Within the reproduction task, these factors included linguistic background (monolingual versus multilingual) and the number of objects presented. The model’s predictive capability for accuracy, as illustrated in Figure 5, hinges on the interaction between linguistic background and the number of objects, incorporating a random intercept for individual participants. The analysis revealed substantial variability in the

intercepts across participants ($Var = 1.009$, $SD = 1.005$), indicating diverse baseline accuracy levels among the study’s participants.

Table 1 presents the fixed effects of the model, demonstrating that the baseline accuracy (intercept) significantly deviated from zero. However, the key predictors, including both main effects and the interaction between linguistic background and the number of objects, exhibited inconsistent predictive power regarding accuracy levels. Importantly, the interaction effect between linguistic background (mono_multi) and the presence of three objects (num_obj3) neared significance ($p=0.078$), alluding to a potential nuanced effect of linguistic background on accuracy that varies with the number of objects, though this did not surpass the conventional threshold for statistical significance. The findings imply that the influence of linguistic background and the number of objects on the task accuracy is subtle, potentially dependent on particular conditions or levels.

Figure 7: Predicted probabilities of accuracy in Verbal Guidance Task.

Table 2: Summary of the fixed effects of the model (Reproduction Task)

Variable	Estimate	Std. Error	Z value	Pr (> z)
(Intercept)	2.90	0.65	4.47	<0.00001 ***
mono_multimul ti	0.33	0.83	0.39	0.693
num_obj3	0.25	0.64	0.39	0.695
num_obj5	0.84	0.61	1.38	0.168
num_obj7	-1.89	0.55	-3.44	0.00059 ***
mono_multimul ti: num_obj3	-0.89	0.82	-1.09	0.278

mono_multimul ti: num_obj5	-0.76	0.80	-0.95	0.342
mono_multimul ti: num_obj7	1.18	0.72	1.63	0.102

Mirroring the approach used for the reproduction task, the verbal guidance task data were subjected to analysis using a Generalised Linear Mixed-Effect Model via R (R Core Team, 2023) and the lme4 package (Bates et al., 2015). As depicted in Figure 6, the model assessed the interaction between linguistic background and the number of objects, with each participant assigned a random intercept. This analysis disclosed considerable variability among participant intercepts (variance = 1.922, standard deviation = 1.386), signifying variance in foundational accuracy levels across participants.

Table 2 outlines the fixed effects within the model, indicating a significant departure of the baseline accuracy (intercept) from zero. Contrastingly, this task’s model delineates a departure from the findings related to the reproduction task, notably through the pronounced negative impact of presenting 7 objects on accuracy ($p=0.00059$). This result elucidates a decline in the probability of providing accurate verbal guidance with an increase to 7 objects, highlighting the cognitive challenges or complexity introduced by managing a greater number of objects. Conversely, factors such as linguistic background and its interactive effects with object count did not present a significant impact on accuracy ($p=0.102$). This suggests that, within this context, the critical factor affecting performance is the number of objects rather than the linguistic background of participants.

5 Discussion

5.1 General Discussion

Figures 2 and 3 illustrate that multilingual participants consistently surpassed monolinguals in every critical trial of the reproduction task. Despite this, monolingual participants maintained a high overall accuracy rate of 87.8%, suggesting that their performance on the reproduction tasks cannot be deemed definitively subpar. Further examination using a Generalised Linear Mixed-Effects Model reinforces this observation, indicating the absence of significant effects concerning the main influences of linguistic background and the number of objects on task accuracy, as well as the interaction between these factors. These findings suggest a trend in the predicted direction, yet do not provide statistically meaningful evidence to support a clear advantage of multilingualism in executing this task or that an increased number of objects significantly confuses participants. Consequently, these results prompt further investigation into whether the reproduction task is a robust measure for assessing perspective-taking abilities in adult participants. A potential rationale is that the degree of perspective-taking required by the task’s nature is minimal and within the capability of most adults, irrespective of their linguistic background. This insight underlies the decision to incorporate a verbal guidance task into the study, which was anticipated to demand greater cognitive effort and a higher level of inhibitory control for successful completion.

Figure 4 presents the outcomes of the verbal guidance task, highlighting a significant divergence in accuracy rates between monolingual and multilingual participants, with the latter group enjoying a 15.5% advantage. This disparity underscores more pronounced differences in performance between the two groups within the context of the verbal guidance task, suggesting that the task’s complexity effectively delineates participants’ abilities based on their linguistic backgrounds. Figure 5, detailing accuracy rates in relation to the number of objects, discloses a notable pattern, particularly when three and five objects were involved. For monolinguals, a slight decrease in accuracy (3.8%) was observed

as the object count rose from two to three, yet an increase in accuracy (11.5%) was noted with a further rise to five objects. Multilingual participants exhibited a similar trend, with accuracy decreasing (15.2%) from two to three objects but increasing (16.5%) from three to five objects. This pattern suggests that, irrespective of linguistic background, participants generally showed improved accuracy in the more complex five-object scenario.

A plausible explanation for this phenomenon could be a training effect among participants. Despite the randomisation of control and critical trials, all participants faced progressively challenging conditions by incrementally increasing the object count, starting from two objects and concluding with seven. Thus, the initial trials with two and three objects might have served as a form of practice, enhancing participants' proficiency by the time they encountered the five-object trials. However, this training effect did not extend to the seven-object scenario, as evidenced by reduced accuracy rates for both monolinguals (67%) and bilinguals (88.5%) compared to the five-object condition. This suggests that the cognitive demands of managing seven objects surpass the participants' improved task familiarity, challenging their ability to override their perspective effectively. The output from the Generalised Linear Mixed-Effects Model reveals a notably harder seven-object condition compared to others, as evidenced by a significant decrease in participant accuracy ($p=0.000591$). This suggests an unexpected pattern where the increase in objects does not uniformly lead to poorer performance, contrary to what might be expected under a simple cognitive load theory. A plausible explanation for this inconsistency could be the presence of training effects, given that the complexity was confounded with the order of presentation in this experimental design. Acknowledging this, future research should consider varying the order of presentation to more accurately disentangle the effects of cognitive load from potential training improvements.

However, a Generalised Linear Mixed-Effects Model disclosed that the quantity of objects is the sole factor significantly impacting participants' performance, with linguistic background not exerting a significant influence ($p=0.102$) on outcomes. While the inferential statistics did not reveal a significant effect, the observed difference in accuracy rates between two groups – 67% for monolinguals and 88.5% for multilingual participants in the seven-object condition – suggests a notable discrepancy that warrants attention. This observed difference, although not statistically significant in the analysis, might be attributed to potential limitations in the study's power or the conservative approach taken in treating the condition as a nominal variable. Lacking direct comparisons due to the novelty of the employed method, this finding nonetheless aligns with the trajectory observed in prior research. Navarro and Conway (2021) reported that bilinguals outperformed monolinguals in a director's task, attributing this advantage to heightened executive control and metalinguistic awareness. Consistently, our results corroborate this pattern, particularly in the complex seven-object condition where the grid becomes densely populated. Monolingual participants struggled with perspective inhibition and subsequently offered less precise verbal guidance, whereas multilinguals demonstrated a reduced difficulty in providing accurate instructions. This suggests that multilingual participants possess superior perspective-taking abilities, resonating with the findings of Navarro and Conway (2021) concerning the director's task.

Also, both the reproduction task and the verbal guidance task exhibited significant variability among participants, indicating pronounced individual differences in performance. This variability suggests that external factors may have disproportionately affected the ability of certain participants to complete the task. A potential factor may stem from the distinctive nature of the experimental approach adopted in this study, which, while drawing inspiration from Keysar et al. (2000)'s director's task, introduced a novel element of perspective-taking by inverting the left/right orientation between participants and the confederate. This adjustment required participants to not only recognise that the confederate possessed a different viewpoint but also to account for the directional aspect of this difference. Consequently, participants with a weaker sense of direction or difficulty distinguishing

between left and right – referred to as left-right confusion – could experience a notable impact on their performance despite their capability for perspective-taking. Research indicates that left-right confusion, characterised by challenges in accurately identifying left and right directions, is more common among women than men (Gormley & Brydges, 2016). Thus, individuals with left-right confusion may face additional challenges compared to those without such difficulties. As a result, the influence of left-right confusion could potentially mask the cognitive benefits associated with multilingualism, suggesting that individual differences in spatial orientation may play a critical role in task performance.

5.2 Limitations and Suggestions on Further Research

A primary limitation of this research was its relatively small sample size, which also exhibited an uneven distribution between monolingual (13 participants) and multilingual (23 participants) groups. An expansion in sample size would significantly augment the study's statistical power, facilitating the detection of nuanced differences in task accuracy between monolingual and multilingual participants that this study may have overlooked. Additionally, there was a notable gender imbalance among participants, with a predominance of female participants, particularly within the multilingual group where 74% identified as women. Given that left-right confusion tends to occur more frequently in women than men, achieving gender parity among participants is crucial in obtaining more reliable results. This imbalance underscores the need for future studies to ensure a more balanced gender representation to accurately assess the impact of linguistic background on task performance.

A further limitation encountered in this research was the considerable variability and individual differences among participants, particularly regarding cognitive abilities and spatial orientation skills. This study did not assess participants' IQ or verbal abilities, not due to an assumption of homogeneity among the University of Edinburgh recruits, but rather due to practical limitations such as lack of resources. Therefore, it remains unexplored whether the observed effects are specific to participants with certain cognitive profiles concerning IQ or verbal abilities. Additionally, no evaluation was conducted to identify participants with a diminished sense of direction or susceptibility to left-right confusion. The findings imply that such individual differences could potentially eclipse the cognitive advantages attributed to multilingualism. Consequently, it is imperative for future research to incorporate assessments that either ascertain a comparable sense of direction among participants or exclude individuals prone to left-right confusion to more accurately discern the impact of multilingualism.

Observing a training effect in the five-object condition suggests that future research could modify the methodology used in verbal guidance tasks. Initially, participants might engage in training sessions focused on two or three-object conditions, which are likely to facilitate accurate responses due to their relative simplicity. Subsequently, the experimental trials could commence with the seven-object condition, progressing to more challenging scenarios by incrementally increasing the number of objects to nine, ten, or beyond. This study revealed that the training effect did not extend to the seven-object scenario, indicating it as a viable starting point for the experimental trials. Introducing even more complex conditions, such as nine or eleven objects, is expected to significantly elevate cognitive demands. This adjustment in methodology aims to better understand the impact of cognitive load on task performance and how participants with different linguistic backgrounds manage, without the influence of prior training effects.

6 Conclusion

This study ventured into assessing the perspective-taking capabilities of adult monolinguals and multilinguals through a novel experimental method, drawing inspiration from the director's task devised by Keysar et al. (2000). The reproduction task uncovered only marginal differences in the accuracy rates between the two groups. However, the verbal guidance task, designed to heighten cognitive demands relative to the reproduction task, was anticipated to elucidate greater disparities in accuracy between the groups. The findings indicated a reduction in accuracy rates for both groups under this increased cognitive load, yet multilinguals demonstrated superior accuracy compared to their monolingual counterparts. Statistical analyses pinpointed a significant drop in participants' accuracy exclusively in the seven-object condition, with linguistic background and other variables showing no significant impact on performance. This outcome could be attributed to a training effect experienced by participants during initial trials with fewer objects, leading to an unexpected pattern where an increase in objects did not consistently result in diminished performance, challenging the predictions of a straightforward cognitive load hypothesis. Alternatively, unmeasured external factors, such as spatial orientation or left-right confusion, may have obscured the cognitive advantages typically associated with multilingualism. Addressing these limitations in future research, including a broader participant base, is imperative. Additionally, diverging from the predominant use of false-belief tasks for evaluating ToM abilities, this innovative experimental approach holds promise for investigating these competencies in both monolingual and bilingual children.

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Perceptual Acquisition of Arabic Emphatic Consonants in the L2: Is Pharyngealisation Enough?

Conal Lowe

University of Cambridge

Abstract. Arabic features a phonological distinction between plain consonants /s/, /ð/, /t/, and /d/, and their emphatic counterparts /s^ʕ/, /ð^ʕ/, /t^ʕ/, and /d^ʕ/ which are variously described as pharyngealised or uvularised. Distinguishing these phoneme pairs constitutes a major obstacle for English-speaking learners of Arabic; didactic material often suggests English speakers to attend to coarticulatory cues of emphasis on adjacent vowels rather than the consonant itself. English-speaking learners of Arabic were presented with a binary forced identification task of Modern Standard Arabic CVC pseudowords. The audio stimuli were cross-spliced so that only some segments were contextually emphatic in order to examine whether emphatic perception makes use of acoustic cues from the target emphatic consonant, the vowel, or the non-target consonant. Results suggest that emphatic effects on vowels are the most salient perceptual cue for English speakers, especially when paired with a target emphatic. Non-target consonants had no effect. Manner of articulation effects were observed as emphatic plosives elicited more accurate responses (particularly of /t/-/t^ʕ/). Vowel quality was also a predictor of emphatic responses as participants were most accurate for stimuli including /a/. These effects evidence the notion that English speakers make use of L1 contrasts (/t/-/d/ and /æ/-/a/ in this case) to acquire nonnative phonemes. No effects of proficiency or pedagogical background were observed. The results provide support for the Extended Native Language Magnet Model (NLM-e) of acquisition. Implications and suggestions for future research are presented.

Keywords: phonology; language acquisition; Arabic; pharyngealisation

1 Introduction

1.1 Emphatic Consonants

Most Semitic languages feature a series of emphatic consonants that are phonemically distinct from plain consonants (Table 1). Emphatic and plain consonants form frequent minimal pairs (e.g., *dalla* ‘to indicate’ vs. *ḍalla* ‘to go astray’).

Arabic emphatics are articulated with dorsal constriction. The exact phonetic status of Arabic emphatics is debated and will be explored in Section 1.1.1. To avoid phonetic uncertainty, convention advises an underdot to represent emphasis (e.g., plain /s/ vs. emphatic /s^ʕ/). This notation is used throughout this paper.

Table 1: *Phoneme inventory of Modern Standard Arabic (MSA). Where there are two consonants in one cell, the left is plain and the right is emphatic. Marginal/debated phonemes in brackets. Information adapted from Thelwall and Sa'Adeddin (1990) and Mustafawi (2017)*

<u>MSA Consonants</u>		Labial	Inter-dental	Alveolar	Postalveolar	Velar	Uvular	Laryngeal
Nasal	Voiced	m		n				
Plosive	Voiceless			t ṭ		k	q	ʔ
	Voiced	b		d ḍ				
Fricative	Voiceless	f	θ	s ṣ	ʃ	x ~ χ		ħ
	Voiced		ð ḍ	z		ɣ ~ ʁ		ʕ
Affricate	Voiced				dʒ			
Approximant	Voiced	w		l (l)	j			
Trill	Voiced			r (r)				

<u>MSA Vowels</u>	Front	Back
High	i i:	u u:
Low	æ æ:	ɑ ɑ:

There are four uncontroversial emphatics. These are the coronals /s/, /t/, /d/, and /ð/ which are often referred to as the primary emphatics (Jaber et al., 2019). They are produced with dorsal articulation in contrast to their non-emphatic counterparts. Primary emphatics also trigger backed allophones of adjacent vowels. The most noticeable of these is /a/ which is generally [æ] (Alghamdi, 1998; Al-Bataineh, 2019) but is pronounced as [ɑ] proximal to emphatics (Ferguson, 1997; Bukshaisha, 1985). Realisations of /d/ and /ð/ vary across dialects. Egyptian and Moroccan dialects realise /ð/ as [z] (Broselow, 1976; Freeman, 2015), Levantine dialects merge them to [d] (Al-Essa, 2022) whereas Algerian, Qatari, and Yemeni Arabic merge them to [ð] (Slimani, 2018; Al-Ansari & Kulikov, 2023; Watson, 1999). In fact, Al-Wer (2003) asserts that no spoken colloquial variety maintains both /d/ and /ð/. For the sake of consistency, this paper focuses on Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) as a ‘neutral’ register that crucially contains all four of the primary coronal emphatics.

/q/ is occasionally considered a primary emphatic. Al-Solami (2013) suggests that coronal emphatics and uvulars (/q/, /χ/, /ʁ/) pattern together phonologically as only coronal emphatics and uvulars trigger nasal place assimilation. Furthermore, Gulf Arabic sometimes features *ghawa syndrome* in which guttural consonants cannot be syllable-final; this does not apply to coronal emphatics nor /q/ (Huneety et al., 2024; Taqi, 2018), see also prohibitions on roots with two gutturals that does not apply for emphatics or /q/, e.g., √qtʕ ‘to cut’.

Therefore, phonologically, the emphatic consonant inventory seems to include /q/. However, many colloquial dialects merge /q/ with /ʔ/, /g/, or /k/ (Jabbari, 2013; Sallam 1980; Saadane & Nabash, 2015) so [q] does not often occur in spoken language. Some dialects (e.g., Saffarini) feature emphatic /k/ as distinct from /q/ (Saleh & Golston, 2019).

Other ‘secondary emphatics’ exist in some contexts (Jaber et al., 2019). Secondary emphatics include sounds such as /m b f x k/ that appear sparsely throughout Arabic dialects (e.g., Harrell, 1957; Cowell, 1964). They tend not to form minimal pairs with their plain analogues. Although Jaber et al. (2019) assert this is true for Urban Jordanian Arabic, Youssef (2014) finds a small number of minimal pairs in Cairene Arabic, e.g., *jamma* ‘mother!’ vs. *jamma* ‘direction’. Even in these cases, these are

highly marginal phonemes appearing in one or two native words each, e.g., *majja* ‘water’ and *maṃma* ‘mother’ (*jaṃma* < *ja maṃma* where *ja* is a vocative particle).

The emphatic /r/ and /l/ are the most proposed secondary emphatics (Jaber, 2001). /l/ is perhaps the more marginal of the two (Younes, 1994). It appears in most dialects in the word for ‘God’, *Allah*. This does form minimal pairs: *wallāhu* ‘and God’ vs. *wallāhu* ‘he appointed him’ in Classical Arabic (this is also a minimal pair in MSA) or *lla* ‘God’ vs. *lla* ‘no’ in Moroccan Arabic (Ferguson, 1956). Other than this, most occurrences of [l] are due to coarticulation with a nearby primary emphatic (Al-Bataineh, 2019). [r] has a similar status: it appears in a handful of words and most often as a backed allophone of /r/. However, /r/ seems to phonologically pattern with emphatics. Some verbs show an inflectional pattern of *yiCCiC* in the perfect. The second /i/ is instead /u/ when adjacent to an emphatic or /r/ (2):

(1) a.	<i>katab</i>	<i>yiktib</i>	‘he wrote’
	<i>xabaz</i>	<i>yixbiz</i>	‘he baked’
b.	<i>xabaṭ</i>	<i>yixbuṭ</i>	‘he struck’
	<i>barad</i>	<i>yibrud</i>	‘he became cold’

(data adapted from Younes, 1994)

It may also form minimal pairs: *raff* ‘shelf’ vs. *raff* ‘it twitched’ in Cairene and *rāyib* ‘curdled’ vs. *rāyib* ‘collapsed’ in Moroccan Arabic (Youssef, 2019). As minimal pairs exist, both /l/ and /r/ may be awarded the title of marginal phonemes. However, they phonologically differ from primary emphatics in that they are often de-emphasised, especially in proximity to /i/ (e.g., *wallāhu* ‘and God’ vs. *bismillah*; *rayyisna* ‘our president’ vs. *riyāsa* ‘presidency’).

Youssef (2019) suggests there are three types of Arabic dialect in this regard. Western dialects (e.g., Egyptian, and Moroccan) are split-R dialects in which /r/ and /r/ are distinctive phonemes. Levantine dialects are emphatic-R as they feature /r/ with [r] and [r] as allophones with complementary distribution. And Gulf dialects are plain-R with /r/ featuring complementary plain and emphatic allophones.

Due to the marginal and dialectal nature of the secondary emphatics as detailed above, they will be excluded from the term *emphatic*. /q/ will be excluded for the latter of these reasons as well as its unique articulation in relation to /k/. Unlike the coronal emphatics, /q/ does not differ from /k/ only in *secondary* articulation; /q/ features primary articulation at the uvula rather than the velum like /k/. This makes comparison of /q/ and /k/ more difficult as more features differ. Thus, *emphatic* here refers only to /s/, /t/, /d/ and /ð/.

1.1.1 Articulatory and Acoustic Characteristics of Emphatics

In terms of emphatic articulation, the most common stance is that they are pharyngealised as supported by articulatory studies (Davis, 1995; Al-Ani, 1970). However, there is growing literature to suggest that emphatics are uvularised. Al-Solami (2013) identifies articulatory similarities between uvulars and emphatics such as that the entire tongue body retracts in both cases. Other investigations (Zawaydeh, 1999; Ghazeli, 1997) have used physiological evidence (e.g., endoscopic and cinefluorographic imaging) to identify the locus of constriction in emphatic consonants as the upper pharynx, by the uvula. Although others have identified emphatics as velarised (Obrecht, 1968), the primary articulatory debate, especially in the modern day, is between uvularisation and pharyngealisation.

Altairi et al. (2017) used ultrasound to isolate which muscles are responsible for uvularisation and pharyngealisation. They found that uvulars and primary emphatics featured backing caused by the styloglossus, a muscle that pulls the tongue up and back towards the uvula. Pharyngeal constriction was instead found to be associated with contraction of the hyoglossus, the complementary muscle that pulls the tongue down and back. This groups emphatics with uvulars rather than pharyngeals.

Often, uvularisation and pharyngealisation are not distinguished; even the IPA uses /ʕ/ for both. Some studies (Herzallah, 1990; Alioua, 1995; Yeou, 1997; Zawaydeh, 1999) suggest that emphatic constriction occurs at a point around the oropharynx and is consistent with both uvularisation and pharyngealisation. Although not clearly separable, Arabic features uvular and pharyngeal consonants, so isolating how emphatics pattern phonetically with these natural classes is important.

The acoustic properties of emphasis may be investigated to isolate the type of constriction present (Stevens & House, 1955). The consensus of production literature suggests that emphasis is directly associated with a significant lowering of F2 in the consonant and surrounding segments (Aldamen & Al-Deaibes, 2023; Jongman et al., 2011; Zawaydeh, 1999; Yeou, 1997; Al-Solami, 2013; Ali & Daniloff 1974; Card, 1983; Obrecht, 1970 among others). Boxberger (1981) finds a decrease of around 650 Hz in F2 transition frequencies of emphatic consonants. This varies significantly depending on the consonant, the adjacent vowels, and the consonant's position in a syllable. Card (1983) instead finds a lower reduction in F2 of around 200-300 Hz. A depressed second formant is consistent with constriction at the uvula (Zawaydeh & de Jong, 2011) as a “straightforward result of tongue retraction” (Al-Ansari & Kulikov, 2023:8). Uvular constriction lengthens the horizontal oral cavity, reducing F2 (Lieberman, 2007). A similar depressed F2 is found during and following uvular consonants (Zawaydeh & de Jong, 2011). This acoustic data points to uvularised emphatics.

Another acoustic correlate of emphasis is raised F1 (Jongman et al., 2011; Zawaydeh, 1999; Yeou, 1995; Al-Ansari & Kulikov, 2023). Compression of the vertical pharyngeal cavity during pharyngealisation increases the frequency of resonant sound waves (Lieberman, 2007) translating to higher F1. This suggests pharyngealised emphatics. However, in studies that find a consistent F1 effect (e.g., Jongman et al., 2011), it is still considerably less noticeable than reduced F2. Other studies (Card, 1983; Kulikov et al., 2020; Norlin, 1987) find no consistent difference in F1. Pharyngeal consonants are also associated with slightly reduced F2. Although this seems to corroborate pharyngealisation, Bukshaisha (1985) found that the effect on F2 was more significant for emphatic than pharyngeal consonants; /a/ was articulated further forward with an F2 of 1500 Hz after /h/, but as back (1000 Hz) after /t/.

Bukshaisha (1985) investigated the production of emphatic consonants in Qatari Arabic. She found two significant effects of emphasis on consonant production: shorter VOT in /t/ than /t/ and a lower spectral mean in emphatic fricatives. /t/ featuring a longer VOT than /t/ is corroborated widely (Alghamdi, 2006; AlDahri, 2012a, 2012b, 2013; Al-Masri & Jongman, 2004). Other investigations (e.g., Jongman et al., 2011; Abudaljuh, 2010) disagree with Bukshaisha's (1985) findings. Jongman et al. (2011) instead find that only emphatic plosives have significantly lower spectral mean than their plain counterparts. Strict aerodynamic constraints govern fricative production and do not allow much variation in the shape of the tongue body. Greater tongue backing for emphatic stops (cf. Ghazeli, 1977) means that the length of the front cavity increases more in stops, thus lowering spectral mean only for plosives.

1.1.2 *Spread of Emphatic Features*

There is a consensus that emphatics have significant coarticulatory effects on adjacent segments; most emphatic literature specifically investigates vocalic properties (Ali & Daniloff, 1974; Jongman et al., 2011; Al-Masri & Jongman, 2004; Card, 1983). Ali and Daniloff (1974) show the initial consonant of a

word may be identified as emphatic even when it was completely truncated. Hence, emphatic coarticulation on adjacent vowels is perceptually salient.

Evidence suggests that rightward spread of emphasis is more constrained than leftward spread (e.g., Watson, 1999; Jaber et al., 2001; Bukshaisha, 1985; Herzallah, 1990; Slimani, 2018). Furthermore, Zawaydeh (1999) showed that (in Ammani Arabic) leftward spread is categorical: F2 is equally low regardless of distance from an emphatic. In contrast, rightward spread was found to be gradient.

The domain of this spread is most often identified as the syllable (Lehn, 1963; Obrecht, 1968; Shaaban, 1977; Sayed, 1981; Algryani, 2014). Brosh (2015) argues that syllabic emphatic spread may be noticeable enough that *sawt* ‘whip’ is homophonous with *ṣawt* ‘sound’. Other studies identify the phonological word as the locus of emphasis spread (Youssef, 2014; Bukshaisha, 1985). Emphasis may spread to previous words (Bukshaisha, 1985), subject to strict locality conditions (Woidich, 2006) and speech rate (Broselow, 1976).

Despite dialectal variation, this section has established that (i) emphatic consonants are uvularized, (ii) cues such as VOT and spectral mean may be salient in emphatic perception, (iii) emphasis spreads variably, triggering backed allophones of adjacent vowels.

1.1.3 *Emphatic Perception I: Perceptual Studies of L1 Arabic Speakers*

Jongman et al. (2011), in a comprehensive study of Urban Jordanian Arabic, used cross-splicing to create intermediary stimuli in which some segments were produced in emphatic context and others in plain context (e.g., an emphatic /s/ followed by the rime /a:b/ produced in plain context). Participants were presented these intermediary stimuli in a forced identification task; they were instructed to indicate whether the stimulus began with an emphatic consonant. Words in which the rime only came from an emphatic context (CṬC) elicited 69% emphatic responses. Meanwhile, those in which only the target consonant was emphatic saw 15% emphatic responses, a statistically significant difference. When including all stimuli, words with a primary emphatic target elicited more frequent emphatic responses than those without (53% vs 36%). Stimuli with emphatic rimes (CṬC and CṬC) elicited 80% emphatic responses whereas those with plain rimes (CVC and CVC) only elicited them 9% of the time. We may suggest the emphatic effect on following segments is a more salient perceptual cue than the initial consonant alone.

When analysing target-final stimuli (e.g., *bas*, *baṣ*), Jongman et al. (2011) observed greater emphatic responses when the initial CV sequence (i.e., the vowel and the non-target consonant) was emphatic (94%) than when the rime of a target-initial word was emphatic (69%)

Jongman et al. (2011) also found manner of articulation differences. They compared responses for the CVC condition between fricatives and plosives. There was no significant difference in emphatic responses between emphatic (48%) and plain (41%) fricatives. Emphatic plosives, however, did elicit significantly greater emphatic responses (60%) than plain ones (28%). This matches their acoustic data, which suggested spectral mean is only significantly lowered in emphatic plosives but not fricatives (*contra* Bukshaisha, 1985).

Although Jongman et al.’s (2011) methodology does not allow for distinctions to be made between the vowel and the non-target consonant (as they were spliced together), they isolate the primary perceptual correlate of emphasis to lowered vocalic F2. Greater lowering of F2 and Yeou (1995)’s findings that F1 alone is not a salient perceptual cue rule out vocalic F1 here. This is seemingly corroborated by evidence that lowered vocalic F2 is a salient cue for emphasis (Aldamen & Al-Deaibes, 2023; Al-Masri & Jongman, 2004; Hayes-Harb & Durham, 2016). However, crucially, none of these studies measured the effect of the non-target consonant; vocalic F2 alone cannot be confidently identified as the primary cue. If we follow the logic that perception and production are linked, Card’s

(1983) detailed phonetic analysis of F2 in vowels and non-emphatic consonants shows that F2 lowers in both even if vocalic F2 decreases further. Although this stresses the importance of the vowel, it suggests that coarticulatory effects of the non-target consonant may have been overlooked.

1.1.4 *Emphatic Perceptions II: Perceptual Studies of L2 Arabic Speakers*

Hayes-Harb and Durham (2016) replicated the Jongman et al.'s (2011) methodology instead investigating English-speaking learners of Arabic. They collected 'overlap scores' from participants by asking them to identify the closest English vowel phoneme to the Arabic vowel in words with and without emphatics. The overlap score represents the percentage of tokens in which the plain- and emphatic-context vowels are identified to be closest to the same English phoneme. The overlap scores for /i/ (71%) and /u/ (69%) were significantly higher than for /a/ (3%). Low overlap implies English speakers perceive the plain and emphatic allophones of /a/ ([æ] and [ɑ]) as exemplars of separate English phonemes.

As expected, English speakers relied on vowel quality for emphatic distinctions. There was no difference in emphatic responses between target-initial **ÇVC** and **CVC** words (7%); the emphatic consonant had no effect on emphatic responses. When the rime was contextually emphatic, the vowel quality was a good predictor of emphatic responses: /a/ elicited 79% emphatic responses, /u/ 60%, and /i/ only 34%. When plain, /a/ elicited the lowest emphatic responses (2%) compared to /i/ (9%) and /u/ (10%). Participants were most accurate for all stimuli featuring /a/. To confirm that this was due to English vowel phonemes, they repeated the same study with native Arabic speakers who instead reported significantly higher emphatic responses for **ÇVC** and **CVC** stimuli with /u/ (87%) followed by /a/ (70%) and /i/ (40%). This provides evidence for English speakers using native distinctions to aid in emphatic perception. Self-reported phoneme similarities by English speakers in Zaba (2007) further support this notion; plain-emphatic overlap with English phonemes was lowest for /a/ followed by /u/ then /i/.

1.2 **Acquisitional Frameworks**

Following the in-depth phonological and phonetic analysis of emphasis in Section 1.1, the pressing matter at hand becomes two-fold: Firstly, (i) what mechanisms do L2 speakers use to distinguish foreign sounds? And (ii) can L2 speakers achieve native-like proficiency, and if so, how? This section will present different acquisitional frameworks and what they predict regarding L2 emphatic perception.

First, we may draw our attention to the Perceptual Assimilation Model (PAM; Best, 1994, 1995; modified to better suit L2 acquisition in Best & Tyler, 2007 as PAM-L2) which suggests that discrimination of some nonnative contrasts may be good without training (Best, 1998) whereas others may require explicit training (Strange & Dittmann, 1984; Pisoni et al., 1982) or extensive naturalistic experience (MacKain et al., 1981; Tees & Werker, 1984; Hayes-Harb, 2007; Enomoto, 1994). Nonnative contrasts are assimilated differently into the L1 phonology, explaining the variable perceptual difficulty observed. There are three relevant types of assimilation: **two-category** (TC) in which a nonnative contrast is assimilated with an existing native contrast (e.g., Tigrinya /t'-/p'/ with English /t-/p/; Best, 1993); **category-goodness** (CG) in which both nonnative sounds are assimilated into the same native category but one is noticeably more deviant from the native ideal (e.g., Zulu /k-/k'/ as a good and deviant exemplar of English /k/; Best, 1994); and **single-category** (SC) where nonnative sounds are assimilated to the same native category and are equally acceptable (e.g., Thompson Salish /k'-/q'/ both as deviant exemplars of English /k/; Best, 1994). The order of difficulty in acquisition is expected to be TC > CG > SC (Al Mahmoud, 2013).

Emphatic contrasts are likely a CG assimilation (Al Mahmoud, 2013); both are assimilated into the same English phoneme with the emphatic variant noticeably more deviant. Perception of emphatics is thus predicted to be significantly above chance (Pisoni, 1973); Best et al. (2001) found an accuracy of 89.4% for CG in a study of Zulu ejectives. In a perceptual study of /t/-/t̤/ and /ð/-/ð̤/ contrasts, Al Mahmoud (2013) instead found less accurate discrimination (68.7%; 64.8% for /t̤/, 72.7% for /ð̤/). Accuracy for /t/-/t̤/ is below what is expected by PAM. The reason for this is hypothesised to be that /t̤/ is perceived as closer to /t/ than /ð̤/ is to /ð/. This is supported by Lababidi and Park (2017) who asked L1 English participants to label Arabic stimuli with an English consonant and rate goodness-of-fit. They found that 37.5% of /t̤/ tokens were identified as /t/ (3.3/10 goodness) whereas only 12.5% of /ð̤/ tokens were identified as /ð/ (6 goodness). However, their data does not support the overall low accuracy of Al Mahmoud's participants: 50% of /t̤/ tokens were identified as /f/ (5 goodness), a phoneme English speakers should have no trouble discriminating from /t/. Furthermore, /ð̤/ was most often identified as an uncategorisable sound (50% of tokens; 4.5 goodness). An uncategorisable sound paired with a categorisable one (/ð̤/) should elicit accuracy higher than that found by Al Mahmoud (2013). Liebenthal et al. (2003) suggest within-category contrasts are discriminated using acoustic memory traces. Compared to phonemes, these traces are less stable and efficient. However, their stability and efficiency may vary depending on the type of acoustic input. Ejectives feature an almost complete termination of glottal air flow during their release (Best et al., 2001). This acoustic cue could form more stable memory traces than uvularisation for English speakers. Thus, the discriminatory accuracy measures found by Best et al (2001) may be inflated.

One of PAM's central ideas is that gesture is the basis of production and perception. Best (1991) compares this to Psychoacoustic Theory (PT; Diehl & Kluender, 1989) that assumes the immediate object of speech perception is raw acoustic experience whereas speech production is governed by gesture. This creates a mismatch between perception and production which is inconsistent with the clear production-perception link found in emphatic literature (see Sections 1.1.3 and 1.1.4). PAM-L2, instead, assumes that gesture is the basis of both production and perception, creating a solid link. Therefore, PAM's ability to account for perception-production links makes it a suitable model for the purposes of this investigation.

The Extended Native Language Magnet Model (NLM-e; Kuhl et al., 2008) is a similar exemplar-theoretic approach. NLM-e focuses on neural commitment. Given experience with the L1, infants create phonetic categories including perfect and poor examples of each native phoneme (cf. Pierrehumbert, 2001). Such "early exposure to language shapes [...] attentional networks, and [...] in adulthood, they make second language learning difficult" (Kuhl et al., 2008). NLM-e comes together with the Perceptual Magnet Effect (PME) which states that established phonetic categories affect perception and "the best instances of the category are associated with reduced discrimination and perceptual clustering" (Iverson & Kuhl, 1995: 560). For emphatics, the PME predicts that /s/-/s̤/ and /d/-/d̤/ may be more difficult to discern as they will both cluster within /s/ and /d/. Whereas /t/-/t̤/ may be slightly easier as the emphatic /t̤/ features considerably lower VOT than /t/ which is usually [t^h] (Bukshaisha, 1985). English voiced plosives are often described as partially voiced (Gonet, 2001; Collins & Mees, 2003), and aspiration is a salient perceptual cue of plosive 'voicing' (Deterding & Nolan, 2007). Therefore, Arabic /t/ and /t̤/ would likely cluster with English /t/ and /d/, facilitating accurate discrimination. Of course, Al Mahmoud (2013) did not find this when compared to /ð̤/-/ð̤/ but provided no data regarding /s/-/s̤/ or /d/-/d̤/. NLM-e also accounts for Hayes-Harb & Durham's (2016) findings regarding /a/ facilitating accurate emphatic perception due to the English /æ/-/a/ distinction. These predictions are similar to those made by PAM-L2.

A point of difference between PAM and NLM-e is the stress of social factors. Although both rightly draw upon principles of statistical learning (Saffran et al., 1996), NLM-e acknowledges centrally the importance of directed speech and teaching in phonological development whereas PAM-L2 does

not. For example, Kuhl et al. (2003) found that, when exposed to a new language at age 0;9, infants only learn phonetically from a live interacting human being, but not a disembodied source. Furthermore, Zhang et al. (2005) show the importance of directed and exaggerated speech for adult Japanese speakers learning the English /r/-/l/ distinction. In this way, NLM-e predicts participants' experience learning Arabic (e.g., independent study vs. class learning) will have an impact on their perceptual acquisition of emphatics.

1.3 Research Questions and Hypotheses

The purpose of this study is to investigate the auditory cues L2 Arabic speakers use to distinguish emphatic consonants from their plain counterparts. The focus is whether speakers can accurately perceive uvularisation on emphatic consonants themselves or if they rely more heavily on coarticulatory effects on the surrounding segments. The experimental research questions and predictions are as follows:

- (1) Are acoustic cues on surrounding vowels more perceptually salient than those on the primary emphatic?

I predict that contextually emphatic vowels will be associated with higher numbers of emphatic responses (cf. Jongman et al., 2011; Hayes-Harb & Durham, 2016 etc.). Phonological primary emphatics will elicit significant (but lower) numbers of emphatic responses. Non-phonologically emphatic consonants spliced from emphatic context will not have a significant effect on responses. However, a contextually emphatic consonant paired with an emphatic vowel may show interaction effects, enhancing emphatic responses (cf. Jongman et al., 2011). Coarticulated segments in emphatic-final words (i.e., /d/ and /u/ from /dut^h/) may elicit greater proportions of emphatic responses due to increased leftward spread (cf. Herzallah, 1990; Zawaydeh, 1999).

- (2) Does vowel quality have significant effects on the proportion of emphatic responses?

I predict that the emphatic quality of the /a/ vowel will be a significant predictor of responses due to its neutral and backed allophones being assimilated into existing English phonemes (cf. Hayes-Harb & Durham, 2016 etc.). I predict that /i/ and /u/ will elicit similar responses but will be more accurate for /u/ (cf. Zaba, 2007).

- (3) Does the manner of articulation of emphatic consonants have significant effects on the proportion of emphatic responses?

I predict that emphatic plosives will elicit higher numbers of emphatic responses than emphatic fricatives due to their significantly different spectral means (cf. Jongman et al., 2011; Abudalbu, 2010 etc.). Stimuli using the /t/-/t^h/ distinction will elicit the highest numbers of correct responses as the Arabic aspirated /t/ [t^h] and unaspirated /t/ [t^l] will be assimilated into the English voicing distinction /t/-/d/ ([t^h]-[t]).

- (4) Do L2 Arabic proficiency and pedagogical background have significant effects on emphatic responses?

I predict that higher Arabic proficiency will be associated with more accurate emphatic perception. Furthermore, highly proficient speakers may display less pronounced vowel quality and aspiration

effects due to less reliance on native contrasts. However, consonantal and vocalic effects are still expected.

Participants with extensive immersion backgrounds will show more accurate responses and higher emphatic responses given only a primary emphatic consonant than participants who primarily self-study. Increased spoken Arabic input is likely correlated with more native-like performance on this perception task.

2 Methodology

2.1 Phase 1: Stimulus Generation

2.1.1 *Speakers Recorded for Stimuli*

Three female native Arabic speakers (ages: 20-28; mean: 23) were recorded with a H4n Pro handheld recorder (96 kHz and 24 bitrate). They are identified with two-letter codes indicating their native dialect: Moroccan (MA), Sudanese (SD), and Egyptian (EG). MA grew up in Morocco, moving to the UK at age 25 (three years prior) and spoke conversational French and rudimentary English; an Arabic-English translator was present. SD lived in Sudan and Qatar, speaking both Arabic dialects, and has lived in the UK for the longest of these countries. EG has lived for the longest in Kuwait, spending significant time in the UAE and Egypt; she moved to the UK for university aged 18 (three years prior). All speakers were instructed to use MSA for recordings.

2.1.2 *Recorded Stimuli*

The stimuli presented were MSA pseudowords. They were all CVC and obeyed Arabic phonotactic rules. The pseudowords formed minimal pairs as one consonant (the target) differed only by emphasis. They were also formulated so there was one minimal pair of words for each vowel quality (/a/, /i/, and /u/) and target consonant quality (/s/, /t/, and /d/) combination. Due to time constraints, the dental fricatives /ð/-/ðˤ/ were excluded (cf. Al-Wer, 2003). Wehr (1952) surveyed triconsonantal roots in Arabic to determine the ranking of most frequent Arabic consonants. The non-target consonant for each pseudoword was the most common consonant that would not form a meaningful MSA word. Uvular and pharyngeal consonants /χ q ħ ʕ/ were excluded, as were /r/ and /l/, due to their potential emphasis-like formant-altering effects (see Section 1.1.1). The letter *ghayn* (غ) is present in two pseudowords where no other consonant would form a non-word (*tagh-ṭagh* and *dugh-ḍugh*). It is variably described as velar /ɣ/ or uvular /ʁ/. Based on these constraints, the stimuli are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: *Experimental pseudowords organised by target consonant and nucleic vowel*

		A		I		U	
		Plain	Emphatic	Plain	Emphatic	Plain	Emphatic
S-Ş	Initial	سَاش	صَاش	بِيك	صِيك	سُون	صُون
		sāsh	ṣāsh	sik	ṣik	sūn	ṣūn
	sa:ʃ	sˤa:ʃ	sik	sˤik	sun	sˤu:n	
	Final	يَس	يَص	بِيس	بِيس	سُس	سُص
yas		yaṣ	bīs	bīṣ	sus	suṣ	
		jas	jaṣˤ	bi:s	bi:sˤ	sus	susˤ
T-Ṭ	Initial	تَغ	طَغ	تِي	طِي	تُوچ	طُوچ
		taḡ	ṭaḡ	ti2	ṭi2	tūj	ṭūj
	tay	tˤay	tiʔ	tˤiʔ	tu:ḍʒ	tˤu:ḍʒ	
	Final	تَات	طَات	وَيْت	وَيْط	دُت	دُط
thāt		ṭhāt	wīt	wīṭ	dut	duṭ	
		θa:t	θa:tˤ	wi:t	wi:tˤ	dut	dutˤ
D-Ḍ	Initial	دَز	ضَر	دِيف	ضِيف	دُغ	ضُغ
		daz	ḍaz	dīf	ḍīf	duḡ	ḍuḡ
	daz	dˤaz	di:f	dˤi:f	duɣ	dˤuɣ	
	Final	دَد	دَض	ثِد	ثِص	تُود	تُوص
dhad		ḍhaḍ	thid	thiḍ	tūd	tūḍ	
		ðad	ðadˤ	zid	zidˤ	tu:d	tu:dˤ

Table 3: *Distractor pseudowords organised by target consonant and nucleic vowel*

		A		I		U	
		Voiceless	Voiced	Voiceless	Voiced	Voiceless	Voiced
S-Z	Initial	سَاش	زَاش	بِيك	زِيك	سُون	زُون
		sāsh	zāsh	sik	zik	sūn	zūn
	sa:ʃ	za:ʃ	sik	zik	sun	zu:n	
	Final	يَس	يَز	بِيس	بِيز	سُس	سُز
yas		yaz	bīs	bīz	sus	suz	
		jas	jaz	bi:s	bi:z	sus	suz
T-D	Initial	تَغ	دَغ	تِي	دِي	تُوچ	دُوچ
		taḡ	daḡ	ti2	di2	tūj	dūj
	tay	day	tiʔ	diʔ	tu:ḍʒ	du:ḍʒ	
	Final	تَات	دَاد	وَيْت	وَيْد	دُت	دُد
thāt		thād	wīt	wīd	dut	dud	
		θa:t	θa:d	wi:t	wi:d	dut	dud
Ṭ-Ḍ	Initial	طَز	ضَر	طِيف	ضِيف	طُغ	ضُغ
		ṭaz	ḍaz	ṭīf	ḍīf	ṭuḡ	ḍuḡ
	tˤaz	dˤaz	tˤi:f	dˤi:f	tˤuɣ	dˤuɣ	
	Final	دَط	دَض	ثِط	ثِص	تُوط	تُوص
dhaṭ		ḍhaḍ	thiṭ	thiḍ	tūṭ	tūḍ	
		ðatˤ	ðadˤ	θitˤ	θidˤ	tu:tˤ	tu:dˤ

Distractor words (Table 3) were also created using the same method, with the plain-emphatic consonant pair replaced with a voiceless-voiced pair. Target consonants of the form /s/-/sˤ/ were replaced with /s/-/z/, /t/-/tˤ/ with /t/-/d/, and /d/-/dˤ/ with /tˤ/-/dˤ/. None of the distractors were meaningful MSA words. Due to concerns of task length, there was only one distractor per three experimental stimuli.

A small selection of real MSA words were also gathered (Table 4). They were used in a short practice trial to aid in familiarity with the experimental task as well as to access the English-speaking learner’s Arabic lexicon and phonology. Six pairs of words were chosen. Two pairs per vowel, one

Table 4: *Real Modern Standard Arabic words used as the stimuli for the practice trial*

A		I		U	
Plain	Target	Plain	Target	Plain	Target
دَم	ضَم	تَيْن	طِين	سُم	صُم
damm	ḍamm	tīn	ṭīn	sum	ṣum
dæm:	dʿæm:	ti:n	tʿi:n	sum:	sʿum:
dye	joining	fig	mud	poison	fast!
طَب	ضَب	سِر	زِر	تُب	دُب
ṭabb	ḍab	sir	zir	tub	dubb
tʿab:	dʿab:	sir	zir	tub	dub:
treatment	cleaving	depart	button	repent	bear

being a plain-emphatic minimal pair, and the other a voiceless-voiced pair. The target consonant was word-initial in all words.

2.1.3 Recording Procedure

Recordings took place in quiet yet convenient spaces for each speaker: MA in an office, SD in a common room, and EG in a secluded library room. Each environment was suitably small and/or padded to minimise echoing. Participants were instructed to read aloud each word three times with small pauses between. The experimenter was present, monitoring the recorded audio using headphones. If any words were unclear or obscured by unavoidable noise, speakers were instructed to repeat. Speakers were paid £7.50 for their participation.

2.1.4 Stimulus Generation

Unedited .wav files of the speakers' recordings were spliced in Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2023). The clearest repetition of each word was identified per speaker. Using the spectrogram (Gaussian window) and waveform, each segment was identified. The nucleic vowel was defined by the clear presence of F1. Isolating the vowel allows for the isolation of the onset and coda consonants. Where this was more difficult (e.g., when the onset consonant was a semivowel), the vowel included the formant transition from the initial semivowel, in keeping with the including of formant transitions in the vowel following other consonants (Figure 1).

When a segment was isolated, the 'extract selected sound' feature was used to create Praat objects consisting of individual segments. The same process was repeated for the corresponding plain or emphatic word. These segments were combined using the 'concatenate (with overlap)' feature. An overlap of 0.01 s was used as standard to reduce audible splicing. Where splicing was still evident, the overlap was increased in 0.01 s intervals until the stimulus was as naturalistic as possible while still maintaining distinction between each segment.

Figure 1: wide-band spectrogram of speaker EG uttering /jas/ segmented by formant transitions.

This cross-splicing was done so each possible combination of plain and emphatic segments was accounted for. We may indicate the target consonant with emboldening; compare *sik* and **şik** with *dut* and **dut**. The context is determined by the target consonant. In *şik*, as the target consonant is emphatic, the VC segments taken from this recording are contextually ‘emphatic’ (and indicated with an underdot). The possible combinations are displayed in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Compass-style figure showing possible splicing patterns using non-words *sik* and *dut* as examples. Emboldened segments are the target consonant (i.e., the consonant that creates the plain-emphatic minimal pairs). An underdot represents a segment produced in emphatic context. Thus, an emboldened and underdotted consonant is an emphatic target.

Experimental conditions are indicated with a code: vPiP refers to the vowel being plain in the context of a plain target consonant (vowel Plain in Plain). Similarly, vEiE is an emphatic vowel in emphatic context. These are congruent as the vowel matches the target. vEiP and vPiE represent an incongruent vowel that is either emphatic in plain, or plain in emphatic, respectively. The same system is used for the non-target consonant by replacing *v* with *c* (i.e., cPiP, cEiE, cEiP, cPiE). Therefore, for each pseudoword, there are eight stimuli created. The fully congruent stimuli (CVC or CVC) were also created via same-splicing.

2.2 Phase 2: Perception Experiment

2.2.1 Participants

Recruitment was carried out via email. Requests for circulation were sent to 56 institutions – including UK, US, and Arabic-speaking universities; Arab and/or Islamic societies; and Middle Eastern studies research institutions. The link for the experiment was also sent via word-of-mouth to other Arabic speakers or learners.

12 participants completed the experiment (ages: 19-25; mean: 21.5). Of these, seven were female and five male. 11 of the 12 participants were native English speakers who have lived most of their life in the UK. Only one was a native Arabic speaker from Lebanon. All English-speaking participants received taught Arabic classes, eight of whom indicated classes as their primary form of learning. Seven of 11 indicated having protracted immersion opportunities. The mode CEFR proficiency was B2 (n=4), followed by B1 and A2 (both n=3), and C2 (n=2, including the native speaker). All participants spoke MSA; the most common other dialect spoken was Levantine (n=6), followed by Egyptian (n=2), and Gulf (n=1).

2.2.2 Procedure

To reach a wider audience, the experiment was carried out online. It consisted of a background questionnaire in the participant's native language (Arabic or English) followed by a pseudoword discrimination task. Both the questionnaire and discrimination task were created using Gorilla (www.gorilla.sc) software (Anwyl-Irvine et al., 2020). Data was collected between 20 December 2023 and 7 February 2024.

Ethical approval for this experiment was awarded by the Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Modern and Medieval Languages and Linguistics at the University of Cambridge on October 16, 2023.

2.2.3 Questionnaires

Participants were asked to identify their native language. This determined the language of instruction for the rest of the experiment. Arabic and English speakers received differing questionnaires, both of which were used to screen participants. Both questionnaires gathered information regarding age, country of origin, gender, consent, and any speech or hearing impairments. Arabic-speaking participants were also instructed to identify their native dialect. English-speaking participants were prompted to provide information regarding Arabic proficiency, primary method of learning Arabic, which dialects they have studied, and their confidence in reading Arabic script.

Participants were excluded from the study based on the information provided in the questionnaires. 11 participants were rejected this way: four minors; three unconfident readers; three speakers with a native language other than Arabic or English; and one with a hearing impairment. From the beginning of the first questionnaire, an 8-hour timer begins. When this ends, participants are automatically rejected if they have not completed the entire experiment. 37 people were rejected this way.

2.2.4 Experimental Design

After completing the questionnaires, participants are redirected to a forced identification task, also hosted on Gorilla. Participants were instructed that the experimental task should be completed in a quiet room wearing headphones and, ideally, on a desktop or laptop computer rather than a mobile phone. The task worked on mobile phones, but issues of text size rendered them suboptimal.

Gorilla features an in-built sound test. Participants were played a short recording of a voice saying “one, two, three” and are asked if they heard the sound clearly. If not, participants were instructed to adjust any parameters and try the sound test again. Only participants that successfully heard the test audio were allowed access to complete the task.

The experiment took the form of a forced identification task. Participants were played on audio file. After the file had been fully played, they were then prompted to identify, out of the two vowelised Arabic-script options on screen, how they would spell the audio. All vowel diacritics (*ḥarakāt*) were included as, without them, there may have been a mismatch between the audio stimuli and how the participants initially read the pseudowords. The two options differed only in the emphasis of one consonant. They could choose either option via a button press or by clicking. When one option was chosen, a buffer screen was shown, allowing for participants to take short breaks if they wished. The next audio would play when a continue button was pressed. No feedback was given to participants at any point. Halfway through the task, there was a dedicated break that participants were encouraged to take for about five minutes to keep their reactions sharp.

Please indicate how you would spell the word in the audio clip.

Figure 3: Screenshot of a Gorilla screen featuring a forced binary identification task with the options being the vowelised Arabic-script pseudowords *dhad* and *dhaḍ*, respectively.

2.2.5 Data Analysis

Participants' responses to each audio stimulus are recorded. Indicating the audio as the word spelled without an emphatic consonant (e.g., < <دَد/ðad/ in Figure 3) would be recorded as *plain* whereas inputting the other option (e.g., < <دَض/ðadʕ/) would elicit the response *target*. These responses were compared against whether the target consonant was emphatic in the audio to isolate if the emphatic judgement was correct or not. These responses are the primary data presented and analysed in Section 3.

3 Results

Unless specified otherwise, the following results are calculated from the 11 L2 participants as intergroup comparisons are not feasible given the significant asymmetry in recruitment.

3.1 Effects of Emphatic Coarticulation by Segment

3.1.1 Analysis

Results for percentage emphatic responses across all stimuli are shown in Figure 4. The highest proportion of emphatic responses was observed for ÇVC (68.25%). This is followed by ÇVÇ (67.34%). The lowest proportion of emphatic responses was observed for CVC stimuli (26.06%) with CVÇ being similar (27.04%). 48.52% of stimuli elicited an emphatic response.

A three-way repeated measures ANOVA with Target Consonant, Vowel, and Non-Target Consonant as independent variables showed main effects for Vowel [$F(1,7)=538.24$, $p=0.027$]. Neither Target [$F(1,7)=85.87$, $p=0.068$] nor Non-Target Consonants [$F(1,7)=1.14$, $p=0.479$] alone showed significant effects. No significant interaction effects were observed.

Post hoc paired G-tests (cf. Ahad et al., 2019) were performed for each Splice Type pair (Table 5). All pairs, bar four, showed significant differences in emphatic responses [all $p<0.001$]. All

Figure 4: Box and whisker plot depicting the percentages of emphatic responses elicited by each splice type in L2 Arabic speakers. ÇVC indicates stimuli in which only the target primary emphatic is

emphatic; CVC when only the vowel is emphatic; and CVC when only the non-target consonant is emphatic. The following conditions follow this convention.

four pairs in which significant effects were not observed featured manipulation of the non-target consonant.

Significant differences were found between stimuli in which only the target was emphatic (CVC; 38.64%) and when only the vowel was emphatic (CVC; 58.47%) [$G(1)=46.753, p<0.001$]. These were also found between CVC and CVC (68.25%) [$G(1)=105.455, p<0.001$].

Table 5: *Post hoc G-test results showing p-values for each splice type combination. Impossible or repeat combinations are greyed out. Red-highlighted values indicate a lack of statistical significance*

	CVC	CVC	CVC	CVC	CVC	CVC	CVC	CVC
CVC		0.000	0.000	0.000	0.093	0.000	0.000	0.000
CVC			0.000	0.000	0.000	0.913	0.002	0.000
CVC				0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.702
CVC					0.000	0.001	0.739	0.000
CVC						0.000	0.000	0.000
CVC							0.002	0.000
CVC								0.000
CVC								

3.1.2 Word-Initial Targets

Emphatic responses when target-initial are shown in Figure 5. The highest average percentage of emphatic responses was again found for TVC (72.3%) with the entirely emphatic TVC falling behind (70.95%). Similarly to the overall data, TVC elicited the lowest number of emphatic responses (27.03%). 51.18% of all stimuli elicited emphatic responses.

A three-factor repeated measures ANOVA with Target Consonant, Vowel, and Non-Target Consonant as independent variables indicated a significant main effect for Vowel [$F(1,7)=1521, p=0.016$] and Target Consonant [$F(1,7)=174.24, p=0.048$]. No significant effect was observed for

Figure 5: Box and whisker plot depicting the percentage of emphatic responses elicited by each target-initial splice type in L2 Arabic speakers. *T* represents the target consonant.

Non-Target Consonant [$F(1,7)=0.64$, $p=0.57$]. No significant interaction effects were observed.

P-values from post hoc G-tests can be found in Table 6. Five pairs showed no significant difference. Four of these were also found in the overall data (Section 3.1.1). However, TVC and TVC showed no significant difference [$G(1)=3.505$, $p=0.061$]. TVC-TVC showed marginally significant effects [$G(1)=3.934$, $p=0.047$]. This was checked with a Fisher’s Exact Test – which is more appropriate for the smaller sample sizes of each pair (cf. Jung, 2014) – which returned the results as insignificant ($p=0.052$).

Table 6: Post hoc G-test results showing p-values for each Splice Type combination. Impossible or repeat combinations are greyed out. Red-highlighted values indicate a lack of statistical significance. Yellow-highlighted values indicate a p-value that was determined as insignificant post G-test

P	TVC	TVC	TVC	TVC	TVC	TVC	TVC	TVC
TVC		0.000	0.001	0.000	0.452	0.000	0.000	0.001
TVC			0.000	0.025	0.000	0.913	0.061	0.000
TVC				0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.783
TVC					0.000	0.019	0.715	0.000
TVC						0.000	0.000	0.000
TVC							0.047	0.003
TVC								0.000
TVC								

3.1.3 Word-Final Targets

When examining only target-final words, similar trends were observed. CVT stimuli elicited the higher proportion of emphatic responses (64.16%). CVT elicited the lowest (25.08%) followed by CVT (26.03%). 45.84% of target-final stimuli elicited emphatic responses.

A three-factor repeated measures ANOVA with Target Consonant, Vowel, and Non-Target Consonant as independent variables observed a significant main effect for Vowel context [$F(1,7)=538.24$, $p=0.027$]. No significant effects were found for Target Consonant [$F(1,7)=85.87$, $p=0.068$] or Non-Target Consonant [$F(1,7)=1.138$, $p=0.479$]. No significant interaction effects were observed.

Figure 6: Box and whisker plot depicting the percentage of emphatic responses elicited by each target-final splice type in L2 Arabic speakers. *T* represents the target consonant.

Post hoc G-tests indicated most pairs as significant, excluding the same four insignificant pairs found in both Section 3.1.1 and Section 3.1.2. Target-final stimuli elicited significantly different responses in the CVT-CV̄T [$G(1)=6.722$, $p=0.01$] and CV̄T-CV̄T [$G(1)=5.502$, $p=0.019$] pairs (unlike for target-initial words).

Table 7: Post hoc G-test results showing p-values for each Splice Type combination. Impossible or repeat combinations are greyed out. Red-highlighted values indicate a lack of statistical significance

P	CV̂	CV̂	CV̂	CV̂	CV̂	CV̂	CV̂	CV̂
CV̂		0.000	0.005	0.000	0.103	0.000	0.000	0.002
CV̂			0.000	0.007	0.017	0.805	0.010	0.000
CV̂				0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.793
CV̂					0.000	0.014	0.913	0.000
CV̂						0.008	0.000	0.000
CV̂							0.019	0.000
CV̂								0.000
CV̂								

G-tests were also performed between complementary target-initial and -final conditions (e.g., between TV̂C and CV̂T). The pairs in which significant differences were observed are as follows: TV̂C-CV̂T [$G(1)=6.722$, $p=0.01$], TV̂C-CV̂T [$G(1)=4.504$, $p=0.034$], and TV̂C-CV̂T [$G(1)=5.024$, $p=0.025$]. In all cases, the target-final condition showed fewer emphatic responses. This is perhaps due to final targets eliciting fewer emphatic responses overall [$G(1)=13.498$, $p<0.001$].

Table 8: Post hoc G-test results showing p-values for comparison of complementary target-initial (horizontal) and target-final (vertical) pairs

P VALUE	TV̂C							
CV̂	0.362							
CV̂		0.010						
CV̂			0.583					
CV̂				0.034				
CV̂					0.971			
CV̂						0.025		
CV̂							0.061	
CV̂								0.591

3.2 Effects of Vowel Quality

Vowel quality effects when both consonants are plain were examined. A three-factor repeated measures ANOVA with Quality, Length, and Emphasis as the independent variables was carried out. Significant main effects were observed for Emphasis [$F(1,9)=40.4$, $p=0.024$]. Neither Length [$F(1,9)=4.971$, $p=0.156$] nor Quality [$F(1,9)=0.021$, $p=0.979$] showed significant effects. No interaction effects were observed.

Figure 7: Bar chart depicting percentage emphatic responses by vowel quality when both consonants are plain.

Post hoc G-tests found significant differences in emphatic responses between plain /a/ (19.7%) and plain /u/ (30.96%) [$G(1)=6.672, p=0.01$]. This originally held for their emphatic counterparts /a/ (63.45%) and /u/ (53.3%) [$G(1)=4.186, p=0.041$]. However, a Fisher’s exact test disqualified this pair as significant ($p=0.052$).

Table 9: Post hoc G-test showing p-values for each vowel pair in CVC

P Value	A	Ǻ	I	Ǫ	U	Ǯ
A		0.000	0.066	0.000	0.010	0.000
Ǻ			0.000	0.331	0.000	0.041
I				0.000	0.457	0.000
Ǫ					0.000	0.283
U						0.000
Ǯ						

Vowel quality effects were also analysed such that both consonants were not required to be plain. A three-way repeated measures ANOVA with Quality, Length, and Emphasis as the independent variables was carried out. Again, only Emphasis showed significant main effects [$F(1,9)=69.32, p=0.014$]; neither Length [$F(1,9)=8.52, p=0.1$] nor Quality [$F(1,9)=0.119, p=0.894$] showed significant effects.

Post hoc G-tests found plain /a/ to elicit significantly fewer emphatic responses (27.32%) than /i/ (34.39%) [$G(1)=9.245, p=0.002$] and /u/ (39.72%) [$G(1)=27.203, p<0.001$]. The difference between /i/ and /u/ was also significant [$G(1)=4.784, p=0.029$]. /Ǻ/ elicited significantly higher emphatic responses (69%) than /Ǫ/ (60.86%) [$G(1)=11.447, p=0.001$] and /Ǯ/ (59.77%) [$G(1)=14.642, p<0.001$]. However, the difference between /Ǫ/ and /Ǯ/ was not significant [$G(1)=0.196, p=0.658$].

Table 10: Post hoc G-test results displaying p-values for each vowel quality pair across all splice types

P Value	A	ʌ	ɪ	ɪ̃	U	ʊ
A		0.000	0.002	0.000	0.000	0.000
ʌ			0.000	0.001	0.000	0.000
ɪ				0.000	0.029	0.000
ɪ̃					0.000	0.658
U						0.000
ʊ						

Post hoc G-tests also showed significant effects of length only when the emphatic context of the surrounding consonants was not controlled. Long plain /a:/ elicited fewer emphatic responses (22.73%) than short /a/ (30.27%) [$G(1)=5.456$, $p=0.019$]. Long emphatic /ɪ:/ also elicited fewer emphatic responses (56.6%) than its short counterpart (65.14%) [$G(1)=6.035$, $p=0.014$]. No other pairs showed length effects.

Figure 8: Bar chart depicting percentage emphatic responses by vowel quality across all splice types.

3.3 Effects of Manner of Articulation

Similar analyses were performed given target consonant quality. First, we focus on target consonants where both the vowel and non-target consonant are plain. A three-factor repeated measures ANOVA with Quality, Emphasis, and Position as the independent variables was executed. Significant main effects were observed for Quality [$F(2,11)=81.242$, $p=0.012$] and Emphasis [$F(1,11)=60.176$, $p=0.162$]. No significant effects were observed for Position [$F(1,11)=2.813$, $p=0.235$]. Significant interaction effects were observed only for Quality*Emphasis [$F(2,11)=31$, $p=0.031$].

Post hoc G-tests identified that there was no significant difference between emphatic responses for plain /s/ (21.43%) and emphatic /s/ (19.39%) [$G(1)=0.251$, $p=0.616$]. There were significant differences between the other emphatic pairs: /t/ (16.67%) with /t̃/ (45.69%) [$G(1)=39.913$,

Figure 9: bar chart depicting percentage emphatic responses by manner of articulation when vowel and non-target consonants are plain.

p<0.001] and /d/ (40.10%) with /d/ (50.76%) [$G(1)=4.524, p=0.033$]. /s/ and /t/ showed no significant difference [$G(1)=1.452, p=0.228$] whereas /s/ elicited significantly fewer emphatic responses than /d/ [$G(1)=16.273, p<0.001$]. /t/ and /d/ also showed significant differences [$G(1)=27.303, p<0.001$]. When emphatic, /s/ and /t/ elicited significantly different responses [$G(1)=31.622, p<0.001$]; /s/ and /d/ did as well [$G(1)=43.609, p<0.001$]. /t/ and /d/ were not significantly different [$G(1)=1.017, p=0.313$].

When the same ANOVA was executed on consonantal data across all splice types, both Quality [$F(2,11)=104.83, p=0.009$] and Emphasis [$F(1,11)=133.941, p=0.007$] showed significant effects, as did their interaction [$F(2,60)=4.718, p=0.012$]. Here, Position showed significant effects [$F(1,11)=29.289, p=0.032$]. Again, only Quality*Emphasis displayed interaction effects [$F(2,11)=37.853, p=0.026$].

Post hoc G-tests showed similar patterns of significance. However, where /s/ and /t/ did not display significant differences when all segments were plain, they did when this is not controlled [$G(1)=15.622, p<0.001$]. Similarly, /t/ and /d/ also showed significant differences [$G(1)=11.107, p=0.001$]. G-tests showed significant differences of position only for /s/-/s/: initial /s/ elicited significantly higher numbers of emphatic responses [$G(1)=5.406, p=0.02$]; this was also true for the emphatic /s/ [$G(1)=7.758, p=0.005$].

Table 11: post hoc G-tests results showing p-values for each consonantal pair in CVC

P Value	S	ʒ	T	Ṭ	D	Ḑ
S		0.616	0.228	0.000	0.000	0.000
ʒ			0.482	0.000	0.000	0.000
T				0.000	0.000	0.000
Ṭ					0.263	0.313
D						0.033
Ḑ						

Figure 10: Bar chart depicting percentage emphatic responses by manner of articulation of the target consonant across all splice types.

3.4 Effects of Arabic Proficiency

3.4.1 L1 Arabic Speaker

Paired G-tests were executed to compare correct and incorrect responses across all trials per participant. The L1 speaker produced the highest number of correct responses (61.34%). However, this was only significantly greater than five of the 11 other participants: two B2 speakers, one B1, and one A2. In fact, the three most accurate participants were native, B1 (61.25% correct) and A2 (60.88%). So, counterintuitively, the native speaker was on par with many L2 speakers.

A series of Fisher's exact tests were performed comparing the mean and median frequency of emphatic and plain responses per splice type of the L2 speakers with the responses of the L1 speaker. Only two splice types showed significant differences: **CVÇ** ($p=0.024$) and **CVC** ($p=0.004$) in both cases with the native speaker giving significantly fewer emphatic responses. However, in both cases, there were at least three L2 speakers that had comparable results; these L2 speakers represented A2, B1, and B2 proficiency groups.

3.4.2 L2 Arabic Speakers

L2 speakers were organised into two proficiency groups: low proficiency (A2 and B1) and high proficiency (B2-C2). A two-factor repeated measures ANOVA with Splice Type and Proficiency as the independent variables was carried out. Both Splice Type [$F(7,80)=33$, $p<0.001$] and Proficiency [$F(1,80)=6.927$, $p=0.01$] displayed significant differences. There was no significant interaction [$F(7,80)=0.409$, $p=0.894$]. High proficiency speakers produced fewer emphatic responses overall. Post hoc G-tests suggest this difference is only significant for **CVÇ** [$G(1)=7.359$, $p=0.007$] and **CVC** [$G(1)=5.454$, $p=0.02$] with high proficiency speakers showing fewer emphatic responses.

Figure 11: bar chart depicting percentage correct responses per participant. Red/orange participants are low proficiency; green are high proficiency. Red participants are A, orange are B1, light green are B2, darker green are C2 and native.

Another ANOVA with Splice Type and Proficiency as the independent variables with number of correct responses as the dependent variable was executed. Significant effects were observed for Splice Type [$F(7,80)=27.978$, $p<0.001$] but not for Proficiency [$F(7,80)=0.693$, $p=0.408$]. No interaction was observed.

3.5 Summary of Results

A short summary of results as relevant to the research questions outlined in Section 1.3 follows:

- (1) Stimuli in which the target and vowel were contextually emphatic showed the highest number of emphatic responses: ÇYÇ (68%) and ÇYÇ (67%). Stimuli in which the vowel was emphatic elicited higher proportions of emphatic responses compared to corresponding stimuli in which the vowel was plain. This is also true, to a lesser extent, with target consonants: CYÇ showed 58% emphatic responses compared to ÇYÇ with 68%.
- (2) There were significant effects of vowel quality on emphatic responses. Vowel length had no effect. From the highest emphatic responses to the lowest, vowels create the following hierarchy A >> I >= U >> U >> I >> A where >> indicates a significant difference. Accuracy was highest for /a/ and lowest for /u/.
- (3) Consonants showed manner of articulation effects. /d/ elicited significantly higher emphatic responses regardless of its emphatic status. /s/-/s/ showed no significant differences with all participants producing low emphatic responses. Participants were most accurate perceiving /t/. The hierarchy of accuracy follows as t-ţ >> d-đ >= s-ş.
- (4) CEFR proficiency had no effect on emphatic responses. The one native speaker, although being the most accurate, was on par with other speakers of varying CEFR proficiencies. Immersion had no significant effect either.

4 Discussion

4.1 Is Consonantal Pharyngealisation Perceptually Salient?

The goal of this study was to examine the acoustic cues of emphasis for native English speakers learning Arabic. Cross-splicing pseudoword stimuli allows for the perceptual effects of different segments to be investigated in isolation and with interactions. Significant (or lack thereof) differences between splice types may reveal which segments L2 speakers attend to for emphatic discrimination.

Looking first at the role of the emphatic target consonant, we see that **ÇVC** stimuli elicited significantly more emphatic responses (39%) compared to the entirely plain **CVC** control (26%). When the vowel and non-target consonant were not controlled, the addition of the emphatic target increased emphatic responses by about 10-15% (e.g., **CVC** elicited 27% emphatic responses compared to **ÇVC**'s 43%; or **CVC**'s 58% compared to **ÇVC**'s 68%). This provides evidence that L2 speakers attend to acoustic cues of uvularisation on the phonological emphatic itself.

However, perhaps the primary emphatic is less perceptually salient than acoustic effects on adjacent vowels. **CVC** stimuli elicited 58% emphatic responses compared to the plain **CVC** control (26%). An emphatically coarticulated vowel increased emphatic responses across all conditions. Unlike the target emphatic though, this increase was generally around 25-30%. For example, **CVC** stimuli elicited 27% emphatic responses, compared to **CVC**'s 59%; **ÇVC** elicited 39% emphatic responses whereas the stimuli with an emphatic vowel (**ÇVC**) elicited the highest emphatic responses at 68%. Furthermore, when only one segment was spliced from emphatic context, both **ÇVC** and **CVC** showed below chance emphatic responses (39% and 27%, respectively), whereas **CVC** elicited 58%. Therefore, we may suggest that, although L2 speakers attend to acoustic cues on the emphatic consonant, the coarticulatory effects on the adjacent vowel are more perceptually salient.

Previous studies using a similar methodology do not separate the vowel and non-target consonant. The present study separated these variables to analyse their independent effects. As expected, the non-target consonant had no significant effects on emphatic responses whereas the vowel's emphatic status was the most accurate predictor of responses. This provides further evidence for the notion that the emphatic effect on adjacent vowels is the most perceptually salient cue (e.g., Jongman et al., 2011; Ali & Daniloff, 1974; Card, 1983; Yeou, 1995). Thus, consonantal pharyngealisation (or, truly, uvularisation) may not be a particularly salient cue for L2 Arabic speakers' emphatic perception.

Brief attention in data analysis was paid to the role of emphatic spread. Vowels were spliced as such to include the formant transitions of their flanking consonants. Therefore, one may assume that, if emphasis spread is more significant leftwards (cf. Watson, 1999; Jaber et al., 2001; Bukshaisha, 1985; Herzallah, 1990; Slimani, 2018), emphatic vowels and initial non-target consonants from target-final stimuli would elicit a greater facilitative effect on emphatic responses compared to their target-initial counterparts. Quantitative analysis suggests this is not the case: **TVÇ** stimuli elicited 28% emphatic responses whereas **ÇVT** stimuli only elicited 26%. This was not significant. Both **TVÇ** and **ÇVT** elicited 43% emphatic responses and G-tests reveal a significant increase in emphatic responses for **TVÇ** (63%) than **ÇVT** (54%) stimuli. This is not consistent with Jongman et al.'s (2011) findings that **ÇVT** elicited greater emphatic responses (94%) compared to **TVÇ** (69%). Although not designed to assess emphasis spread, the present study tentatively provides evidence to the contrary of more significant leftward spread. However, Zawaydeh (1999) suggests that the primary difference between left- and rightward spread is that leftward spread is categorical whereas rightward is gradient which cannot be assessed with **CVC** stimuli.

4.2 Vowel Quality, Manner of Articulation, and Phonological Acquisition

Segmental quality had significant effects on participant responses. L2 participants were significantly more accurate with their emphatic judgements when the nucleic vowel was /a/ (69% emphatic when /a/; 27% when /a/), whereas /u/ was the most difficult (60% emphatic when /u/; 40% when /u/). This provides evidence to Hayes-Harb and Durham's (2016) suggestion that English speakers make use of their native /ɑ/-/æ/ distinction to differentiate Arabic emphasis. PAM-L2 predicts this as /a/ and /a/ would be a two-category assimilation which is associated with highly accurate perception. Whereas /u/-/u/ would likely be category-goodness (with less accurate discrimination) as /u/ is not acoustically very close to the English /ʊ/. /i/-/i/ could be either, dependent on whether /i/ is assimilated with English /i/ or /ɪ/, explaining its intermediate accuracy. Zaba (2007) and Hayes-Harb and Durham (2016) suggest that /i/ is most regularly assimilated with /i/ rather than /ɪ/ which may explain why accuracy was lower for /i/ than /a/. Long /i:/ may be more likely to assimilate as English /i:/, hence explaining why /i:/ elicited fewer emphatic responses than its short counterpart. However, these assimilation patterns cannot be uncritically assumed to hold in the present study as the current finding that participants were least accurate for /u/ is not corroborated by these investigations.

However, Best et al. (2001) found correct discrimination of above 90% for TC assimilation. This is corroborated for vowel phonemes by Tyler et al. (2014). Echoing somewhat Al Mahmoud's (2013) argument, perhaps this is indicative of orthographic effects. Best et al. (2001) and Tyler et al. (2014) use naïve listeners in their perceptual studies. These speakers all used alphabetic writing systems for their native languages. As the vocalic distinction between [a] and [æ] in Arabic is (i) not usually written and (ii) not part of explicit Arabic teaching (unlike the vocalic distinctions between e.g., /a/ and /i/), it is possible that L2 speakers have become entrenched in their formal phonological teaching (cf. McCandliss et al., 2002; Ellis, 2006) and attend to certain vocalic cues less accurately as they would in English. Perhaps this is an issue with PAM-L2. It aims to attribute levels of discrimination to different forms of assimilation. Different assimilation types are difficult to empirically identify; factors such as the individual phonemes, participant differences, and other methodological concerns may render the identification of specific discrimination percentages unreliable. NLM-e, on the other hand, also correctly predicts highest accuracy for /a/-/a/ but does not attempt to provide an absolute range of discrimination, instead taking a relative approach.

Significant effects of consonantal quality were also found. Particularly, the /s/-/s/ distinction was the most difficult for participants. This follows from Jongman et al.'s (2011) and Abudalbh's (2010) findings regarding emphatic fricatives not differing in spectral mean from their plain counterparts (*contra* Bukshaisha, 1985). The equally low number of emphatic responses for both /s/ and /s/ suggests both were assimilated into the plain /s/ as a single-category (SC) assimilation. Low accuracy is explained by both PAM-L2 and NLM-e. But PAM-L2 may be circular. The identification of /s/-/s/ as SC assimilation is due to participants' inaccuracy, which is, in turn, a predictor of SC assimilation. PAM-L2 attempts to make specific predictions but lacks an empirical metric by which to identify assimilation types.

The highest accuracy for /t/-/t/ is explainable via aspiration. We may take the view that aspiration is the primary perceptual cue for voicing in English plosives (Deterding & Nolan, 2007) and that Arabic /t/-/t/ differ in VOT. Thus, English speakers may use VOT cues to aid in the differentiation of /t/ and /t/. G-test analysis of distractor responses showed /t/ elicits significantly greater voiced responses (23%) than /t/ (4%) [$G(1)=57.288, p<0.001$]. Although voiced responses for /t/ were still significantly less frequent than those of /d/ (91%) or /d/ (87%), partial assimilation of /t/ as voiced as opposed to the solidly voiceless and aspirated /t/ may have contributed to the relative accuracy of responses. In such a

case, this provides some evidence that L2 speakers make use of native distinctions even when not phonemic; they attend to different dimensions of the same stimulus (Iverson et al., 2003). This again provides evidence for NLM-e as the Perceptual Magnet Effect would be less pronounced for /t-/t/ than /s-/s/ and /d-/d/. PAM-L2 may also explain these patterns but, again, the exact percentage of accurate discrimination is still not consistent with the theory's assumptions.

4.3 Proficiency and Pedagogical Background

Overall, participants showed difficulty in identifying emphatic consonants. Comparisons between L1 and L2 participants cannot be drawn due to the unequal sample sizes. So, if we compare the results with those of Jongman et al. (2011), we may see that the L2 participants (as well as the one native speaker) displayed considerably less accurate responses. Jongman et al.'s L1 participants produced 90% emphatic responses for **ÇVÇ** stimuli and only 3% when plain **CVC**. The present study observed a significant difference between these two conditions but L2 speakers only produced 67% emphatic responses for **ÇVÇ** and 26% for **CVC**. These results are consistent with Hayes-Harb and Durham (2016) who focused on L2 Arabic speakers who displayed 61% emphatic responses for **ÇVÇ** and 7% for **CVC**. Thus, even in high proficiency cases, L2 Arabic speakers show difficulty reaching native-level emphatic perception. NLM-e predicts overall lower discrimination than PAM-L2 as neural commitment to the L1 renders the exemplar network of phonemes resistant to change. Whereas PAM-L2 assumes extremely high accuracy for TC and CG assimilations (around >90% and >75%, respectively). This may be a strength of NLM-e given the present study's results.

The significantly less accurate performance of the L1 speaker compared with those found by Jongman et al. (2011) may have multiple causes. Firstly, this study uses entirely non-words. Therefore, participants do not have access to a mental lexicon with which they may bolster their emphatic judgements. This has the strength of not disadvantaging L2 participants that may have a smaller vocabulary than native or high proficiency participants. However, this may have affected the performance of the L1 speaker. Secondly, there is no information about their language history beyond being a first language speaker; it is possible they moved to a non-Arabic speaking country at an early age and thus experienced attrition of their language abilities. However, studies of heritage speakers and international adoptees suggest early exposure to a language increases accuracy of phoneme perception into adulthood even if they cannot speak the language (e.g., Oh et al., 2010, Tees & Werker, 1984). Emphatic consonants are not normally masterfully acquired by L1 speakers until at least age 6;4 (Amayreh & Dyson, 1998); if the L1 speaker stopped primarily speaking Arabic at a very young age, it is perhaps not surprising that their accuracy was low. Due to the lack of available comparisons with other L1 speakers, it is more prudent to treat their results as an anomaly.

NLM-e places heavy emphasis on the style of input. Exaggerated acoustic cues are found to be helpful for first language acquisition (e.g., Maye et al., 2002) as well as in adult classroom settings (cf. Odisho, 2005). This investigation cannot shed light on the role of classroom teaching as all participants received classes. No significant effect of immersion was found, so we may cast some doubt upon the notion that immersion is an effective method of learning such difficult phoneme distinctions. Perhaps the effect of ambient input is significantly reduced once adulthood is reached as the brain has already neurally committed to the L1.

5 Conclusions

The present study examined L2 Arabic speakers' perception of intermediary spliced pseudoword stimuli in a forced identification paradigm.

The results suggest that English speakers show considerable difficulty accurately identifying emphatic consonants even in naturalistic stimuli. English speakers attend primarily to acoustic cues on the adjacent vowels of emphatic consonants to make emphatic judgements; the acoustics of the consonant alone are not always adequate in producing emphatic responses. Thus, consonantal pharyngealisation and/or uvularisation is not fully sufficient for emphatic perception.

Particularly, the present study provides evidence that English speakers make partial use of native phonemic distinctions to aid in emphatic perception. Aspiration distinctions for English plosives and the /æ/-/ɑ/ distinction are the most relevant here.

Accuracy in emphatic responses is presented as highly individual as neither proficiency nor pedagogical background displayed significant effects between participants. These trends are in line with both PAM-L2 and NLM-e. But the overall lower accuracy of participants suggests NLM-e may be more suitable.

5.1 Limitations and Future Research

Limitations of the present study have been addressed where relevant in Section 4. Here, the most important limitations are again summarised.

First, the number of participants surveyed is low. This renders quantitative analysis less reliable. Issues caused by a small sample size are exemplified in the low accuracy of the L1 Arabic speaker surveyed. The causes of their relatively poor performance cannot be known given the information collected. In the Arabic questionnaire, questions could have been included that probed the participants' language history more closely. However, the performance of this participant could not have been anticipated given previous similar studies.

The lack of participants also has ramifications for analysis of pedagogy and proficiency. Controlling such complicated variables to allow for more consistent and valid analysis is difficult given this sample. As NLM-e stresses the type of input in language acquisition, the lack of control in these areas may partially compromise the evidence found in favour of the model. Furthermore, proficiency was self-reported using CEFR guidelines which was originally developed for European languages. Thus, CEFR accuracy for Arabic may be inadequate (cf. Bellassen, 2011) and self-report results are not always reliable.

This study presented participants with pseudoword stimuli. This may have contributed to the overall low accuracy of responses as participants could not use their repertoire of lexical items to aid in perception. All stimuli were CVC and thus the effects of emphasis across larger domains could not be properly evaluated. Finally, as each stimulus had to form two minimal pairs (an experimental emphatic pair and a distractor voicing pair) while also being nonwords, the potential forms these pseudowords could have taken was significantly constrained. Therefore, some uvular consonants (specifically /ʁ/) had to be included. The F2 lowering effect of the uvular may have had confounding effects on the coarticulatory effect of the uvularised emphatic.

Finally, the method of administration (i.e., online on different devices) may have had limiting effects on the cross-participant reliability of responses due to device limitations (cf. Anwyl-Irvine et al., 2020; Jia et al., 2018; and Woods et al., 2015) and/or environmental distractors. Latency with this method particularly devalues response time data.

Future investigations should address the above concerns. The scope of the study could be extended to include a more controlled comparison of proficiency and pedagogy to evaluate NLM-e and the role of teaching in perceptual acquisition. Expanding the methodology to include polysyllabic real words could increase the understanding of perceptual acquisition in more naturalistic scenarios. Perhaps accurate response time data could be analysed to assess processing difficulties.

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Grammar Against Humanity: How Does Grammatical Incongruity Affect Perceptions of Humour?

Bronwyn Way
University of Sussex

Abstract. Incongruity theory is one of the reigning theories of humour, explaining why we find jokes ‘funny’ — its argument is that humour comes from the unexpected. Prior linguistic studies of humour focus on semantic incongruity, that is when the meaning of the ‘punchline’ is unexpected from the ‘set up’ of the joke (as is the case with puns, irony, and double entendre joke-constructions). However, this prior research does not explore other kinds of incongruity such as grammatical incongruity. Memes are a great contemporary example of grammatical incongruity in humour such as Jeremy Clarkson (The Grand Tour, 2022) exclaiming ‘A egg!’ The question is raised, does the comedy come from his untraditional use of the consonant-predicating indefinite article a rather than the vowel predicating an, or the unexpected response? This project explores the relevance of grammatical incongruity for humour perceptions. Specifically, it seeks to understand if grammatical incongruity can improve, negate, or create a barrier to perceptions of humour in fill-in-the-blank joke constructions. To achieve this, a digital questionnaire based on the popular card game Cards Against Humanity is used to assess participants perceptions of grammatically incongruous joke-constructions and determines through quantitative and qualitative analysis that without semantic resolution it negates but with semantic resolution it can improve perceptions of humour.

Keywords: humour; grammar; grammatical incongruity

1 Introduction

In the ever-evolving landscape of humour, joke constructions mirror societal changes and technological advancements. As described by Holt (2004) the joke ‘is a form of humour that comes and goes with the rise and fall of civilizations.’ The features of joke-constructions, and what makes them ‘funny’ also shifts with cultural perspectives. David Crystal (2019, p. 97) notes that memes, a product of digital communication, demonstrate an innovative use of nonstandard grammar in multi-modal joke constructions. This dissertation questions whether the familiarisation with nonstandard grammar in memes has influenced humour trends and made using nonstandard grammar a method of crafting successful joke-constructions.

In this dissertation, data collected from a digital questionnaire based on the card game Cards Against Humanity (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2011) is used to assess whether grammatical incongruity negates, improves, or creates a barrier to perceptions of humour. After introducing key concepts, incongruity theory, my motivations, and Cards Against Humanity (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2011), I will outline my methodology, the key data, and analyse my findings. Overall, I show that grammatical incongruity often has a negative impact on whether fill-in-the-blank joke-constructions are perceived as humorous. However, this is impacted by a few factors: error eye-detection, the grammatical flexibility of the incongruity type, and whether or not the incongruity can be resolved.

2 Background

There are a few assumptions and key concepts that need to be established as they are the foundations of this research. This includes introducing a definition of humour, how it can be measured, and the elements that contribute to its perception. I will also discuss David Crystal's *Netspeak* (2001) and how it creates a link between these fundamental aspects of humour and memes.

2.1 A Definition of Humour and Laughing at the Unexpected

Attardo (1994, p. 3) discusses the interdisciplinary issue of defining 'humour' for research and makes three conclusions: it is not productive to create theoretical differentiations of humour types (e.g. comic, ridiculous, mockery), laughter is not a successful defining criteria for humour perception, and the use of a 'humour competence' (Raskin, 1985 as cited in Attardo, 1994, p.12) is most successful as a 'working solution' (1994, p. 3). Attardo (1994, p. 196) summarises Raskin's idea of a 'humour competence': 'Because a speaker can tell if a sentence belongs to the set of grammatical sentences, argues Raskin, the speaker can tell if a text is funny or not [...] considering a text humorous is merely being aware of its perlocutionary goal and/or effect'. Arguably then, finding something humorous is something that can often be self-assessed by the individual. Therefore, using self-assessment may be an appropriate method of collecting data.

Another significant issue is the cause of humour perception; Attardo (1994, p. 14) conducts a survey of the literature on this topic. He argues that incongruity theory is the most productive for linguists as an essentialist argument (1994, p. 2). Incongruity theory is the most suitable framework for my project as I focus on grammatical incongruities that are unexpected and unexplainable. Eagleton (2019, p. 67) describes incongruous humour as 'a clash of incongruous aspects [...] a momentary defamiliarizing of the familiar.' Suls (1972, p. 85) provides a 'Humor-appreciation model' to illustrate this effect. To best explain this model, using cognitive 'script' terminology can be useful, but as this has many different definitions across the linguistic discipline I will operate on Attardo's (1994, pp.198-200): 'A script is an organized chunk of information about something', more specifically, 'a cognitive structure internalized by the speaker which provides the speaker with information on how things are done, organized, etc. [...] it contains information which is typical, such as well-established routines and common ways to do things and to go about activities.' In example (1) the reader will have an expectation based on their KNIGHTED script which may link to other scripts such as DIGNITY, FORMALITY, HONOUR.

- (1) 'your trousers falling down while you are being knighted.' (Eagleton, 2019, p. 67)

Juxtaposition is then created by a second TROUSERS FALLING DOWN script, which may link to other scripts like EMBARRASSMENT and INDECORUM. Suls (1972, p. 87) suggests that at 'this point one engages in problem solving to find how the punch line follows from the main body of the joke'. In example (1) this is a case of irony; the reader can see how awkward that situation might be and potentially find it humorous due to how unlikely it might be.

Suls' model has been a useful starting point for further frameworks. However, Suls argued that if there is no logic connecting the two expectations this will result in 'puzzlement' (1972, p. 85), which fails to account for absurdist humour. Attardo (2002, p. 27) argues that incongruous elements of joke-constructions 'may or may not be fully or in part (playfully or not) resolved by the occurrence of the punch line', and Kierkegaard argues a 'contradiction between expectation and experience' (2009 quoted in Couder, 2019, p. 5) can create humour perception. This raises the argument that incongruous aspects

can be humorous despite lacking a logical connection. This research does not create purposeful logical connections between set ups and punchlines, which further tests this theory.

2.2 Cartoons, Memes, and Netspeak

Additionally, whilst Suls (1972, p. 85) was concerned with understanding the cognitive appreciation of joke-constructions in cartoons, this dissertation is inspired by memes. To apply Suls' model (1972, p. 85) to appreciating memes, it has to be noted how memes work in online communication. David Crystal (2001, p. 25) noted that the majority of scholars referred to Netspeak as written down spoken language but observed that the language differed from written and spoken language conventions. Instead, he offered up Netspeak which had its own rules and conventions, which further differed in different mediums. He notes the difference between online webpages and chatrooms where 'The situations are not all equally 'spoken' in character. We 'write' e-mails, not 'speak' them. But chatgroups are for 'chat' and people certainly 'speak' to each other there' (Crystal, 2001, p. 29). Crystal (2019, p. 97) discusses memes and notes they are shared digitally and the 'chief linguistic feature is the use of nonstandard forms — in early chat developments such as text messaging, chiefly deviant spelling; in more recent varieties, deviant grammar.' Therefore, memes act more similarly to standard spoken language conventions than written, and this often includes nonstandard grammar. This dissertation questions whether familiarisation with meme joke-constructions, and their nonstandard grammar, could have created a trend in joke-constructions leading to people appreciating grammatical incongruity in joke-constructions outside of the meme medium.

Today, physical printed cartoons have declined in popularity. I argue that the same positionality is now carried by internet memes that are 'often used to channel humour on the internet and on social media' (Tacharungroj & Nueangjamnong, 2015, p. 289). Trends in joke-constructions change with societal preferences. This can be supported by a case study of two cartoons from *Punch* (*Punch*, 1841-2002) magazine published over 60 years apart. *Punch* (*Punch*, 1841-2002) was a highly popular magazine, credited with bringing the term cartoon into the mainstream (Applebaum & Kelly, 1981) making it a reliable source for considering popular societal trends in cartoon joke-constructions. Figure 1 is an example of a comic cartoon in *Punch* (*Punch*, 1841-2002) magazine from 1902.

Using Suls' framework (1972, p. 85) there is an expectation created that the fisherman is reading the name of the boat but juxtaposed by his misreading of it. A semantic resolution is available if the fisherman is assumed to not know the word *psyche*. The humour comes when the viewer understands that phonetically *ps* could be pronounced /f/, *y* could be pronounced /i/ and *che* should be pronounced /ʃ/. It requires problem solving on the part of the viewer.

Figure 2 shows a later example from *Punch* magazine (*Punch*, 1841-2002), a cartoon about the 'British Car Industry' (Lemmings, 2022) published in 1977.

Figure 1: *Critical* (Punch, 1920, p. 6).

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Image details Mini cars driving off the cliffs of Dover into water.] — Editor's Note

Figure 2: *1970s British Car Industry Cartoons from Punch magazine* (Lemmings, 2022).

Here the problem solving requires contextual information outside what is shown in the cartoon — it depicts Mini cars driving off the cliffs of Dover, because between 1969 and 1973 Mini's gained popularity overseas and they began manufacturing them outside of England (Adams, 2024). An expectation is created but only resolved with contextual information. Overall, Figure 1 and Figure 2 show a difference in joke-construction style, with one requiring problem solving and the other requiring contextual information. There is a scarcity of research on the history of joke-constructions and the change to their semantic incongruity resolution. However, I think as suggested by Figure 1 and Figure 2 and Holt (2004) there are trends, and this dissertation questions whether grammatical incongruity could be a current trend started by joke-constructions in memes.

Across the last four decades memes with grammatical incongruities are common, as supported by Crystal (2019, p. 97).

Figures 3, 4 and 5 provide cross-decade examples of this comedic trend. Particularly Figures 4 and 5 were observed by Crystal as 'Among the most successful inventions' in memes with nonstandard grammar. Figure 1 was originally a translation error for the video game *Zero Wing* (Toaplan, 1992 as cited in Dubs, 2009) but Figures 4 and 5 are examples of Lolspeak — a variant of Crystal's Netspeak (2001). Fiorentini observes the 'nonstandard orthography, morphology and syntax' of Lolspeak and its

'extreme variability' (2013, p. 1). I think that those who saw Figure 4 and 5 outside of their community context may find them examples of absurdist humour. The scholars previously referred to (Suls, 1972; Attardo, 1994) focused on semantic incongruities within joke constructions, but this comedic trend raises a question of whether grammatical incongruities also affect perceptions of humour. To my knowledge, this has not been a previous consideration for the study of humour.

Figure 3: *All Your Base are Belong To Us* (Dubs, 2009).

Figure 4: *Happy Cat* (Menning, 2010).

Figure 5: *Doge* (NovaXP, 2014) .

2.3 Cards Against Humanity

Cards Against Humanity (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2011) is a popular card game; six days after its release on Amazon it became the number one game sold (Kickstarter, 2012), and over six thousand copies sold last month in America at the time of writing (Amazon, 2024).

The game consists of a white and black deck of cards. Each black card has a ‘question or fill-in-the-blank phrase’ acting as the set-up for joke-constructions; each white card has a word or phrase that ‘fills in the blank’ or ‘answers the question’, acting as the punchline (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2024). Players have a hand of white cards and must choose the funniest option to play, then a designated player will choose the winning white card (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2024).

The simplicity of this game made it feasible for me to manipulate joke-constructions to be grammatically incongruous. Suls (1972, p. 84) notes that ‘adults need to know they are hearing a joke: other incongruous situations may not be suitable stimuli for humor.’ Therefore, using a joke-construction card game adheres to this caveat. The participants may also be more familiar with evaluating how humorous they found joke-constructions if they have played Cards Against Humanity (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2011) before. Additionally, Cards Against Humanity (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2011) (often takes inspiration from memes which might make grammatical incongruities appear less obvious.

Any white card can grammatically fit with any black card, but they may make less semantic sense and Suls’ appreciation model (1972, p. 85) indicates they would be unresolvable. For example:

- (2) Black Card: Toys bore me, and I don’t care for sweets I prefer ____
- a. a wet, cold, slice of garlic bread.
 - b. Me, your dad.

Answer (2a), a wet, cold, slice of garlic bread would make more semantic sense as an answer to (2) than (2b), me your dad, as (2b) entails the impossible situation of the speaker being their own father. Therefore, other incongruities may be less apparent as participants familiar with the game would be used to semantic incongruities occurring and helping to avoid demand characteristic biases (Rhul, 2023).

3 Methodology

This section outlines the creation and implementation of the digital questionnaire used to collect data for this research dissertation, and how the design will allow me to answer my research questions. To reiterate, the key research questions for this dissertation are:

- Does grammatical incongruity in fill-in-the-blank joke constructions improve, negate, or create a barrier to perceptions of humour?
- Does incongruity type affect the answer to the first question?

There will also be further considerations into the questions:

- Grammatical incongruity is successful in memes, has this established a new comedic trend whereby grammatical incongruity is now acceptable in another digital medium?

This section will discuss the card game framework in a digital medium, the incongruity types chosen, the two types of question chosen, and the sample, as well as discussing limitations and their impact throughout.

3.1 Making a Card Game into a Questionnaire

The Cards Against Humanity original edition includes offensive humour. Thus, to protect the safety of participants and maintain ethical standards I used the family edition, which is designed to be inoffensive. From this deck I further removed white cards with brands, American expressions, and pop culture references as participants who couldn't contextualise them may have biases towards the other options. I only included fill-in-the-blank black cards, and removed questions or double blank ones, for feasibility.

For the first question set I used the chosen fill-in-the-blank black cards as the question and gave three white cards to choose from as the answers. The game is designed for every white card to fit any black card drawn. The white cards take the form of nouns, noun phrases, and gerund phrases. I chose three types of grammatical incongruity that would require minor modifications to the cards based on this. I also factored in which kinds of grammatical incongruity appeared in Figures 3, 4, and 5, as they represent successful grammatically incongruous joke-constructions.

Davies (2019) observes the impact survey fatigue can have on the integrity of digital questionnaire responses. To negate survey fatigue: I completed pilot tests to make sure the survey would not take longer than 15 minutes to complete, ensured consistency in question design and formatting, and did not include open text questions. Another impactful factor was participants consciously or subconsciously noticing and responding to the grammatical incongruities inconsistently with how they would naturally as a result of demand characteristics (Ruhl, 2023). The multiple-choice section of the questionnaire had 24 questions in total, with eight for each incongruity type. To lessen the likelihood of demand characteristics being detected by participants, six of the 24 questions had only congruous options to conceal what features were being investigated.

3.1.1 Articles

Jeremy Clarkson exclaimed 'A egg!' in a viral video, using the consonant predicating form of the indefinite article a rather than an. This example of grammatical incongruity was simple to apply to the white cards as several had noun phrases that included the indefinite article a, such as: 'A horse with no legs', or 'A corn dog' (Cards Against Humanity LLC, 2024). For each question in the article section of the first question set, I added the indefinite article a to a black card and chose synonyms that began with vowels to be the incongruous option, this can be seen below in example (3).

- (3) The aliens are here. They want a ____.
- enormous honkin carrot
 - big wet kiss from Great Aunt Sharon
 - glorious beard

Example (3) is the first article question on the questionnaire. Answer (3a), enormous honkin carrot, is incongruous. Answers (3b) and (3c), big wet kiss from Great Aunt Sharon and glorious beard, are congruous. The congruous counterpart for (3a) was huge honkin carrot. The incongruous counterparts for (3b) and (3c) were enormous wet kiss from Great Aunt Sharon and amazing beard. I chose white cards with noun phrases on them that included an adjective as the first word to make finding synonyms

simpler and less semantically impactful. Other synonyms included infant for child, old man for pensioner and oily for greasy - see appendix to view the other synonyms chosen.

3.1.2 *Gerunds*

As with the Doge meme shown in Figure 5 in the previous section, using an incongruous verb form is a common way of incorporating grammatical incongruity into memes. Such as ‘concern’ (NovaXP, 2014) rather than this is concerning, or I am concerned. As several white cards used gerunds this was straightforward as I could change the -ing suffix for -ed or remove it entirely, see example (4) below.

- (4) This is gonna be the best sleepover ever. Once Mum goes to bed, it’s time for _____.
- a. do maths
 - b. stuffing my underwear with pancakes
 - c. seeing Aunt Linda

Example (4) is the first question of the gerund section. Answer (4a), do maths, is incongruous. Answers (4b), stuffing my underwear with pancakes, and (4c), seeing Aunt Linda, are congruous. In example (4a) I removed the -ing suffix making it incongruous. For answers (4b) and (4c) they became stuffed and see. Other examples of this include braiding becoming braid or being becoming be - see appendix to view the rest of the changes made to white cards in the plural section.

3.1.3 *Plurals*

This section was not inspired by a meme but was chosen due to its feasibility for the cards available. I added quantifiers to the black cards such as plenty of or many which would then require a plural noun. Example (5) demonstrates this:

- (5) When I look in the mirror, I see many _____.
- a. teeny tiny turd
 - b. bears
 - c. old people

I then adjusted the white card options to be plural or singular. Thus, answer (5a), teeny tiny turds, became teeny tiny turd, (5b), bears, became bear and (5c), old people, became old person. Despite being chosen for feasibility this section had some errors which I will consider in the analysis section of this dissertation.

3.2 **A Semantically Incongruous Results**

If a white card was perceived as amusing because of semantic meaning it may be chosen more often despite grammatical incongruity. To be able to cross-compare individual white cards’ incongruous and congruous forms I created three versions of the questionnaire that rotated which white card was incongruous. I randomised the order of questions and white cards for participants, to offset the effect of demand characteristics which would be heightened if the incongruous option was always in the same place in the answer order.

Additionally, I included a second section to the questionnaire that asked participants to rate joke-constructions on a scale of 1-5. Figure 6 shows the basic layout that was repeated for each possible answer.

The rating scale question set was divided into two sets of 54 statements, separating the incongruous and congruous versions of constructions randomly so participants wouldn't rate both versions of one example. Out of 54, 12 statements were randomly distributed to each participant. Two pilot tests were conducted, one on someone who reads for pleasure who completed the questionnaire in nine minutes and another on someone who does not read for pleasure who completed it in 14 minutes; this supported minimising survey fatigue.

The rating scale question set allows for cross-comparison of congruous and incongruous forms of white cards. In the first question set participants are comparing three white card options, whilst in the rating scale question set, they evaluate them individually. Therefore, I was able to see which cards were chosen most often for each question, and if there were any where the incongruous form was preferred, I could then compare these specific statements with their rating in the second section to view if they were rated higher than their congruous forms. If the incongruous form was not rated higher than their congruous counterparts, it is likely that they were the most amusing semantically and this was more important to perceptions than their grammatical incongruity.

How amusing do you find these possible pairings to the previous question?

	Not amusing	Not very amusing	Neutral	Slightly amusing	Very amusing
The aliens are here. They want a huge honkin' carrot.	<input type="radio"/>				
Papa, come quickly! There, in the garden! Do you see a old guy respecting people's boundaries? Tell me you see it Papa!	<input type="radio"/>				
Come on, Danny. All the cool kids are doin' them. You should try those hunky man.	<input type="radio"/>				

Figure 6: *Example of Rating Scale Question*

3.3 The Sample

There were 100 responses, but some were removed due to incompleteness leaving 76 usable responses. Meyerhoff, Schleaf and MacKenzie (2015, p. 78) recommend a sample size of at least 30 for normal distribution. To monitor potential sample bias and take social variables into account I requested participants 'age' and 'gender-identity' in the questionnaire. There were 25 men, 47 women and four non-binary people. 37 participants were between 18 and 39, and the other 39 were between 40 and 79. To take this into account my following analysis uses relative frequency when referring to results.

I would also note that whilst an argument could be made that younger participants may be more exposed to the grammatical incongruities in memes, the majority of the Lolspeak memes were popular between 2005 and 2010 (Dubs, 2009), making anyone between the ages of 30 and 50 possibly more exposed. Additionally, this questionnaire was shared on six social media platforms meaning the sample was those most likely to use those platforms. Therefore, this research is not a suitable assessment for that hypothesis or a comparison of social media users and non-social media users. This dissertation only concerns a general impact on humour perception. Whether the impact of grammatical incongruity on humour perception differs between specific groups is beyond the scope of this project, but the social variables will be considered for a preliminary idea of these further questions.

This methodology was limited by a few errors made in the questionnaire due to missed autocorrected white cards, and a missing question from the rating section. These errors have caused some questions to be removed from the data pool but otherwise do not impact the analysis. Also, the flexibility of plural nouns was underestimated in design, but this overlook provided some interesting opportunities for cross-comparison particularly regarding construal.

4 The Data and Preliminary Analysis

This section will identify useful data from the questionnaire responses. Here, I will discuss the overall results, and in subsequent sub-sections I will discuss the results for each incongruity type (articles, gerunds, and plurals). Finally, I will identify the key takeaways.

For clarity, note that the order of white card options for the first question set was randomised for participants and is only relevant for the analysis. In the following graphs, ‘congruous 1’ refers to the option preceding the incongruous card in the analysed order, while ‘congruous 2’ refers to the subsequent option, which changes depending on which version of the questionnaire was answered. Therefore, comparison between ‘congruous 1’ and ‘congruous 2’ is irrelevant.

Figure 7 shows the overall results for which option was chosen in the multiple-choice question set.

Figure 7: Overall Results.

Overall, the congruous options were chosen 15-25% more than the incongruous, which is a notable amount. This suggests that grammatical incongruity may have a negative effect on perceptions of humour. However, when considering each incongruity type these results differ

The mean rating for the joke-constructions overall, congruous, and incongruous forms included, was 2.8 which provides a point of comparison for evaluating if a joke-construction did particularly well. The overall mean rating for incongruous options was 2.5 (out of 5), and the mean rating for congruous options was 3.1 (out of 5). The rating data can be useful for cross comparing congruous and incongruous versions, and both the mode and mean will be used in the subsequent analysis of each incongruity type.

Overall, age and gender as social variables show no significance, this was tested using a Chi Square test both for the overall data and individual data sets for the three incongruity types. The p value was consistently above 0.04, thus suggesting no statistical significance for the results. As aforementioned, this sample may be biased as it targeted social media users, and those who likely follow language interest pages. To assess the impact of social variables on humour perception of grammatically incongruous joke-constructions, further research involving a more diverse sample would be necessary to determine any statistically significant differences. As such, the social variables will not be further considered in this analysis.

4.1 Gerunds

The gerund results showed the least preference for incongruous options.

Figure 8: Gerunds *Multiple Choice Question Data*.

Figure 8 shows that the incongruous form was selected 13% of the time, which is a notable decrease from the overall results. Thus, incongruous verb forms may be more of a barrier to humour perception than the other incongruity types.

Additionally, the rating scale data showed a near uncontested agreement that congruous forms were preferred over their incongruous counterparts. There was one outlying result that had the same mean rating for both the congruous and incongruous form, the results question can be seen below in example (6).

(6) Kids dad is trying something new this week, it's called ' ___ '.

- a. eating cocktail weenies
- b. eat cocktail weenies

Both answers for example (6) had a mean rating of three. However, the mode was four for the congruous form, eating cocktail weenies, and three for the incongruous form, eat cocktail weenies. As three was the neutral point this means that most participants considered the congruous form somewhat amusing and the incongruous form neutral. Additionally, both answers could have been interpreted congruously because of the quotation marks. Quotation marks expect integrity to what is being referenced, therefore it's possible that errors would be leniently received (American Psychological Association 2022). If example (6) was interpreted congruously it would have been an anomalous result.

4.1.1 *Gerunds, Characterisation and Error Detection*

The gerund incongruity type was the least popular of the three types studied, but the most common in the Happy Cat and Doge memes as shown in Figures 4 and 5. This disparity raises the question of why the inspiring memes were successful and the joke-constructions on this questionnaire were not. Whilst the questionnaire style, length, sample or Cards Against Humanity framework are factors, I argue that the negative results are due to error-tracking and a lack of incongruity resolution without a character.

Larigauderie, Guignouard and Olive (2020) conducted research on error-tracking and the impact of memory on different types of errors. Overall, they determined that 'orthographical errors had the lowest rate of detection', followed by grammatical errors and then phonological errors (2020, p. 1030). Changing the verb form would be a grammatical error according to their guidelines (Larigauderie et al, 2020, p. 1020). As such, the verb form incongruity type in the questionnaire was the most likely to be noticed. Therefore, the gerund incongruity type results may show the sincerest attitudes towards nonstandard grammar in joke-constructions as there is less chance of misreading and assuming congruity was intended.

Additionally, the memes that inspired this incongruity type such as Happy Cat in Figure 4 and Doge in Figure 5, both have characters speaking with grammatical incongruities. The memes show cats and dogs using incongruous verb forms and adjectives such as 'concern' (NovaXP, 2014), or 'I can has cheezburger' (Menning, 2010). Suls' two-stage model suggests that the script of ANIMAL and THOUGHT would be activated in these memes. The script of THOUGHT and ANIMAL individually do not imply grammatical incongruities will occur, but they do, creating a complication. However, a semantic resolution is available whereby animals cannot speak English, but if they could their language may be nonstandard. The viewer can resolve the incongruity, and rather than reach puzzlement be open to perceiving the joke-construction as amusing.

Additionally, considering the medium of the meme versus the medium of the questionnaire, the conditions of Netspeak may have been affected. Crystal (2001, p. 25) observed that an issue with prior contributions to the study of language on the internet was 'Write the way people talk' sounds sensible enough, until we have to answer the question: which people?' Here Crystal notes the plethora of variations of spoken language, and thus the mass-variation of internet language that would exist if this was true. If the speaker in the Doge (NovaXP, 014) and Happy Cat (Menning, 2010) memes is being near-transcribed, and this is considered grammatically standard for the medium, then their joke-constructions may be entirely congruous. As Netspeak is partially based on spoken language, particularly in chatrooms where memes are shared, then in this instance the animal is the 'speaker' and thus in the memes the language may appear congruous as it represents the hypothetical real language. In the questionnaire, it would not appear that way as there is no visually identifiable speaker, or if there is such as 'Dad' from example (6) there is no logical resolution for why their language would be grammatically nonstandard.

To summarise, the gerund-incongruity type results indicate that in multimodal joke-constructions the character using grammatically incongruous language is important to whether it improves or negates perceptions of humour, and different digital mediums could impact this success. Additionally, grammatical incongruities appear to create a barrier to humour perception and can lead to puzzlement unless resolution occurs.

4.2 Articles

The article incongruity type showed the highest rate of preference for the grammatically incongruous forms.

In Figure 7 the incongruous option accounts for nearly a third of choices, showing less negation to humour perception than the gerund incongruity type. The data from the rating scale question shows that 65% of incongruous options were rated lower than their congruous counterparts, but only by 0.1-0.6 which is far less a disparity than the gerund incongruity type displayed. Furthermore, the mode for both incongruous and congruous options was four. Thus, both congruous and incongruous grammatical forms were considered somewhat amusing by most participants.

Figure 7: *Articles Multiple Choice Data.*

Example (7) had the lowest mean rating for congruous option, bothersome kid, with 1.7 (out of 5). Example (7a), annoying kid, was rated 2.25 in contrast.

- (7) The warm August air was filled with change. Things were different, for Kayla was now a ____.
- annoying kid
 - bothersome kid

Both means indicate they were not perceived as amusing, but bothersome kid was notably less so. There is the possibility that the synonyms chosen annoying and bothersome were perceived differently. I self-selected the synonyms to be as semantically similar as possible, and my personal biases may have affected these results. Despite possible bias, the article results suggest that incongruous indefinite articles do not create a barrier to humour perceptions and neither improve nor negate them either.

4.2.1 Indefinite Articles and Error Detection in Verbal and Written Language

Research on error-tracking observed that orthographical errors were least likely to be detected (Larigauderie et al., 2020, p. 1030). Their orthographical errors included ‘letter omissions’ (Larigauderie et al 2020:1018) which would include a rather than an. Additionally, change blindness studies support this observation that readers would notice changes to articles less than verb changes (Christensen et al., 2021 as quoted in Soby, Ishkanyan & Kirsten, p. 2023). Logically, incongruous articles may not have been noticed by participants in written language. Therefore, the article results showing neither improvement nor negation in perception may only show a lack of perceiving incongruity.

The meme that inspired this incongruity type to be included was a video of Jeremy Clarkson exclaiming ‘A egg!’ (The Grand Tour, 2022) at a farm, which I could only find as a video and not as a still image. The meme’s lack of popularity as a still image may be a result of nonstandard articles being less noticeable in written language.

The allophones a and an exist for ease of spoken language. Pak (2016, p. 12) observes four variants of the indefinite article in spoken language: ‘/ə/, /ən/, e(j) and either /æn/ or /ɛn/’, depending on what is the most comfortable transition from any previous word to the indefinite article and to the following word. Despite this, only two forms of the article exist orthographically an and a. This indicates that in written language the indefinite article requires less variation and is therefore less noticeable. Thus, incongruous use of the indefinite article in joke-constructions is a topic that needs to be investigated verbally, but not in written language as this research did.

4.3 Plurals

The plural incongruity type may have biases, as aforementioned in the methodology section of this dissertation – these will be considered alongside the analysis in this section. Figure 8 shows the overall results for the plural incongruity type.

Figure 8: Plurals Multiple Choice Question Data.

Figure 8 shows similar results to the gerunds type; the plural incongruity type had a low preference rate with 14% of selection. However, the rating scale data produced three examples where the incongruous form was chosen over its congruous counterpart. Combined, these examples display the difficulty of making plurals incongruous.

Example (8) had a mean rating of 3.5 for (8a), cocktail sausage, and three for (8b), cocktail sausages.

- (8) Oh, that's my mom's friend Carl. He comes over and helps her with plenty of _____.
- a. cocktail sausage
 - b. cocktail sausages

Out of 32 respondents for the incongruous form, answer (8a), 19 selected it. Contrastingly, 16 participants out of 23 chose the congruous form in the second question set and 13 out of 25 participants in the last question set. Relative frequency makes this an equal success rate of 59-60% for either option.

Example (9) shows the second and third examples of the higher rated incongruous options.

- (9) I'm not like other children. Toys bore me, and I don't care for sweets, I prefer _____.
- a. nipple
 - b. nipples
 - c. humble earthworm
 - d. humble earthworms

Answer (9a), nipple, had a mean rating of 3.6 whilst (9b), nipples, had a mean rating of 2.8. Answer (9c), humble earthworm, had a mean rating of three and answer (9d), humble earthworms, had a mean rating of 2.9. The difference between (9c) and (9d) is less of a disparity, with a 0.1 difference, than (9a) and (9b), with a 0.8 difference. It should be noted that example (9) shows a black card question without a quantifying determiner such as plenty of, some, or many which may influence whether participants construed it as incongruous or not.

4.3.1 *Euphemism and the Semantics of Abstract and Proper Nouns*

Shown in the section above, example (8) supports the conclusion that grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour if there is a resolution — similarly to the characterisation issue in the gerund section. In example (8), scripts of 'mom', and 'friend' are created — all of which have some sense of responsibility and do not explicitly imply sexual themes. However, sausage is a known euphemism for penis and to say one is receiving lots of sausage in this sense would be to imply they participate in lots of sex, usually with one individual — hence sausage and not sausages. The addition of cocktail to the euphemism, may just work as a determiner of size to the euphemism. If one was using it as a euphemism in this example, as it refers to one individual 'Carl' it would make more semantic sense to use cocktail sausage. Therefore, when the original expectations are confronted by the incongruity, a logical link can be created that the statement is referring to the euphemistic sense rather than the food substance sense. This is an example of a double entendre joke-construction.

Most joke-constructions in the questionnaire did not have a resolution, and grammatically incongruous versions were rated lower and chosen less often than their congruous counterparts. In example (8) answer (8a), nipple, was incongruous but had a possible resolution and it improved

perceptions of humour. Therefore, this example would suggest that grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour if a semantic resolution is available.

Nipple in its singular form could be construed as an abstract noun. In this sense it could be another euphemism. In the song Greased Lightnin one of the lyrics is: ‘we’ll be getting lots of tit’ (Travolta, 1978). Here, they’re referring to seeing or feeling lots of nipples because they are engaging in sexual activity. Thus, in this sense (9a) could be referring to liking lots of sex, whilst (9b) could be referring to liking nipples specifically. If this is the case the semantic incongruity may occur because of the CHILD script, where respondents may not expect a child to express a committed preference to nipples over sweets and toys. There are two possible semantic resolutions. Firstly, the script of NURSING could be used to suggest the child is expressing preference for being breastfed. Alternatively, the child character could be interpreted as expressing an overtly sexualised interest which would juxtapose the typically innocent CHILD script. Both of these interpretations would constitute a semantic resolution.

Therefore, both (9a), nipple, and (9b), nipples, could be construed as congruous, and thus their results are not representative of absurdist unresolvable grammatical incongruity. Answer (9a), nipple, could be interpreted as an abstract noun and possibly a euphemism and support the earlier conclusion that grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour if they contribute to semantic resolution.

Regarding (9c), humble earthworm, and (9d), humble earthworms, it is unlikely they would be interpreted euphemistically. However, it could be construed as an abstract noun. As a singular noun phrase humble earthworm would require an article to make grammatical sense. The lack of article and plurality makes it appear more like a proper noun or abstract noun. However, due to the lack of capitalisation, it is most likely to be construed as an abstract noun.

- (10) I’m not like other children. Toys bore me and I don’t care for sweets, I prefer
 ____.
 a. adventure

Example (10) demonstrates an abstract noun in place of humble earthworm. It makes grammatical sense without plurality or an article. If construing humble earthworm as an abstract noun it could refer metaphorically to SIMPLE, NATURAL, and ANTI-MODERNIST, scripts suggesting a desire to return to the natural world as symbolised by the idea of the humble earthworm. Humble earthworm as an answer to example (9) could construct an incongruous scenario where the child exhibits a preference for mundanity and simplicity, which juxtaposes typical interests and desires associated with children. Therefore, the child could appear to the viewer more akin to a wise, old man who has no preference for materialistic desires. The semantic resolution available would then be that the child character is unexpectedly mature for his young age, which could be perceived as amusing. This further indicates that a resolution for why the character speaking is using nonstandard grammar may be significant for grammatical incongruities in joke-constructions to be successful in improving perceptions of humour.

4.4 Key Takeaways

This analysis aimed to answer whether grammatical incongruity improves, negates, or creates a barrier to humour perceptions in joke-constructions. The results indicate that grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour if it plays a role in the semantic resolution of the semantic incongruity. The examples of characterisation, euphemism, and abstraction of singular nouns demonstrate that when supporting the semantic resolution grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour.

When the grammatical incongruity did not contribute to semantic incongruity resolution then it worsened perceptions of humour. If the grammatical incongruity was less noticeable via error-detection skills, then the negative impact to perceptions of humour were decreased. Error-detection skills can be affected by several factors such as memory (Larigauderie et al., 2020, p.1032), but generally larger lexical changes like the gerund incongruity type will be most noticeable, followed by incorrect noun type (Larigauderie et al., 2020, p.1030). Nonstandard articles are the least likely to be detected (Larigauderie et al., 2020, p.1030), and this was proven in these results as well.

Additionally, noun changes can impact the sense in which joke-constructions are construed. This research has given some data to suggest that grammatical changes can be influential in the success of joke-constructions that rely on semantic sense, such as the euphemism examples in the plural incongruity type section.

5 Conclusions

Ultimately, this research draws three main conclusions in answer to whether or not grammatical incongruities in fill-in-the-blank joke constructions negates, improves, or creates a barrier to perceptions of humour.

Firstly, grammatical incongruities without resolution do negate perceptions of humour and this is dependent on how noticeable the incongruity is. The less noticeable in accordance with error detection research, the stronger the negation to perceptions of humour. This is shown by the strong correlation between incongruous forms being chosen less often than congruous forms, and the incongruous forms being rated lower than their congruous counterparts. This further suggests that absurdist humour may not work with grammatical absurdities – possibly because it appears to the viewer more like an error than a purposeful decision to not use standard language rules.

This dissertation also investigated whether the grammatical incongruity trend found in memes could be successful in a different medium. Thus, these results do not necessarily reflect the correlation between incongruity and humour perception in meme joke-constructions. There does appear to be a difference between the success of grammatical incongruity types on improving perceptions of humour in memes and fill-in-the-blank written joke constructions. This is suggested by the Doge (NovaXP, 2014) and Happy Cat (Menning, 2010) memes and the gerund results, as despite their popularity the incongruity type was the least preferable out of the three. This could be due to the digital medium used — as aforementioned, memes use more spoken language conventions, but a questionnaire would act more similarly to a webpage and use more written language conventions. As described in the gerund sub-section of the data section, the characters speaking, and the spoken language conventions could mean that the grammatical incongruities are not incongruous in their medium context. On the other hand, in the questionnaire they certainly would be viewed this way. Further studies could examine this further by testing different mediums and doing a cross-comparative study, or by using a meme-based game as the framework such as What Do You Meme? (Tebele & Kaplan, 2016).

Another conclusion of this dissertation is that the incongruity type used affects the results. As aforementioned, error-tracking research leads me to believe that less noticeable grammatical incongruities are less likely to create a barrier to perceptions of humour. However, this then suggests that grammatical incongruities do create a barrier because if they go unnoticed their incongruity is inconsequential. Alternatively, this conclusion also points out that some features of grammar are more flexible than others and that participants may construe them differently, as exemplified by the difference for noun types.

As I was not purposefully testing for this, a limitation of this research is that incongruity types were not based on error-tracking in design, although the clear links between error-tracking and which

incongruity types received more or less preference suggests this to be a less impactful limitation. Further investigation into this conclusion including more varied incongruity types may provide more information. Additionally, error-tracking is affected by many factors such as memory (Larigauderie et al., 2020, p. 1032). As the sample was not assessed on the factors that could skew this, it is not an appropriate conclusion for the scope of this project and further research may be required to validate the claim, once again though the clear correlation makes this a less-impactful limitation.

Additionally, unintentional congruous construal should be considered for further research, as in the case for the plurals section of this dissertation as this could affect results and was a limitation for this research. Furthermore, if a meme format was used in future research, then limiting the options to verbal or written incongruities, or testing them separately, would be beneficial. The article incongruity type demonstrates the drastic change in results that not taking this into account can cause.

This dissertation concludes that grammatical incongruity can improve perceptions of humour when it plays a role in resolving the semantic incongruity of a joke-construction. The examples of characterisation and euphemism in the gerund and plural incongruity types demonstrate that when a semantic resolution is available, perceptions of humour can be improved by deviances from standard grammatical choices. In the case of memes, visual elements can provide an additional layer of context that can provide resolution to grammatical incongruity. One of the research questions was whether grammatical incongruity could improve perceptions of humour in different mediums, and I can conclude that it can if a semantic resolution is available.

In the three case study memes All Your Base are Belong to Us (Dubs, 2009), Happy Cat (Menning, 2010), and Doge (NovaXP, 2014), the grammatical incongruities are resolvable, as I resolved in the early part of this dissertation. Therefore, there is a consistent observation that resolvable grammatical incongruities may improve perceptions to humour, both in real world examples and in this research. This leads to another question, does semantic sense/resolution make grammatical incongruities appear congruous because the purpose of grammar changes in these joke-constructions? This would be an interesting further study not just for the study of humour but for semanticists generally.

Additionally, Crystal (2019, p. 97) notes that ‘There are hundreds of meme wannabes on the Internet now, all hoping (but few achieving) a permanent place in language history. Some sites provide instructions on ‘how to create your own meme’. We must expect a significant increase in the amount of linguistic idiosyncrasy both on and off the web now, srsly.’ Whilst my research sought to investigate whether this trend appeared outside of meme joke-constructions, this argues that this trend may no longer be popular and as such joke-constructions using the trend may negate perceptions of humour. Further studies could compare the online popularity of memes with nonstandard grammar across the last two decades to determine whether this trend has fallen out of fashion.

Overall, these results and conclusions contribute to a final thought: despite looking for the effect of grammatical incongruity I have resolved that at the level of linguistic features, language is so flexible that it can often be made congruous despite incongruous design. Linking back to Attardo’s definition of humour, if an individual can create a semantic link and make a construction make sense to them, even if it appears absurd, then it can be perceived humorously.

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Section B

Squibs & Write-ups

Classification Vectors as a Tool for Modelling Human Speech Perception

Paula Arkhangorodsky, Ewan Dunbar

University of Toronto

Abstract. Humans perceive speech through the lens of their native phonemic categories, which fundamentally shape both the identification and discrimination of speech sounds. This connection between how we identify and discriminate phonemes is widely recognised as the phenomenon of Categorical Perception. We present two studies that quantitatively explore the role of categorical perception in human speech perception, focusing on how native phonemic categories influence the identification and discrimination of speech sounds when comparing an approach which operationalises categorical perception compared to one that does not. In Study 1, we apply classification vectors to model English-listener identification experiments, using Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) and other input representations such as wav2vec 2.0 and DeepSpeech2. Study 2 extends this approach to English-listener discrimination experiments. Our findings indicate that computational models, particularly those using wav2vec 2.0, offer more precise simulations of human speech perception surpassing acoustic-only models. By demonstrating that these classification vectors can effectively model both identification and discrimination tasks, this research provides a quantitative framework that solidifies the importance of categorical perception in human speech perception.

Keywords: computational linguistics; categorical perception; computational modelling

1 Introduction

Babies acquire their native phonemic categories roughly by the time they turn 12 months old (Polka, 1996; Werker & Tees, 1984). From this point, we keep these categories through and past adulthood. We use these categories every time we perceive speech sounds, as they guide and heavily influence our identification (‘classification’) of sounds (Liberman et al., 1957). Ultimately, we perceive all speech sounds in terms of these native phonemic categories, even if the sounds are not present in our native language. Moreover, our ease in classifying sounds is directly related to how easy it is to tell them apart (‘discrimination’). This relationship between identification and discrimination is fleshed out in the notion of categorical perception, which is described in more detail below.

The *Perceptual Assimilation Model* (PAM) is a prominent model of human speech perception in the literature (Best, 1995). It states that non-native speech perception is dependent on the way a listener classifies a non-native sound with respect to their native categories. Crucially, PAM allows this classification to be indeterminate, meaning that the non-native sound is not perceived as similar enough to any native sound, and thus does not get classified as any. However, a limitation of PAM is that it is a qualitative model, and thus is difficult to validate with human data.

To address the limitations of PAM while building on its foundation, Levy (2009) proposes the *overlap score*, a quantitative metric for predicting human speech perception which describes how similar a given pair of phones are. The overlap score has been found to have a strong correlation with human discrimination task results, ultimately supporting the findings of PAM.

While the literature on the effects of categorical perception on human speech perception is vast, few studies have evaluated categorical perception using an explicit computational model applied to the stimuli human listeners heard in an experiment. Thus, this current paper seeks to address this gap in

the literature. Explicitly, we study the effect categorical perception has on human speech perception through two computational modelling studies. In Study 1, we examine the question using classification vectors to model English-listener identification experiments, and, in Study 2, we use classification vectors to model English-listener discrimination experiments. We seek to determine whether predicted categorical perception explains listeners' behaviour better than a model that only makes use of the acoustic signal, without categories.

1.1 Identification Tasks

A *phoneme identification task* is a task where participants have a sound played for them, and then are asked to identify which sound they heard out of a set of options, usually in the form of sample words from their native language.

A simple example of this is of the form where an English speaker would have a sound played for them of the sound /pæf/, and would be asked, 'Which of the English vowel sounds is the central vowel of this syllable most similar to?' Participants would see the following list of response words, followed by their respective IPA forms: 'kit' /kɪt/, 'dress' /dɹɛs/, 'trap' /tɹæp/, 'stop' /stɒp/, 'strut' /stɹʌt/, 'look' /lʊk/, 'fleece' /flis/, 'goat' /gɔʊt/, 'tape' /teɪp/, and 'loop' /lʊp/. More likely than not, the English native speaker would respond 'trap'.

1.2 Discrimination Tasks

An *ABX phoneme discrimination task* is a task where participants have three sound files played for them, call them A, B, and X, the participants listen to them and respond with which sound they felt was closer to X: A or B.

An example of such a task could involve playing three sound files for an English speaker participant; A: 'rush', B: 'book' and X: 'bush'. When asked which sound is more similar to X; A or B, more likely than not, the participant will respond B. In an example like this, B is the 'correct' answer, while A is 'incorrect'. In many cases, the stimuli are not real words, though these are used for ease of explanation. Results from discrimination tasks serve to tell us how easily participants find it to discriminate between the sounds A and B.

1.3 Experimental Data (Millet et al., 2021)

In both Study 1 and Study 2, we use the data from Millet et al. (2021). Their study produced experimental results from English and French speakers that participated in a phoneme identification task. The dataset includes CVC sound file stimuli of vowels from seven languages: 'twelve Brazilian Portuguese vowels ([ĩ], [i], [e], [ɛ], [ê], [ũ], [u], [ê], [ô], [o], [a], [ɔ]), seven standard German vowels ([e], [i], [ɛ], [a], [o], [ɔ], [a:]), eight Bavarian-accented (Münich) German vowels ([i:], [ɪ], [ɣ], [ʊ], [ø], [y:], [u:], [a:]), five Turkish vowels ([i], [y], [u], [ʉ], [œ]), six Estonian vowels ([i:], [ø:], [y:], [ɣ:], [æ:], [a:]), thirteen French vowels ([i], [ɛ], [e], [œ], [a], [ɔ̃], [y], [ø], [o], [u], [ɔ], [ê], [ã]), and ten English vowels ([i], [ɪ], [ɛ], [eɪ], [u], [ʊ], [ʌ], [oʊ], [æ], [ɑ])' (Millet et al., 2021, p. 662). English and French participants each saw their response options in their own native languages. For our current paper, we focus on modeling the English results.

We begin by focusing on the response data from the study, in particular, that of the English listeners. Looking at this data, we see, on average, how the participants responded to a specific stimulus. We begin with the example of [ɣ:] from Estonian. Figure 1 shows how English speakers, on average, identified [ɣ:] with respect to their native phonemes. We can see that, on average, English speakers

identified [ɜ:] as [u] most often, then [ʊ] as the second most common response, with a small proportion as [oʊ]. The other options generally received no responses.

Figure 1: Average English-listener participant's assimilation profile for Estonian [ɜ:] vowel.

For the remainder of this paper, this type of figure, showing how a speaker group identifies a specific sound, *p*, with respect to their native phonemes, will be referred to as the *assimilation profile* of *p*.

It has been documented in the literature that speakers of the same native language background tend to pattern their responses to such tasks in the same ways (Abramson & Lisker, 1970). We can see this by comparing three assimilation profiles from the data, namely Estonian [ɜ:], French [o], and Brazilian Portuguese [u]. We see from Figure 2 that on average, English speakers identify these vowels in the same way; that is, they have similar assimilation profiles. In contrast, on the right-hand side of Figure 2, we see that French speakers do not share this behaviour, as their assimilation profiles for these vowels are not the same when compared with each other.

Figure 2: Average assimilation profiles for Estonian [ɜ:], French [o], and Brazilian Portuguese [u], for both English-listener participants and French-listener participants.

In Study 1, we model the data shown in Figure 3, which shows the identification data for the English participants for all of the stimuli from Millet et al. (2021). We will do this by simulating the process of phoneme classification using a classifier.

Figure 3: Average assimilation profiles for English-listener participants, for each stimulus from the Millet et al. (2021) dataset.

1.4 Articulation Index Corpus (Wright, 2005)

This dataset contains sound files in CV and VC syllables which contrast all English vowels. For the purpose of this study, the /ɔ/ vowel was omitted to match Millet et al. (2021). They excluded this vowel from their experiment because many of their American English-speaking participants merge this vowel with /a/.

1.5 Classification Vectoriser

For the purposes of this study, we will be constructing a *classification vectoriser*, which follows the principles of *k-Nearest Neighbours* (kNN). kNN is a *classifier*, an automated system that produces a prediction for what category something is. Classifiers are built using reference data for which category labels are known, and then can be applied to future new examples, never before seen by the classifier, to assign them category labels.

kNN is a classifier which begins with reference data, which is represented as points in Cartesian space, and has a class label associated with each data point. Thus, data is first converted from its original form into representations in Cartesian space. A method which is used to convert the data in this way will be referred to as its *input representation*, for which there are a variety of different options used and being developed.

Then, for each new data point for which the class label is not known, kNN follows this series of steps:

- (1) Compute the distance between the new point and *every* point in the reference set.
- (2) Find the *k*-nearest neighbours to the new point, using some way to compute and compare distance (for example, Euclidean distance or cosine distance). Here, *k* is a constant number. We will discuss the specific *k* value chosen in a later section. The *k*-nearest neighbours are simply the *k* closest points.
- (3) Tally the class labels for each of the *k*-nearest neighbours.

(4) Finally, output the class label associated with the most tallies from the k -nearest neighbours.

To modify this procedure to make a classification vectoriser, we change step (4). Instead, we use the tallies to construct a predicted assimilation profile of that new point. To do this, we simply convert the tallies to proportions, which represent what proportion of the k -nearest neighbours are of a given phone label. For the purposes of this study, we will refer to assimilation profiles of new points which are outputs of this classifier as *classification vectors*, keeping ‘assimilation profile’ reserved only for referring to human results.

1.6 Optimal k -Value

A common heuristic for selecting the value of k in k -Nearest Neighbors is N , where N is the number of points in the reference set (Cover & Hart, 1967; Cover, 1968). This is a heuristic that is often paired with cross-validation of different k -values. In our case, different k -values made little to no difference, thus, we adhere to this, choosing $k = N$ as our final value.

1.7 Categorical Perception

As previously mentioned, humans perceive sounds in terms of their native phonemic categories, but in more recent literature, it has been suggested that we use the entire assimilation profiles of sounds to predict what phoneme they are (Levy, 2009; Gwilliams et al., 2018). This connection between how we identify sounds (their assimilation profiles) and how we discriminate between them (telling them apart) is widely known as the phenomena of Categorical Perception, which generally states that the closer two sounds are in identification, the more difficult it will be to discriminate between them, and vice versa. The behaviour of the area in between, where sounds are somewhat similar to each other in identification, is much less agreed upon in the literature. Thus, to model the effects of categorical perception, we must first model human identification experiments.

2 Study 1: Using Classification Vectors to Model Human Identification Experiments

We use a classification vectoriser of the form described above to classify English vowels. However, since modelling identification data using classification vectors has not been investigated in the literature, it is unclear what method for converting sounds into points in Cartesian space would yield the best prediction of human behaviour, if any. This leads us to the key questions we discuss in this first study: (1) Can we simulate the process of phoneme identification using a classifier? (2) Which input representation simulates the process of phoneme identification best?

To answer the first question, we look for an intuitive input representation. While we could be tempted to use formants since they are simple to convert to two-dimensional points in space, formants lack information encoding nasality, which is an important contrast in many of the world languages (and in the data from Millet et al., 2021, as well). Thus, we will choose perhaps the next intuition: some form of a spectrogram.

In considering how to represent speech audio for this purpose, we opted for the *Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficient* (MFCC) over the raw Mel filter bank representations (Mermelstein, 1976). While MF representations capture the energy present in the Mel-scale frequency bands, MFCCs go a step

further by applying a discrete cosine transform to these filter bank energies. This process decorrelates the features and emphasises the most important coefficients.

For our analysis, we use the first 13 MFCC coefficients for each sound file in the dataset, which are computed using Librosa (McFee et al., 2015). Additionally, we trimmed each sound file to only compare 65ms of the vowel portion of the CVC syllable, averaging the MFCC representations across the time dimension to end with a single 13-dimensional vector for each sound file.

To model the phoneme classification process of an English speaker, we trained a classification vectoriser (of the form described above) on the Articulation Index Corpus. For the purpose of this study, only one representative from the *caught-cot* vowel merger was kept, keeping the data balanced and matching the data from Millet et al. (2021). Moreover, similar to the process described above, the stimuli from the Articulation Index Corpus were transformed into MFCC representations, keeping 65ms of the vowel, and averaging across the time dimension to get a single 13-dimensional vector for each sound file.

To simulate the process of phoneme classification, the trained vectoriser provided classification vectors for each sound from Millet et al. (2021) data. Then, classification vectors representing the same vowels were averaged together to result in the average classification vectors for each vowel. These results are summarised in Figure 4. From the results, we see that the MFCC input representation generally follows the same pattern observed from the English listener data, but generally overpredicts the possible category responses of each vowel, and thus underpredicts how sure English listener participants are when answering. Thus, the answer to the first question is generally yes, with room for improvement.

Figure 4: Average classification vectors produced from an English trained classification vectoriser, for each stimulus from the Millet et al. (2021) dataset, computed using MFCC input representations.

To answer the second question, we compare the MFCC results with a different input representation, namely, *wav2vec 2.0* (Baevski et al., 2020). Wav2vec 2.0 is different from MFCCs as it is a trained neural network model, rather than simply a series of computations done on a sound file. Moreover, wav2vec 2.0 is widely used today in the literature instead of MFCCs, as it is often seen to self-discover the underlying phonemic structure of a language without explicitly being trained to do so. The wav2vec 2.0 model we use is pretrained in English, and we take our representations from layer 4 of the context network (for details on this architecture, see Baevski et al., 2020). Using the same method of averaging across the time dimension as discussed in the above section on MFCCs, we obtain a 768-dimensional vector for each sound file in the datasets used.

Figure 5 shows that, when simulating the process of phoneme identification using the wav2vec 2.0 representations, wav2vec 2.0 performs much closer to the English results compared to MFCCs. It

is more certain of the classifications, while also answering predominantly the same way English-listener participants did.

Figure 5: Average classification vectors produced from an English trained classification vectoriser, for each stimulus from the Millet et al. (2021) dataset, computed using wav2vec 2.0 input representations.

This process was repeated with another input representation, particularly DeepSpeech2 (Amodei et al., 2015). This representation, like wav2vec 2.0, is a model, but unlike wav2vec 2.0, it is a supervised model — meaning that in its training, it was provided with labelled data, rather than unlabelled data like wav2vec 2.0. The vectors produced by this model live in 1024-dimensional space. From Figure 6, we see that DeepSpeech2 gave similar results to wav2vec 2.0. We can quantify these differences between classification vectors from each input representation and the responses given by English-listener participants as a 70% similarity between the MFCC results and the English results, an 81% similarity for wav2vec 2.0, and a with 78% similarity DeepSpeech2. Here, similarity is measured as the Pearson correlation between the assimilation profiles and the classification vectors of a given vowel.

Figure 6: Average classification vectors produced from an English trained classification vectoriser, for each stimulus from the Millet et al. (2021) dataset, computed using DeepSpeech2 input representations.

Thus, to the second question of which input representation currently simulates the process of English phoneme identification best, our answer is wav2vec 2.0.

3 Study 2: Using Classification Vectors to Model Human Discrimination Experiments

One method to model discrimination experiments is through distances. Specifically, each sound file is converted into a point in Cartesian space using some input representation, like the ones described in the previous study. From there, for each trial in an ABX task, the distances between A and X and between B and X are compared. The difference (‘delta’) between A and X and between B and X is recorded for each trial. If this method of comparing distances is a good model of English listener responses, these deltas and whether English listeners answer correctly should be well correlated.

The process of converting sound files to points in Cartesian space and measuring distances has been investigated in the literature (Millet & Dunbar, 2022). However, using purely how similar/dissimilar input representations of a sound are does not take phonemic categories into account. I operationalise the idea of phonemic categories through classification vectors. In this study, we answer the question of whether we can simulate the process of phoneme discrimination better using classification vectors (as computed in the previous study).

Thus, in this study, we begin by converting the sound files from Millet et al. (2021) and the Articulation Index Corpus to various input representations: MFCC, wav2vec 2.0, and DeepSpeech2. We use a classification vectoriser (of the form described above) trained on the Articulation Index Corpus to produce classification vectors for each of the stimuli in the Millet et al. (2021) dataset. Then, we will simulate an ABX phoneme discrimination task by comparing the distances between the classification vectors of A and X, and of B and X. We will measure how well this method works compared to the method of computing deltas directly from the input representations of A, B, and X, by the correlations between the deltas and whether English listeners got the correct answer.

Table 1: *Pearson correlation between deltas of input representations (MFCC, wav2vec 2.0, DeepSpeech2) in an ABX trial and whether English-listener participants answered correctly in the same trial, for both conditions: Directly from input representations and using classification vector*

Input Representation	Condition	
	Directly from Input Representation	Classification Vectors
MFCC	0.517	0.649
Wav2vec 2.0	0.572	0.680
DeepSpeech2	0.672	0.714

As we can see from Table 1, across all input representations, the method of computing deltas from classification vectors outperforms the method of computing deltas directly from input representations in a statistically significant way ($p < 0.05$). Thus, we can conclude that incorporating the notion of assimilation profiles when modelling English-listener discrimination behaviour is a better representation of English-listeners’ behaviour than simply using the raw representations of the sounds.

4 Summary and Discussions

In summary, in Study 1, we demonstrate that kNN classification gives similar results to English-listener phone identification experiments, with wav2vec 2.0 doing much better than MFCC. In Study 2, we show that using classification vectors improves models of English-listener discrimination tasks, supporting the idea of categorical perception.

The assimilation profiles using a simulated model predict human behaviour remarkably well. This is surprising given that the architecture of the classification vectoriser we use is very simple.

Furthermore, the representations derived from machine learned models of speech are far better than spectral representations, presumably because they emphasise linguistically relevant information. This is true even for wav2vec 2.0, in spite of the fact that it is not trained with explicit phoneme labels.

Moreover, our measure of similarity between the classification vectors (delta) is an excellent predictor of discriminability in English-speaking listeners, much better than comparing the numerical representations directly. Not only does this strongly support the idea of categorical perception, but it also supports the proposal of Levy (2009) that the overlap in assimilation profiles forms the link between identification and discrimination in human listeners.

A limitation of this study is that we have studied only English-speaking listeners. In future work, we will extend the study to the French-speaking listeners studied by Millet et al. (2021).

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Syntax, Phylogenetics, and Language Contact

Eve Canning

University of Cambridge

Abstract. Language histories are often considered in terms of genetic relationships, which are often represented using phylogenetic trees. Traditionally, these relationships have been uncovered through the application of the comparative method to sets of cognate lexical items, with only a minor focus on morphological evidence and virtually no consideration given to syntax. More recently, computational methods have been employed for the inference of phylogenies; however, most work has focused on vocabulary cognacy. The Parametric Comparison Method (PCM; described by Longobardi & Guardiano, 2017), by contrast, uses a set of syntactic parameters which account for cross-linguistic variations to generate syntax-based phylogenies. To explore whether evidence of language contact — a secondary concern in previous PCM work — can be found in syntactic phylogenies generated using the PCM, I created a novel parametric database through the combination of Ceolin et al.’s (2021) nominal database and Baker and Roberts’ (In prep.) clausal database. I examined phylogenies generated from this database for their adherence to traditional phylogenies and for evidence of language contact leading to syntactic transfer in the histories of Celtic, Germanic, and Romance. My findings suggest that parametric syntactic phylogenies can provide evidence of language contact, and this is exemplified by a case study involving Afrikaans and English. However, contact effects are subtle and require careful examination of phylogenies and individual parameter settings. I argue that models of linguistic history, including those based on syntax, should account for language, as language contact is an essential component of the story of any speech community.

Keywords: historical linguistics; phylogenetics; syntax

1 Introduction

1.1 Issues in Linguistic Subgrouping

Traditional approaches to linguistic subgrouping have been grounded in the comparative method — see Fox (1995) for an overview — and have generally placed the greatest emphasis on evidence from the lexical-phonological domain. In particular, Campbell and Poser (2008, p. 172) note that evidence from sound changes represents ‘a staple of traditional approaches to determining language families’. This can be contrasted with what Campbell and Poser term ‘grammatical’ evidence, harder to interpret and therefore less of a staple in subgrouping endeavours. Where they do address the use of grammatical evidence, Campbell and Poser deal primarily (pp. 162-224) with morphological evidence, as opposed to evidence from syntax. This can presumably be attributed to the very sparse use of syntactic evidence in linguistic subgrouping as a whole — Clackson (2022, p. 23) notes, for instance, that ‘[i]n the Indo-European language family, little use has been made of syntactic changes for subgrouping’.

Although phylogenetic trees are undoubtedly useful, there are a number of issues concerning the relationship between reconstructed linguistic history (including phylogenies) and real but unattested linguistic history, as observed by Clackson (2022). The tree model assumes that the diversification always occurs following the split of a single speech community into multiple groups which subsequently fall out of touch. Furthermore, it assumes a single, uniform proto-language. Both of these are idealisations. The latter assumption is problematic on uniformitarian grounds (see Roberts, 2017) — there exists today no language which does not exhibit some form of social or geographic variation, and it follows that no such language existed in the past. Counterexamples to the former assumption are myriad throughout history (see, for example, Dance (2016) on contact between Old Norse and Old

English). Therefore, an approach which integrates the insights of the phylogenetic tree with an understanding of language contact is desirable.

The work of Neureiter et al. (2022) represents one attempt at this integration through the incorporation of reconstructed contact events into a computationally generated phylogenetic tree. Their work is, however, focused on the lexical domain. Transfer in the lexical domain is, however, only one of several possible outcomes of language contact. Thomason and Kaufman (1988, pp. 74-75) conceive of transfer in terms of a ‘borrowing scale’, where ‘casual contact’ is expected to lead only to lexical borrowing, but ‘[v]ery strong cultural pressure’ may enable the borrowing of any aspect of language, including major aspects of morphosyntax. Syntactic borrowing is not necessarily as easy to identify as lexical borrowing, although Bowerman (2008) attempts to enumerate some indicators. She nonetheless ‘highlights the importance of using complementary methods’ (p. 18). I argue that these complementary methods should include syntactic phylogenetic reconstruction. The comparison of syntactic phylogenies (the construction of which does not involve the removal of potential transfers) to lexical and phonological phylogenies (which do exclude suspected transfers) may reveal instances of transfer.

1.2 Parametric Comparison

Although lexical approaches to subgrouping and reconstruction are invaluable tools, they are not without limitations imposed by the ease of lexical borrowing and the nature of sound change. Therefore, the development of a method to achieve these goals with reference to other aspects of language may be a profitable goal. Longobardi, Guardiano, and their associates have worked to establish a method for syntactic comparison and reconstruction on the basis of syntactic parameters — the Parametric Comparison Method (PCM). Parametric approaches to syntax characterise cross-linguistic syntactic variation in terms of binary parameters which may have a ‘positive’ or ‘negative’ setting. Longobardi and Guardiano (2017, p. 249) suggest that because parameters are discrete variables, they ‘lend themselves to precise calculations’, enabling quantitative analyses which are not possible using the ‘classical’ comparative method. Furthermore, they argue that parameters are drawn from a universal list (although see Biberauer & Roberts, 2017) and can therefore be used to compare any group of languages, discarding the required prior knowledge of genetic affiliation inherent in many other methods of syntactic reconstruction. Note that parameters, or parameter settings, are not cognates. A parameter setting may be expressed through some element of morphology with associated phonological material (e.g., inflectional person marking on verbs), or through movement, without any overt phonological material (e.g., WH-movement). Where there is no phonological material, it is difficult to assert that a given piece of syntax (i.e., a parameter setting) has been transferred from another language — there is no clear syntactic analogue to the violations of Neogrammarian sound change regularity which mark out lexical transfers. Therefore, the discarding of suspected borrowings which forms part of the lexical-phonological comparative method is not part of the PCM.

The PCM is successful at returning phylogenies which generally resemble those constructed through traditional methods and through vocabulary-based computational methods. The results of Ceolin et al. (2021), who employ nominal parameters, include the successful identification of Indo-European within a broader sample of languages. Ceolin et al. (2020), using the same dataset, return a tree which shows a full internal articulation of Indo-European, including all conventional subgroups represented in the sample. Baker and Roberts (In prep.; henceforth B&R) apply the PCM to a set of clausal parameters, generating a phylogeny which identifies Indo-European from a broader sample of languages and generally (although not perfectly) identifies conventional subgroups within Indo-European. It remains to be seen, however, how the combination of nominal and clausal parametric data

may improve the accuracy of phylogenetic trees. No study has yet collated these data, and in doing so I will be able to provide a more complete overview of the historical signal present in syntax.

An important principle introduced by Ceolin et al. (2020, p. 14) is the ‘Homology Conjecture’. This states that ‘[s]yntactic and lexical histories provide the same evolutionary topologies once interference is equally taken into account’. This is significant because, as mentioned above, the traditional comparative method and other methods for lexical phylogeny crucially involve discarding suspected cases of linguistic transfer in the dataset. The PCM includes no such step. We should therefore expect to find no effects of language contact in lexical phylogenies (interference is ‘taken into account’ before the tree is made); and where syntactic phylogenies differ from lexical ones, we may infer that this is an instance of interference which must now be taken into account.

1.3 Research Aims

As suggested by the above, there are gaps in literature at the intersection of syntactic reconstruction, linguistic phylogenetics, and language contact. This study represents a first effort to explore these gaps by examining the topology of phylogenetic trees generated from a combined dataset of parameters relating to the nominal and clausal domains and examining them for potential evidence of language contact through the application of the Homology Conjecture. Particular attention will be paid in the wider study to the Celtic, Romance, and Germanic languages, in order to enable direct comparison with Neureiter et al. (2022), and this paper will focus on a case study within the Germanic languages.

2 Methodology

2.1 Sources of Data

The data used in this study are drawn from two sources. The first is the set of 94 nominal parameters with settings in 58 languages assembled by Ceolin et al. (2021), available in the digital supplementary information to that paper. The choice of this set of nominal parameters is discussed in §2.2. The second is the set of 87 clausal parameters with settings in 36 languages assembled by B&R. I combined these to create a database of 181 parameters in the 32 languages common to both datasets, which are as follows (note that all groupings listed below, and all subsequent references to ‘conventional’ etc. groupings, follow the groupings in Comrie, 1987).

Table 1: *The 32 languages sampled in the combined nominal/clausal parametric database*

Language	Conventional Family (Subgroup)
Afrikaans	Indo-European (Germanic)
Arabic	Semitic (Central Semitic)
Cantonese	Sino-Tibetan (Sinitic)
Danish	Indo-European (Germanic)
Dutch	Indo-European (Germanic)
English	Indo-European (Germanic)
Estonian	Uralic (Finnic)
Finnish	Uralic (Finnic)
French	Indo-European (Romance)
German	Indo-European (Germanic)

Greek	Indo-European (Hellenic)
Hebrew	Semitic (Northwest Semitic)
Hindi/Urdu	Indo-European (Indo-Iranian)
Hungarian	Uralic (Ugric)
Icelandic	Indo-European (Germanic)
Irish	Indo-European (Celtic)
Italian	Indo-European (Romance)
Japanese	Japonic
Kazakh	Turkic (Kipchak)
Korean	Koreanic
Malagasy	Austronesian (Western Malayo-Polynesian)
Mandarin	Sino-Tibetan (Sinitic)
Norwegian	Indo-European (Germanic)
Polish	Indo-European (Slavic)
Portuguese	Indo-European (Romance)
Romanian	Indo-European (Romance)
Russian	Indo-European (Slavic)
SerBo-Croatian	Indo-European (Slavic)
Slovenian	Indo-European (Slavic)
Spanish	Indo-European (Romance)
Turkish	Turkic (Oghuz)
Welsh	Indo-European (Celtic)

Note the overrepresentation of certain families in the sample; this may ‘normalise’ certain parameter settings and ‘exoticise’ those languages which display the opposite setting, even in cases where a representative survey of the world’s languages would show that this opposite setting is cross-linguistically more frequent.

In addition to the 32-language database, a separate database of the 7 Germanic, 5 Romance, and 2 Celtic languages was created. This was done to enable the creation of phylogenies involving only these three subgroups, for the sake of direct comparison to Neureiter et al. (2022).

2.2 Format of Data

The parameters represented in the dataset take the form of answers to questions such as the example below.

Table 2: Baker and Roberts’ (In prep., p. 62) diagnostic question for P_{V1}

Parameter	Diagnostic(s)
P_{V1} (VGP) Grammaticalised Person in EP(V)	Does the language show agreement for person within the clause?

A negative answer is coded as [-] and represents the ‘default’ setting of the parameter (Crisma, Guardiano & Longobardi, 2020, p. 112); a positive answer is coded as [+] and represents a non-default (usually marked) parameter setting. Crisma, Guardiano and Longobardi (2020) argue that parameters should, in theoretical models, be set wholly on the basis of positive evidence, without recourse to negative evidence. Negative parameter settings are part of the ‘initial state of the mind’ (p.112). Many

parameters are connected by implicational relationships, in which parameter Y may only be positive if parameter X is also positive. A negative setting for parameter X entails a negative setting for parameter Y. For example, B&R’s PV4 (PCV — Φ-feature checking on V) asks whether morphological agreement with the person/number of the subject is realised on V. A number of languages in the sample, however, do not show person or number agreement in the clause (they have negative settings for PV1 (VGP) and PV2 (VGN)). These languages therefore cannot have a positive setting for PV4 — they cannot realise person/number agreement with the subject on V:

- (1) *Ek werk. / Hy werk. / Ons werk.* (AFRIKAANS)
 I work / He work / We work
 ‘I work.’ / ‘He works.’ / ‘We work.’
 (Donaldson, 1993, p. 217)
 [-] P_V1 (VGP), [-] P_V2 (VGN) → [-] P_V4 (PCV)
- (1) *Rén lái le.* (MANDARIN)
 Person come PFV/CRS
 ‘The person has come.’ / ‘The people have come.’
 (Li and Thompson, 1981, p. 20)
 [-] P_V1 (VGP), [-] P_V2 (VGN) → [-] P_V4 (PCV)
 [-] P_N1 (FGM — Grammaticalised morphology)

These ‘implicational’ parameter settings which are predictable on the basis of an earlier parameter setting are coded in the database as [0]. In rare cases, an informant may be unable to determine the status of a given parameter in their language. In these cases, the parameter is coded as [?].

2.3 Methods

The phylogenetic trees in this study were assembled using two distance-based methods for phylogenetic inference. The first step in distance-based methods is the assembly of a distance matrix, which contains the pairwise Jaccard distance between every language in the dataset. This is calculated as follows, after Ceolin et al. (2020, p. 5):

$$\Delta_{\text{Jaccard}}(A, B) = \frac{(N_{\bar{+}} + N_{\pm})}{(N_{\bar{+}} + N_{\pm} + N_{++})}$$

where N_{-XY} is the number of instances where language A has parameter setting X and language B has Y. As observed in §2.1., [-] represents the default setting of the parameter, and I therefore follow Ceolin et al. in treating A/B pairings as follows.

Table 3: *The treatment of various parameter setting pairings in the calculation of pairwise distances between languages*

Pair type	Counted as
[-]/[+], [+]/[-]	Difference
[+]/[+]	Identity
[-]/[-]	Disregarded
[0]/[X], [X]/[0]	Disregarded

[?]/[X], [X]/[?] Disregarded

Once a distance matrix has been assembled, a variety of algorithms can be used to construct phylogenies. I employed two: the Unweighted Pair Group Method with Arithmetic Mean (henceforth UPGMA) and Neighbour-Joining. The UPGMA and Neighbour-Joining phylogenies were both generated using the programme NEIGHBOR. Following B&R, the UPGMA phylogenies were visualised as rooted trees using the programme DRAWGRAM, while the Neighbour-Joining phylogenies were visualised as unrooted trees using the programme DRAWTREE. All three programmes are part of the PHYLIP package (Felsenstein, 2005). See Goldstein (2020) for analysis of some advantages and drawbacks of each algorithm.

3 Results

The results of the distance calculations and subsequent phylogenetic analysis can be visually represented in a number of ways. The simplest of these is a colour-coded heatmap presentation of the distance matrices, where low distances are represented in shades of red and high distances in shades of blue, as below.

Figure 1: Heatmap visualisation of the combined nominal and clausal syntactic distances between the complete sample of 32 languages, with distances closer to the minimum of 0 in red and distances closer to the maximum of 0.744 in blue.

	English	Afrikaans	Dutch	German	Norwegian	Danish	Icelandic	French	Italian	Spanish	Portuguese	Romanian	Welsh	Irish
English	0	0.305085	0.278689	0.348485	0.3050847	0.263158	0.343284	0.446154	0.432836	0.344262	0.4	0.452055	0.305085	0.372881
Afrikaans	0.305085	0	0.278689	0.296875	0.3064516	0.266667	0.385714	0.462687	0.485714	0.446154	0.4492754	0.450704	0.476923	0.53125
Dutch	0.278689	0.278689	0	0.15873	0.25	0.224138	0.289855	0.338462	0.343284	0.338462	0.3529412	0.361111	0.393939	0.4375
German	0.348485	0.296875	0.15873	0	0.2698413	0.274194	0.231884	0.352941	0.333333	0.333333	0.3188406	0.295775	0.393939	0.396825
Norwegian	0.305085	0.306452	0.25	0.269841	0	0.186441	0.257576	0.387097	0.390625	0.377049	0.4	0.338235	0.435484	0.423729
Danish	0.263158	0.266667	0.224138	0.274194	0.1864407	0	0.292308	0.403226	0.380952	0.393443	0.40625	0.38806	0.435484	0.47541
Icelandic	0.343284	0.385714	0.289855	0.231884	0.2575758	0.292308	0	0.405405	0.4	0.318841	0.3287671	0.3625	0.323529	0.363636
French	0.446154	0.462687	0.338462	0.352941	0.3870968	0.403226	0.405405	0	0.166667	0.238806	0.2205882	0.283784	0.38806	0.349206
Italian	0.432836	0.485714	0.343284	0.333333	0.390625	0.380952	0.4	0.166667	0	0.208955	0.1641791	0.232877	0.405797	0.363636
Spanish	0.344262	0.446154	0.338462	0.333333	0.3770492	0.393443	0.318841	0.238806	0.208955	0	0.109375	0.28	0.318182	0.378788
Portuguese	0.4	0.449275	0.352941	0.318841	0.4	0.40625	0.328767	0.220588	0.164179	0.109375	0	0.289474	0.343284	0.338462
Romanian	0.452055	0.450704	0.361111	0.295775	0.3382353	0.38806	0.3625	0.283784	0.232877	0.28	0.2894737	0	0.405405	0.4
Welsh	0.305085	0.476923	0.393939	0.393939	0.4354839	0.435484	0.323529	0.38806	0.405797	0.318182	0.3432836	0.405405	0	0.166667
Irish	0.372881	0.53125	0.4375	0.396825	0.4237288	0.47541	0.363636	0.349206	0.363636	0.378788	0.3384615	0.4	0.166667	0

Figure 2: Heatmap visualisation of the combined nominal and clausal syntactic distances between the sample of 14 Celtic, Germanic, and Romance languages, with distances closer to the minimum of 0 in red and distances closer to the maximum of 0.531 in blue.

The UPGMA algorithm produced a phylogeny, visualised as a rooted tree using DRAWGRAM, which in large part agrees with traditional linguistic groupings. This is shown in Figure 3. The UPGMA tree

generated from the restricted Celtic/Germanic/Romance sample did not differ from this phylogeny, and has been omitted for space.

Figure 3: UPGMA phylogeny from the combined nominal and clausal syntactic distances between the complete sample of 32 languages.

In the non-rooted tree produced using the Neighbour-Joining algorithm and visualised using DRAWTREE, the Indo-European, Semitic, Turkic, Uralic, and Sinitic families all emerge. Celtic forms a subgroup with Germanic, although there is a large distance between the groups. Slavic and Greek form a subgroup with Romance, and Hindi/Urdu is the most peripheral member of Indo-European. Turkic clusters with the ‘eastern’ languages of the sample rather than with Uralic, as it did in the UPGMA phylogeny. This is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: *Neighbour-Joining phylogeny from the combined nominal and clausal syntactic distances between the complete sample of 32 languages.*

In the restricted-sample unrooted tree, Celtic, Germanic, and Romance form three distinct groups. Celtic has a long branch length and is distinct from the other two subgroups. Germanic and Romance show approximately the same branch length, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: *Neighbour-Joining phylogeny from the combined nominal and clausal syntactic distances between the sample of 14 Celtic/Germanic/Romance languages.*

4 Case Study

Although the results presented in Section 3 are, on the whole, in line with the findings of established work on linguistic subgrouping, there are a number of discrepancies. Among the most notable of these is the tendency of Afrikaans and English to form a unique subgroup (seen most clearly in Figures 3 and 5). This is at odds with the findings of both computational phylogenetic studies employing lexical data (Chang et al., 2015; Neureiter et al., 2022), which group Afrikaans with languages such as Dutch and Flemish, and traditional assessments of Germanic subgrouping such as Hawkins (1987, p. 68), who refers simply to ‘Dutch (including Afrikaans)’. The topology of the syntactic tree diverges from that of lexical trees; therefore, the Homology Conjecture suggests that there are interference effects which must be taken into account.

The histories of both Afrikaans and English are known to involve extensive language contact, probably more extensive than any other Germanic language in the sample. Van der Wouden and Muysken (2012, p. 3) outline the contact history of Afrikaans, starting in the 17th century, which includes contact between Dutch, Khoekhoe (spoken by indigenous populations in the Cape province), Malagasy, Malay, Indo-Portuguese Creole (all three spoken by slaves brought to the colony), and English (following the occupation of the colony by the British). Contact in the history of English,

meanwhile, occurs over a longer time period, involving the Celtic varieties present in the British Isles upon the arrival of Germanic speakers, the Old Norse of 9th-11th century settlers, and Norman French following the invasion of 1066.

In order to examine whether the effects of language contact are causing Afrikaans and English to diverge from the rest of Germanic in the syntactic phylogenies of Section 3, it will be useful to identify exactly which parameter settings distinguish the languages. The following seven parameters differ in Afrikaans and/or English compared to the majority setting in Germanic.

Table 4: *Notable points of variation in the parameter settings of Afrikaans and/or English compared to the rest of the Germanic languages in the sample.*

Parameter	Afrikaans	English	Other Germanic languages
P _V 13 (TCV — Tense-checking V)	[-]	[+]	[+]
P _V 30 (NNI — Null prohibitive)	[-]	[-]	[+] except for Danish
P _V 39 (AXS — Auxiliary split)	[-]	[-]	[+] in Dutch, German, and Danish
P _V 68 (DAT — Dative Case)	[-]	[-]	[+] except for Norwegian and Danish
P _V 77 (QCV — Q-checking V)	[+]	[-]	[-]
P _V 83 (NMU — Multiple negation)	[+]	[-]	[-]
P _V 86 (INC — Noun incorporation)	[+]	[-]	[-]

I will briefly examine each of these parameters in turn to determine whether the divergent settings of Afrikaans/English can be attributed to language contact. Note that PV77 (QCV — ‘Are interrogatives marked by bound morphology on V?’) has been greyed out in Table 4 because it was found to be an error in the dataset (Biberauer, p.c.). Afrikaans does not show any bound morphology on V, including in interrogatives. However, the correction of this parameter setting did not lead to any changes in the trees generated from the dataset.

PV13 (TCV — Tense-checking V) asks whether Tense ‘may [...] be realised just on V’ (B&R, p. 65). Afrikaans is the only language in the sample to have a [-] setting for this parameter. Past and future meaning are both expressed periphrastically:

(3) Ek het gewerk. (AFRIKAANS)

I have worked

'I worked.' / 'I have worked.' / 'I had worked.'

(4) Ek sal dit doen as ek tyd het.

I will it do if I time have

'I'll do it if I have the time.'

Donaldson (1993, pp. 217, 235)

[-] PV13

The negative setting of this parameter is clearly an Afrikaans innovation — Tense on V was found in Middle Dutch (van Kerckvoorde, 1992, p. 89) as well as in modern Dutch. The lack of morphological tense expression on the lexical verb is reminiscent of the invariant verb forms of many creole languages

(as described by Holm, 2012, p. 174). De Kleine (1997) argues that the loss of the morphology expressing tense on the verb, and the taking over of this function by periphrastic constructions, suggest significant contact-induced restructuring in the history of Afrikaans.

PV30 (NNI — Null prohibitive) asks whether bare or non-finite verbs in a negative context may have imperative force. Compare the following sentences in Italian and Dutch ([+] PV30) to their English ([-] PV30) translation:

- | | | | |
|-----|-------------|-----------------|-----------|
| (5) | <i>Non</i> | <i>fumare.</i> | (ITALIAN) |
| | NEG | smoke.INF | |
| | | ‘Do not smoke.’ | |
| (6) | <i>Niet</i> | <i>roken.</i> | (DUTCH) |
| | NEG | smoke.INF | |
| | | ‘Do not smoke.’ | |

The positive setting for this parameter in the broader Indo-European language family is widespread, but does not characterise any particular subgroup: [+] and [-] settings are found for this parameter in every well-represented Indo-European subgroup. The negative settings in English and Afrikaans therefore probably need not be explained through language contact.

PV39 (AXS — Auxiliary split) determines whether auxiliaries in periphrastic constructions vary on the basis of some predictable factor other than voice (for example, a HAVE/BE split periphrastic perfect constructions). The only languages with a positive setting for this parameter are Dutch, German, Danish, French, Italian, and Romanian. These languages are associated with the core of Haspelmath’s (2001) Standard Average European (SAE) Sprachbund. The presence of a ‘HAVE-perfect’, a construction which commonly exhibits an auxiliary split in these languages, is one of Haspelmath’s (1998) 11 defining features of SAE. Its development and/or retention, and the retention of a HAVE/BE split in many languages of Western Europe may be a result of sustained language contact. However, the split was lost in English, another language in the core SAE area. The use of *be* as a perfect auxiliary persisted in English as late as the 19th century (McFadden, 2017; van Gelderen, 2014, p. 219). McFadden and Alexiadou (2010) do not relate the loss of the construction (which they do not analyse as structurally identical to the HAVE-perfect) to language contact, but to language-internal factors. Conradie (2015) does not directly relate the loss of the BE-perfect in Afrikaans to language contact, instead linking it to factors such as the loss of the preterite, creating a less direct association with language contact.

PV68 (DAT — Dative Case) concerns the presence or absence of a dative case assigned to Goals/Recipients in double object constructions. In Afrikaans and English, the distinction between accusative and dative has been lost even in the pronominal systems (where it is retained marginally in, e.g., French), which instead distinguish only between subject (e.g., English *he*, Afrikaans *hy*) and object/oblique (e.g., English *him*, Afrikaans *hom*). Already in Old English there was significant syncretism between the accusative and the dative in, for example, the declension of weak nouns, as well as in the personal pronouns:

Table 5: *Selected Old English personal pronouns in the accusative and dative, after Mitchell and Robinson (2011, pp. 18-19)*

	Singular		Plural	
	ACC	DAT	ACC	DAT
1	<i>mē, mec</i>	<i>mē</i>	<i>ūs, ūsic</i>	<i>ūs</i>

2	<i>þē, þēc</i>	<i>þē</i>	<i>ēow, ēowic</i>	<i>ēow</i>
3	<i>hine (M)</i>	<i>him (M)</i>	<i>hīe, hī</i>	<i>hīm, heom</i>

Phonological changes such as the merger and loss of final /m/ and /n/ (Lass, 1992, p. 65) and the loss of final /ə/ (Lass, 1992, p.79) and analogical pressures eventually led to the loss of a distinct dative in English. Some of this paradigmatic simplification may be attributable to contact with speakers of Old Norse (see, e.g., van Gelderen, 2014, p. 98). The input system for Afrikaans probably already had minimal distinct dative marking. The Middle Dutch accusative and dative personal pronouns, for example, were formally identical except in the neuter singular (van Kerckvoorde, 1992, pp. 65, 75). Language contact in the history of Afrikaans may have encouraged the loss of a distinct dative, but this was clearly already underway, and the distinction is marginal in modern Dutch.

PV83 (NMU — Multiple negation) concerns whether negative concord is permitted in a language. Afrikaans is the only modern Germanic language which allows negative concord:

(7) *Hy is nie moeg nie.* (AFRIKAANS)

He is NEG tired NEG

'He is not tired.'

(8) *Hy is nooit moeg nie.*

He is never tired NEG

'He is never tired.'

Biberauer and Zeijlstra (2012, pp. 355-356)

[+] P_v83 (NMU)

Compare to English:

(9) *He is never not tired.*

In standard varieties this requires the positive reading 'he is always tired'. There are two theories regarding the rise of multiple negation in Afrikaans, reflecting arguments about the overall origins of Afrikaans. Either it is descended from a feature of 17th century dialectal Dutch, or it was taken over from a Dutch-based creole or pidgin spoken in the Cape province. The frequency of negative concord in creole languages is noted by Holm (2012, pp. 195-197), although he notes that these structures are often permissible in source languages. Den Besten (1986) rejects the notion that Afrikaans multiple negation is descended from dialectal Dutch, and endorses the contact argument.

PV88 (INC — Noun incorporation) asks 'May nominal arguments incorporate into the verb?' (B&R, p. 81). This is a feature particularly characteristic of polysynthetic languages, and Afrikaans is the only language in the sample with a positive setting for PV88. Non-finite verbs are briefly discussed in Ponelis (1993, p. 579) Bare nouns may be productively incorporated into (only) non-finite verbs:

(10) *Ons gaan DVDkyk.* (AFRIKAANS)

We go DVD-watch

'We are going to watch a DVD.'

[+] P_v88 (INC)

This is distinct from:

- (11) Ons gaan 'n DVD kyk.
 We go a DVD watch
 'We are going to watch a DVD.'

Barrie and Spreng (2009) argue that noun incorporation may be found in German, and Booij (2009) argues for 'quasi-incorporation' in Dutch. Basilico (2016) analyses a similar construction in Frisian, which allows not only non-finite but also finite verbs to be formed in this way. He argues, however, that this construction should be analysed as a 'more typologically appropriate instance of synthetic compounding' rather than as true noun incorporation. This suggests that the [-] settings for this parameter in Germanic languages such as German and Dutch are to some degree a question of analysis, and the construction's presence in Afrikaans is not necessarily the result of language contact (although closer examination of the relative productivity/frequency of such constructions in Afrikaans vs. German, Dutch, etc., may reveal differences which would require explanation).

Nonetheless, many of the parameter settings which set English and Afrikaans apart from the other Germanic languages can be related to the intensive contact which these languages have undergone throughout their histories. While this case study draws upon (more-or-less) known instances of language contact, it suggests that divergences between syntactic phylogenies and lexical ones truly can be indicative of interference arising from contact.

5 Conclusion

The case study of Afrikaans and English presented above showcases the potential of the PCM as a method for exploring potential instances of language contact and its effects. It is clear, however, that syntactic phylogenies can serve only as a signpost or rough guide towards contact events, and the researcher cannot be absolved of the need for careful, context-sensitive, fine-grained work. While the 'headline' aspect of the PCM is its use in generating phylogenies, in light of the above it should also be recognised that much power lies in having a set of cross-linguistically comparable syntactic parameters, which enables work such as that in Section 4.

Why, however, does it matter whether we can incorporate language contact into models of linguistic history? In attempting to construct phylogenies for the languages of the world, we are implicitly attempting to construct narratives about our origins — and the origins of others. A model of linguistic divergence which takes the form of a binary branching tree suggests a narrative in which peoples became sharply differentiated from one another, any similarities between them the relic of a distant shared past. This narrative is, as discussed in Section 1.1, untrue. A model of syntactic phylogeny and reconstruction which accepts the notion of syntactic transfer and seeks out instances of language contact promotes a conceptualisation of human history which is less rigidly divided and more full of collaboration, conquest, and all other kinds of contact.

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Exploring ChatGPT’s Capacity for Modal Subordination Via Discourse Representation Theory

Chunxi Luo, Diya Goel
University of Edinburgh

Abstract. The inherent ambiguity of language presents a challenge to natural language understanding, with modal subordination being one such scenario. The scope of modals, especially those that codify certainty and possibility, gives language the ability to express hypothetical worlds through basic modal logic. This paper will compare the human understanding of modal subordination using Discourse Representation Theory, with the capacity of ChatGPT 3.5 to understand such ambiguity. This is done by asking ChatGPT 3.5 to complete tasks that test its ability to resolve modal subordination, including but not limiting to asking the existence of a discourse referent, and choosing true propositions given a modal scenario. Our results will demonstrate that ChatGPT 3.5 tends to follow the behaviour of modal subordination in clear-cut cases per Discourse Representation Theory, but falls short when pragmatic elements are introduced, or when there exist two modalities.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; modal subordination; Discourse Representation Theory

1 Introduction

The inherent ambiguity of language presents a challenge to natural language understanding, with modal subordination being one such scenario. The scope of modals, especially those that codify certainty and possibility, gives language the ability to express hypothetical worlds through basic modal logic. This is crucial in languages, as this allows us to reason with hypotheticals, which coincides with one of Hockett’s design features of communication (Hockett & Hockett, 1960).

With the rise of Large Language Models (LLMs), one question arises: can LLMs process language with the same rate of efficiency and accuracy as humans? A part of the answer relies on the capacity of LLMs to process and reasonably function within hypothetical spaces. We have chosen modal subordination as the avenue for exploring this within ChatGPT 3.5, a popular LLM. This paper will thus argue that ChatGPT in particular does not exhibit the same capacity as humans when processing modal subordination utterances, by comparing the human understanding of modal subordination using Discourse Representation Theory, with the capacity of ChatGPT 3.5 to understand such ambiguity, through probing techniques that are inspired by previous papers exploring the capacities of LLMs (Chatterjee & Schockaert, 2023).

2 Theoretical Background

Dynamic semantics is a particular branch of semantic theory that expands on static semantics, by allowing scenarios to be updated with new information as the discourse progresses. One of the earliest forms of dynamic semantics is Discourse Representation Theory (DRT: Kamp, 1981). This section will give a brief overview of DRT and how it can be applied to resolving the ambiguity of modal subordination.

2.1 Discourse Representation Theory

Discourse Representation Theory (DRT) is a method for keeping track of utterances in discourse. Each new utterance either introduces new characters known as “discourse referents”, or updates the descriptions of the stage and the relations between the discourse referents.

DRT expands on the truth-conditional meaning approach to account for pragmatic influences, and allows for formal semantics to deal with phenomena such as scope ambiguity, donkey anaphora and, as discussed below, modal subordination.

Below, we will give an example of DRT at work. Consider this set of utterances:

- (1) John has a cat.
- (2) It is black.

The first sentence introduces two discourse referents – John and a cat, and expresses a relation of ownership from John to the cat. This is expressed symbolically as below; the discourse referents are marked at the top, whilst the predicates that describe the scenario are detailed underneath the referents.

x	y
John(x)	
cat(y)	
have(x, y)	

In more detail, this sentence introduces two discourse referents into the scenario – x and y . x is given the property “John(x)”, y is given the property “cat(y)”, and the relation between the two referents is expressed using “have(x, y)”.

The second sentence starts with an “it”. This anaphora can be resolved by looking at the referents and their properties. Since “it” signifies that the referent must be an animal, and only “ y ” among the current referents satisfies this condition, the sentence thus updates the property of y . This is expressed as below.

x	y
John(x)	
cat(y)	
have(x, y)	
black(y)	

These boxes are called “Discourse Representation Structure” (DRS: Kamp, 1981). One can think of them as scopes. This is exemplified by the following example.

- (3) Every student takes a test.

This sentence corresponds to two readings, and thus we can craft two different DRSs. The first reading is narrow scope, in which the universal quantifier scopes over “student”, indicating that there is one test that every student takes. This is represented as follows:

The narrow scope meant that there is only one discourse referent introduced in the main DRS — the test, since that is the only concrete individual in the sentence. Thus, referent t is introduced and given the property “test(t)”.

To proceed, the narrow scope reading can be rephrased as “If there is a student, they will take the test.” This can be done by introducing two new DRSs, one corresponding to the antecedent and one to the consequent.

The antecedent scenario “there is a student” can be constructed per the process of the first example. Since this scenario is a hypothetical that exists within realm of the whole sentence, we put that DRS inside the main DRS. The consequent scenario “they take the test” does not introduce any new referents; thus, the top part of the DRS remains blank, and the relation between the referent introduced in the antecedent and the main DRS is expressed with “take(x,t)”. These scenarios are linked by using the implication symbol.

The wide scope — where the universal quantifier scopes over the entire sentence — is different from the narrow scope, as there are no referents introduced in the main sentence. This is because there are no concrete individuals. The full DRS is expressed as follows:

The scope ambiguity thus is expressed through the existence of discourse referents in either the main DRS or the consequent DRS.

The example above shows that DRSs can be combined with logic symbols to express complex meaning. This will prove crucial to express modal subordination in the next section.

2.2 Modal Subordination

Modal subordination refers to the phenomenon where modality carries over across sentences (Roberts, 1989). For example, consider the following sentences:

- (4) Jack might eat an ice-cream.
- (5) It will be chocolate.

Here, the first sentence indicates that the utterance “eat an ice-cream” and the corresponding discourse referents is inside a “possible world”; in other words, it is enclosed in the possibility modality. This possibility carries to the next sentence; though normally the modal “will” signifies certainty or future, here it extends in the meaning into “if Jack actually did eat an ice-cream, that ice-cream will have to be

chocolate”. By itself, sentence (5) does not carry the modality of possibility; however, the combination of (4) and (5) changes this.

We can explain this phenomenon by using modal logic symbols in DRT. Below, the \square will represent “certainty”, while the \diamond will represent “possibility”. Sentence (4) introduces the referent “Jack” in the common ground. However, since the predicate “eat an ice-cream” is under the scope of the possibility modality, the “ice-cream” referent is being introduced not in the common ground, but in the “world”, or DRS, inside the possibility modality. This is represented as follows:

Sentence (5) thus exhibits modal subordination by simply updating the DRS inside the scope of the possibility modality, as follows:

3 Methodology

In order to investigate if ChatGPT 3.5 can correctly identify and process modal subordination, we crafted several scenarios, detailed below, that test its capacity of doing so.

3.1 Existence Scenario

This is the simplest of the four scenarios that will be tested on ChatGPT 3.5 is the “existence scenario”. This tests whether or not ChatGPT 3.5 knows where to instantiate new discourse referents. This is showcased in the following example:

- (6) There is a garden where only two types of flowers bloom, roses and tulips. It’s said that “There may be a rose in the garden. It will blossom under the full moon.” It is now the full moon. What will happen in the garden?

The correct analysis of this scenario is as follows: The sentence fragment “In a garden where only two types of flowers bloom, roses and tulips”, the common ground DRS is introduced with a new referent: m , referring to the garden. The next sentence, “there may be a rose in the garden”, updates a new DRS inside the common ground DRS, and the new discourse referent “ x ” — the “rose” — is instantiated

inside the modality DRS instead of the common ground DRS. This is because one cannot discern that there is indeed a rose in the garden; instead, only the possibility is being discussed. The following sentence “It will blossom under the full moon” thus creates a conditional shown in the common ground DRS, and the final sentence “It is now the full moon” updates the common ground DRS with the $\text{fullmoon}(m)$ property, meaning “there is a full moon in m ”.

There will be 20 questions that follow this pattern.

Figure 1: *Existence scenario DRS.*

Thus, if ChatGPT 3.5 instantiates new discourse referents correctly, the answer should be “There is not enough information,” as no roses are instantiated in the common ground DRS. Otherwise, there is a high probability that ChatGPT 3.5 incorrectly updated the new referent in the common ground DRS.

3.2 Scope Scenario

The “scope scenario” aims to test whether or not ChatGPT 3.5 recognizes that the additional information does not update the common ground DRS, but instead the DRS inside the scope of the modality operator. The following example shows an instance of the prompt used to test this behaviour:

- (7) Imagine a universe in which there are two bookstores only: Blackwells and Waterstones.
Now, consider this utterance: “John has bought a book. If the book is from Blackwells, then the book must be a mystery novel. The book would be red.”

Given this utterance, if the book is from Waterstones, is it red?

The correct analysis of this scenario is as follows: The first paragraph sets up the common ground DRS, and instantiates the discourse referents b (Blackwells), w (Waterstones), and their respective identities. The next utterance “John has bought a book” introduces two more referents j (John), x (book) and their relationships. Continuing to look at the scenario, the next utterance updates the DRS with a conditional.

The next utterance “The book would be red” is crucial. A person that correctly interprets this scenario needs to realize that this is talking about the hypothetical scenario in which the book is from Blackwells, and thus the property of “the book is red” should be updated in the consequent DRS of the conditional, instead of the common ground DRS. This is why, after updating the common ground DRS with the information that “the book is from Waterstones” from the question, the correct answer is “There is not enough information.”, as there is no indication shown in the DRS about the book’s colour when it is from Waterstones.

Figure 2: *Scope scenario DRS.*

If a person updated the information of “the book is red” in the wrong scope, i.e. at the common ground DRS, then they would answer incorrectly, saying “Yes, the book is red”. Thus, this shows that these types of questions are adequate in testing whether or not ChatGPT can update information in the right scope, when faced with a modal subordination construction.

There will be 20 questions that follow this pattern.

3.3 Double Modality

The “double modality scenario” aims to test whether or not ChatGPT 3.5 can process two modalities in a stream of utterances that exhibit modal subordination correctly. The following example shows an instance of the prompt used to test this behaviour:

- (8) Consider this utterance: “Kevin will bake a cake. It could be chocolate.”
 Which of the following is possible?
 (a) After some time, Kevin baked a chocolate cake.
 (b) There isn’t a time where Kevin baked a cake.
 (c) After some time, Kevin baked a vanilla cake.

The correct analysis is as follows: The first utterance states a necessity modal DRS, and thus the common ground DRS is updated as such. The second utterance updated the common ground DRS with the conditional expressed through modal subordination. In this scenario, the necessity operator means that it is necessary that Kevin will bake a cake some point in time, thus (b) is incorrect. As for (a) and (c), both should be possible, as the consequent of the conditional in the common ground DRS is only a possibility modal.

A wrong analysis can occur if the analyser did not correctly recognize that there is another modality outside of the modal subordination, or that this modality does not interact with the conditional created through modal subordination. There will be 22 questions that follow this pattern.

Figure 3: Double modality DRS.

3.4 Pragmatics Scenario

The “pragmatics scenario” aims to test whether or not ChatGPT 3.5 can process deontic modality in the framework of an ideal world, instead of the real world. The following example shows an instance of the prompt used to test this behaviour:

- (9) Consider this utterance: “Employees must attend the mandatory training session. It could enhance their skills.” In an ideal world where everyone follows the rules, which of the following is possible?
- (a) Alfred attended the training session and enhanced his skills.
 - (b) Alfred did not attend the training session and enhanced his skills.
 - (c) Alfred attended the training session and did not enhance his skills.
 - (d) Alfred did not attend the training session and did not enhance his skills.

The analysis is the same as the previous section. The crucial idea that an analyser needs to realize is that though the modality expressed here is deontic, the prompt is asking the analyser to analyse this case in the ideal world where everyone follows the rules. Thus, choice (a) and (c) are the only possible ones.

An analyser that cannot reason in a given framework, in this case the ideal world, will wrongly suggest that all four options are possible.

There will be 20 questions that follow this pattern.

Figure 4: Pragmatics scenario DRS.

4 Results

4.1 Existence Scenario

Table 1: *Results of existence scenario questions.*

	Right Conclusion	Wrong Conclusion
Right Logic	18	0
Wrong Logic	2	0

The table above shows the result of the existence scenario questions. All questions are answered correctly by ChatGPT 3.5, and taking in account of the probabilistic nature of ChatGPT 3.5, there is a high probability that ChatGPT 3.5 did indeed process where it should instantiate new discourse referents in the DRS correctly.

4.2 Scope Scenario

Table 2: *Results of scope scenario questions.*

	Right Conclusion	Wrong Conclusion
Right Logic	15	0
Wrong Logic	5	0

The table above shows the result of the scope scenario questions. All questions are answered correctly by ChatGPT 3.5, and taking in account the probabilistic nature of ChatGPT 3.5, there is a high probability that ChatGPT 3.5 did indeed “understand” where to update new information in the DRS correctly. However, we do see a decrease in logic correctness when comparing this to the existence scenario above, though again this can be considered variation due to the probabilistic nature of ChatGPT.

4.3 Double Modality Scenario

The table above shows the result of the double modality scenario questions. Here, one can see that ChatGPT is now having problems in processing two modals in the context of modal subordination.

Table 3: *Results of double modality scenario questions.*

	Right Conclusion	Wrong Conclusion
Right Logic	4	12
Wrong Logic	1	5

Only five out of 22 questions are answered correctly.

After an analysis of the wrong answers, we have discovered that the most common mistake that ChatGPT has done is modal substitution — that is, substituting a necessity modal operator with a possibility one, or vice versa. This suggests that ChatGPT may have wrongly concluded that in the DRS framework, two modalities will affect each other.

4.4 Pragmatics Scenario

Table 4: *Results of pragmatic scenario questions.*

	Right Conclusion	Wrong Conclusion
Right Logic	0	0
Wrong Logic	1	19

The table above shows the result of the pragmatics scenario questions. As evidenced from results above, one can see that ChatGPT almost always ignored the limitation to reason in the ideal world “where everyone follows the rules”, and instead preferred to reason in the framework of the real world.

5 Discussion

From our experiments, it can be seen that though ChatGPT can correctly analyse basic modality scenarios with one modal operation, it fails at handling more complex modality scenarios, as well as having trouble in interpreting modality situations in the established universe the user has given it.

What this implies is that ChatGPT may have trouble in processing more complex hypothetical scenarios, as seen from the third set of questions, or a blatant refusal of considering hypothetical universes, as seen from the fourth set of questions. While the latter might be preferable in some contexts, this still shows the possibility that ChatGPT cannot properly reason hypothetical utterances in the framework of other hypothetical universes that are different from the real world.

If ChatGPT can be said to understand languages, it must be able to process and analyse complex hypothetical scenarios. Our research suggests that this goal has not been reached yet.

This paper is an attempt to contribute to reasonable and explainable Natural Language Processing (NLP), or explainable AI (XAI), from a linguistics perspective. Many attempts at XAI require a foundation in computer science, and often times ways to dissect how AI interprets language from a perspective other than computer science is ignored. Through our research, we have demonstrated a possible way for linguistics, specifically semantics, to contribute more to the development of XAI and explainable NLP processes.

Limitations of our research exist. ChatGPT is constantly learning and evolving, and due to financial limitations, we cannot feasibly do this experiment in ChatGPT 4 or later versions. It would be an interesting avenue to take to compare diachronically if ChatGPT improved in reasoning in hypothetical scenarios. Another avenue that could be explored is synchronous comparisons. Due to time limitations, we are not able to compare results from different large language models (LLMs). To reiterate, it would be an interesting direction to take for future research, to compare different LLMs in terms of their capacity in reasoning hypothetical scenarios.

6 Conclusion

We have shown that there is non-trivial evidence that suggests ChatGPT cannot properly process hypothetical scenarios through probing using scenarios that used modal subordination structures. Evidence has supported our thesis, in that though ChatGPT can process simple scenarios involving one modal, scenarios more complex than that will run into logical errors or inconsistencies.

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A Linguistic Analysis of the Borderscape: Signs of Migration on the French-Italian Border

Alessandra Terranova
University of Edinburgh

Abstract. Linguistic landscapes provide us with a valuable insight into linguistic diversity, language barriers, boundaries, and the link between language use and identity, particularly in politically contested or border areas. This study explores such borderscapes by looking at linguistic signs of migration in two areas of the French-Italian border, along the mountain paths between Ventimiglia and Menton and between Clavière and Briançon. The primary data source is Luca Prestia's photography project 'Beyond the border. Migration and multilingual signs at European borderscapes' (Prestia and Faloppa, 2022), supplemented by sources such as activist media, online newspapers, and street-level images captured on Google Street View. I will analyse the signs both quantitatively and qualitatively, following the taxonomy proposed by Spolsky and Cooper (1991). Moreover, by applying Scollon and Scollon's (2003) Geosemiotics framework, this project aims to go beyond quantifying the number of languages: signs can only be understood when related to their placement in a social and cultural context. The signs come from a variety of sources such as activists, migrants, and organisations, and are directed towards multiple viewers: the people migrating, the authorities limiting their freedom of movement, the drivers along the roads they cross, and the wider society they interact with. By applying a precise framework such as the one introduced by Scollon & Scollon (2003) may lend us a new way to look at these borders and at the multiple human and social dynamics shaping their Linguistic Landscape, where multilingualism is a possible mean to overcome cultural boundaries.

Keywords: semiotics; sociolinguistics; linguistic landscapes; multilingualism

1 Introduction

Linguistic landscapes provide us with a valuable insight into linguistic diversity, language barriers, boundaries, and the link between language use and identity. The role of language in the negotiation of power dynamics, agencies, and identities becomes particularly central in politically and socially contested areas (Themistocleous, 2020), multi-ethnic and multilingual centres, or in border zones along migrant routes (Faloppa, 2023).

This study considers borderscapes as a fluid zone of multifaceted encounters and relationships and explores them by looking at linguistic signs of migration in two areas of the French-Italian border, in particular along the mountain paths between Ventimiglia and Menton and between Clavière and Briançon. This attempt at a sociolinguistic analysis of the borderscape through a linguistic landscape (LL) approach shows its whole potential — and complexity — when confronted with the different codes and multiple human and social dynamics that exist and interact around borders (Faloppa, 2020).

2 Background

Linguistic Landscape literature has studied areas along borders, such as the border between coastal cities in France and Italy (Tufi & Blackwood, 2016), Greek and Turkish Cyprus (Themistocleous, 2019), and between urban and rural areas of Hong Kong (Militello et al., 2023), and it has recognised the complexity of such landscapes.

In these dynamics, Linguistic Landscapes play a significant role, and their investigation can offer us an insight into language use and identity, and the language barriers and boundaries that exist alongside — but often do not coincide with — geopolitical boundaries (Landry & Bourhis, 1997). Such a study can lead to a deeper understanding of sociolinguistic stratification and multilingual interactions, exemplifying the linguistic diversity that top-down language policies and discourses may not take into account, language conflict, and cultural mediation.

Borders and border zones in relation to migration phenomena exist on a both very concrete and symbolic level, where discursively framed borders serve as a powerful narrative mechanism, and the border is seen as an imaginative place, a “process of bordering” (Vaughan-Williams, 2015, p. 6), which furthers the exclusion or — more rarely — inclusion of bodies and voices (Faloppa, 2020). Applying the concept of borderscapes, initially intended by Appadurai (Appadurai, 1996) as an area that overcomes the idea of clear-cut national territories and is instead shaped by transnational flows, to Linguistic Landscape research can provide new perspectives from a multicultural and multilingual angle, and it can challenge dynamics of othering, inclusion, and exclusion (Faloppa, 2023).

This project focuses on the signs found on the migration routes that intersect Ventimiglia (the last Italian town before the French border) and the Côte d’Azur, and that follow the mountain paths between Clavière and Briançon, in the touristic Hautes-Alpes (see Appendix D). When in 2015 France unilaterally suspended the Schengen treaty to deal with the increased number of migrants crossing the Italian-French border, these areas, crucial points for migrants transiting through Italy and trying to reach Central Europe, became insurmountable barriers on the French side, but fragile and busy borderscapes in the Italian sections.

These border zones, where one could be stuck for weeks, months, waiting for the border to be reopened, became populated with signs: indexical, like the objects left on the paths; iconic, such as a map of the border sketched on a leaflet (Figure A.1); and symbolic, such as the graffiti on the pillars of a viaduct (Figure B.7) or the signboard from an activist organisation (Figure B.3). These border areas show a multilayered landscape of signs, from the top-down street signs in French and Italian, depending on which side of the border they appear on, to the bottom-up signs created by political activists, volunteer organisations, locals, and migrants. An analysis of these signs can enable researchers to explore how written public signs contribute to the creation of communities, complex identities, and a sense of belonging (Themistocleous, 2020).

3 Method

The idea for this study, and the primary source of data, resides in the photography by Luca Prestia for the project ‘Beyond the border: Migration and multilingual signs at European borderscapes’ (Prestia & Faloppa, 2022). His photos appear quite logical and not over-emphatic. They try to capture details — often linguistic — that would have otherwise been left behind, and collect traces of passages, presences, and interactions.

The rest of the data used to construct the Linguistic Landscape in this study was collected through photographic stills available on the internet, from sources such as activist media and online newspapers, and from street-level images captured on Google Street View. While this approach is different from traditional LL fieldwork, the diversity of sources as a whole compensates for the partiality of the point of view in individual photos (Kitis & Milani, 2015). The data analysed makes up a diverse set of incomplete perspectives, which can offer us a panoramic view of such complex landscapes. The total dataset comprises 36 pictures: the ones captured by Luca Prestia’s lenses (Appendix A), the ones relating to the border zone of Ventimiglia (Appendix B), and those of the areas around Clavière and Briançon (Appendix C).

I will analyse the signs both quantitatively and qualitatively, distinguishing between top-down and bottom-up signs and following the taxonomy proposed by Spolsky and Cooper (1991), which classifies the signs according to the language found in each one of them and distinguishes between monolingual and multilingual signs. Moreover, by applying Scollon and Wong Scollon's (2003) Geosemiotics framework, this project aims to go beyond quantifying the number of languages: signs can only be understood when related to their placement in a social and cultural context, and the notions of code preference, inscription, and emplacement, together with the status of the signs, can give us a deeper understanding of the relationship between a Linguistic Landscape and its socio-cultural context.

4 Analysis and Discussion

The data collected for this project comprises a mix of top-down and bottom-up signs. The top-down signs account for less than one third of the total data and, in most cases, their function for the purposes of our LL analysis is two-fold: on one hand, they show the languages chosen by the language policies of two different nations, while on the other they often consist of street signs that other agents in the landscape have written over with spray paint, and therefore serve as a medium for the different messages and languages used in bottom-up transgressive signs (Figure C.1).

The monolingual top-down signs typically include writing in French or Italian, depending on which side of the border they appear on; they usually give information to the drivers crossing the border and, when they contain multiple languages, the official language of the country they are situated in appears first, with a partial translation in the official language of the other country and in English (Figures B.10, B.11).

Bottom-up signs show a higher degree of variability in the languages used. French and English are the languages most prevalently used for graffiti, protest signs, and social and political messages. The signs created by local support organisations tend to be multilingual and, differently from the signs placed by authorities, they often include languages other than French, Italian, and English, such as Arabic. Table 1 summarises the languages found in the Linguistic Landscape and their prevalence.

Table 1: *Languages in the Linguistic Landscape of the observed areas of the French-Italian border*

Language(s) on public signs	Number	Percentage
French	17	40%
Italian	5	12%
English	7	16%
French, Italian & English	3	7.5%
French, English & Arabic	2	5%
French, Italian, English & Arabic	2	5%
French, Italian, English, Arabic & other languages	1	2.5%
No Language or unclear	5	12%

Total	43	100%
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The top-down signs in this dataset are clearly not directed towards the migrants, and they do not even take into account or show their presence in the area. A sign that stands out as the only one that indirectly acknowledges the flux of migration through this border area is the one in Figure 1: it is written just in Italian and directed to the drivers on the highway, warning them of the presence of possible pedestrians. The “pedestrians” the sign refers to are the migrants that, often during the night, would try to cross the border on foot, risking and sometimes losing their lives.

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: a variable message sign above the entrance of a tunnel, showing the words ‘Possibili pedoni, prudenza’ [Possible pedestrians, caution] in red. This image can be found in di Blasio (2016). — Editors’ note]

Figure 1: *‘Possible pedestrians, caution’, Ventimiglia (Di Blasio, 2016).*

The majority of the data comprises bottom-up signs, which will be the main focus of the rest of this study. They can be loosely classified in three different categories: the ones placed by activist organisations and volunteers to help migrants, the graffiti with socio-political messages, and the protest signs and messages left by migrants in refuge centres.

The leaflets, banners, and signboards placed by activist organisations and volunteers aim to help migrants or give information about the area and the existing refuge centres; these consist of authorized signs, such as the ones placed by the Red Cross while it was active in Ventimiglia (Figure B.1), and more often transgressive signs placed by grassroots and activist organisations that became active because of a lack of official or institutional help (Figures B.3, B.4). Figure 2 shows the sign of a self-managed refuge, and both the lexical and code choices clearly position the activist organisation who created it on the side of migrating people and opposed to right-wing politics and authority. The text is constructed in a complementary way (Reh, 2004), switching between French, Italian, and English, evoking an idea of openness, inclusivity, and an ideal absence of borders.

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: two signs next to each other on the exterior of a glass window.]

Left: a sign handwritten in block capitals, which reads (the slash symbol indicates a line break): ‘;Chez Jesus! / Rifugio autogestito / here nessuno is etrangere / tranne:.fasci.sbirri. passeurs.’ [Chez Jesus! / (Italian:) Self-managed refuge / (English:) here (Italian:) no one (English:) is (French:) foreign / (Italian:) apart from: fascists, cops, (French:) smugglers.]

Right: a smaller, printed sign with more text; parts that are legible from the photo, from top to bottom, all in capitals: ‘CI ACCUSANO DI SOLIDARIETÀ / SIAMO TUTTI COLPEVOLI’ [Italian: They accuse us of solidarity, we are all guilty]; ‘SU QUEI SENTIERI C’ERAVAMO TUTTE!’ [Italian: We were all on those trails!]; and in English, ‘DEFEND SOLIDARITY / SMASH THE BORDERS’. This image can be found in “Val Susa” (2018). — Editors’ note]

Figure 2: *‘Chez Jesus! Self-managed refuge, here no one is foreign apart from: fascists, cops, smugglers’, ‘They accuse us of solidarity, we are all guilty! Defend solidarity, smash the border!’ signs in Clavière (“Val Susa”, 2018).*

The graffiti found on walls and abandoned buildings, on street signs, highway guard rails, and rocky mountain paths are transgressive signs probably created by activists and locals. In most cases they show social and political messages that call for no borders and freedom of movement (Figures A.9, A.10, C.3, C.4, C.5), and express the consequences of strict border control (Figure C.2); exceptions are the arrows and crosses used to show which path is more or less safe to the migrants passing through the border zone (Figures A.2, A.8). The signs collected around Clavière are often graffiti carrying social and political messages. Figure 3 poses itself as an interesting example because it shows the layering of signs: someone painted on a highway guard rail the message “no one is illegal” in Italian, then authorities tried to cover up the sign with white paint.

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Faloppa (2020, Fig. 15). — Editors’ note]

Figure 3: *Writing saying ‘no one is illegal’ in Clavière, covered (Photo by Luca Prestia).*

The protest signs (Figure B.13) and messages left by migrants in reception centres such as the Refuge Solidaire in Briançon (Figures A.3, A.4, A.5, A.6) are often written in French, as the language shared with the authorities that deny them access to France. A sign in English stands out (Figure 4): ‘hope’ is seen as a word that can be read and understood by as many people as possible, where the choice of code uses English as a lingua franca (Backhaus, 2006).

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 21). — Editors’ note]

Figure 4: *Photo by Luca Prestia.*

The careful investigation of some bottom-up data through the Geosemiotics framework (Scollon & Wong Scollon, 2003) can help us report a sociolinguistic landscape that shows the continuous negotiation and adaptation through language by the people that pass through, live, and coexist at the border.

The Orientation map in Figure 5 represents a bridge between the borderscapes of Ventimiglia and Clavière, 200 kilometres apart from each other but united in a Linguistic Landscape with common social actors. The emplacement system of this sign is particularly significant. The map shows the sign of a long journey: it was found nearby Ventimiglia, on a mountain trail leading to France, but it was made by civil society organisations to help migrants trying to cross the border between Clavière and Haute Savoy (Faloppa, 2023). In terms of code preference, English appears first, then French, and then Arabic, and the three languages are related by a duplicating relationship (Reh, 2004).

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: a creased map on the ground. The title of the map is given in three languages in the upper left corner: in English, ‘Map of borders four you [sic] safety’; and, of the same meaning, in French and Arabic. To the left, a map legend is given in the same three languages. Part of the French-Italian border is shown on the map, with its majority labelled as ‘border always dangerous’, and a small section near Clavière as ‘border less dangerous’. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 16). — Editors’ note]

Figure 5: ‘Orientation map of border crossing points at Clavière [...] found at Ventimiglia’ (Prestia & Faloppa, 2017-2020), August 2019 (photo by Luca Prestia).

Kesha Niya, a grassroots organisation working in Ventimiglia, primarily supports people who have been illegally denied entry into France, and the signs depicted in Figure 6, both inscribed on movable objects, are clear examples of that.

Figure 6 (a) contains overlapping text (Reh, 2004) in English, Italian, French, and Arabic, and it schematically provides information about the area migrants find themselves stuck in, a sketched map, bus times, and points of interest for medical aid and distribution of food and necessities.

Figure 6 (b) becomes very significant when examined with regard to its emplacement. In fact, it is probably one of the first signs people see when they stop at the ‘breakfast spot’ put up by Kesha Niya before trying to cross the border. The sign aims at catching the viewer’s attention to warn them about the danger of French border authorities stealing their documents, and it does so through its bright colours and illustration. The codes seem to not be organised hierarchically, the text is duplicated in Arabic, English, Italian, French, and two other languages (possibly Urdu and a language written with Aramaic script). The material used to produce the signs, cloth and tin, are more permanent than paper, but indicate less permanence than an official sign would.

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Nyia (2021, 4th image). — Editors’ note]

(a) Welcome sign showing a map of the area, bus, times, and necessities distribution, May 2021

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Nyia (2022, 2nd image). — Editors’ note]

(b) ‘Migrants! Police can steal your documents, make a copy, or take a picture’ sign, March 2022

Figure 6: Pictures from Kesha Niya organisation.

5 Conclusion

The sociolinguistic analysis of borderscapes tells us that there is still a lot to study and learn about the signs found along border zones. The Linguistic Landscape of two areas along the border between Italy and France, in the proximity of Ventimiglia and Clavière, presents us with a stratification of information and languages. The signs come from a variety of sources such as activists, migrants, and organisations, and are directed towards multiple viewers: the people migrating, the authorities limiting their freedom of movement, the drivers along the roads they cross, and the wider society they interact with. Recomposing the wide array of signs and carefully analysing data through a precise framework such as the one introduced by Scollon and Wong Scollon (2003) may lend us a new way to look at these borders and at the multiple human and social dynamics shaping their Linguistic Landscape, where multilingualism is a possible means to overcome cultural boundaries.

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- Ventimiglia? Per la Francia è un problema da italiani spaghetti mandolino e clandestini. (June 2015). Retrieved from *Tempi*: <<https://www.tempi.it/ventimiglia-per-la-francia-e-un-problema-da-italiani-spaghetti-mandolino-e-clandestini/>>. Page archived at <<https://web.archive.org/web/20250212040717/https://www.tempi.it/ventimiglia-per-la-francia-e-un-problema-da-italiani-spaghetti-mandolino-e-clandestini/>>

8 Appendices

8.1 Appendix A: Beyond the Border: Migration and Multilingual Signs at European Borderscapes

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: a creased map on the ground. The title of the map is given in three languages in the upper left corner: in English, ‘Map of borders four you [sic] safety’; and, of the same meaning, in French and Arabic. To the left, a map legend is given in the same three languages. Part of the French-Italian border is shown on the map, with its majority labelled as ‘border always dangerous’, and a small section near Clavière as ‘border less dangerous’. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 16). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.1: *‘Orientation map of border crossing points at Clavière [...] found at Ventimiglia’ (Prestia & Faloppa, 2017-2020), August 2019 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 17). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.2: *‘signs to alert migrants of possible dangers along the trail from Ventimiglia [...] to Menton’ (Prestia & Faloppa, 2017-2020), August 2019 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 7). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.3: *Messages left by migrants at the Refuge Solidaire, Briançon, July 2020 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Faloppa (2020, Fig. 13). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.4: *Messages left by migrants at the Refuge Solidaire, Briançon, July 2020 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Faloppa (2020, Fig. 14). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.5: *Messages left by migrants at the Refuge Solidaire, Briançon, July 2020 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 8). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.6: *‘The West kills Africa’, on a wall of the Refuge Solidaire, Briançon, July 2020 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Faloppa (2020, Fig. 15). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.7: *Writing saying ‘no one is illegal’ in Clavière, covered (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found Faloppa (2020, Fig. 16). — Editors’ note]

Figure A.8: *Arrows to show the way, Briançon (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found Faloppa (2020, Fig. 17). — Editors' note]

Figure A.9: *Graffiti on an abandoned building in Briançon, 'no borders' (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 9). — Editors' note]

Figure A.10: *Graffiti along the road leading to France nearby Clavière, 'there are no borders', July 2020 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 18). — Editors' note]

Figure A.11: *'An informal check point set up by the French border patrol on the hills above the city of Menton' (Prestia & Faloppa, 2017-2020), August 2019 (photo by Luca Prestia).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Prestia and Faloppa (2017-2020, Figure 21). — Editors' note]

Figure A.12: *'The "Hope" sign, and colourful knots left by migrants on the fence at the Italian-French border at 'Hill of the dead' (Italy), July 2017' (Prestia & Faloppa, 2017-2020; photo by Luca Prestia).*

8.2 Appendix B: Pictures from Ventimiglia and Menton

[Image not included due to Google's restrictions on the use of Google Street View imagery. Originally pictured here: Exterior of a windowed, one-story building, with various pieces of graffiti on the visible wall:

https://www.google.com/maps/@43.8170809,7.5893452,3a,90y,233.03h,80.89t/data=!3m7!1e1!3m5!1sJlgPMpAPIIFH_XsTkdBn_Q!2e0!6shttps:%2F%2Fstreetviewpixels-pa.googleapis.com%2Fv1%2Fthumbnail%3Fcb_client%3Dmaps_sv.tactile%26w%3D900%26h%3D600%26pitch%3D9.11%26panoid%3DJlgPMpAPIIFH_XsTkdBn_Q%26yaw%3D233.03!7i16384!8i8192?entry=tту&g_ep=EgoyMDI1MTAwMS4wIKXMDSOASAFQAw%3D%3D — Editors' note]

Figure B.1: *Abandoned building where Campo Roja used to be. Google Streetview 2023.*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Della Croce (2017, cover photo). — Editors' note]

Figure B.2: *Notice of closure of the reception centre for families in Sant'Antonio alle Gianchette (Della Croce, 2017).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Niya (2018, 5th image). — Editors' note]

Figure B.3: *Breakfast at the Kesha Niya organisation (Kesha Niya, 2018).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Nyia (2022, 4th image). — Editors' note]

Figure B.4: *Welcome sign from Kesha Niya organisation (Kesha Niya, 2021).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Nyia (2022, 2nd image). — Editors’ note]

Figure B.5: *‘Migrants! Police can steal your documents, make a copy or take a picture’ sign (Kesha Nyia, 2022).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Kesha Nyia (2019, 2nd image). — Editors’ note]

Figure B.6: *Modified date of birth on refusal of entry (Kesha Nyia, 2019).*

[Image not included due to Google’s restrictions on the use of Google Street View imagery. Originally pictured here: View of the shaded space beneath a viaduct. Various piece of graffiti can be seen on the base of the supporting pillars: https://www.google.com/maps/@43.8008418,7.5955398,3a,75y,81.31h,84.84t/data=!3m7!1e1!3m5!1sfMB_6WV_uEHBkypfZe7_2A!2e0!6shttps:%2F%2Fstreetviewpixels-pa.googleapis.com%2Fv1%2Fthumbnail%3Fcb_client%3Dmaps_sv.tactile%26w%3D900%26h%3D600%26pitch%3D5.159999999999997%26panoid%3DfMB_6WV_uEHBkypfZe7_2A%26yaw%3D81.31!7i16384!8i8192?entry=tту&g_ep=EgoyMDI1MTAwMS4wIKXMDSOASAFQAw%3D%3D — Editors’ note]

Figure B.7: *Viaduct used as shelter. Google Streetview, November 2023.*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: a variable message sign above the entrance of a tunnel, showing the words ‘Possibili pedoni, prudenza’ [Possible pedestrians, caution] in red. This image can be found in di Blasio (2016). — Editors’ note]

Figure B.8: *‘Possible pedestrians, caution’, Ventimiglia (di Blasio, 2016).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Alfano (2023). — Editors’ note]

Figure B.9: *‘Open the border’ on a rock in front of the French border control (Alfano, 2023).*

[Image not included due to Google’s restrictions on the use of Google Street View imagery. Originally pictured here: View on a highway. On the side of the highway is a sign with blue background and white lettering that reads: ‘Bienvenue / L’autoroute est à vous / Benvenuti / Welcome’ [(French:) Welcome / The highway is yours / (Italian:) Welcome / (English:) Welcome]: https://www.google.com/maps/@43.7895122,7.5258047,3a,75y,303.74h,75.95t/data=!3m7!1e1!3m5!1sBY0l-FgbF61cgwqGE4eBBg!2e0!6shttps:%2F%2Fstreetviewpixels-pa.googleapis.com%2Fv1%2Fthumbnail%3Fcb_client%3Dmaps_sv.tactile%26w%3D900%26h%3D600%26pitch%3D14.04710447267064%26panoid%3DBY0l-FgbF61cgwqGE4eBBg%26yaw%3D303.73542294061036!7i16384!8i8192?entry=tту&g_ep=EgoyMDI1MDgxMy4wIKXMDSOASAFQAw%3D%3D — Editors’ note]

Figure B.10: *‘Welcome’ sign on the French highway. Google Streetview, November 2023.*

[Image not included due to Google’s restrictions on the use of Google Street View imagery. Originally pictured here: View on a highway. On the side of the highway is a sign with blue background and white lettering that reads: ‘Merci et à bientôt / A presto / See you soon [(French:) Thank you and see you soon / (Italian:) See you soon / (English:) See you soon]: <https://www.google.com/maps/@43.789545,7.5252838,3a,21.6y,119.12h,90.85t/data=!3m7!1e1!3m5!1sp-51MadbGWrHAzs7ofK07A!2e0!6shhttps:%2F%2Fstreetviewpixels-pa.googleapis.com%2Fv1%2Fthumbnail%3Fcb_client%3Dmaps_sv.tactile%26w%3D900%26h%3D600%26pitch%3D-0.8534998120734656%26panoid%3Dp-51MadbGWrHAzs7ofK07A%26yaw%3D119.1223334313394!7i16384!8i8192?entry=tту&g_ep=EgoYMDI1MTAwMS4wIKXMDSOASAFAQAw%3D%3D> — Editors’ note]

Figure B.11: ‘See you soon’ sign on the French highway. Google Streetview, November 2023.

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in “Ventimiglia?” (2015, 1st image). — Editors’ note]

Figure B.12: ‘But where has the country of human rights gone?’ (“Ventimiglia?”, 2015).

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Colotti (2016, cover photo). — Editors’ note]

Figure B.13: ‘But where is humanity headed?’ (Colotti, 2016).

8.3 Appendix C: Pictures from Clavière and Briançon

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Massenzio (2023, cover photo). — Editors’ note]

Figure C.1: ‘France murders’ graffiti on the border between Clavière and France (Massenzio, 2023).

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Dubale (2022, cover photo). — Editors’ note]

Figure C.2: ‘The border kills’ graffiti in a tunnel in Clavière (Dubale, 2022).

[Image not included due to Google’s restrictions on the use of Google Street View imagery. Originally pictured here: A message spray-painted in white on the exterior of a building, in block capitals: ‘La vie n’as pas besoin de papiers’ [Life doesn’t need papers]. — Editors’ note]

Figure C.3: ‘Life doesn’t need papers’ written on a wall in Clavière. Google Streetview, November 2023.

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Dumont (2018, last image). — Editors’ note]

Figure C.4: ‘Ain’t no mountain high enough! Migration is liberty’ written on a wall in Clavière (Dumont, 2018).

[Image not included due to Google’s restrictions on the use of Google Street View imagery. Originally pictured here: Three messages spray-painted on a wall in block capitals, presumably all by different hands. In red: ‘Nous danserons sur vos centres de rétention’ [We will dance on your detention centres]. On top of the previous message, in black: ‘Mort aux fachos’ [Death to the fascists]. To the left of the previous message, in white: ‘a’ and ‘anti-’, positioned in such a manner that when combined with the message in black it reads ‘A mort aux anti-fachos’ [To death to the anti-fascists]. — Editors’ note]

Figure C.5: *Graffiti in Clavière: ‘We will dance on your detention centres’, ‘death to the fascists’, ‘to death to the anti-fascists’.* Google Streetview, November 2023.

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. This image can be found in Dubale (2022, 1st image, not counting the cover photo). — Editors’ note]

Figure C.6: *‘Freedom of movement!’ graffiti in an abandoned building in France (Dubale, 2022).*

[Image not included due to copyright concerns. Originally pictured here: two signs next to each other on the exterior of a glass window.

Left: a sign handwritten in block capitals, which reads (the slash symbol indicates a line break): ‘; Chez Jesus! / Rifugio autogestito / here nessuno is etrangere / tranne:.fasci.sbirri. passeurs.’ [Chez Jesus! / (Italian:) Self-managed refuge / (English:) here (Italian:) no one (English:) is (French:) foreign / (Italian:) apart from: fascists, cops, (French:) smugglers.]

Right: a smaller, printed sign with more text; parts that are legible from the photo, from top to bottom, all in capitals: ‘CI ACCUSANO DI SOLIDARIETÀ / SIAMO TUTTI COLPEVOLI’ [Italian: They accuse us of solidarity, we are all guilty]; ‘SU QUEI SENTIERI C'ERAVAMO TUTTE!’ [Italian: We were all on those trails!]; and in English, ‘DEFEND SOLIDARITY / SMASH THE BORDERS’. This image can be found in “Val Susa” (2018). — Editors’ note]

Figure C.7: *‘Chez Jesus! Self-managed refuge, here no one is foreign apart from: fascists, cops, smugglers’, ‘They accuse us of solidarity, we are all guilty! Defend solidarity, smash the border!’ signs in Clavière (“Val Susa”, 2018).*

8.4 Appendix D: Maps of the Border

Figure D.1: *Way from Ventimiglia to Menton. Google Maps, November 2023.*

Figure D.2: *Way from Clavière to Briançon. Google Maps, November 2023.*